

26th Polymer Networks Group Meeting

Dresden, June 21-25, 2026

Abstracts

Deutsches Hygiene Museum Dresden

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Conference homepage: <https://png2026.ipfdd.de/home/>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.21155766

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1 Plenary Talks

Effect of network architecture on crack initiation: experiments and simulations

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Multiple polymer networks comprising a sacrificial and a matrix network, exhibit exceptional mechanical toughness and strength, commonly attributed to the development of an extended dissipative zone involving sacrificial bond scission in front of a growing crack. However, crack initiation in such materials remains poorly understood[1]. We report a combination of advanced mechanochemistry experiments and coarse-grained molecular dynamics simulations to investigate how the local force redistribution at the polymer strand scale of single-network and double-network elastomers delays crack nucleation. Mechanochemical experiments show that microscopic rearrangements and bond breaking events are very localized near the crack tip in single networks, readily causing the crack to advance, while double networks exhibit delocalized bond scission and microscopic rearrangements well ahead of and not directly correlated with crack propagation[2], effectively delaying the correlated bond scission needed for crack growth. Molecular scale simulations show that, in contrast to single networks, where anisotropic stress redistribution promotes rapid localization and catastrophic fracture, the presence of a soft matrix in double networks induces a screening of stress redistribution generated by sacrificial bond scission. This screening suppresses correlated rupture events and stabilizes multiple damage zones, leading to a strongly delocalized damage landscape over a broad deformation range. Together, these results identify stress-screening-induced damage delocalization as a central microscopic mechanism underlying toughness enhancement in multiple-network elastomers[3,4].

[1] Sloopman, J. et al. PNAS, 2022 ; <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.211612711>

[2] Ju, J. et al. PNAS, 2024 ; <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.241051512>

[3] Orr, NP et al. PNAS, 2026 ; <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2530175123>

[4] Le Goff et al. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2601.04759>

Bio-inspired Processing of Polyelectrolyte Complexes

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Natural materials such as spider silk and mussel adhesives achieve exceptional mechanical performance through tightly controlled aqueous processing pathways. In contrast, conventional synthetic routes often rely on harsh conditions and provide limited control over structure formation. Increasing evidence shows that many biological materials are processed via coacervates: dense, liquid-like polymer phases that enable flow, deformation, and molecular reorganization prior to solidification.

Here, we explore coacervates as bio-inspired intermediates for materials processing. By decoupling shaping from solidification, coacervates allow materials to be processed in a fluid state and subsequently fixed through controlled environmental triggers. In our work, we demonstrate how environmental switching strategies, including changes in ionic strength, pH, and temperature, can be used to tune intermolecular interactions and guide structure formation. This approach has enabled the development of coacervate-based adhesives and fibers, as well as printable materials and three-dimensional scaffolds under fully aqueous conditions [1-4].

Importantly, gradual changes in interactions provide access to a continuum of material states, allowing structure and function to be programmed during processing. This work highlights a pathway-driven approach to materials design, where controlling processing conditions rather than composition opens new routes toward sustainable, bio-inspired materials.

[1] A. H. Hofman et al., *Adv. Mater.* 30 (2018) 1704640.

[2] M. Dompe et al., *Adv. Mater.* 31 (2019) 1808179.

[3] J. Sun et al., *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 10 (2022) 15968.

[4] M. Khoonkari et al., *Adv. Mater.* (2023) 2210769.

My Forty-Eight Years with Hydrogels

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I started my scientific career in 1978 as a PhD student in the Department of Macromolecular Chemistry at Vienna Technical University. My PhD thesis focused on water-soluble cationic polymers based on acrylamide, which were not related to hydrogels. After completing my PhD, I spent 48 years at various universities and research institutions working with hydrogels of different architectures as summarized in the following sections.

Microgels. A microgel is an intramolecularly cross-linked macromolecule dispersed in normal or colloidal solutions. In 1990, together with Werner Funke, we discovered a novel strategy for preparing reactive microgels with nuclei fractions up to 25–30 mass % without macrogel formation [1]. We initiated the polymerization of 1,4-divinylbenzene (1,4-DVB) using living poly(4-tert-butylstyrene) (PBS) in n-heptane which is a good solvent for PBS but a non-solvent for polystyrene or poly(4-vinylstyrene) (PVS). The chains of the living polymer act as initiators for the polymerization of 1,4-DVB and as steric stabilizers for the separated particle phase. By this method, reactive microgels possessing 10 to 5,000 PBS chains per nucleus, closely packed at the surface, were obtained.

Macroporous copolymer networks. Between 1985 and 2000, our research group focused on the formation mechanism of macroporous copolymer networks resulting from phase separation during the free-radical cross-linking copolymerization of vinyl and divinyl monomers in the presence of an inert diluent [2]. We also developed theoretical models that accurately predict the phase separation conditions during the cross-linking process, as well as the total porosity of the resulting macroporous networks. These works, reviewed in Prog. Polym. Sci., have been cited about 1,020 times.

Cryogels. Cryogels have attracted significant interest in the past 20 years, mainly due to their exceptional properties compared to classical hydrogels. Our group extended the application of the cryogelation technique to organic media to produce high-toughness macroporous organogels based on various rubbers [3]. We patented these macroporous rubbers as reusable oil sorbents for removing oil spills from water, which is important worldwide.

From static cross-linked systems to dynamic and multifunctional architectures. Over the past 20 years, hydrogel research in my group has shifted from static, covalently cross-linked systems to dynamic and multifunctional architectures. Micellar polymerization to produce hydrophobically modified semi-crystalline hydrogels broadens the accessible property range by combining stiffness, toughness, extensibility, self-healing and shape-memory functionality, reflecting a broader move toward bioinspired hydrogel design [4].

[1] O. Okay, W. Funke, *Macromolecules* 23 (1990) 2623-2628.

[2] O. Okay, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* 25 (2000), 711-779.

[3] D. Ceylan, O. Okay, *Macromolecules* 40 (2007) 8742-8749 (2007)

[4] B. Yetiskin, O. Okay, *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.* 4 (2022) 5234–5245.

The Art of Network Design

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We discuss several methods for designing polymer networks and gels, as well as various approaches to making these networks tougher, including the use of stored length and sacrificial bonds, slide rings, entanglements, and microphase separation. It turns out that whether weaker or stronger crosslinks lead to tougher networks depends on the placement of these crosslinks – either as parts of network strands or as connections between primary chains. The optimal strength of the sacrificial crosslinks and their concentration depend on the strength of the primary chain bonds. An interplay between main chain pull-out and bond cleavage depends on the deformation rate. A combination of these approaches in double networks utilizes double microphase separation on two different scales. All these methods lead to the narrowing of the tension distribution in network strands and, most importantly, the reduction of tension in the overstretched strands.

Weak interchain bonds make networks stronger [1].

[1] S. Wang, Y. Hu, T. B Kouznetsova, L. Sapir, D. Chen, A. Herzog-Arbeitman, J. A Johnson, M. Rubinstein, and S. L Craig, *Science* **380**, (2023) 1248-1252. DOI: [10.1126/science.adg3229](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adg3229)

Non-equilibrium dynamic polymer networks

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Since its inception a century ago, the forefront of polymer science has mostly evolved around non-crosslinked polymers (thermoplastics), with major developments centered on how to precisely control the chain structures so to push the limits of the macroscopic material properties. By comparison, crosslinked polymer networks (thermosets) had achieved industrial success before the concept of macromolecule/polymer came into life. Surprisingly, however, major theories/methods on controlling their structures have been notably lacking throughout the history of modern polymer science. The root cause lies in the difficulty on precise control of the polymerization conditions during their synthesis, coupled with the occurrence of gelation during polymerization. Consequently, network structures of crosslinked polymers often correspond to highly disordered equilibrium states, with very limited freedom for structural tuning. This has led to challenges to meet emerging demands for flexible and sustainable manufacturing of high performance polymeric materials. Non-equilibrium states are fundamental to the diversity of nature and offer inspirations for the design of next-generation materials. Can the concept of non-equilibrium be introduced into crosslinked polymer networks and what unique benefits would this offer in pushing this type of materials beyond their conventional limits? In this talk, I will describe our adventure in this direction, including the origin of the concept of non-equilibrium dynamic polymer networks, its evolution over the years in terms of the molecular design scope, and how this may reshape the landscape of polymer materials.

2 Invited Talks

Multimodal Mechano-Sensing in Polymer Networks

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Mechanical force offers a unique way to bias chemical reactivity in polymer networks by directing stress along specific molecular coordinates.^[1] However, in many established mechanophore systems, force tends to funnel reactivity into a single dominant pathway. In this talk, I will describe how the molecular-level design of tri-/di-arylmethane mechanophores,^[2] combined with controlled variations in the polymer-matrix microenvironment, enables selective access to different reaction pathways under load.

Our studies show that substituent effects and leaving-group structure modulate the intrinsic radical-ionic balance of these mechanophores, while local hydrogen-bonding interactions further bias their behavior in the solid state.^[3,4] This interplay allows the same mechanophore scaffold to yield either radical or carbocationic products, depending on its environment, ultimately resulting in distinct optical and EPR signatures.

Collectively, these results outline a general design perspective in which mechanophore structure and polymer microenvironment act synergistically to shape mechanochemical reactivity. This perspective supports ongoing efforts toward predictive models of mechanochemical reactivity and provides a foundation for mechanoresponsive materials whose performance can be tuned— and ultimately guided—through rational chemical design.

[1] Y. Chen, G. Mellot, D. van Luijk, C. Creton, and R. P. Sijbesma, [*Chem. Soc. Rec.* **50** \(2021\) 4100-4140](#)

[2] J. R. Hemmer, C. Rader, B. Wilts, C. Weder, and J. A. Berrocal, [*J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **143** \(2021\) 18859-18863](#)

[3] D. A. Mache, E. García-Padilla, F. Fratelloreto, G. Egizzo, J. R. Hemmer, J. Valverde-Bastidas, S. De La Flor, F. Maseras, and J. A. Berrocal, *submitted*.

[4] G. Egizzo, E. García-Padilla, F. Fratelloreto, F. Monie, D. A. Mache, F. Maseras, and J. A. Berrocal, *submitted*.

Charge Regulation in Weak Polyelectrolyte Hydrogels

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Weak polyelectrolyte hydrogels are polymer networks containing weakly acidic or basic groups. The ability of these functional groups to dynamically regulate their charge gives rise to a multitude of complex effects that are difficult to describe theoretically as acid-base equilibria, ion partitioning, and hydrogel swelling are tightly coupled. In this talk, I will provide an overview of our efforts to understand and model the behavior of weak polyelectrolyte hydrogels using coarse-grained simulations [1-5] and mean-field approaches [1,3]. At the particle-based level, recent advances in simulation methodology enable consistent modeling of charge regulation in weak hydrogels [1], including the partitioning of mono- and multivalent ions [1, 2, 4]. Comparison of our simulation approach with swelling experiments reveals overall good agreement [2]. At the mean-field level, cell-model approaches combining the Poisson-Boltzmann equation with a bulk charge regulation term allow for computationally efficient predictions of hydrogel swelling and ionization over a wide range of conditions [1,3]. Finally, I will discuss recent simulation results regarding the transport of multivalent ions through dynamically charge-regulating hydrogels [5], which have important implications for various technological applications and biological systems.

[1] J. Landsgesell, D. Beyer, P. Hebbeker, P. Košovan, and C. Holm, *Macromolecules* 55 (2022), 3176-3188.

[2] D. Beyer, P. Košovan, and C. Holm, *Macromolecules* 55 (2022), 10751-10760.

[3] M. E. Brito, E. Höpner, D. Beyer, and C. Holm, *Macromolecules* 58 (2025), 2494-2507.

[4] D. Beyer and C. Holm, *Macromolecular Chemistry and Physics* 227 (2026), e00476.

[5] P. Walker*, D. Beyer*, C. Holm, and Z.-G. Wang, manuscript in preparation.

Ultrasound-Driven Nanoparticle Transport in Polymer Networks: A Molecular Stick-and-Release Mechanism

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The transport of nanoparticles through polymer networks is a central problem in soft matter physics and biomedical applications, from drug delivery in tumors to filtration and sensing. In extracellular-matrix-like hydrogels, nanoparticle motion is often strongly hindered by a combination of steric constraints and transient adhesive interactions with the network. Low-intensity ultrasound has been reported to enhance nanoparticle diffusion in such systems, yet experimental observations remain contradictory [1,2] and the underlying mechanisms are still debated.

In this talk, I present a molecular-level study of ultrasound-driven nanoparticle transport in hydrogels using coarse-grained Langevin dynamics simulations [3]. After validating the approach against an exact analytical solution in dilute solution, we systematically investigate diffusion in polymer networks with tunable steric and adhesive interactions. We find that ultrasound does not enhance diffusion in purely steric networks. In contrast, enhancement emerges when nanoparticles interact attractively with the network, where ultrasound reduces particle-polymer contact times via a stick-and-release mechanism. This framework explains why acoustic enhancement is observed only under specific interaction strengths and ultrasound conditions, reconciling conflicting experimental observations.

Figure 1: Simulation snapshot of nanoparticles diffusing in a hydrogel under ultrasound, shown for a purely steric network.

[1] C. Einen et al. *Gels* 9 (2023), 9, 771.

[2] D. Ma, J. S. Marshall and J. Wu, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 144(6) (2018) 3496–3502.

[3] P. M. Blanco, H. H. Rønneberg, and R. S. Dias, *JCIS* 704(2) (2026) 2139402.

Diels-Alder chemistry: An old workhorse for new sustainable polymer networks

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Diels-Alder (DA) chemistry, although introduced almost a century ago, is a powerful platform for designing reversible polymer networks that reconcile high performance with sustainability. This talk covers recent advances our group has made in thin-film adhesives, bulk networks, nanocomposites, and functional devices, highlighting how thermo-reversible covalent bonding enables extended service life, reparability, and recycling. Reversible DA crosslinking has been successfully implemented in vapor-deposited poly(furfuryl methacrylate) films, yielding robust yet reusable adhesives.¹ Fundamental understanding is achieved by detailed kinetic studies of furan-maleimide reactions, where activation energies were quantified and linked to temperature-dependent processing windows for additive manufacturing.² Beyond classical networks, DA chemistry enables novel material concepts, such as directly using carbon nanotubes as reactive fillers that act simultaneously as reinforcements and reversible crosslinkers, imparting electrical and thermal self-healing capabilities.³ At the device level, DA-based self-healing polymers have been integrated into soft robotic grippers.⁴ Finally, emerging complexities such as the double DA reaction, which strengthens materials but can hinder recyclability if overlooked, are discussed.⁵ Together, these studies illustrate the versatility, opportunities, and challenges of DA-based reversible networks.

[1] Guo, J. et al. *ACS Applied Polymer Materials* **2025**, 7 (2), 889-900.

[2] van den Tempel, P. et al. *Materials Today Chemistry* **2024**, 42, 102361.

[3] Guo, J. et al. *Polymer* **2023**, 283, 126260.

[4] Orozco, F. et al. *Soft Robotics* **2023**, 10 (4), 852-859.

[5] van den Tempel, P. et al. *Polymer* **2023**, 274, 125884.

Combining CANs and Dual Cure Networks

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Covalent adaptable networks (CANs) provide processing potential otherwise inaccessible in thermosets. The rearrangement of network topology by bond exchange under stimulus (light, heat, pH), is core to the processing capacity; however, is not desirable in some end-use products. Therefore, the implementation of sequentially-controlled orthogonal stages with variable processes is favorable. The combination of dual-cure and dynamic networks overcomes these limitations by arresting dynamic capacity with a permanent network once desired dynamic processing is completed.

These types of dual-cure polymer networks enable multistage control over the processing of materials to ensure both desirable processing and end-use properties. Traditionally leveraged for adhesives, coatings, and dental applications, this approach, particularly when combined with the CANs paradigm has the potential to be broadened for applications in numerous areas including holography and volumetric additive manufacturing. Through sequentially-controlled orthogonality, multistage CANs overcome the desired-property mismatch in processes including dynamic stress relaxation, holographic photopolymer writing, and volumetric additive manufacturing.

Specifically, tomographic volumetric additive manufacturing has powerful advantages over other 3D printing techniques in that the entire volume of the part is polymerized simultaneously. To realize fully this technology, the field must move from traditional resins for SLA and DLP to material platforms intended for the methodology. A tunable, degradable, CAN scaffold enabled the use of a wide range of monomers and therefore provided access to a wide array of mechanical properties. Notably, green parts with glassy properties were achieved. The platform further provided consistent print timing and quality for small features, which were revealed upon degelation of the unpolymerized out-of-part scaffold.

Diels-Alder-based polymer network design: structure, reactivity, processing and properties relations

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The macroscopic behaviour of dynamic polymer networks can be designed very versatile through in-depth knowledge of the dynamic character of the dynamic covalent chemistries and design of the polymer network structure. The choice of the dynamic chemistry and the concentration of the reactive groups determine the chemical reaction kinetics, while the prepolymer architecture, molecular weight and functionality determine how the chemical dynamics translate into macroscopic physical behaviour in response of external triggers.

The combination of structure-reactivity [1] and structure-property [2] relations enables simulating the chemical and physical behaviour under processing conditions and during application. Mechanistic models relate the gel point and gel transition temperature to the reaction kinetics and thermodynamics, and the viscoelastic behaviour as a function of temperature and shear conditions to the prepolymer architectures. Several orders of magnitude difference in shear behaviour and stress relaxation [3] can be achieved by changing the prepolymer molecular weight, functionality and architecture, or the addition of fillers [4] without significant changes in mechanical stiffness and self-healing performance.

[1] Vermeersch L., *et al.*, *Macromolecules*, 2025, 58, 32–44.

[2] S. Terryn, *et al.* *Macromolecules*, 2022, 55, 13, 5497–5513.

[3] A. C. Cornellà, F. Furia, *et al.*, *Advanced Materials*, 2024, 36(46), 2407663.

[4] Furia F., *et al.*, *Additive Manufacturing*, 2024, 91, 104342.

Bio-inspired peptide-reinforced amphiphilic polymer conetworks

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Amphiphilic polymer conetworks (APCNs) are water- and organo-swellable polymer networks that find applications in soft contact lenses, as biomaterials, sensing materials, membranes, microcapsules, or as catalyst supports. These materials already possess superior mechanical properties compared to many conventional hydrogels. Still, their strength, extensibility, and toughness can be further improved by reinforcement with peptide blocks and cellulose nanocrystals, inspired by the hierarchical reinforcement of soft materials found in nature.

In the APCNs presented herein, hydrophilic poly(2-hydroxyethyl acrylate) is crosslinked by polydimethylsiloxane or poly(ethylene glycol) crosslinkers that feature short peptide blocks at their chain ends.^[1-2] As a result, nanophase-separated materials with hard and soft segments are obtained in which the hard peptide segments reinforce the elastic material, similar to the reinforcing mechanism of silk proteins. The polymer networks can be further reinforced by incorporating cellulose nanocrystals.^[3] The networks are synthesized as free-standing membranes for separation applications, or as microcapsules via double-emulsion microfluidics.^[4]

- [1] S. T. R. Velasquez, D. Jang, P. Jenkins, P. Liu, L. Yang, L. T. J. Korley, N. Bruns, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2022**, 32, 2207317.
- [2] S. Russell, J. A. Thomas, D. Jang, P. Grysan, L. Sprandl, M. Biesalski, L. T. J. Korley, N. Bruns, *RSC Applied Polymers* **2026**, 4, 704.
- [3] S. T. R. Velasquez, D. Jang, J. Thomas, P. Grysan, L. T. J. Korley, N. Bruns, *Polymer Chemistry* **2025**, 16, 2618.
- [4] S. T. R. Velasquez, A. Belluati, E. Tervoort, I. Mattich, B. Hertel, S. Russell, M. G. Gouveia, P. Grysan, C. Mugemana, A. R. Studart, N. Bruns, *Advanced Materials Technologies* **2024**, 9, 2400109.

Bottlebrush Polymers, Networks, Gels, and Devices

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A bottlebrush polymer consists of a long linear backbone densely grafted with many relatively short side chains. Unlike classical linear polymers, the bottlebrush architecture enables mechanical, biophysical, and biochemical properties to be encoded independently, making bottlebrush polymers a versatile platform for soft (bio)materials design and innovation. In this talk, I will describe my lab's recent efforts to understand and apply bottlebrush polymers. I will begin with a theoretical framework for their molecular structure. Corroborated by experiments, we discover that, in some cases, the bottlebrush backbone can fold to store length despite the strong steric repulsion among highly overlapping side chains, a finding that challenges the prevailing view [1]. I will show that using these "foldable" bottlebrush polymers as network strands offers a universal strategy to decouple intrinsic stiffness-extensibility tradeoff in unentangled single-network elastomers, the fundamental component of all kinds of polymer networks [2]. I will then highlight a few applications of bottlebrush polymers and networks, including therapeutic delivery [3], modular cell-instructive biomaterials, advanced (bio)manufacturing [4], and high-performance solid-state polymer electrolytes. I will also discuss open questions unique to bottlebrush polymers, including glass transition, molecular dynamics, entanglements, and machine learning-accelerated polymeric materials discovery.

[1] L.-H. Cai. [*Macromolecules* **58** \(2025\) 4320-4339.](#)

[2] B. Huang, S. Nian, L.-H. Cai. [*Science Advances* \(2024\) **10**, eadq3080.](#)

[3] Z.-J. He, B. Huang, L.-H. Cai. [*ACS Nano* \(2024\) **18** 17586-17599.](#)

[4] B. Huang, M. Kim, P. Zhang, E. Oduro, D.A. Rau, L.-H. Cai. [*Advanced Materials* \(2026\) **38** e1280629.](#)

Quinolinone-Gated Chemistry: A Versatile Platform for Recyclable and Stimuli-Responsive Polymer Networks

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Controlling and reversing covalent bonds remains a central challenge for truly recyclable polymer systems. Here, we establish quinolinone motifs as multi-stimuli-responsive gating units for orthogonal covalent chemistry, based on a reversible $[2n+2n]$ cycloaddition activated by light and/or heat. Systematic evaluation across wavelengths and conditions reveals highly efficient, orthogonal photoprocesses with near-quantitative conversions and exceptional cyclability over eight cycles.[1] Incorporation of quinolinone units into oligomers enables catalyst-free, fully reversible photopolymerization in solution, yielding polymers up to 60 kDa that can be quantitatively depolymerized over multiple cycles. Oxygen emerges as a key environmental control parameter, shifting photoreversion from UV-C to UV-B while preserving high efficiency and cyclability, significantly expanding the operational window.[2] In parallel, we demonstrate at the molecular level for the first time that quinolinone dimers undergo quantitative thermal cleavage in the solid state, achieving >99% monomer recovery within 10 minutes at 210 °C. Building on this, integration as pendant groups enables light-induced crosslinking and thermally triggered cleavage of polymer networks, providing a direct route to recyclable crosslinked materials. This approach further enables precise tuning of material properties through controlled processing, supporting advanced applications such as coatings with programmable debonding.[3]

Overall, this work establishes quinolinone-gated chemistry as a design framework in which responsiveness is encoded as a functional variable, enabling polymer systems with controlled lifecycles from synthesis to deconstruction.

[1] M. Streicher, C-H. Stamp, D. M. Kluth, A. Ripp, C. Calvino, *Macromolecular Rapid Communications*, **45** (2024) 2400474.

[2] L. Charton, R. Remy, C. Calvino, *Polymer Chemistry*, **17** (2026) 347.

[3] C-H. Stamp, A. Groß, I. A. Beato, B. Balzer, C. Calvino, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, **1473(36)** (2025) 32830-32839.

Functional Gel Platforms for Biomedical Applications

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Recent advances in polymer science and biotechnology have enabled the design of advanced gel-based biomaterials that better replicate the dynamic, structural, and functional features of native tissues. This presentation highlights original gel design strategies addressing key challenges in biomedical applications, including spheroid formation, mechanical instability of natural polymers, controlled therapeutic delivery, and dynamic tissue interaction. Water-in-water (w/w) emulsion-based hydrogel systems were developed as biomimetic microenvironments that enable matrix-supported spheroid formation while minimizing shear- and pressure-induced cell damage, demonstrating strong potential for 3D cell culture and bioprinting [1]. In parallel, starch-based hydrogels and Ca²⁺-crosslinked beads were engineered to overcome intrinsic mechanical limitations and evaluated as sustainable, injection-ready depots for localized cancer therapy [2]. In addition, alginate-based cryogels integrated with cationic liposomal systems were designed to combine macroporous architectures with targeted and sustained drug delivery, while smart, crosslinker-free nanocomposite hydrogels exhibiting self-healing, shape-memory, and multi-stimuli responsiveness were introduced for regenerative wound-care applications [3]. These studies show that physical, supramolecular, and nanocomposite gel platforms can yield adaptable, biofunctional materials with significant potential in advanced biomedical technologies.

- [1] Sarıkaya A., „Applications of Hydrogels Prepared by Light Stimulation“, Ph.D. thesis, Bezmialm Vakif University (2026).
- [2] Avcı, H., Ceylan D., and Aytekin N.A., *Journal of Macromolecular Science, Part A*, 2025. 62(12): p. 1359-1370.
- [3] Kılıç, H. and Ceylan D., *Journal of Materials Chemistry B*, 2025. 13(1): p. 336-353.

Ultrasound-Triggered Gelation for Spinal Disc Repair

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Lower back pain is a leading cause of disability, often associated with intervertebral disc (IVD) degeneration, which originates in the nucleus pulposus (NP), a gel-like structure within the IVD. An estimated 619 million people lived with this condition worldwide in 2020.^[1] Current treatments rely on conservative methods, such as physiotherapy, or invasive surgical procedures, such as spinal fusion. Previous studies have investigated hydrogels as biomaterials for restoring the biomechanical properties of NP, but these hydrogels are either self-curing, or they rely on light-initiated radical crosslinking, which is depth-limited.

To circumvent these challenges, we present an ultrasound-triggered gelation approach as a minimally invasive process that offers spatiotemporal control to the clinician at clinically relevant depths.^[2] This concept relies on the use of an injectable and biocompatible free-flowing precursor solution consisting of an anionic polysaccharide, calcium-loaded thermosensitive liposomes and glass microspheres. Following optimization, alginate was chosen as the lead polysaccharide candidate. Focused ultrasound was used to heat the implant material to just above the lipid phase-transition temperature (41 °C), leading to calcium release and on-demand ionic crosslinking, and subsequently to a free-standing hydrogel. Ex vivo experiments in nine bovine spinal units confirmed effective ultrasound-triggered gelation, and subsequent biomechanical evaluations indicated partially restored mechanical performance without material herniation. Taken together, this study presents a promising approach for in-situ ultrasound-triggered hydrogelation.

[1] GBD 2021 Low Back Pain Collaborators, *Lancet Rheumatol.* 5 (2023) E316-E329.

[2] V. A. Brans,‡ A. P. Constantinou,‡ *et al.*, *Adv. Healthcare Mater.* (2025) e01823.

Supramolecular Restructuring of Ultra-low

Crosslinked Microgels

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Ultra-low-crosslinked (ULC) PNIPAM microgels were supramolecularly complexed by the addition of tannic acid. The resulting physical crosslinking, mediated by strong hydrogen-bond interactions between the polymer and the polyphenol, has a dramatic impact on the microgel structure and properties. Specifically, the initially soft and highly deformable microgels undergo a transition into a kinetically trapped core-shell architecture, characterized by a depleted core and a dense outer shell resembling a supramolecular capsule. Scattering and electron microscopy experiments evidence this structural transformation. Supported by molecular dynamics simulations, we show that tannic acid's strong affinity for PNIPAM drives and stabilizes this nonequilibrium restructuring, providing a molecular-level explanation for the experimentally observed morphology. Beyond structural control, this supramolecular restructuring provides a sensitive route to infer polymer-guest affinity directly from the resulting microgel architecture, offering a powerful, structure-based approach to characterize interactions in ultrasoft polymer networks.

Self-assembled Polypseudorotaxanes crosslinked by Dynamic disulfide bonds

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Polypseudorotaxanes (PPR) are linear polymers threaded by macrocyclic molecules, which can act as a versatile scaffold to build functional architectures. We report here the “one-pot” synthesis of self-assembled thiol-rich PPR, where thiolated- α -cyclodextrins spontaneously thread onto polymers and are subsequently crosslinked by the oxidation of thiols into disulfide bonds, forming a 3D network. The dynamic thiol groups along the polymer chains provide remarkable modularity for the functionalization of thiophilic nanoparticles (NPs), as demonstrated with Au and CuS NPs.[1]

Next, a self-capping strategy was employed to prevent the de-threading of cyclodextrins from the chains, resulting in “sliding gels” with high stretchability, compressibility and recovery. The dynamic nature of the disulfide crosslinks provides unique post-synthetic programmability, with re-healing ability (via disulfide metathesis) and self-strengthening (via thiol-ene Michael addition).

[1] X. Xu et al. “Self-Assembled Polypseudorotaxanes Crosslinked by Dynamic Disulfide Bonds as Modular Functionalisation for Thiophilic Metal Nanoparticles”, *Angewandte Chemie*, 64, e202515585 (2025).

[2] X. Xu, “Self-assembled Poly(disulfide)rotaxanes via “One-Pot” Synthesis for Functionalising CuS NPs”, Ph.D. thesis, King’s College London (2026).

Formation and structure of polyaspartic-polyurea networks for coatings and thermosets towards sustainability. Experimental insights and statistical modelling

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Polyaspartates are a novel class of thermosetting materials with great potential for sustainability and environmental friendliness through rapid cure under environmental conditions, use of no diluent or catalyst, and reduction of coating layers – without compromising the material performance. PASPE-PU networks are formed through urea bonds accompanied with aminolysis and conversion of urea bonds into ureido-carbonyl structures. We will introduce insight into formation mechanism of these networks and present design strategies to achieve gelation and structure control.

The paper conjoins experimental insights with recently developed simulations that combine kinetic theory and the statistical approach of the Theory of branching processes [1]. Side reactions are incorporated through their effect on the building units, which in turn govern the gelation, network evolution, and final material properties. The resulting model provides a predictive tool useful for designing realistic systems of next-generation polyaspartic coatings and thermosets.

- [1] A. Sharma, Z. Morávková, S. Abbrent, O. Kočková, S. Natourová, Z. Walterová, J. Podešva, J. Šomvářsky, M. Dušková-Smrčková, Experimental and statistical modelling of gelation in aspartate-based polyurea networks, *Polymer* 339 (2025)

Polyoxometalates as Smart Crosslinkers in Cellulose Ether Solutions

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α -Keggin polyoxometalates (POMs), such as $\text{SiW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{4-}$, interact with non-ionic solutes, such as polymers, driven by a water-mediated driving force, called the superchaotropic effect.^{1,2} In aqueous solution of hydroxypropylcellulose (HPC), a non-ionic cellulose ether that is widely employed as a thickener, this binding results in a substantial viscosity increase that depends on the charge density of the POM. For $\text{SiW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{4-}$, the thickening appears due to association of the POM with HPC with $K_A = 200 \text{ mM}^{-1}$, where bound POMs act as physically linked electric charges or as physical crosslinks between polymer chains depending on composition as found by Small Angle Neutron Scattering and rotational rheometry.³ POM binding thus enables network formation in non-ionic polymer solutions into hydrogels.

As Keggin POMs are photocatalysts,⁴ photoredox reactions can be employed to reduce the POM, increase its charge density and thus promote its hydration and diminish its binding to HPC. Photoredox cycles with ascorbic acid as a sacrificial reducing agent and atmospheric O_2 as an oxidizing agent were then used to generate switchable HPC-solutions and gels. The concept of smart chaotropicity for POMs enables a unique and simple strategy to make non-ionic polymer solutions and gels addressable through UV-light for soft material applications.

[1] K.I. Assaf, M.S. Ural, F. Pan, T. Georgiev, S. Simova, K. Rissanen, D. Gabel, W.M. Nau. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **54** (2015) 6852-6856.

[2] T. Buchecker, P. Schmid, I. Grillo, S. Prevost, M. Drechsler, O. Diat, A. Pfitzner, P. Bauduin. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **141** (2019) 6890-6899.

[3] M. Hohenschutz, P. Bauduin, C. G. Lopez, B. Förster, W. Richtering *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **62** (2023) e202210208

[4] T. Yamase *Chem. Rev.* **98** (1998) 307-326

Bicontinuous nanophasic amphiphilic conetworks, their gels and nanohybrids for advanced applications: from intelligent drug release to highly efficient nanocatalysts and beyond

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Undoubtedly, multicomponent polymer assemblies have gained significant interest over the years due to their special properties and to the large variety of application possibilities. Among such macromolecular materials, amphiphilic conetworks (APCNs), composed of chemically (covalently) bonded hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymer chains, belong to a special class of rapidly emerging nanostructured materials with various unique structural features and characteristics. Due to the immiscibility of the components, the synthesis of such macromolecular assemblies is quite challenging. Several successful synthetic routes have recently been developed by us, including various protection-deprotection schemes. Unique bicontinuous (cocontinuous) nanophase separated morphology exists in APCNs in a broad composition window with domain sizes in the range of ~2-30 nm [1-5]. This provides unprecedented possibilities to obtain various new specialty intelligent (smart, responsive) and organic solvent selective superabsorbent poly(ionic liquid) conetwork gels, and catalytically active organic-inorganic nanohybrids by applying one of the nanophases as nanoreactor. These novel materials have a variety of high value-added potential applications from specialty nanohybrids to biomaterials, sensor, organic superabsorbents etc.

Acknowledgements. Support by the National Research, Development and Innovation Office, Hungary (NN116252, NN129366, K135946, PD139162) and the European Research Area ERA-Chemistry program is acknowledged.

[1] Petróczy, A.; Szanka, I.; Wacha, A.; Varga, Z.; Thomann, Y.; Thomann, R.; Mülhaupt, R.; Bereczki, L.; Hegyesi, N.; Iván, B. *Gels* **2025**, *11*, 318.

[2] Pásztor, Sz.; Becsei, B.; Szarka, Gy.; Thomann, Y.; Thomann, R.; Mülhaupt, R.; Iván, B. *Materials* **2020**, *13*, 4822.

[3] Stumphauser, T.; Kasza, Gy.; Domján, A.; Wacha, A.; Varga, Z.; Thomann, Y.; Thomann, R.; Pásztoi, B.; Trötschler, T.; Kerschler, B.; Mülhaupt, R.; Iván, B. *Polymers* **2020**, *12*, 2292.

[4] Fodor, Cs.; Kali, G.; Thomann, R.; Thomann, Y.; Iván, B.; Mülhaupt, R. *RSC Adv.* **2017**, *7*, 6827-6837.

[5] Iván, B.; Haraszti, M.; Erdődi, G.; Scherble, J.; Thomann, R.; Mülhaupt, R. *Macromol. Symp.* **2005**, *227*, 265-274.

Control of cell and tissue stiffness by filamentous biopolymer networks and particle inclusions

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Filamentous biopolymer networks are ubiquitous in biology. Collagen fibers form much of the extracellular matrix, the cytoskeleton controls cell mechanics, and chromatin fibers span the volume of the nucleus. The mechanical properties of biopolymer fibers, the way in which the fibers link into networks, the reorganization of network structure by enzymes and molecular motors, and the types of cells within the network all affect the way in which these materials respond to mechanical stress. One of the most striking characteristics of stiff or semiflexible polymer networks is their non-linear rheology, characterized by a high degree of stiffening in shear deformation that does not occur in gels or elastomers formed by flexible polymers (1). When sparsely connected fibrous networks such as the cytoskeleton or the extracellular matrix are deformed in shear, only a small fraction of the fibers carries most of the load, and remodeling enzymes can preferentially react with either the tensed or the slack fibers to remodel the network to optimize its response to mechanical stresses (2).

When particles larger than the network mesh size are present, several of the nonlinear responses of biopolymer networks are qualitatively altered: fibrous networks switch from compression-softening to compression-stiffening but lose their strain stiffening in response to shear or extension (3). Reproducing these nonlinear mechanical responses in synthetic polymeric materials is essential for creation of improved materials for tissue engineering and other applications.

- [1] C. Storm, J. J. Pastore, F. C. MacKintosh, T. C. Lubensky, and P. A. Janmey, *Nature* **435** (2005):191-194.
- [2] T.T. Dutta, L. Suprewicz, P. Mollenkopf, X. C. Shi, L. Hoole, J. X. Tang, and P. A. Janmey, *Polymer* **336** (2025) ARTN 128860.
- [3] A. S. G. van Oosten, X. Chen, L. Chin, K. Cruz, A. E. Patteson, K. Pogoda, V. B. Shenoy, and P. A. Janmey, 2019, *Nature* **573** (2019):96-102.

Deconstructing Polymer Networks to Decode Their Structures and Impart New Functions

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Polymer networks are among the most important materials in modern society, yet our ability to predict how their molecular structure governs their bulk performance remains incomplete. In this talk, I will describe our group's efforts to combine efficient synthetic methods, designed model networks, and physical organic chemistry principles to both construct and deconstruct polymer networks in ways that reveal hidden structure and enable new functions.

I will first discuss Network Disassembly Spectrometry (NDS),¹ which enables direct measurement of topological defects in polymer networks by converting latent structural information into analytically readable molecular fragments. Building on this platform, I will describe our development time-dependent NDS, which reveals that network deconstruction itself can be topology-selective, uncovering a link between network topology and chemical reactivity and suggesting new opportunities for “topological editing” of synthetic macromolecules.² These insights into hidden topology motivated a broader question: can topological design be used not only to understand polymer networks, but also to make them tougher and more sustainable (Figure 1)? I will next describe our recent efforts in polymer mechanochemistry, where force-responsive covalent motifs are strategically embedded into networks to control fracture^{3,4} and ballistic energy dissipation.⁵

[1] M. Zhong *et al.*, *Science* **2016**, *353*, 1264–1268.

[2] A. Davis *et al.*, *ChemRxiv* **2026**, doi:10.26434/chemrxiv.10001693/v1

[3] S. Wang *et al.*, *Science* **2023**, *380*, 1248–1252.

[4] A. Herzog-Arbeitman *et al.*, *Nat. Chem.* **2026**, *18*, 309–316.

[5] Z. Sang *et al.*, *Nature* **2026**, *accepted*.

Defect engineering in covalent adaptable networks

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The design of covalent adaptable networks (CANs) has long focused on the chemistry of the exchange reaction, which influences mechanical properties via its thermodynamics and kinetics. However, like all polymer networks, CANs inevitably contain topological defects such as loops and dangling ends. For many associative mechanisms, excess nucleophilic groups are necessary to mediate the exchange reaction, but also influence the mechanical properties as dangling ends. Moreover, theoretical studies suggest that loops play an important role in accelerating stress relaxation.¹ Unlike conventional static networks, the loop fraction in CANs is not set at synthesis.^{2,3} Using network disassembly spectrometry, we study the impact of dynamic bonds on loop fraction and the effect of loop fraction on viscoelasticity. These studies reveal opportunities to manipulate CAN properties via topological defects—“defect engineering” for polymer networks.

[1] S. Ciarella, F. Sciortino, W. G. Ellenbroek, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **121** (2018) [058003](#).

[2] C. M. Hemmingsen, S. J. Chapman, C. Deng, Y. Xiong, C. J. Hanley, V. Zhang, M. Olvera de la Cruz, J. A. Kalow, *Macromolecules* **58** (2025) 7957-7966.

[3] D. Ezzeddine, D. C. Barzycki, R. G. Ricarte, *ACS Macro Lett.* **14** (2025), [1011-1018](#).

Stimuli responsive covalent nanogels: a chemically versatile drug delivery platform

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Nanogels are hydrogels within the nanometer range consisting of crosslinked porous polymer networks with the ability to retain high volumes of water or biological fluids whilst maintaining their structure. They have a wide range of chemical flexibility in their design, allowing their characteristics such as size, charge, degree of porosity and degradability to be easily tuned by the choice of monomeric building blocks. Since nanogels can retain a high volume of water, they are extremely biocompatible. This excellent and unique property makes them an ideal nanoplatform for the delivery of biological drugs such as enzymes and proteins. Nanogels are prepared via polymerization of monomers or precursors by chemical crosslinking or via physical crosslinking of preformed polymers via amphiphilic or electrostatic interactions. In particular, covalently crosslinked and co-polymerized nanogels (Figure 1) have superior properties as they offer: 1) encapsulation stability for biologically sensitive payloads, 2) low immunogenicity and toxicity and can be designed to be fully biodegradable, 3) delivery of multiple biological payloads in a single nanogel, facilitating combination therapies, 4) aqueous-based synthesis that is readily scalable, and 5) soft nanoparticle architectures that can squeeze through restricted sites under hemodynamic shear flow. In this manner, nanogels are an ideal delivery platform for biological drugs, especially since biological therapeutics can be encapsulated using mild aqueous reaction conditions. In this talk I will present some of our work on stimuli-responsive nanogels [1-4].

Figure 1. Covalently crosslinked and co-polymerized stimuli responsive nanogels

[1] R. Dabas, N. Navaratnam, H. Iino, S. Matile, D. Carling, D. S. Rueda, S. Saidjalolove, N. Kamaly, *Mater. Today Bio* 215 (2025) 101425. [2] R. Dabas, N. Kamaly, *Eur. Polym. J.* 215 (2024) 113183. [3] S. Patri, N. T. K. Thanh, N. Kamaly, *Nanoscale* (2024), DOI: 10.1039/D4NR02058H. [4] B. S. Basak, H. A. Khare, M. Roursgaard, P. J. Kempen, J. H. Lee, S. Bazban-Shotorbani, M. Kraemer, S. Chernyy, T. L. Andresen, K. Almdal, N. Kamaly, *Biomacromolecules* 22 (2020) 386.

Soft colloids at interfaces

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Microgels are soft polymeric objects with an internal gel-like structure and overall dimensions in the colloidal regime [1]. It is known that microgels strongly adsorb to liquid/liquid and liquid/air interfaces. Many studies in the last two decades attempted to understand the phase behavior of soft, deformable microgels at such liquid interfaces. Typically, the microstructures in dependence on applied surface pressure are studied *ex situ* using transfer of microgel monolayers from the liquid to a solid interface followed by investigation with different types of microscopies. Interestingly, *in situ* studies at the liquid interface are scarce to nonexistent.

We tackled two challenges in this respect: 1) We managed to synthesize core-shell microgels that are large enough to be studied by optical microscopy or small-angle scattering using light [2]. 2) We build a setup that combines a Langmuir trough with small-angle light scattering (LT-SALS) that allows for the large area study of monolayers during compression with excellent resolution in time [3]. In this work we present first results of the *in situ* analysis of microgel monolayers at air/water interfaces. Instead of the commonly reported solid-solid isostructural phase transition [4,5], we find a continuous compression of the monolayer with continuously decreasing interparticle distances [3]. Furthermore, drying of a thin liquid film with the monolayer at the liquid/air interface on hydrophilic and hydrophobic substrates shines light on the complex interplay between softness, adhesion and capillary interactions [6].

We then studied the role of uniaxial compression/expansion by using our LT-SALS setup. Upon compression and/or expansion the monolayer remains somewhat anisotropic and a fast and a slow relaxation process is observed during an equilibration phase, i.e. when compression or expansion is stopped. Possible explanations for this behavior will be discussed.

[1] M. Karg, et al., *Langmuir* **35** (2019) 6231-6255.

[2] K. Kuk, et al., *Gels* **8** (2022) 516.

[3] K. Kuk, et al., *Soft Matter* **19** (2023) 175-188.

[4] M.Rey, et al., *Soft Matter* **12** (2016) 3545-3557.

[5] A. Rauh, et al., *Soft Matter* **13** (2017) 158-169.

[6] K. Kuk, et al., *Advanced Science* **11** (2024) 2406977.

Transition phenomena in vitrimers

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Vitrimers, a class of dynamic polymer networks, can reversibly change from a cross-linked thermoset state into a viscous flow state, typically controlled by temperature. Although this transition evidently takes place, the nature of the transformation is still poorly understood. A corresponding characteristic anomaly in thermodynamic susceptibilities, such as the specific heat capacity, remains elusive. Current interpretations of the physical nature of the underlying transformation process range from a second glass transition to a dynamic depercolation transition [1,2].

In this talk, the temperature-dependent transition behaviour of vitrimers is critically revisited from the perspective of shear relaxation and thermal volume expansion, and placed in the context of other transition phenomena in polymers [3]. To overcome the time-dependent thermal activation process of bond exchange, UV irradiation was employed. The photo-initiation enables the vitrimer transition in a model vitrimer system on significantly shorter timescales than the thermal process and amplifies the macroscopic response. The refractive index and the dynamic thermal volume expansion were used as probes to gain new insights into the transition behaviour of vitrimers, and are simultaneously measured via temperature-modulated optical refractometry (TMOR).

[1] M. Capelot, M. Unterlass, F. Tournilhac, L. Leibler, *ACS Macro Letters* **1** (2012), 789–92

[2] A. Klingler & J.-K. Krüger, in *Multifunctionality of Polymer Composites (2nd Ed.)*, Elsevier (2025), 1041-1076.

[3] A. Klingler, D. Reisinger, S. Schlögl, B. Wetzels, U. Breuer, J.-K. Krüger, *Macromolecules* **57** (2024), 4246–53.

Microgels as stabilizers for foams: A multiscale approach

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Foams appear in many applications such as in personal care products, firefighting and food technology. An elegant tool to tune the foam stability is the addition of polymers of different charge, amphiphilicity or molecular architecture. An example, which will be addressed here are foams which are stabilized by stimuli-responsive microgels.

For understanding macroscopic foam properties, it is important to get deeper insight into the different length scales, *i.e.* the structuring of microgels at the *air/water interface*, in *foam films*, which separate the *air bubbles* from each other and (macroscopic) *foams*.

The presentation will focus on microgels based on Poly-N-isopropylacrylamid (PNIPAM). Their stiffness and deformation at the air/liquid interface are controlled by the amount of cross-linker content, which dominates the lateral pattern formation at the liquid interface [1]. A challenge for studies of microgel-stabilized foam films is their massive inhomogeneities, which make it difficult to measure the respective foam film thickness. To get insight into foam film properties, we use a camera-based thin film pressure balance to study microgel-stabilized foam films in terms of disjoining pressure inside the foam films, drainage kinetics, and foam film stability [2, 3]. Film thickness profiles give insights into particle bridging, agglomeration and network formation in the foam films. A correlation is shown with the mechanical properties of the microgels as determined by atomic force microscopy (AFM) nanoindentation measurements. For a complete picture, optical foam scanning, conductivity and small angle neutron scattering (SANS) measurements on macroscopic foams provide additional insights into the link between foams and single foam films [2, 3, 4].

[1] H. Robertson, J. Zimmer, A. Sifuentes Name; C. Lux; S. Stock; R. von Klitzing; O. Soltwedel, *Soft Matter*, 22, 127 – 136, **2026**, DOI: [10.1039/D5SM00115C](https://doi.org/10.1039/D5SM00115C)

[2] M. Kühnhammer, K. Gräff, E. Loran, O. Soltwedel, O. Löhmann, H. Frielinghaus, R. von Klitzing, *Soft Matter*, 18, 9249 - 9262, **2022**, DOI: [10.1039/D2SM01021F](https://doi.org/10.1039/D2SM01021F)

[3]https://download.hrz.tu-darmstadt.de/media/FB05/SMal/V0011_Microgel_Foam_Films_KG_v2.mp4

[4] M. Kühnhammer, L. Braun, M. Ludwig, O. Soltwedel, L. Chiappisi, R. von Klitzing, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, 55, 758, **2022**, DOI: [10.1107/S1600576722004691](https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600576722004691)

Resolving the Effects of Chemistry and Network Structure on the Viscoelasticity of Dynamic Covalent Networks

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The viscoelasticity of dynamic covalent networks arises from the interplay between bond exchange kinetics and polymer chain dynamics. In this work, we will discuss recent efforts in our lab to use catalysts as well as multiple dynamic bonds to co-optimize elasticity and flow in dynamic covalent networks. First, we will discuss our recent work¹ on how catalysts can be used to control bond dynamics *independently* of network structure. Here, we introduce ‘time-temperature-chemistry’ superposition principles to universally describe dynamics across many decades of time by understanding both elasticity and concentration effects. Subsequently, we extend this concept to consider mechanistically-distinct dynamic bonds that use *shared* reactants. We show that by reversibly sequestering reactive intermediates via dissociative covalent bonds, elastic properties of networks can be fully preserved at low temperatures. However, bond dissociation at high temperature can be harnessed by associative exchange pathways to access the low viscosities needed for reprocessing. Finally, we highlight the distinct role of the dynamics of ‘free’ polymer ends in mediating these chemical pathways and the emergent viscoelastic response.

[1] S. Kannapadi, R. Ghanta, J.J. Rivera-Otero, A.S. Cook, E.F. Granzeier, F. Scanu, J.J. Griebler, S.A. Rogers, and A.S. Kuentler, *Macromolecules* **59** (2026), 3465–3476.

A Unified Scaling for Freezing Morphodynamics in Polymer Solution Droplets

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The freezing of polymer solutions underlies a wide range of processes, from cryogel fabrication to ice templating, yet a predictive framework linking transport to macroscopic morphology remains lacking. In this talk, I present a unified study of the morphodynamics of polymer solution droplets during unidirectional freezing.

Using poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) and poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate (PEGDA) as model systems, we show that polymer additives fundamentally alter both freezing dynamics and final droplet shape. In dilute solutions, freezing is governed by heat transport and follows a Stefan-type balance, while polymer-induced changes in density and swelling progressively suppress the classical pointy ice tip [1]. This suppression occurs up to the overlap concentration, beyond which polymer chains interact, and swelling is arrested.

At higher concentrations and molecular weights, polymer chains are rejected by the advancing freezing front, leading to the formation of a concentrated boundary layer ahead of the interface. This accumulation increases local viscosity and limits solute redistribution, slowing front propagation and suppressing deformation. Freezing thus transitions to a transport-limited regime in which droplet morphology becomes increasingly isotropic. This transition is first captured by a Capillary number, which quantifies the competition between viscous stresses and capillary forces. In parallel, the coupled transport of heat and solute within the interfacial boundary layer introduces a Lewis number that compares thermal and mass diffusion. Together, these effects define a single dimensionless control parameter, the Capillary–Lewis number, that governs both freezing dynamics and droplet morphology.

When expressed in terms of this parameter, circularity, deformation, and freezing time collapse onto a universal curve spanning over eight orders of magnitude, revealing a sharp transition between diffusion-dominated and viscous–capillary regimes. These results establish a minimal transport-based framework for predicting and controlling freezing morphologies in polymer solutions.

[1] S. Kharal and JF. Louf, *Langmuir* **40** (2024), 118-124.

Furan chemistry for the design of sustainable network polymers

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Petroleum-derived compounds such as bisphenol A (BPA) are widely used in thermosets, but their reliance on non-renewable feedstocks raises sustainability concerns. This has spurred the development of bio-based alternatives, with dynamic network polymers emerging as more sustainable substitutes. Among bio-based chemical platforms, furan-based compounds are promising, as their furan moieties enable reversible Diels–Alder (DA) chemistry. Here, we introduce a rigid, bio-based monomer, 3,4-di(furan-2-yl)cyclobutane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid (CBDA), and explore its potential as a renewable platform for the synthesis of polyesters and thermoreversible crosslinked polymers via DA chemistry[1]. The rigid cyclobutane core and furan functionalities of CBDA provide enhanced thermal and mechanical properties while enabling dynamic covalent networks aimed at achieving material reprocessability and self-healing ability. Novel polyesters derived from CBDA and aliphatic diols were synthesized and exhibited limited solubility that appears intrinsic. Model studies confirmed the reactivity of CBDA in DA chemistry, demonstrating cycloaddition with mono-, bis-, and trismaleimides at 65 °C and reversible retro-DA reactions near 110 °C. These insights define the structure–reactivity landscape of CBDA, guiding the design of renewable polymer networks with tunable properties.

[1] Grilo, L. M., Faoro, S., Agostinho, B., Sousa, A. F., Guigo, N., Loos, K., Maniar, D., & Lacerda, T. M. *Polymer Chemistry* **16** (34) (2025) 3808-3818.

Design of Conductive Eutectogels for Bioelectronics

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In this presentation we will show our recent works in the development of eutectogels. Eutectogels are soft ionic materials made by embedding (deep) eutectic solvents (DES) within a three-dimensional polymer network. This presentation will discuss the design of innovative eutectogels such as bio-based eutectogels, hydrophobic eutectogels or mixed ionic electronic conducting eutectogels. After the discussion of the synthetic and characterization methods, the presentation will include its additive manufacturing 3D printing and some examples of applications in bioelectronic devices. The presentation will highlight some of the recent results of the Staff Exchange project IONBIKE 2.0 (www.ionbike.eu) including:

- Preparation of bio-based eutectogels based on photopolymerization and 3D printing of natural deep eutectic solvents [1].
- Eutectogels based on hydrophobic deep eutectic solvents [2].
- Organic Mixed-Ionic electronic conducting eutectogels based on the combination of PEDOT conducting polymers and DES. [3].
- Application of eutectogels in bioelectronic devices such as OECTs and bioelectrodes for body signal recording and stimulation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sebastián Locatelli et al. ACS Appl. Polym. Mater. 2025, 7, 5, 2945–2954
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acsapm.4c03592>
- [2] Jon López de Lacalle et al. ACS Materials Lett. 2023, 5, 12, 3340–3346
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmaterialslett.3c00938>
- [3] Ana Aguzin et al. Mater. Horiz., 2023, 10, 2516–252
<https://doi.org/10.1039/D3MH00310H>
- [4] Yizhou Zhong et al. Chem. Mater. 2024, 36, 4, 1841–1854
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.3c02385>

Polymer gels whose network strands are super-stretched

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From a structural viewpoint, a polymer network should be able to deform to its ultimate state, where the majority of its strands reach their stretching limit. However, most real polymer networks cannot deform to such ultimate states. Recently, we have found some experimental methods to achieve deformation of a polymer network up to its structural limit. The first method is the "molecular stent" method for swelling [1,2]. To swell a polymer network beyond its original swelling equilibrium, linear polymers (molecular stents) are introduced into the network. The trapped linear polymers generate additional osmotic pressure, and the swelling equilibrium shifts to a higher degree of swelling (Figure). At the conference, I will introduce the phenomena of excess swelling and swelling-induced degradation of a polymer network. The second method is the use of a double-network system for typical modes of deformation, such as uniaxial stretching. A real polymer network typically breaks before reaching its ultimate deformation state because of stress concentration at defects. To avoid such stress concentration, a soft, supportive network is introduced into the principal network to form a double-network material. Since the supportive network suppresses stress concentration in the principal network, the double-network material can be stretched to the limit of the principal network. The resulting fully stretched polymer network exhibits several unique mechanical and chemical behaviors, including inverse mechanical-swelling coupling and positive energy elasticity [3].

Figure 1. Excess swelling of a polymer network using the molecular stent method

[1] T. Nakajima, J. P. Gong *et al.*, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2012**, *22*, 4426–4432

[2] S. Ohmura, T. Nakajima *et al.*, *Small* **2026**, *21*, 2503209

[3] C. Imaoka, T. Nakajima *et al.*, *Sci. Adv.* **2023**, *9*, eabp8351

Aryl Amides for the Design of Covalent Adaptable Networks

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With inspiration from the strong hydrogen bonds of salicylic acid and derivatives,^[1] this study introduces a *dynamic covalent chemistry* platform via *direct transamidation of aromatic amides*, establishing a new strategy for the development of (*re*)processable polyamide networks. While amide bonds are well known for their chemical stability, we report here that direct transamidation at elevated temperatures (>140 °C) can be facilitated by adjacent aromatic groups without any additional catalyst. It is also demonstrated that the exchange reaction is influenced by the electron density of the aromatic ring and is significantly enhanced by *intramolecular hydrogen bonding*. This principle enables the straightforward synthesis of cross-linked poly(salicylamide) and poly(benzamide) structures as a new generation of *covalent adaptable networks*.^[2]

While intermolecular hydrogen bonds improve the tensile strength of poly(benzamide) networks, the additional intramolecular hydrogen bonds in poly(salicylamide) networks promote transamidation exchange, thereby enhancing their flow capability. Both dynamic poly(salicylamide) and poly(benzamide) networks exhibit stress relaxation ability, with activation energies of 127 and 224 kJ·mol⁻¹, respectively. As a result, these polyamide networks can undergo multiple reprocessing cycles at elevated temperatures (e.g., 180 °C) without significant loss of properties, contributing to the expanding library of *polyamide-based covalent adaptable networks*.

[1] Gholami, S, Aarabi, M and Grabowski, S. J. J. Phys. Chem. A **125** (2021) 1526–1539.

[2] Bowman, C, Du Prez, F, and Kalow, J. Polym. Chem. **11** (2020) 5295–5296.

Silk fibroin-based multiple-shape-memory organohydrogels

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Unlike synthetic gels, biological systems such as cells and tissues have synergistic biphasic structures composed of both hydrophilic and lyophilic domains. This dual-phase organization gives them unique properties, including adaptive mechanical behavior and resistance to freezing. Inspired by these systems, hydrogels that integrate hydrophilic and lyophilic components known as organohydrogels (OHGs) have emerged as promising materials capable of replicating such biological functionalities and offering broad application potential.

We will present a simple method for fabricating adaptive OHGs with controllable and programmable mechanical properties, as well as multi-shape-memory capability [1]. The designed OHGs consist of a continuous silk fibroin (SF) hydrogel phase and dispersed hydrophobic microdomains formed from semicrystalline poly(*n*-octadecyl acrylate) (PC18A) and several long-chain saturated hydrocarbons (HCs) with various chain lengths between 14 and 32 carbon atoms [2]. Notably, SF acts as a natural self-emulsifying agent, enabling the formation of oil-in-water emulsions without external chemical emulsifiers, making it an environmentally friendly alternative.

First, a stable oil-in-water emulsion was prepared by dispersing *n*-octadecyl acrylate (C18A) monomer and HCs in an aqueous SF solution. To enhance emulsion stability over time, gelation of the SF continuous phase was triggered by adding ethanol, which induces a conformational transition in SF from random coil to β -sheet structures. Next, the C18A+HC droplets within the emulsion were polymerized in situ under UV irradiation in the presence of a photoinitiator. This process produced high-strength OHGs exhibiting effective triple- or quintuple-shape memory behavior.

[1] C. B. Oral, B. Yetiskin, E. Su., and O. Okay. ACS Appl. Bio Mater. 6 (2023), 1594-1603.

[2] C. B. Oral, E Su, and O.Okay, ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces 16 (2024) 56146–56158.

Fracture Across Scales in Polymer Networks

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Polymer networks in the form of gels, elastomers, and thermosets are some of the most common and important polymer materials due to their high extensibility. Substantial recent work has focused on how to also increase their toughness, increasing durability and enabling use in a wider range of applications. These experimental efforts are greatly facilitated by an increased theoretical understanding of fracture. Our lab has developed a coarse-grained simulation engine that is capable of performing simulations of large networks, reproducing key macroscopic properties.[1] Herein, this methodology is applied across different length scales to investigate how individual bond strengths translate into chain breakage and into disordered net topologies within networks that lead to the observed macroscopic failure properties. First, we investigate how the topological position of strong and weak bonds within a polymer network can impact its overall strength, explaining key experimental observations that topology can fundamentally change the role of weak bonds in a polymer.[2,3] Using scaling relationships, we illustrate the key regime in which these experiments operate and why this regime gives such unexpected results. Building on this work that focuses on local connectivity, we expand to larger-scale net structures and explore how the differences in these nets are manifest in varying fracture properties.[4] Examining the spectrum from idealized net to a fully disordered topology provides insight into the quantitative role that topological defects play in controlling network properties.

[1] Arora, Lin, and Olsen. *Macromolecules* **2021**.

[2] Beech et al. *ACS Macro Letters* **2023**.

[3] Herzog-Arbeitman et al. *Nat. Chem.* **2026**.

[4] Sen and Olsen. *Phys. Rev. Materials* **2025**.

Amphiphilic Polymer Conetworks: Self-assembly, Mechanical Properties, Recyclability and an Application

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I will present our recent work on amphiphilic polymer conetworks (APCNs) [1], highlighting the self-healing capability and recyclability conferred upon these materials by their dynamic covalent groups installed in the crosslinks [2] of the particular APCNs. Furthermore, I will indicate that our APCNs are highly stretchable, 10-fold or more, despite their high water content, ~80% [3,4]. Most importantly, I will share with you our efforts to instill into these materials aqueous self-assembly with long-range ordering [3,4], as this is determined using small-angle scattering.

APCN self-assembly and the effect of deformation on the obtained morphologies was also investigated using simulations [5] and Flory-Huggins-type calculations [6]. The results of these investigations indicate that APCN bulk melts organize into the common linear block copolymer morphologies, *i.e.*, lamellae, cylinders and spheres. However, tension transforms these structures into lamellae, whereas compression transforms them to cylinders, with both transformations driven by the reduction of the interfacial area upon the application of the particular type of deformation.

Finally, I will present an energy-related APCN application, namely the employment of APCNs as matrices for gel polymer electrolytes for use in lithium ion batteries [7].

[1] C. S. Patrickios, Ed., „Amphiphilic Polymer Co-networks: Synthesis, Properties, Modelling and Applications“, The Royal Society of Chemistry, Cambridge, UK (2020).

[2] D. E. Apostolides, C. S. Patrickios, *Polym. Int.* **67** (2018) 627-649.

[3] D. E. Apostolides, G. Michael *et al.*, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **16** (2024) 23813-23825.

[4] D. E. Apostolides, G. Michael *et al.*, *Chem. Mater.* **37** (2025) 5515-5528.

[5] D. G. Tsalikis, M. Ciobanu, C. S. Patrickios, Y. Higuchi, *Macromolecules* **56** (2023) 9299-9311.

[6] K. Andronikou, C. S. Patrickios, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **227** (2026) e00356.

[7] D. E. Apostolides, C. S. Patrickios *et al.*, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **227** (2026) e00363.

Toward Programmable Emulsion Stability with Responsive Microgels

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Microgels such as poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (PNIPAM) readily adsorb irreversibly at fluid interfaces and are known to stabilize Pickering emulsions and foams [1]. This stabilization arises from microgel deformation and their ability to form interfacial entanglements through their polymer shells, thereby imparting interfacial elasticity [2]. Notably, these systems can be destabilized on demand due to the temperature-induced swelling-to-collapse transition of PNIPAM. However, predicting their final properties remains challenging, as they result from a complex interplay between microgel architecture, size, emulsification conditions, and interfacial conformation. Recent advances have improved this understanding, particularly regarding the role of microgel concentration [3] and internal structure, spanning from ultra core-shell to more homogeneous architectures [4].

A promising strategy to further control emulsion stability involves intercrosslinking microgels at interfaces, thereby enhancing interfacial elasticity. In contrast to permanent chemical crosslinking, physical multivalent interactions offer reversibility. In this context, nanometric anions such as polyoxometalates (POMs), which belong to the class of superchaotropic ions with low charge density, can interact with a wide range of nonionic polymers. They have been shown to induce internal crosslinking within PNIPAM microgels. Beyond reducing microgel softness, POMs also promote additional reversible crosslinking between microgels at interfaces, ultimately leading to enhanced emulsion stability [5].

[1] V. Ravaine, V. Schmitt, „ Micro and Nano Gels Synthesis Characterization Modelling and Applications” Volume 1 (2026), 349–383.

[2] M.-C. Taty, E. Laurichesse et al., *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **629** (2023) 288

[3] A. Brézault, N. Sanson et al., *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **704** (2026) 139371

[4] A. Brézault, P. Perrin et al., *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **709** (2026) 139858

[5] S. Buritica, J. Gutteriez, et al., *J. Colloid. Interf. Sci.* **699** (2025) 138257

Network Topology and Blend Properties of Polybutadiene Vitrimers

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Rubbers consist of polymer chains covalently bonded by permanent cross-links. Their elasticity, toughness, and solvent resistance make them essential in the aerospace, agricultural, and automotive industries. Their permanent cross-links, however, hinder recycling and create significant challenges for end-of-life disposal. In contrast, vitrimers are polymer networks featuring dynamic covalent cross-links that engage in an associative exchange — new bonds form before old ones break. This mechanism preserves network connectivity while allowing topological changes, rendering vitrimers insoluble yet processable at high temperatures. Although these paradoxical traits suggest that vitrimers may be a promising rubber replacement, the relationship between their molecular structure and macroscopic properties remains an open question. Here, we combine experiments and theory to elucidate the underlying physical chemistry of vitrimers. Our study focuses on a model system composed of polybutadiene (PB) networks cross-linked by dioxaborolane linkages that exchange via a metathesis mechanism, alongside control PB networks with permanent cross-links. First, we evaluate the static network properties. Cross-link density is quantified using a network disassembly approach. Differential scanning calorimetry, shear modulus, and vapor swelling measurements indicate that PB vitrimers contain fewer network topology defects than their permanent counterparts. Second, we perform linear viscoelastic measurements. PB vitrimers exhibit two distinct relaxation regimes. The fast dynamics correspond to segmental motions of the PB backbone. The slow dynamics, however, exhibit a much stronger temperature sensitivity than predicted by sticky Rouse theory. Third, we prepare blends of PB and polydimethylsiloxane vitrimers to investigate the relationship between morphology and viscoelasticity.

Resolving the Nanoscale Architecture of Microgels at the Air-Water Interface

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Microgels are soft, three-dimensional colloidal networks comprised of cross-linked polymers, whose surface activity [1] and mechanical properties [2] can be precisely tuned via cross-linker density. In the bulk phase, particularly when composed of thermoresponsive polymers like poly(oligoethylene glycol methacrylate), these microgels exhibit stimuli-responsive behaviour, allowing their size and surface charge density to be controlled via temperature modulations. However, transitioning these particles from the bulk to an interface alters their physicochemical behaviour [3].

Here we map the structural evolution of polymer microgels as they transition from bulk solutions to distinct interfacial environments. At the solid-water interface, *ex situ* atomic force microscopy (AFM) reveals decorated microgel surfaces can impart functional, stimuli-responsive elasticity. In contrast, adsorption at the fluid air-water interface induces significant structural deformation relative to the bulk state, causing the core-shell particles to flatten dramatically into a two-dimensional core-corona (or “fried-egg”) morphology.

Accurately capturing these disparate behaviours requires tailored characterisation. While AFM provides essential, high-resolution structural insight at solid substrates, it is inherently limited when evaluating long-range lateral structure over delicate fluid boundaries. To address this, *in situ* specular and off-specular X-ray reflectivity (XRR) is utilised to directly probe the air-water interface without doping or transfer-induced artefacts. This technique successfully resolves the long-range vertical and lateral ordering of the microgels as a function of surface pressure [4]. Furthermore, by directly comparing this *in situ* XRR data with *ex situ* AFM measurements, we explicitly confirm and quantify the structural transfer effects that occur during Langmuir-Blodgett deposition, highlighting the critical need for *in situ* methodologies when evaluating interfacial microgel behaviour.

[1] Karg *et al.*, Langmuir 35 (2019) 6231--6255.

[2] Burmistrova *et al.*, Colloid Polym Sci 289 (2011) 613—624.

[3] Kuk *et al.*, Soft Matter 19 (2023) 175–188.

[4] Robertson *et al.*, Soft Matter 22 (2026) 127—138.

Dynamic Phenyllogous Ester Networks: Looking at Transesterification from a Different Perspective

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Since the seminal work of Leibler et al. [1], transesterification has emerged as a powerful dynamic covalent chemistry (DCC) for designing tailor-made covalent adaptable networks (CANs). Its versatility enables the preparation of (re)processable thermosets with a wide range of properties using different strategies such as the introduction of external or covalently-bonded catalysts as well as neighboring group participation effects [2]. However, despite being one of the oldest chemical motifs used in CANs, aromatic esters remain largely underexplored due to the poor nucleophilicity of phenols compared to aliphatic alcohols, resulting in a slow exchange, thereby requiring very high processing temperatures.

Here, we present a strategy to incorporate phenyllogous esters as dynamic crosslinks in low- T_g thermosets using activated phenols. Model compounds studies were first performed to evaluate the dynamicity of these motifs considering substitution patterns (ortho-, meta-, para-) and electronic effects (Hammett parameters). These revealed significant differences in reactivity, which were further supported by DFT calculations.

Building on these insights, CANs were readily prepared from the most promising motifs and their thermal, chemical and dynamic properties were evaluated. Finally, the chemical recyclability was also demonstrated, thus highlighting the potential of the phenyllogous ester DCC as a viable platform for the development of reprocessable and recyclable thermosetting materials [3].

[1] D. Montarnal, M. Capelot, F. Tournilhac, L. Leibler. *Science* **334** (2011) 965-968.

[2] M. Delahaye, J. M. Winne, F. Du Prez, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **141** (2021) 15277-15287.

[3] A. Roig, P. Cnudde, H. Kriekemans, V. Scholiers, M. M. J. Smulders, F. E. Du Prez (submitted).

Precision Gel Science: From Homogeneous to Heterogeneous Gels

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A central unresolved issue in gel science is how to define and quantify network inhomogeneity in a universal, physically grounded manner. Although chemically crosslinked gels are almost inevitably heterogeneous, the field has lacked a general criterion that specifies how far a real network deviates from an ideal homogeneous state, making rigorous structure-property comparisons difficult. Our route toward “Precision Gel Science” therefore starts from tetrahedron-like poly(ethylene glycol) (TetraPEG) gels, which provide nearly ideal homogeneous networks and a benchmark for relating connectivity to swelling and elasticity [1,2]. In a good solvent, these model networks obey a universal semidilute osmotic-pressure scaling law independent of detailed architecture [2], thereby defining a reference state for a homogeneous gel.

Fig. 1. Hierarchy of Gel Network Heterogeneity

We use this reference to analyze heterogeneous poly(*N,N*-dimethylacrylamide) gels formed by free-radical polymerization (FRP) and reversible addition-fragmentation chain transfer (RAFT) polymerization. Comparing measured osmotic pressure with the semidilute reference quantifies the osmotically active fraction of the network and hence its inhomogeneity [3]. FRP gels deviate strongly from the homogeneous limit, especially at low monomer concentration or high crosslinker content. RAFT suppresses large nanogel clusters and improves transparency, but transparent gels can still remain osmotically inhomogeneous. Increasing the monomer concentration beyond a critical level (240 g L⁻¹ for PDMAAm/MBAAm) restores osmotic homogeneity irrespective of FRP or RAFT, whereas RAFT alone gives only partial improvement under highly crosslinked conditions.

Mechanical analysis adds a second filter. Even among osmotically homogeneous gels, elastic effectiveness depends on topology: RAFT-derived networks more closely follow the ideal proportionality between shear modulus and cycle rank than FRP networks. These results establish a hierarchy of structural quality - optical transparency, osmotic homogeneity, and elastic effectiveness - and show how homogeneous model networks can guide the diagnosis and redesign of practical heterogeneous gels. The framework offers a general basis for rational gel design in soft materials and biointerfaces.

[1] T. Sakai et al., *Macromolecules* 41 (2008) 5379-5384.

[2] T. Yasuda et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 125 (2020) 267801.

[3] R. Ito et al., *Macromolecules* 58 (2025) 5487-5493.

With light towards functional dynamic polymer networks

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Combining the chemistry of dynamic covalent bonds with light-driven reactions offers versatile routes to advance the functionality of dynamic polymer networks. Herein, examples of photochemical reactions are provided, which are used to shape functional dynamic polymers along various length scales, to locally and reversibly control bond exchange kinetics and to (reversibly) reprogram material properties during post-processing steps [1]. In particular, reversibly switchable catalysts for promoting acid- and based- catalyzed bond exchange reactions are explored for reversible nanoimprint lithography, writing and erasing microstructures by photolithography, reversible reshaping and self-folding of photopolymers [2].

[1] D. Reisinger, A. Sietmann, A. Das, S. Plutzar, R. Korotkov, E. Rossegger, M. Walluch, S. Holler-Stangl, T. S. Hofer, F. Dielmann, F. Glorius, and S. Schlögl, *Advanced Materials*, **36** (2024), 2411307.

[2] D. Reisinger, L. Wimberger, R. Korotkov, M. Alfreider, T. F. Scott, N. R. Cameron, C. Boyer, and S. Schlögl, *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **147** (2025) 39671–3968.

Molding and actuating hydrogels for organ on chip development

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Organ on chip represents a next generation of *in vitro* biological models with a great potential in biology, biophysics and clinical application. In this context, mimicking the extracellular matrix composition, architecture as well as the forces experienced by the organ is crucial. In this talk, I will discuss how these different aspects can be implemented on chip to replicate *in vivo* conditions, and how they can be tuned to investigate their effects on the organ physiology.

Amphiphilic and Adaptive Polymer Gels with Model-Network Structure

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Amphiphilic polymer gels are composed of a polymer network with both hydrophilic and hydrophobic parts. They feature favorable properties with delicate dependency on the environmental medium polarity, such as environmentally sensitive viscoelasticity and selective permeability. To truly exploit this potential for applications, it is necessary to understand the interplay between the network nano- and microstructure and the resulting gel properties. We target at gaining such understanding in view of the preparation conditions, the resulting network structures, and the yet resulting gel properties, primarily focusing on their viscoelastic mechanics and permeabilities. This is done by adaption of the tetra-PEG approach for model-network synthesis to preparing amphiphilic model networks of two kinds: irreversibly and reversibly crosslinked [1].

[1] S. Seitel, D. Beyer, R. Scholz, C. Bunk, Y. El-Faramawi, J. Grün, K. Hagmann, F. Böhme, C. Holm, K. Saalwächter, F. H. Schacher, R. von Klitzing, M. Weinhart, M. Lang, S. Seiffert, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **227** (2026) e00497.

Bottlebrush elastomers and gels: Programming tissue-mimetic properties by architecture

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In contrast to biological networks, where mechanical properties can be independently tuned, synthetic polymer networks obey a long-standing constraint: their physical properties are intrinsically coupled and cannot be adjusted independently of one another. Here, we challenge this paradigm using bottlebrush macromolecules as architecturally programmable building blocks for tissue-mimetic materials.

Bottlebrush polymers enable access to sought-after combinations of softness, damping, swelling, and adhesion that are difficult to realize in conventional networks. Densely grafted side chains govern physical properties in two ways: (i) they disentangle network strands and (ii) they increase strand persistence length [1]. The first effect alleviates constraints on crosslink density, enabling supersoft and highly swelling polymer networks that closely match soft tissues such as brain and jellyfish [2]. The second, i.e., variable persistence length, controls elastic modulus, strain-stiffening, and relaxation times [3].

By independently tuning the size and flexibility of brush-like network strands, we decouple key mechanical parameters and create materials exhibiting seemingly oxymoronic property combinations, including soft-yet-firm, elastic-yet-dissipative, and stiff-yet-stretchable. These results establish macromolecular architecture as a powerful design variable for overcoming intrinsic limitations of conventional polymer networks and for engineering next-generation soft materials.

[1] W.F.M. Daniel, et al. *Nature Materials* **15** (2016) 183-189.

[2] C.J. Wang, et al. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **35** (2024) 2410905.

[3] M. Maw, et al. *ACS Central Sci.* **9** (2023) 197-205.

Plasmonic Single-Molecule Affinity Detection at 10^{-20} Molar

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DNA can be readily amplified through replication, enabling the detection of a single-target copy. A comparable performance for proteins in immunoassays has yet to be fully assessed. Surface-plasmon-resonance (SPR) serves as a probe capable of performing assays at concentrations typically around 10^{-9} molar. In this study, plasmonic single-molecule assays for both proteins and DNA are demonstrated, achieving limits-of-detections (LODs) as low as 10^{-20} molar (1 ± 1 molecule in 0.1 mL), even in human serum, in 1 h. This represents an improvement in typical SPR LODs by eleven orders-of-magnitude. The single-molecule SPR assay is achieved with a millimeter-wide surface functionalized with a physisorbed biolayer comprising trillions of recognition-elements (antibodies or protein-probe complexes) which undergo an acidic or alkaline pH-conditioning¹. Potentiometric and surface-probing imaging experiments reveal the phenomenon underlying this extraordinary performance enhancement. The data suggest an unexplored amplification process within the biomaterial, where pH-conditioning, driving the biolayer in a metastable state, induces a self-propagating aggregation of partially misfolded proteins, following single-affinity binding. This process triggers an electrostatic rearrangement, resulting in the displacement of a charge equivalent to $1.5e$ per 10^2 recognition elements. Such findings open new opportunities for reliable SPR-based biosensing at the physical detection limits, with promising applications in point-of-care plasmonic systems.

[1] E. Macchia, C. Di Franco, C. Scandurra, L. Sarcina, M. Piscitelli, *et al.*, *Advance Materials*, **2025**, vol.37, 2418610.

Polysaccharide-based Microgels in Food Applications

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Microgels are becoming increasingly relevant in food science as a tool to structure complex food matrices and to modulate their texture. However, in contrast to many synthetic systems, microgels for food applications must be prepared from food-grade polymers to be legally allowed and to meet consumer expectations for natural ingredients. As a result, food engineers work with complex and often poorly defined materials such as polysaccharides, proteins, or mixtures thereof, and apply them in equally complex, multiphase systems. Understanding structure–function relationships is therefore a matter of translating material properties into functionality.

In this contribution, polysaccharide-based microgels are studied using pectin as a model system. Pectins are complex heteropolysaccharides found in plant cell walls. Their molecular structure and particularly the degree of esterification affect ionic gelation and thus microgel formation. By controlling process and formulation parameters, microgels with defined size and mechanical properties can be obtained.

These particles are then used in two types of systems. In oil-in-water emulsions, pectin-based microgels stabilize the interface while also contributing to the continuous phase. Their functionality depends on particle deformability, concentration, and their impact on rheology, which together determine emulsion stability and structure. In protein-based gels, the microgels act as inactive filler particles influencing, e.g. stiffness, fracture behavior, and texture.

Overall, these examples show how polysaccharide-based microgels can be used to design and control food structures. At the same time, they serve as model systems to study how soft particles interact with interfaces and evolving networks under non-ideal, multicomponent conditions. The focus is on linking particle properties and processing conditions to functionality as well as on identifying which concepts from polymer network science remain valid and where additional considerations become relevant.

Harnessing Light-Curable Chemistry for Superior 3D-printing of Hydrogels Serving Regenerative Medicine

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Volumetric bioprinting is opening new possibilities for rapidly fabricating centimeter-scale living tissues, yet the development of advanced bioinks remains a key challenge for bone regeneration. In this talk, I will present recent progress in designing gelatin-based bioinks using step-growth crosslinking strategies, which enable improved printing efficiency, cytocompatibility, and mechanical performance compared to conventional approaches. These systems support high-resolution fabrication under mild conditions while promoting osteogenic differentiation.

I will further discuss how material design can be leveraged to guide tissue maturation, including control over degradation, mechanics, and stem cell behavior. Particular attention will be given to strategies for vascularization, such as engineered, time-dependent dissolution features that enhance both angiogenesis and osteogenesis, as well as comparisons between recombinant and animal-derived gelatin hydrogels in driving in vivo vascular responses.

Case studies using digital light processing, volumetric additive manufacturing, and indirect 3D printing of MRI and CT-traceable scaffolds will be presented, alongside recent advances in real-time in vivo implant monitoring. In addition, I will highlight emerging approaches such as NMP polymerization on printed gelatin constructs to further expand post-fabrication functionalization.

Finally, these developments will be positioned across multiple biofabrication platforms, including volumetric printing, DLP, and two-photon polymerization, illustrating new opportunities for scalable, functional, and trackable tissue engineering constructs.

[1] J. Duquesne, ..., S. Van Vlierberghe, *Biofabrication* **17** (2025) 025002.

[2] Z. Geffert, ..., S. Van Vlierberghe, P. Soman, *Advanced Functional Materials* (2026) [early access](#).

[3] N. Pien, ..., S. Van Vlierberghe, *Biomaterials Advances* **162** (2024) 213923.

[4] N. Pien, ..., S. Van Vlierberghe, *Additive Manufacturing* **109** (2025) 104850.

[5] K. Kolouchova, ..., S. Van Vlierberghe, *Chemistry of Materials* **36** (2024) 4417-4425.

Network Architecture and Chain Relaxation Govern Fracture of Polymer Networks

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Despite their extreme stretchability, soft polymer networks often fail in a brittle, flaw-sensitive manner. Classical fracture theories attribute toughness to bond scission along the crack plane, yet experiments report fracture energies orders of magnitude larger, with damage zones spanning hundreds of microns, clear evidence that fracture involves a spatially extended process zone governed by collective network behavior.

Using a discrete mesoscale network model, we show that network architecture controls damage distribution through collective mechanisms that cannot be reduced to single-chain physics. The model reveals that force redistribution following local bond scission engages surrounding strands cooperatively, giving rise to emergent damage delocalization across polydisperse and double-network architectures. Non-affine deformation amplifies these effects: kinematic heterogeneity concentrates force on short sacrificial strands while long strands transmit load non-affinely over extended regions, producing large process zones and high toughness. Extending to dynamic networks, we show that chain relaxation and loading rate introduce a second control axis: limited relaxation at high rates amplifies collective force buildup and enlarges the process zone, while slow rates recover architecture-dominated behavior. Together, these results establish that toughness is co-governed by network architecture and relaxation dynamics, a mechanistic framework linking molecular network design to macroscopic fracture resistance

References

- [1] Z.T. White, A.M. Smith, and F.J. Vernerey, "Mechanical cooperation between time-dependent and covalent bonds in molecular damage of polymer networks", [Communications Physics 8 \(2025\) 265](#).
- [2] S. Assadi, Z. White, and F.J. Vernerey, "Network Pre-stretch Governs Fracture of Polymer Networks", unpublished (2026)

Rheological properties of model vitrimers

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Vitrimers are known to combine the desirable properties of both thermoset and thermoplastic materials. The key feature is the presence of associative dynamic covalent bonds. We present a systematic rheological investigation of two types of well-studies (that are needed to identify microphase separation and clustering where appropriate). One involves low-T_g telechelic primary segment that forms the network, the other involves high-T_g segment with randomly distributed bonds. We explore the thermal annealing and address the challenge of topological transition temperature T_v and its unambiguous determination. There is an interesting analogy for the former class of vitrimers to triblock copolymers and the latter to random copolymers. We also address the nonlinear rheology of these interesting materials, as it is relevant to their possible processing and blending with homopolymers. The latter is important for possible recycling applications and we discuss some first results in this direction.

3 Contributed Talks

3.1 Advanced Synthesis & New Architectures

Controlled Architecture of Starch integrated Poly(acrylamide-co-itaconic acid)/ZnO Biocomposite Beads: Comparison of Mechanical Properties with Hertzian and Rubber Elasticity

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The properties of polymeric gel systems can be modified through various strategies, such as obtaining semi- interpenetrating networks (semi-IPNs) by incorporating linear polymers into network structures. This study is based on the selection of starch as a linear polymer incorporated into semi-IPN gels due to its abundance, renewability, biocompatibility, and hydrophilicity, with the hypothesis that the incorporation of natural polymers into networks is crucial not only for improving system properties but also for minimizing environmental concerns [1]. Since modification of the network structure can also be achieved by the addition of inorganic substances, zinc oxide (ZnO) was incorporated into poly(acrylamide-co-itaconic acid) (PAI) gels synthesized in the presence of starch. ZnO is preferred over conventional organic antimicrobial agents such as quaternary ammonium salts and chlorine disinfectants because of its longer shelf life, higher resistance to temperature and pressure, and ease of integration into polymer networks [2].

The network structure consists of a copolymer of acrylamide and itaconic acid cross-linked with N,N'-methylenebisacrylamide, while Hylon VII starch, characterized by its high amylose content, is incorporated into the matrix. In the strategy, which was realized using three different methods and two different geometric shapes, cylindrical hydrogels synthesized at room temperature were named STx-PAI/ZnO Hgel, while cryogels synthesized at -18 °C were named STx-PAI/ZnO Cgel. Bead-shaped structures (STx-PAI/ZnO Bead) were produced by dropping the precursor solution into liquid nitrogen. This study investigated the effects of two different starch concentrations, while keeping the ZnO content constant, on the swelling behavior and mechanical properties of hydrogels, cryogels, and beads. Furthermore, the applicability of Hertzian contact theory and classical rubber elasticity theory to spherical gels was evaluated. This work provides insights into the structural-mechanical relationships of starch-based semi-IPN/ZnO biocomposites and can contribute to the development of antibacterial biomaterials and materials for water treatment applications.

[1] Çiftbudak, S., Orakdoğan, N. *Soft Matter*, 20 (2024) 4434–4455. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4SM00234A>

[2] Hu, X.; Jia, X.; Zhi, C.; Jin, Z.; Miao, M. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 210 (2019) 204–209.

Responsive Hydrogels and Snail Slime Enabling Multi-Functional Microfluidic Reaction Chambers

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Microfluidics allow for a multitude of chemical reactions in small volumes and highly confined spaces. Solvent waste, exothermic reactions (heat dissipation) and the amount of chemicals used are no longer an issue to worry about. Using an array of functional hydrogel dots, we have developed a microfluidic platform enabling a multitude of applications like catching and releasing functional molecules as well as applying snail slime a sustainable resource.

Figure 1: A photomask is used for lithographic production of the hydrogel dots (left), which form an array within the microfluidic flow chip (right)

The hydrogel dots are prepared using photolithography, allowing for a reproducible production of the chip. Using various functionalities, this platform was enabled to catch and release (bio)macromolecules and small molecules. By hosting various enzymes, enzymatic cascade reactions can be held in this chip in a single- and multi-chamber setup.¹

The enzymatic reactions and further functionalisation of the hydrogels often occur on the surface of hydrogel dots. Special care was hence taken to thoroughly characterise thin hydrogel films, which model the surface area.^{2,3} Bearing in mind that these chips have to be prepared in a sustainable fashion, snail slime was successfully implemented as an alternative carbon source and also led to a functional microfluidic device.⁴

We hence developed a sustainable and broadly applicable microfluidic platform.

1. Koball, A.; Obst, F.; Gaitzsch, J.; Voit, B.; Appelhans, D. *Boosting Microfluidic Enzymatic Cascade Reactions with pH-Responsive Polymersomes by Spatio-Chemical Activity Control*. *Small Methods* **2024**, *8*, (12), e2400282.
2. Hofmann, D.; Bittrich, E.; Appelhans, D.; Gaitzsch, J. *Dynamic Characteristics of Redox- and Thermoresponsive Hydrogel Films on the Nanometer Scale to Compensate Structure Defects*. *Journal of Polymer Science* **2025**, *63*, (18), 3631-3639.
3. Hofmann, D.; Sychev, D.; Zagradka-Paromova, Z.; Bittrich, E.; Auernhammer, G. K.; Gaitzsch, J. *Surface Topology of Redox- and Thermoresponsive Nanogel Droplets*. *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2024**, *45*, (14), 2400049.
4. Koball, A.; Gaitzsch, J. *Bio-based microfluidics with snail slime: A by-product of agriculture plays an exciting role in the chemistry of microfluidic reaction chambers*. *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2025**, *46*, e00578.

Linear-dendritic polyelectrolytes as universal network builders

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The present contribution aims to highlight linear-dendritic polyelectrolytes based on natural amino acids as prospective building blocks for the formation of functional polymer networks. Due to the high number of easily tunable peripheral functional groups of dendrons based on L-aspartic acid acrylates, these copolymers are versatile building blocks for the formation of 3D networks, with a broad range of potential applications, e.g., in biomedicine, catalysis, etc. Thus, such linear-dendritic hybrids with oppositely charged peripheral functional groups could form nano- or macroscopic gels in low-polar solvents via electrostatic interactions (A and B in the Figure below).[1] Alternatively, the introduction of peripheral hydrophobic fragments promotes the formation of supramolecular gels in organic solvents and water-containing mixtures (C,D).[2] Finally, using non-stoichiometric amounts of bifunctional amines, these linear-dendritic copolymers form covalently cross-linked hydrogels (E). By varying the reagent ratio, functional ionogenic groups can be retained, enabling the sorption and release of charged bioactive compounds.

[1] S. Khatuntsev, et al., *Polym. Chem.* **14** (2023) 708-719.

[2] L. Kaberov, et al., *in preparation* (2026).

Synthesis and functional properties of itaconic acid-based hydrogels: toward the design of biobased and (bio)degradable materials

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Hydrogels are soft and elastic materials that can swell or shrink in response to external stimuli, making them suitable for a wide range of applications, from everyday uses to emerging technologies. To date, acrylate-based hydrogels dominate the market, but their petrochemical origin and non-biodegradability raise serious environmental concerns. Natural polymers such as chitosan or cellulose offer sustainable alternatives but exhibit limited structural control and often require grafting with petro-based monomers to enhance their swelling capacity. This has prompted the search for bio-based monomers that can replace acrylates and allow the design of sustainable, well-structured hydrogels. In this context, itaconic acid (IA), obtained by microbial fermentation, has emerged as a promising candidate owing to its renewable origin, biodegradability, and chemical similarity to acrylates.

A new mild synthesis route for fully IA-based hydrogels is developed, in which monomer concentration and crosslinking density are varied to investigate structure-property relationships. The obtained hydrogels, stable in water, exhibit significant swelling that can be modulated by the formulation and external factors such as pH and ionic strength, due to their polyelectrolyte nature. Their dual-network architecture, combining covalent and hydrogen bonds, provided mechanical strength, thermo-responsive behavior and non-Fickian swelling kinetics, all tunable through hydrogen-bond density. Finally, biodegradation was evaluated according to OECD 301F and ISO 20200 standards to assess the end-of-life of the synthesized materials.

Nanostructuring epoxy thermosets using Block Copolymers synthesized by RAFT-PISA in reactive media

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Epoxy thermosets have a wide range of applications such as adhesives, automotive and coatings. They display many advantages due to their thermomechanical properties (modulus and T_g); however, their high crosslink density leads to intrinsic brittleness. To improve the durability of these materials, we recently reported the generation of block copolymers (BCPs), made of an epoxy-miscible first block to promote colloidal stability and an immiscible low T_g block to favor energy dissipation and local plasticization, by RAFT polymerization-induced self-assembly (PISA) in epoxy monomers.¹ The self-assembly of the BCPs in the epoxy precursor leads to a range of morphologies (spheres, worms, vesicles) which are maintained during the formation of the epoxy polymer network (epoxy-amine systems), see Figure below. In this contribution, the strategy to prepare nanostructured epoxy-amine thermosets with different BCP morphology will be described and the impact of these BCP inclusions on the fracture resistance of the resulting networks will be discussed.

[1] T. Ienn, C. Lo Van, R. Brunel, D. Albertini, E. Chamczyk, P. Alcouffe, G. Sudre, F. Lortie, J. Bernard, [Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.](https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202618861), 2026, 65, e18861.

Photo-Degradable Polyester Networks and 3D-Printed Objects

Based on Cyclic Ketene Acetals

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Radical ring-opening polymerization (RROP) of cyclic ketene acetals (CKAs) constitutes a powerful avenue to prepare biodegradable polyesters via radical polymerization. Despite their potential as degradable soft matter materials, CKA-based RROP-networks remain scarce. Herein, we introduce biodegradable RROP-polyester networks based on poly(2-methylene-1,3,6-trioxocane) (PMTC). MTC was selected as CKA building block due to its superior reactivity during RROP in combination with enhanced hydrophilicity.^[1] Following the relatively high reactivity, MTC was converted into exclusive CKA-based networks, where a CKA-based cross-linker even matched a vinylic counterpart. Following the higher amount of ester bonds, relying only on CKAs leads to a faster and complete degradation.^[2]

Figure 1. Photoreversible PCKA networks assessment comprising (A) Synthesis, (B) Solution-state photochemistry, (C) Photorheology and (D) multi-photon printing and degradation.

Based on this network, we now establish a photoreversible PMTC network by decorating the PMTC chains with pendant pyrene chalcone (PyChal) moieties (**Figure 1**). Photoinduced [2+2] cycloaddition affords covalent photo-reversible cross-links. An in-depth assessment of the photochemistry showcased the reversible nature by repeatable gel-sol transitions as assessed via photorheology, enabling light-driven 3D multi-photon printing without the need of any additives or initiators, allowing for the fabrication of arbitrary architectures, which can be degraded by exposure to UV irradiation, base and enzymatic hydrolysis.^[3] Our study thus establishes a versatile and degradable PCKA-based resist platform for advanced and modulable soft matter manufacturing.

- [1] T. Meissner, P. Friedel, J. A. Carroll, C. Barner-Kowollik, J. Gaitzsch, *Polym. Chem.* **2025**, *16*, 704-711.
- [2] T. Meissner, S. Schäfer, C. Barner-Kowollik, S. Seiffert, J. Gaitzsch, *ACS Applied Polymer Materials* **2025**.
- [3] T. Meissner, J. Fanelli, V. X. Truong, J. Gaitzsch, C. Barner-Kowollik, **Manuscript in preparation**.

Spatially Controlled Polymerization-Induced Phase Separation for Photonic Structure Fabrication

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Polymerization-induced phase separation (PIPS) has been disliked for ideal polymer synthesis while is recently attracting attention for a method to create tough and functional materials. In conventional PIPS, the phase distribution is not controlled and random, thereby showing turbid appearance. If the PIPS is precisely controlled in space, resulting materials will show photonic functionalities. In this study, combining a bottom-up PIPS and top-down interference polymerization light source, we developed a simple synthetic approach for fabricating photonic-structured materials in a binary system.

For material synthesis, a large amount of the hydrogen-abstraction-type photoinitiator benzophenone was added to pure *N*-methoxymethyl acrylate (MOMA) monomer with *N,N'*-methylenebisacrylamide (MBAA) cross-linker. The solution in a glass mold was irradiated for 10 minutes with high-intensity UV light generated by an arrayed LED-UV light source. The obtained PMOMA exhibited iridescent structural colors under transmitted light. Static optical diffraction experiments using a 532 nm monochromatic laser revealed a lattice-like diffraction pattern with periodicities of approximately 1.8 μm along the orthogonal directions and 1.1 μm along the diagonal direction. These values are well-agreed with the theoretically predicted interference fringe spacings (1.8 μm and 1.2 μm) determined by the UV interference pattern used during polymerization. Moreover, when the PMOMA was immersed in solvents like 1,4-dioxane and propylene carbonate, organogels can be obtained with photonic modulation. In the presentation, we will present about the mechanism from compatibility change over the polymerization.

Dynamic Covalent Bonding in Inorganic–Organic Polymer Networks

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Conventional polymer chemistry has emphasized durable, carbon-based macromolecules, but this very persistence now hinders sustainability and recycling. To overcome this, we investigate incorporating inorganic components to embed cleavable, dynamic covalent bonds within macromolecular systems. Lewis pairs (LPs), which form coordinate covalent bonds with tunable dissociation rates and energies, remain underexplored in polymer

design. Here, we present several simple methods for synthesising LP-based polymers by combining organoborane-functionalized polydimethylsiloxane with commercially available Lewis base (LB) polymers. Importantly, for designing dynamic covalent polymer networks (DCPNs), the bond strength and rate of dissociation can be easily tuned by substituents, giving a modular system with response temperatures and kinetics that can be tuned across a wide range. Furthermore, the straightforward mechanism means that side reactions are lower than those in many commonly used dynamic chemical reactions. This system demonstrates tunable reversibility, self-healing, and facile mixing, highlighting the potential of organoborane-based LPs in DCPNs and their incorporation into a variety of polymer systems, from stiff covalent networks to soft bottlebrush elastomers. Nature also inspires dynamic bonding, particularly through phosphorus-based systems, such as the phosphate transfer in ATP regeneration. This hydrolytic sensitivity can be leveraged to design cleavable synthetic polymers with phosphorus backbones, where substituents control cleavage rates. We therefore also report recent progress in incorporating phosphorus-bound amino acid-based monomers for photochemical additive manufacturing, offering new pathways for cleavable and cured photopolymer systems and bottlebrush elastomers.

3.2 Amphiphilic Gels & Networks

Surface Structure and Nanomechanics of a Micellar Hydrogel

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Surfaces of fully swollen hydrogels in solvent are rarely imaged by atomic force microscopy (AFM) due to experimental challenges arising from their softness, from surface gradients in cross-linking, and from adhesion to loosely bound polymers. We have prepared smooth surfaces of a crosslinked hydrogel which is built from self-assembled micelles of amphiphilic triblock copolymers. Using a dedicated AFM mode of frequently repeated force-distance curves, we succeeded in imaging the organization of micelles at the surface and to reveal differences in mechanical stability and adhesion between micelle core and corona.

The micellar hydrogel was prepared from Pluronic F127 diacrylate and crosslinked by means of photo-initiated radical polymerization [1]. The AFM tip penetrates the micelles' core more easily than their corona, leading to higher adhesion at the sites of cores. Dimensional reduction of force-curve data and clustering analysis reveals nanometer-sized spots on the surface where single polymers attach to the AFM tip, followed by stretching and force-induced unbinding upon retraction. The results indicate new opportunities to detect local variations in physical and chemical interactions at the surfaces of hydrogels with self-assembled nanometer-scale structures.

[1] S. Bhusari, S. Sankaran, A. del Campo,
<https://advanced.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/advs.202106026> .

Function Design of Amphiphilic Hydrogels with Designed Nanodomain Structure via PISA Process

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To further approach the sophisticated dynamic functions of natural hydrogels, careful design and precise construction of stimuli-responsive nanodomain structure in artificial gels are considered important. In this context, we have recently developed a gel with a crosslinked domain (CD) structure that exhibits thermoresponsive mechanical toughening in air while maintaining the original volume and transparency [1]. This gel was synthesized via polymerization-induced self-assembly (PISA) process using reversible addition-fragmentation chain-transfer (RAFT) polymerization of *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAAm) in water at a temperature above the transition temperature of PNIPAAm, in the presence of a divinyl crosslinker using a hydrophilic bifunctional macro-chain transfer agent (macro-CTA). In addition, the incorporation of fluorescent dyes into a gel with CD structure enables simultaneous changes in both mechanical properties and photoluminescent properties [2, 3].

[1] M. Morimura, S. Ida, M. Oyama, H. Takeshita, and S. Kanaoka, *Macromolecules* **54** (2021) 1732-1741.

[2] S. Ida, T. Okuno, M. Morimura, K. Suzuki, H. Takeshita, M. Oyama, K. Nakajima, and S. Kanaoka, *Polym. Chem.* **13** (2022) 3479-3488.

[3] H. Wakuda, S. Ida, M. Oyama, K. Nakajima, H. Takeshita, and S. Kanaoka, *Polym. Chem.* **16** (2025) 3287-3295.

WOC & Roll – Polyampholytic Crosslinked Hydrogels as Matrices for Light-Driven Water Oxidation Catalysis

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Polymers are a versatile class of materials with almost unlimited combinations of functional groups being present in close proximity. This in combination with a widely tunable solubility has enabled quite a range of examples where building blocks for light-driven catalysis (i.e., photosensitizers and catalysts) are immobilized using either covalent anchoring or non-covalent interactions. During recent years, we have developed different soft matter matrices for either light-driven hydrogen evolution (HER) or water oxidation (WOC) based on unimolecular graft copolymers, block copolymer micelles, hydrogels, or nanoporous block copolymer membranes.[1] In all cases, close proximity of the immobilized building blocks facilitated light-driven reactivity, but we also observed additional effects during our studies, such as prolonged lifetime of photosensitizers, altered degradation pathways, or the possibility to repair / exchange catalysts or sensitizers. Herein, we focus on water oxidation catalysis (WOC) using polyampholytic hydrogels featuring PEG crosslinks[2, 3] – with particular emphasis on whether the matrix suffers oxidation or degradation during these processes. Altogether, we hope to derive some general guidelines for the design of (charged) soft matter matrices for light-driven catalysis.[4].

[1] Kund J., Kruse J.-H., Gruber A., Trentin I., Langer M., Read C., Neusser G., Blaimer D., Rupp U., Streb C., Leopold K., **Schacher F. H.**, Kranz C., "Multimodal analysis of light-driven water oxidation in nanoporous block copolymer membranes", *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2023**, 62, e202217196 (DOI: 10.1002/anie.202217196)

[2] Ceper T., Langer M., Vashista N., Dietzek-Ivansic B., Streb C., Rau S., **Schacher F. H.**, "Poly(dehydroalanine)-Based Hydrogels as Efficient Soft Matter Matrices for Light-Driven Catalysis", *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2024**, 45, 2300448 (DOI: 10.1002/marc.202300448).

[3] Ceper T., Costabel D., Kowalczyk D., Peneva K., **Schacher F. H.**, "Noble Metal-Free Light-Driven Hydrogen Evolution Catalysis in Polyampholytic Hydrogel Networks", *ACS Appl. Mater. Int.* **2024**, 16, 24796-24805 (DOI: 10.1021/acsami.4c04045)

[4] Nabiyan A., Neumann C., Turchanin A., **Schacher F. H.**, "Hybrid nanoreactors formed by interpolyelectrolyte complex formation: a colloidal platform for light-driven catalysis", *J. Mater. Chem A* **2024**, 12, 14389-14397 (DOI: 10.1039/D4TA01824A)

Scattering of (amphiphilic) polymer model networks: understanding structure with computer simulations

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From large-scale computer simulations of polymer gels consisting of complementary A₄ and B₄ stars, we can discriminate between static scattering on the time-average density and dynamic scattering arising from thermal fluctuations [1]. For vanishing contrast between A and B material, this procedure allows to distinguish between a dynamic correlation length scaling with the polymer volume fraction and a static correlation length Ξ , which encodes the size and mobility of the larger cross-link blobs in homogeneous networks [1].

Scattering with maximum contrast between A and B reproduces key features of block copolymers with finite repulsion between both components [2]. Moreover, it provides the distance between connected star centers. Contrast arising only from star cores reveals a combination of the star polymer form factor and the structure factor of the star centers [2].

In a selective solvent, amphiphilic gels minimize the unfavorable interactions with the solvent by forming dense clusters of the non-soluble polymers. Scattering data calculated with maximum contrast allows to trace the onset of nanophase separation, whereas scattering from the phase separated domains provides access to aggregation number and cluster statistics [3]. The cluster size resembles the physics of block-copolymer micelles, whereas the preparation conditions affect the connectivity between the clusters and the elastic modulus.

[1] R. Scholz and M. Lang, *Macromolecules* **57** (2024) 2539-2555.

[2] R. Scholz and M. Lang, *Macromolecules* **58** (2025) 11581-11599.

[3] R. Scholz and M. Lang, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* (2026) *accepted*.

Structure and Dynamics of Model Amphiphilic Polymer Co-Networks

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Amphiphilic polymer co-networks (APCNs) comprise hydrophilic and hydrophobic components that enable swelling in water and organic solvents. This results in environmentally responsive viscoelasticity and selective permeability for hydrophilic and hydrophobic species. Understanding the relationship between the microstructure of APCNs and their macroscopic properties is crucial for the targeted design of advanced materials.

We studied a model APCN synthesized via hetero-complementary coupling between 2-(4-nitrophenyl)-benzoxazinone-terminated tetra-poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (t-PCL) and amino-terminated tetra-poly(ethylene glycol) (t-PEG), as described by Bunk et al.^[1] To establish structure-property relationships, we investigated the network structure, dynamics, and transport properties, using multiple methods. First, we investigated the diffusion of hydrophilic PEG and hydrophobic PCL star polymers within the network using Fluorescence Recovery After Photobleaching (FRAP) and Forced Rayleigh Scattering (FRS) to assess tracer-network interactions and the underlying diffusion mechanisms.^[2] Second, diffusion measurements with spherical silver nanoparticles and esterified dextrans were performed by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) to assess the correlation length and the hydrodynamic screening length as key diffusion-governing length scales, providing insight into the network microstructure.^[3] Third, networks swollen in the co-solvent THF were investigated using light scattering to extract dynamic and static correlation lengths. Finally, Small-Angle Neutron Scattering (SANS) was used to characterize the structure of the water-swollen networks.^[4]

[1] C. Bunk, L. Löser, N. Fribiczer, H. Komber, L. Jakisch, R. Scholz, B. Voit, S. Seiffert, K. Saalwächter, M. Lang and F. Böhme, *Macromolecules* **55** (2022) 6573–6589.

[2] S. Seitel, L. K. R. J. Zank, S. Ihmann, F. Böhme, M. Lang, B. D. Olsen and S. Seiffert, *Macromolecules* **59** (2026) 1282–1292.

[3] S. Seitel, N. Perez Lopez, S. Ihmann, F. Böhme and S. Seiffert, *Soft Matter* **21** (2025) 7860–7871.

[4] S. Seitel, N. Fribiczer, B. Carrick, S. Ihmann, F. Böhme, B.D. Olsen and S. Seiffert, *Macromolecular Chemistry and Physics* (2026), *submitted*.

Functional bio-based thiol-ene UV-curable networks

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Thiol-ene photopolymerization has emerged as a highly versatile and robust synthetic methodology, distinguished by its rapid curing kinetics, relative insensitivity to oxygen inhibition, and capacity to yield homogeneous polymer networks with minimal volumetric shrinkage. These advantageous characteristics render it particularly suitable for advanced technological applications, including 3D printing, flexible electronics, and high-performance protective coatings.¹ In the present study, we report advanced design strategies for the development of bio-based, UV-curable polymer networks that effectively integrate sustainability with high-performance functionality. One strategy involves the utilization of a triallyl isocyanurate monomer derived from renewable eugenol. Upon UV-curing using polythiol, this system forms polymer networks exhibiting excellent UV-shielding capability alongside high optical transparency. Notably, the retention of pendant phenolic hydroxyl groups imparts intrinsic antioxidant properties.² Another approach entails the conjugation of bio-based tricyclic oxanorbornene derivatives with polypropylene glycol (PPG),³ establishing a modular platform for thiol-oxanorbornene UV curing. This system facilitates the formation of polymer networks with tunable glass transition temperatures (T_g) and precisely controlled mechanical properties, spanning from highly flexible elastomeric materials to rigid films.

[1] T. O. Machado, C. Sayer, and P. H. Araujo, *European Polymer Journal* **86** (2017) 200-215.

[2] M. Naguib, M. Sangermano, and M. A. Yassin, *Reactive and Functional Polymers* **222** (2026) 106701.

[3] M. A. Yassin, H. Komber, M. Naguib, M. Abdelraof, D. Appelhans, and B. Voit, *ACS Applied Bio Materials* **8**(2) (2025) 1720-1731.

3.3 Bio-Medical Applications

Mechanical Programming of PEGDA- β CD based Polyrotaxane Organohydrogels via Host-guest Molecular Recognition

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Polyrotaxane-based hydrogels with mechanically interlocked structures offer unique opportunities for designing biomaterials with tunable mechanical properties in tissue engineering. However, the unequal existence of PEG- β CD polyrotaxane between aqueous and solid state limits their integration into well-defined hydrogel networks. Here, we report a series of organohydrogels $P_5C_ZHGC_{10}$ -Cur constructed from PEGDA- β CD polyrotaxanes bridges this inequality, in which the threading density is regulated to dictate the macrofunction. The increasing number of threaded β -CD units induces an evolution of microstructure from disordered porous to ordered laminar morphology, thereby transforming the mechanical behavior from highly elastic, low-dissipated (13.53%) to high-damping states (46.56%), accompanied by enhanced toughness and modulus. Notably, low threading density variants exhibit desirable elasticity and recovery for skin wound dressings, while higher threading densities enable mimicking of highly dissipative biological tissues. *In vivo* studies further demonstrate the excellent wound healing performance of $P_5C_ZGC_{10}$ -Cur, due to its suitable mechanical properties and anti-inflammatory properties. This work highlights the critical role of polyrotaxane threading density in coupling supramolecular structure with mechanical and biological functions, providing a versatile strategy for advanced tissue engineering materials.

Mimicking the ‘J-Shaped’ Strain Stiffening of Human Aorta to Control Blood Flow in Ex-Vivo Heart Preservation Device

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Natural biological tissues such as blood vessels exhibit a J-shaped strain–stiffening response: they are compliant at low strains and stiffen at higher strains, limiting excessive deformation and preventing damage [1]. They also show marked anisotropy and spatial heterogeneity, which are difficult to replicate with homogeneous synthetic materials. Ex-vivo heart perfusion (EVHP) preserves donor hearts by maintaining them in a viable, beating state outside the body under near-physiological conditions at 37 °C. However, conventional EVHP systems use rigid, noncompliant plastic tubing, which causes early pressure-wave reflections during the cardiac cycle. This may increase mechanical stress at the tissue–tube interface and raise the risk of graft injury or rejection. We propose that compliant, rapidly strain-stiffening (“J-shaped”) tubing that mimics the human aorta could address this limitation.

In this work, we replicate the nonlinear, anisotropic mechanical behavior of the human aorta using engineered elastomeric composites to replace rigid tubing. Mechanical characterization of human and porcine aortas across five anatomical regions quantified nonlinearity and anisotropy [2]. Fabric-reinforced composite elastomers were developed, and a constitutive model was established [2]. Compliant elastomeric tubes with external fabric “jackets” were fabricated to control radial expansion and prevent aneurysm-like deformation [3]. A custom hydraulic pressure system and 3D finite element modeling supported their characterization [3]. Performance was validated in a mock EVHP setup, where pressure waveform measurements confirmed effective flow modulation [4]. Ongoing

work focuses on integrating the jacketed design into EVHP systems and exploring broader biomedical and industrial applications.

References:

- [1] D. Zhalmuratova, H.-J. Chung. [ACS Appl. Polymer Mater., 2 \(2020\) 1073-1091.](#)
- [2] D. Zhalmuratova, ..., H.-J. Chung. [ACS Appl. Mater. Interf., 11 \(2019\) 33323-33335.](#)
- [3] N. Jen, ... , H.-J. Chung. [iScience 25 \(2022\) 104369.](#)
- [4] N. Jen, ..., H.-J. Chung. [J. Mech. Behav. Biomed. Mater. 145 \(2023\) 105994.](#)

A Multi-Stimuli Responsive Vitamin B₁₂-modified Nanogel for Targeted Delivery of Drug with Enhanced Selectivity

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In this study, we developed a novel vitamin B₁₂-conjugated nanogel carrier for targeted, pH and glutathione-responsive drug delivery of doxorubicin (DOX). This B₁₂-nanogel demonstrated enhanced targeting capability and selectivity towards carcinoma cells HT-29 and A549, compared to a control-nanogel lacking the strategic modification with B₁₂. Encapsulation of DOX within the B₁₂-nanogel significantly lowered cytotoxicity toward normal CCD 841 CoN cells (8.2-fold) and MRC-5 cells (4.4-fold), a major drawback leading to severe side effects. To synthesize the B₁₂-nanogel, we introduced a new 5'-modified B₁₂ monomer. This site of modification of the natural product is well known to preserve transcobalamin II (TCII) binding, enabling receptor-mediated cancer cell targeting.

Comprehensive characterization with FT-IR, NMR, UV-Vis and Raman spectroscopies, electron microscopies and dynamic light scattering confirmed covalent 5'-B₁₂ conjugation, resulting in a uniform, narrowly distributed nanogel exhibiting pH and temperature sensitivity, negligible hemolytic activity (<1%), as well as stability under various conditions, and responsiveness to glutathione-induced degradation. This nanogel exhibited high DOX encapsulation and dual stimuli-responsiveness, releasing about 80% of DOX under tumor-like conditions and only 20% in blood circulation.

[1] Alberto, R., Zelder, F., 2012, Handbook of Porphyrin Science, 25, 83–130.

https://doi.org/10.1142/9789814397605_0018

[2] Shi, J., Kantoff, P. W., Wooster, R., & Farokhzad, O. C., 2017, Nature Reviews Cancer, 17(1), 20–37. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrc.2016.108>

[3] Dagdelen, S., Mackiewicz, M., Osial, M., Wałęka-Bargieł, E., Romanski, J., Krysinski, P., & Karbarz, M., 2023, Journal of Materials Science, 58, 4094–4114. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-023-08168-1>

Magnetic Polymeric Scaffolds for the Mechanotransduction Stimulation in Tendon Tissue Regeneration

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Tendon injuries represent a global health issue that annually affects millions of individuals. An innovative approach for their treatment is represented by the development of polymeric scaffolds able to support the cells' adhesion, differentiation, and proliferation. To improve healing control, we investigated the possible mechano-stimulation of cells when combined with bio-mimetic scaffolds doped with Magnetite nanoparticles (Fe_3O_4), improving the tenogenic differentiation. We developed and characterized fibrous scaffolds, able to mimic the tendon fascicles, based on polyhydroxybutyrate and gelatin and doped with Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles. They possess a superparamagnetic behavior and a slow degradation rate that should guarantee structural support during tissue regeneration. The structural properties of fibrous scaffolds on different length scales were investigated by microscopy, small angle X-ray scattering, infrared spectroscopy, and thermal analysis. The macroscopic mechanical properties were correlated with the nanoscopic mechanics of the polymer matrix. Also, the viscoelastic behaviour was investigated by observing the evolution of the nanoscale structure while the scaffolds were subjected to elongation.

The magnetic scaffolds promoted cell proliferation and alignment onto the matrix, when combined with the application of an external magnetic field and the cells could differentiate and produce collagen I extracellular matrix. These promising results contribute to the investigation of the mechanisms of external mechanostimulation by static, and in the future oscillating, magnetic fields, and to the design of tools to enhance and stimulate the tendon tissue regeneration.

Surfactant-Assisted Viscoelastic Modulation of Fmoc-Phe Hydrogel for Topical Drug Delivery

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Supramolecular hydrogels formed through self-assembly of low molecular weight gelators (LMWGs) have gained significant interest, particularly in drug delivery applications. The inherent stimuli-responsive behaviour and self-healing ability of these hydrogels makes them promising for therapeutic applications. Herein, we modulated the viscoelastic and thermal properties of a well-known antibacterial gelator, Fmoc-Phenylalanine (Fmoc-Phe) using commercially available surfactants-based nanoparticles such as CTAB (cationic), SDS (anionic), and TX100 (non-ionic)-as model surfactants. We further investigated the drug release profiles of these supramolecular hydrogels by successfully loading a chemotherapeutic drug daunorubicin into the hydrogels for potential skin treatment. This study evaluates the concentration-dependent effects of surfactants below, at, and above their critical micellar concentrations (CMCs). At neutral pH, the terminal -COOH of Fmoc-Phe hydrogels predominantly exists as COO⁻ ions. The cationic CTAB micelles shield the negative charges ultimately leading to an increase in mechanical strength and thermal properties. In contrast, the anionic SDS micelles, disrupt the self-assembly of Fmoc-Phe hydrogels, lowering mechanical strength particularly at concentrations above CMC. Meanwhile, TX100 modulates the viscoelastic behavior through π - π interaction. These findings provide valuable insights for supramolecular chemists for fine-tune the viscoelastic and thermal properties of hydrogels for applications in drug delivery, tissue engineering and other biomedical applications.

Building an Olympic gel from >16,000 DNA rings

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An Olympic gel comprises a three-dimensional network of molecules, but instead of distinct crosslinks, the network is held together *purely* by mechanically interlocked molecular rings. Polymer physicists have theorized that such a material would exhibit highly unusual mechanical properties. Yet, Olympic gels have remained a notoriously challenging target that has defied traditional synthesis approaches. In this talk, I present a scalable and versatile approach towards Olympic gels by employing concepts of DNA nanotechnology, synthetic biology, and combinatorial supramolecular chemistry [1]. A key innovation is the use of large combinatorial libraries of DNA plasmid rings that contain thousands of chemically distinct molecules. The rings contain enzymatically activated lock & key domains that allow reversible mechanical interlocking. Their large constitutional diversity and exceptional binding selectivity avoid non-specific cross-reactions. The Olympic gels exhibit swelling and concentration-dependent scaling properties that are fundamentally different from traditional molecular networks. Our approach provides access to a new class of soft, biologically inspired materials that can have unusual stretchability, toughness, and swelling behavior. This work demonstrates that exotic material properties can emerge in systems with a high compositional complexity that is more reminiscent of biological than synthetic matter.

[1] S. K. Speed, Y.-H. Peng, A. Atabay, K. Gupta, T. Müller, C. Fischer, I. M. Hermes, J.-U. Sommer, M. Lang, E. Krieg, [Advanced Materials \(2026\) e20549](#).

Cell-instructive glycosaminoglycan-based hydrogels with tunable mechanics and adhesion guiding human epiblast model morphogenesis

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Synthetic hydrogel networks are increasingly used as defined extracellular matrix analogues for three-dimensional (3D) stem cell culture and organoid engineering, yet design rules linking network properties to multicellular morphogenesis remain limited. Here, we present glycosaminoglycan-based hydrogels that enable orthogonal control over mechanical properties and the presentation of biochemical adhesion ligands, allowing the systematic investigation of structure–property–function relationships in cell-instructive polymer networks.

The hydrogels are formed via Michael-type addition between maleimide-functionalized glycosaminoglycans and matrix metalloproteinase (MMP)-cleavable multi-arm starPEG-peptide conjugates under physiological conditions, enabling cell-mediated matrix remodeling [1]. Network stiffness is tuned by polymer content and crosslinking density, while integrin-binding peptides derived from fibronectin and vitronectin are incorporated without altering bulk mechanical properties, allowing independent control of mechanical and biochemical network parameters within a defined 3D microenvironment.

Human induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) embedded in these hydrogels self-organize into lumenized epithelial cysts resembling peri-implantation epiblast structures, providing a model system to study matrix-guided morphogenesis [2]. Using a design-of-experiments approach, we systematically evaluated how network stiffness and adhesion ligand presentation influence cell survival and identified adhesion ligand presentation as the primary determinant of iPSC viability. Under survival-permissive conditions, matrix stiffness and biochemical cues act synergistically with Rho-associated protein kinase (ROCK) inhibition to regulate lumen formation, morphogenesis, and epithelial organization.

These findings establish design principles for cell-instructive glycosaminoglycan-based hydrogels and show that independent tuning of mechanical and biochemical network parameters controls multicellular organization and morphogenesis in 3D culture.

[1] M.V. Tsurkan, K. Chwalek, et al., *Advanced Materials* 25 (2013) 2606–2610.

[2] Y.D.P. Limasale, P. Atallah, et al., *Materials Today* 92 (2026) 269–281.

Hydrogel substrates for controlling cell adhesion

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Living cells sense and respond to their microenvironment through complex physicochemical interactions, leading to behaviors such as adhesion, migration, proliferation, and differentiation [1]. Cell behavior at cell–material interfaces is regulated by surface properties such as chemistry, topography, and stiffness [2]. The substrates proposed here are glass slides modified by grafted hydrogels which are fabricated using a Cross-Linking And Grafting (CLAG) strategy in two steps: synthesis to obtain ene-functionalized polymers, followed by the development of micro-patterned surfaces using spin-coating, and photolithography. This versatile approach enables easy tuning of both chemical properties (e.g., charge density) and physical properties (e.g., topography and stiffness) of surface-grafted hydrogel films [3]. To study the influence of polymer charge, hydrogels based on poly(sodium acrylate) (PAA, negative), poly(2-(dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate) (PDMAEMA, positive), and poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (PNIPAM, neutral) were prepared. Ellipsometry and AFM techniques are used to characterize the thickness and swelling, while nanoindentation evaluates stiffness under cell culture conditions. Cell culture experiments assess the toxicity of CLAG-derived hydrogel films and study cell adhesion using different cell lines (L292, U2OS, and HeLa-CFP). The results demonstrate that the CLAG strategy is non-toxic for cells. Cells adhere mainly to the top of PAA hydrogel pillars (500 nm thick) (a), while on PDMAEMA hydrogels, they preferentially adhere at the pillar base (30 nm thick) (b and c). These hydrogel substrates are promising platforms for the selective spatial control of cell adhesion.

[1] D. Letourneur, D. Mantovani, and C. Le Visage, *Biomatter* **3** (2013) e25414.

[2] E. Marie, C. Tribet, and M. Piel, *Advanced Materials* **25** (2013) 1687–1691.

[3] B. Chollet, E. Martwong, and Y. Tran, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **8** (2016) 24870–24879.

Force-history probes enable 4D mapping of cell–matrix interactions

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Mechanical interactions between biological cells and the surrounding extracellular matrix (ECM) are critical for many biological processes. However, visualizing these interactions in three-dimensional space and time remains a fundamental challenge. Here, we introduce DNA-based force-history probes, which convert transient pico-Newton forces into cumulative fluorescent signals within a DNA-crosslinked cell culture matrix [1]. The probes provide tunable control over signal lifetimes, allowing stress patterns to be recorded over minutes to days with adjustable temporal memory [2]. We use this system to record the mechanical activity of breast cancer spheroids and map the trajectories of migrating cancer cells. By combining different fluorophores and DNA-encoded signal lifetimes, we produce dual-color probes that can record the chronology of mechanical events. Force-history probes are a new biophysical tool that is readily accessible without specialized equipment. This method opens new opportunities for studying the role of cell–matrix interactions in development and disease.

[1] Y.-H. Peng *et al.*, "Dynamic matrices with DNA-encoded viscoelasticity for cell and organoid culture," *Nat. Nanotechnol.*, vol. 18, no. 12, Art. no. 12, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1038/s41565-023-01483-3.

[2] Y.-H. Peng *et al.* "Force-history probes enable 4D mapping of cell–matrix interactions" *manuscript in preparation*.

Biodegradable Polymer Networks based on Poly(propylene fumarate) for Biomaterial

Applications

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Biodegradable network polymers are of significant importance in biomedical engineering, particularly for applications such as tissue scaffolds, controlled drug delivery systems, and temporary implants. Their ability to provide structural integrity while degrading into non-toxic byproducts eliminates the need for secondary surgical removal. Among these materials, poly(propylene fumarate) (PPF), an unsaturated polyester, has attracted considerable attention for bone tissue engineering and drug delivery applications. In this study, PPF was crosslinked with vinyl phosphonic acid (VPA) and vinyl phosphonic acid diethyl ester (VPES) via radical polymerization to produce biodegradable polymer networks. Thermal curing, UV photopolymerization, and body-temperature curing (37 °C) were carried out using appropriate initiators and catalysts. The influence of composition and curing method on crosslink density, mechanical properties, biodegradation, and biocompatibility was systematically evaluated.

High-temperature-cured PPF/VPA and PPF/VPES copolymers exhibited compressive modulus values ranging from 10 to 836 MPa and compressive strength values between 14 and 119 MPa. In vitro evaluations, including MTS assay, mineralization studies, and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) and osteocalcin (OCN) activity measurements, confirmed that all copolymers were biocompatible and they enhanced bone growth and supported osteogenesis, demonstrating strong potential as bone tissue engineering scaffolds. PPF/VPES- β -tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP) composites (5–20 wt%) were also prepared via curing at 37 °C. These materials showed lower compressive modulus (1.45–4.89 MPa) and strength (1.03–6.86 MPa) compared to high-temperature-cured systems. Nevertheless, they promoted human osteoblast cell attachment, proliferation, and differentiation. Based on their mechanical performance, these composites are more suitable for cartilage tissue engineering rather than load-bearing bone applications. This work was supported by TÜBİTAK (Project No. 114M195).

[1] G. Cemali, A. Aruh, G.T. Köse and E. Can, *Polym. Int.* **69** (2020) 1283-1296.

[2] G. Cemali, B. Okutan, E. Can and G.T. Kose. *J. Polym. Res.* **30** (2023) 347.

[3] A. Aruh, "Poly(propylene fumarate) (PPF) based composites as scaffolds for bone tissue engineering" M.Sc. Thesis, *Yeditepe University* (2019).

Multifunctional alginate and chitosan/alginate hydrogel membranes: a strategy to control infection-driven fibrosis in chronic wounds

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Chronic and infected wounds frequently remain in a prolonged inflammatory state due to persistent bacterial colonization and biofilm formation, which sustains immune activation and amplifies profibrotic signaling. This environment promotes fibroblast-to-myofibroblast differentiation, excessive extracellular matrix deposition, and ultimately pathological scarring. Because infection control and fibrosis modulation are tightly linked in such wounds, there is a growing need for multifunctional biomaterial dressings that can simultaneously limit bacterial burden and attenuate profibrotic responses.

Here, we report the development of natural polysaccharide hydrogel membranes based on sodium alginate or chitosan/alginate polyelectrolyte complexes, designed as a platform for controlled release of a licorice-derived anti-fibrotic flavonoid while maintaining antimicrobial functionality. Hydrogels were fabricated under aseptic conditions using internal ionic crosslinking for alginate systems and controlled mixing/crosslinking for chitosan/alginate systems. To overcome the solubility barrier of the hydrophobic bioactive compound, we employed a nanoemulsion/micellar-type incorporation strategy using non-ionic surfactants: a widely used pharmaceutical polysorbate – Tween 20 and a plant-derived sugar-based surfactant – decyl glucoside. The resulting membranes were characterized for ultrastructure and porosity (SEM), swelling capacity, mass loss, and release kinetics quantified by UV–Vis spectroscopy. Cytotoxicity and the ability to inhibit fibroblast-to-myofibroblast transition (FMT) were evaluated using adult human dermal fibroblasts. Antibacterial performance was evaluated using hydrogel eluates against clinically relevant Gram-positive and Gram-negative reference strains via colony-forming unit quantification.

The results obtained point to a great potential of examined materials to serve as next-generation wound dressings for chronic wounds, where infection-driven fibrosis remains a major clinical challenge.

Acknowledgments: this work was financially supported by the National Science Centre project agreement number UMO-2024/53/N/ST5/00539.

3.4 Dynamics, Dynamic Networks & Self-Healing

Real-Time Monitoring of Lipid Nanoparticle Self-Assembly Using Multi-Angle DLS

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Lipid nanoparticle (LNP) self-assembly is a highly dynamic process in which physicochemical properties such as hydrodynamic radius and polydispersity are established within seconds of formulation. Conventional DLS methods lack the temporal resolution and angular sensitivity required to capture these early-stage kinetics [1–2]. Here, we employ the DLScat (Swabian Instruments), a simultaneous multi-angle DLS instrument acquiring scattering data at four angles (74.4°, 90.0°, 105.6°, 163.0°), to monitor LNP formation in real time. The DLScat continuously records the full photon arrival stream from all detection angles simultaneously, which is subsequently partitioned into short time slices. Each slice yields an independent intensity autocorrelation function from which hydrodynamic radius and polydispersity are extracted, providing a time-resolved sequence of size measurements with high temporal resolution. Nucleic acid-loaded LNPs were formulated by rapid mixing and measured continuously for 600 s, commencing within 5 s of preparation. Distinct self-assembly behaviors were observed depending on the aqueous medium: water-based formulations exhibited sustained particle growth and elevated polydispersity over time, whereas acidic buffer conditions yielded smaller, colloiddally stable particles, consistent with buffer-mediated modulation of electrostatic interactions and lipid packing. Simultaneous multi-angle detection markedly improved measurement precision and reproducibility over single-angle approaches, enabling direct, uninterrupted observation of nanoparticle evolution under realistic formulation conditions.

[1] T. Hiroi, S. Samitsu, and K. Ishioka, *Sci. Technol. Adv. Mater. Meth.* **1** (2021).

[2] O. Urquidi, N. Barbosa, J. Bazard, and T. B. M. Adachi, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **94** (2023).

Hierarchical Assembly in Metallo-Supramolecular PEG-Peptide Hydrogels

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Self-assembling peptide-polymer conjugates offer a versatile platform to engineer nanostructures with tunable morphology and function. Our former study revealed pH-induced assembly in PEG-peptide hydrogels using short polymer precursor of 3 kg mol⁻¹ and pentameric peptide with alternative phenylalanine and histidine sequences, in the form of long β -sheet nanofibers.[1] The combination of circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy, TEM imaging, and rheological studies revealed that metal ions further improve and even change the type of secondary assembly, depending on the coordination geometry preference of the employed metal ion. Moreover, they significantly stabilize the structure while remarkably improve self-healing. However, the assembly behavior was highly compromised by the entropic penalty of chain stretching. To assess the self-assembly at chain overlap concentration and beyond that, we extend our synthesis and employ linear PEG chains with 10 kg mol⁻¹ molar mass. We expect the provided accessibility of chain ends to promote the formation of secondary structure in the hydrogel state and clearly reveal the effect of metal coordination of structure formation. Besides CD spectroscopy and TEM imaging of the assembly process in dilute solution, we further analyze the structure formation with SAXS and try to correlate the rheological properties with the structure that is quantified by fitting SAXS data.

[1] M. Ahmadi, K. Wittek, H.S. Rieger, M. Thomas, L. Hartmann, P. Besenius, S. Seiffert, *Chem. Mater.*, (2026).

Contrast-engineered polymer colloids enabling 3D pore-scale tracking in porous media

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Understanding how microgels and polymer colloids are transported and retained in natural porous media is essential for subsurface applications, such as assessing microplastic risks and improving polymer-based subsurface energy technologies. However, their three-dimensional pore-scale transport behavior remains poorly understood because most existing studies rely on bulk-scale black-box column experiments, destructive sampling, and simplified two-dimensional micromodels [1]. X-ray microcomputed tomography (μ CT) offers strong potential for non-destructive pore-scale analysis, but its application to polymer particles remains limited due to their low X-ray contrast in water-saturated porous media [2].

To address this challenge, contrast-engineered polymer particles incorporating high-Z elements were synthesized. Combined with controlled-flow sand-packed column experiments and high-resolution μ CT scanning, this approach enabled reliable 3D particle localization. This strategy establishes a new experimental platform for linking polymer structure with pore-scale transport behavior and supports the development of functional soft polymer colloids for applications in complex porous environments.

[1] Lim, S. J., K.-j. Lee, H. Nam, S. H. Kim, E.-j. Kim, S. Lee, and J. Chung, *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry* 179 (2024) 117851.

[2] Tötzke, C., B. Kozhuharova, N. Kardjilov, N. Lenoir, I. Manke, and S. E. Oswald, *Science of the Total Environment* 907 (2024) 167927.

Dynamic crosslinking of Acrylic Hot-Melt Adhesives

Based on Itaconic-Anhydride Copolymers

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Hot-melt adhesives (HMAs) are attractive alternatives to solvent-based adhesives due to their low toxicity, fast processing, easy cleaning, but their thermoplastic nature limits mechanical performance and solvent resistance.¹ Here, dynamically crosslinked networks based on a copolymer of *n*-butyl methacrylate and bio-based itaconic anhydride are developed. Dynamic crosslinking occurs via anhydride ring-opening with diols, enabling monoester-anhydride exchange through neighboring group participation and internal catalysis, without the need for external catalysts.²

The resulting materials exhibit excellent solvent resistance, high lap-shear strength (4 MPa), and a sharp viscosity transition within the HMA processing window (120–180 °C), ensuring good substrate wetting and mechanical integrity. Notably, they are additive-free and outperform conventional ethylene-vinyl acetate thermoplastic, which is the most widely used matrix for HMA and typically shows lap-shear strength below 1 MPa without additives.³ These findings highlight the potential of itaconic-based acrylic networks as dynamic adhesive platforms for next-generation HMAs.

[1] Zhong, K. et al. in *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 60, 6925–6931 (2021).

[2] Delahaye, M. et al. in *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 141, 15277–15287 (2019).

[3] Park, Y. J. et al. in *J. Adhes. Sci. Technol.* 17, 1831–1845 (2003).

Locking in performance: tunable reinforcement of complex coacervates *via* dynamic covalent crosslinking

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Complex coacervation is an associative liquid-liquid phase separation process driven by electrostatic interactions between oppositely charged (bio-)macromolecules and the release of bound counter-ions, typically resulting in the formation of a polymer dense phase (the coacervate) and a dilute supernatant.^[1] Through the modification of the local ionic strength, the physical properties of this coacervate phase can be tuned from a free-flowing viscoelastic fluid to a solid-like polyelectrolyte complex. However, being governed solely by non-covalent interactions such as electrostatic attraction and physical entanglements, these materials tend to yield and flow relatively quickly under sustained load.^[2] Reinforcement using permanent covalent crosslinks has proven unattractive, as it sacrifices the inherent tunability and adaptability of the coacervate system.^[3]

In this work, we demonstrate the use of dynamic covalent crosslinks as a viable strategy for the reinforcement of a complex coacervate. Specifically, the two reactive components of the acylhydrazone motif — an aldehyde and an acylhydrazide — are grafted onto the backbones of two oppositely charged polyelectrolytes, such that crosslink formation occurs upon mixing and coacervation. The resulting dynamically crosslinked coacervates are characterised by rheology.

The properties of the final material can be tuned through two independent handles: the addition of a simple inorganic salt such as sodium chloride shields the electrostatic interactions and weakens the coacervate network, while the introduction of a benzaldehyde competitor selectively disrupts the dynamic covalent crosslinks. Together, these orthogonal control mechanisms offer a versatile route to reinforced coacervate materials with retained adaptability.

[1] C. E. Sing and S. L. Perry, *Soft Matter* **2020**, *16*, 2885-2914.

[2] Y. Liu, H. H. Winter and S. L. Perry, *Adv Colloid Interface Sci* **2017**, *239*, 46-60.

[3] N. T. Nguyen, J. Jennings, A. H. Milani, C. D. S. Martino, L. T. B. Nguyen, S. Wu, M. Z. Mokhtar, J. M. Saunders, J. E. Gautrot, S. P. Armes and B. R. Saunders, *Biomacromolecules* **2022**, *23*, 1423-1432.

Subtle Polymer and Material Dynamics Revealed by Fluorescence Lifetime Imaging Microscopy

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This work presents the development of fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM) to investigate the dynamics of ring-opening metathesis polymerization (ROMP)-based polymers. A ROMP-functionalized, viscosity-sensitive fluorescent molecular rotor was designed to alter its fluorescence lifetime according to the viscosity of its polymeric microenvironment, enabling the imaging of changing physical parameters and catalytic activity in living polymers.[1] By coupling FLIM with fluorescence intensity microscopy, a correlation between the decreasing catalytic activity of Grubbs catalysts within the polydicyclopentadiene particles and the increasing microenvironment viscosity was established, providing a physical mechanism for the changing reaction kinetics observed for single Grubbs catalysts. Additionally, the high sensitivity of the molecular rotors revealed previously undisclosed differential block-selective responses to solvation changes upon the addition of DMSO and THF to self-assembled ROMP-based amphiphilic block copolymers.[2,3] This approach offered unique insights into block-selective, solvent-triggered assembly and disassembly mechanisms, with superior sensitivity compared to traditional ¹H-NMR spectroscopy.

[1] Eivgi, O.; Blum S. A. Real Time Viscosity-Catalytic activity Relationships in the Microscale *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2022**, 144, 13574–13585.

[2] Eivgi, O.; Ravenscroft, A. C.; Blum, S. A. Imaging Block-Selective Copolymer Solvation *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2023**, 145, 2058–2063.

[3] Lopez, P. A.; Eivgi, O.; Idris, N. S.; Patterson, J. P.; Blum, S. A. Self-Assembly Methods Induce Different Individual-Polymer-Block Solvation Responses, *Chem.-Eur. J.* **2025**, e202501617

Development of Dynamic Covalent Networks in Thermo-Responsive Coatings for Battery Safety

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Enhancing battery systems remains critical due to accidents caused by hazardous failures, which can lead to overheating and fire events. While recent research has focused on preventive measures, this study proposes a complementary precautionary approach by developing a thermo-responsive polythiourethane-urethane coating capable of releasing a tracer gas (TG) at well-defined temperatures (90 - 95 °C) [1]. The polymer matrix incorporates a thiol component that is cleaved and emitted in the gas phase during overheating events, enabling detection by metal oxide (MOx) sensors that trigger an alarm to signal a hazardous battery condition. To improve sustainability, the system is designed to be functionally recoverable by reintroducing the thiol compound into the polymer matrix, which shows gas release behavior comparable to the pristine one, as evaluated using quantitative methods and MOx sensor measurements. Following gas release, the coatings can be reprocessed and subsequently reused for further applications due to their network architecture based on dynamic covalent bonds. The reprocessed coatings were further characterized using rheological techniques, including stress relaxation and dynamic mechanical analysis. The latest work represents a continuous upgrade and optimization of the polymer network, allowing it to accommodate a higher TG content, as well as the addition of a catalyst to facilitate more efficient bond exchange in the polyurethane after releasing thiol gas.

[1] Hoang, V. K., Bautista, D., Ferdigg, G., Schlögl, S., Polymer (2026): 129758.

Programming Green Dynamic Polymer Networks Through Temperature Orthogonality

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Dynamic polymer networks capable of healing, reshaping, and reprocessing offer significant environmental benefits by extending service life and reducing material waste.[1,2] In covalent adaptable networks (CANs) governed by associative bond exchange reactions such as transesterification, bond exchange kinetics controls the balance between mechanical stability during service and rapid flow during processing. Thermally latent catalysts are particularly attractive because their activation depends solely on temperature, enabling use in bulk materials and additively manufactured parts without geometric or optical constraints.[3] Here, we systematically synthesise and investigate thermobase generators (TBGs) with well-defined activation and deactivation temperatures and study their influence on stress relaxation in thiol–ene based CANs. [4] Cyanoacetate- and oxalate-based TBGs releasing organic amine bases are characterized using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), and stress relaxation measurements, directly correlating catalyst (de)activation with macroscopic viscoelastic behaviour. By integrating TBGs with non-overlapping thermal activation windows into a single network, we achieve temperature orthogonality, enabling independent, temperature-selective control over multiple catalytic pathways. Stress relaxation experiments demonstrate reversible, multi-cycle switching between four distinct dynamic regimes using temperature alone. This approach decouples high creep resistance under service conditions from rapid flow during reshaping, repair, or welding. The concept is demonstrated in 3D-printed objects that can be reshaped and healed through controlled thermal triggers. By enabling programmable mechanical responses and efficient material reuse, temperature orthogonal latent catalysis provides a versatile platform for sustainable polymer networks, including switchable adhesives, soft actuators, and reprocessable materials for circular-economy manufacturing.

References

- [1] D. Reisinger, S. Kaiser, E. Rossegger, W. Alabiso, B. Rieger, S. Schlögl, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 60 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202102946>
- [2] W. Alabiso, S. Schlögl, *Polymers* 12 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym12081660>
- [3] D. Reisinger, M. U. Mayer-Kriehuber, M. Bender, D. Bautista-Anguís, B. Rieger, S. Schlögl, *Adv. Mater.* 35 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202300830>
- [4] M. U. Mayer-Kriehuber, E. Sattler, D. Reisinger, D. Bautista-Anguís, S. Gaca, C. Schmidleitner, I. Duretek, E. Vidovic, S. Schlögl, *RSC Adv.* 15 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1039/D5RA05095B>

Photopolymerized vegetable oil-based formulations with dynamic polymer network properties

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The development of renewable and degradable polymeric networks plays a central role in reducing carbon footprints and promoting a circular materials economy. The introduction of dynamic covalent chemistries such as transesterification lead to Dynamic Polymer Networks (DPNs) characterized by reversible crosslinks that can rearrange over time, enabling stress relaxation, self-healing, and reprocessability. In this work we have reported the design of vegetable oils derived biobased formulations exploitable in UV-Curing process.

In the first study [1] Grapeseed oil (GSO) and castor oil (CO) were selected as raw materials. GSO was maleinized and following methacrylated (MAGSO). Both GSO and CO were epoxidized via an environmentally friendly process. MAGSO combined with epoxidized oils enabled dual-cured systems: photopolymerization was followed by thermal curing through epoxy-acid reactions, yielding highly cross-linked networks. Biobased formulations were successfully 3D-printed. The crosslinked materials showed reprocessability, while also being chemically recyclable and degradable under mild alkaline conditions.

In a second work [2], fully bio-based photocurable formulations based on epoxidized castor oil (ECO) and epoxidized soybean oil (ESO) were developed for DLP 3D printing. ECO provided dynamic polymer network behavior due to its hydroxyl groups but suffered from high viscosity. Blending with lower-viscosity ESO improved printability. Thermal, mechanical, and rheological properties were evaluated, and dynamic behavior was assessed using stress relaxation tests with a biobased catalyst. The ECO-ESO 70-30 blend preserved good network dynamics. The formulations showed good 3D printability and thermal reprocessability, highlighting the promise of plant-oil-based materials for sustainable additive manufacturing.

[1] R. Alarcon, A. Cellai, M. Porcarello, B. Sölle, E. Rossegger, C. C. Schmitt, M. Sangermano, *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, 13 2025 16136–16153

[2] M. Porcarello, E. Greco, A. Cellai, R. Turra Alarcon, E. Rossegger, M. Sangermano, *Polymer Chemistry* submitted.

Recyclable Thermosets: Covalent Adaptable Networks Based on Methacrylated Lignin

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The depletion of fossil resources and the increasing level of environmental pollution intensify the demand for sustainable polymer materials. This challenge is particularly pronounced for thermosets, as desirable end-of-life solutions such as recycling are hindered by their permanently crosslinked network structure.

A promising approach to overcome this limitation is the concept of covalent adaptable networks (CAN), in which dynamic covalent bonds are incorporated into the polymer network, enabling recycling and reprocessing of otherwise permanently cured materials.

In this work, this concept is applied to the synthesis of lignin-based CANs. As lignin is one of the most abundant natural polymers, this strategy offers significant potential for the large-scale production of bio-based recyclable thermosets.

In our approach, lignin is functionalized with methacrylic anhydride to obtain lignin methacrylate. The synthesis is investigated with respect to the influence of different lignin sources, with particular focus on kraft and soda lignin, and is further optimized with regard to potential scale-up.

Network formation is achieved by reacting the methacrylated lignins with amines, yielding dynamic β -amino esters. Key parameters such as lignin source, degree of functionalization, and the incorporation of different comonomers are systematically varied to evaluate their influence on the dynamic mechanical properties, in particular relaxation behavior, and the reprocessability of the CANs.

[1] R. Tannert et al., *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* 309 (2023) 2300236

[2] R. Tannert et al., *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* (2026) *submitted*, PrePrint available, DOI: 10.26434/chemrxiv.15000657/v2

[3] G. Salfate et al., *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 278 (2024) 134697

Insight in thermal stability and dynamic wetting of PDMS-based covalent adaptable networks

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Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)-based elastomers, better known as silicones, are one of the most important materials for electrical insulation. However, a major drawback is their challenging recyclability. In recent years, numerous PDMS-based covalent adaptable networks (also called vitrimers) have been developed in an effort to integrate silicones into a sustainable circular economy.

The aim of our project is to identify vitrimer syntheses that are potentially of interest from an industrial viewpoint, implement them on a *larger* scale (i.e. ~ 500 g scale), and evaluate the suitability of the received materials as electrical insulators materials. Next to the mechanical and dielectrical properties that need to meet several target values,[3] the dynamic wetting properties of PDMS materials are of high importance, also for a good resistance against electrical stress.[1]

We analyzed the performance of (filled/unfilled) vinylogous urethane-based systems, [2] with regard to their thermal and mechanical stability and dynamic wetting behaviour. Samples '*as made*' will be compared with standard PDMS materials, reprocessed materials and materials that were stored for longer times (at increased temperatures).

We will discuss our results within the framework of dynamic bond exchange, which is measured by DMTA-measurements and analyzed using different models (e.g. relaxation spectra) in order to interconnect microscopic behaviour with macroscopic observations.

Initial results indicate that the filled dynamic PDMS networks show promising electrical properties and sufficient hydrophobicity. The long-term stability (even at room temperature) seems however to be strongly dependent on the presence/absence of fillers and network density. We will discuss derived hypotheses.

[1] F. Praße, S.Kornhuber, B.Voit, J.Weber, ACS Applied Polymer Materials 4 (2022) 4109

[2] Y. Spiesschaert, M. Guerre, L. Imbernon, J. M. Winne, F. Du Prez, Polymer 172 (2019) 239

[3] IEC TR 62039:2021, „Selection Guide for polymeric materials for use under HV stress“. International Electrotechnical Commission, 2021

Tough and Rapidly Relaxing Hydrogels *via* Programmable Crosslink Kinetics

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Replicating the synergy of high toughness and rapid stress relaxation found in native tissues remains a central challenge for synthetic polymer networks on account of their intrinsic mechanical-temporal trade-off. While previous work has primarily focused on network structure and topology as determinants of fracture behavior, these approaches offer limited control over time-dependent mechanics. Here, we introduce a supramolecular hydrogel platform that leverages kinetic programming to precisely regulate crosslink dynamics through molecular dissociation kinetics. This molecular design allows independent tuning of relaxation dynamics and fracture toughness, decoupling properties that are typically correlated. The resulting hydrogels exhibit stress relaxation ($t_{1/2} = 0.1\text{--}100\text{ s}$) two orders of magnitude faster than conventional networks while achieving exceptional fracture energy ($G_c = 14,500\text{ J/m}^2$), well above natural rubber. Systematic variation of crosslink dissociation kinetics reveals that slower bond exchange enhances energy dissipation under load, demonstrating a direct link between molecular kinetics and macroscopic toughness. These results establish crosslink kinetics as a fundamental design axis for programming time-dependent mechanical behavior, enabling the rational design of adaptive, high-performance soft materials.

Figure 1. (a) Conventional networks exhibit a trade-off between mechanical strength and relaxation dynamics. (b) Kinetic programming of crosslink lifetimes enables time-dependent mechanics in single polymer networks. (c) Crosslink kinetics regulate fracture behavior.

[1] Wei, Y.; O'Neill, S. J. K.; McCune, J. A.; Scherman, O. A. *Adv. Mater.* 2026, DOI: 10.1002/adma.202523440.

26th Polymer Networks Group Meeting Dresden 2026 - Contributed talk 3.4.13
Self-similar dynamics of dense, monodisperse, soft matter

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The spectral self-similarity of soft matter is examined. Two distinct self-similar regions, described by five physical parameters, govern linear viscoelasticity (LV) across several classes of structurally dissimilar systems. What these systems share is that they are densely disordered, monodisperse soft matter (DDMSM). The apparent universality of this dual self-similarity appears to arise primarily from monodispersity. Elements of uniform size, shape, and chemical character crowd one another and interact to form transient, cage-like constraints. In this environment, each element both cages its neighbors and is caged by them. The dual self-similarity is embodied in the BSW relaxation-time spectrum $H(\tau)$ [Rheol. Acta 29:400–408, 1990], featuring two opposing power-law regimes bounded by a longest relaxation time τ_{\max} , and intersecting at $(\tau_{\beta}, H_{\beta})$ (see figure). Powerlaw exponents range near $n_{\alpha} \approx 1/4$ (arm with slow cage modes) and $n_{\beta} \approx -3/4$ (arm with fast Rouse-like modes).

Caging of linear chains (“reptation”)

- long, linear, flexible,
- nearly uniform size

Caging of spherical particles

- slightly polydisperse

Is there a common analytical function for caging rheology ????

Spectral self-similarity has been reported for (a) polymers of long linear chains (melts and solutions), (b) hard sphere colloidal suspensions near the glass transition, (c) thermally vitrifying small-molecule liquids, and (d) two-dimensional particle mono layers; all being disordered and monodisperse or nearly monodisperse. In each case, variations in molecular weight or particle concentration

primarily shift the spectrum along the time or frequency axis while maintaining α - β slopes, see figures for DDMSMs a+b.

Remarkably, this dual scale invariance, clearly visible in relaxation time spectra $H(\tau)$, has largely gone unnoticed, possibly because LV is most commonly modeled using $G(t)$ or G' & G'' , which, as will be shown, obscure the self-similarity thereby adding extra parameters.

Experimental observations point to caging as the organizing principle of DDMSM rheology, rather than chemical detail or structural specificity, or specific interaction. The fast Rouse-like β -process is localized and largely oblivious to cage constraints until cooperative, cage-like dynamics emerges to cause the β - α transition. Beyond that, at larger τ , the slowly relaxing α -process is overpowering for most DDMSMs: A hierarchy of interacting cages and cage assemblies produces self-similar dynamics across scales, with the possibility of dynamical arrest arising upon percolation. Although the molecular or particulate origins of self-similarity differ among DDMSM types, their macroscopic rheology is strikingly universal, defining a distinct class of iso-caged matter which may be called "isocagers".

3.5 Elasticity and Fracture of Gels, Elastomers & Composites

In situ rheological monitoring of network formation and adhesion in protein gels

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Proteins are natural polymers capable of hierarchical self-assembly across multiple length scales. Under suitable conditions, partially unfolded proteins form amyloid fibrils that further organize into percolated three-dimensional networks, yielding gels with distinctive mechanical properties, such as the strong underwater adhesion observed in barnacles [1].

Here, two globular proteins, bovine serum albumin and lysozyme, are used as model systems exhibiting distinct fibrillation and gelation pathways. We investigate the influence of physicochemical conditions (pH and ionic strength) on these processes and reveal consistent relationships between fibril formation, network percolation, and the resulting macroscopic mechanical and adhesive properties, providing insight into structure-property relationships in protein-based networks and the design of bioinspired adhesive soft materials.

Fibrillation and gelation are induced and monitored *in situ* in a rheometer under controlled temperature and shear. The resulting gels are then subjected to probe tack inspired tests in the same geometry, enabling quantification of adhesion while preserving the fibrillar network. This approach requires only small sample volumes, making it well suited for biological systems.

Figure 1. In situ rheological induction of protein fibrillation and subsequent adhesion testing (inset: rheology spectra, SEM image, probe-tack spectra).

[1] K. Fears, B. Orihuela, D. Rittschof, and K. Wahl, [Advanced Science](https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.201800762) 5 (2018) 1700762

Rheological properties of a plant protein network close to the gel point

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Gluten is a complex protein network that plays a pivotal role in breadmaking quality and is widely employed in the food industry as a texturing agent. It exhibits structural and mechanical characteristics of dynamic polymer gels, including remarkable extensibility, strain hardening, and self-healing capabilities. Investigating this material rheology in both linear and nonlinear regimes, we demonstrate that it behaves as a near critical gel [1,2] and that singular properties, such as a two-step yielding at very large strain, are measured close to the gel point [3,4]. We further show that repeated large-amplitude shear deformations modify the gluten network structure, whereas extended rest periods promote partial self-healing [3]. The proximity to the gel point thus emerges as a key parameter governing the mechanical response of such gels under large strain. This insight is particularly relevant for various food-related processes, including dough kneading, gas bubble stabilization, and the mastication of food gels, and may also have implications for adhesive applications.

[1] M. Dahesh, A. Banc, A. Duri, MH. Morel, L.Ramos *Food Hydrocolloids* (2016) 52, 1.

[2] Louhichi, Morel, Ramos, Banc, *ACSMacroLetter* (2024) 13, 7, 826–831.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmacrolett.4c00121>

[3] J G Pichon, „ Rheological properties of plant protein dispersions close to the gel point: from gelation control to adjustment of the response to large deformations. “, Ph.D. thesis, University of Montpellier (2025).

Hydrogen-bonding mediated liquid metal-elastomeric architectures for soft matter engineering

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Liquid metal (LM)- integrated elastomeric composites are a breakthrough in soft, multifunctional materials with immense transformative potential, leveraging innumerable possibilities for high-end engineering applications. LMs, such as the eutectic gallium-indium alloy, mitigate longstanding filler-matrix modulus mismatch issues in rigid filler-based composites while imparting immense functionality [1]. However, the challenge that remains in the fabrication of such promising materials lies in fundamental issues of phase incompatibility and the lack of interaction between the polymer and the LM, leading to critical failures during fabrication. In this work, we report a novel hybrid material by integrating an eutectic gallium-indium LM alloy into different thermoplastic elastomeric (TPE) matrices, which are further hybridized with carbonyl iron particles, resulting in a soft, ultra-stretchable hybrid elastomer architecture that exploits the H-bonding interaction between LMs and TPEs[2]. The incompressible nature of the LM-inclusions exhibits synergistic adaptative deformation with the elastomer matrix, imparting ultra-stretchability and reduced hysteresis loss while inducing multifunctional attributes such as outstanding dielectric permittivity, thermal conductivity, and robust piezo-responsiveness. The experimentally determined results are also theoretically validated using Eshelby's and modified Eshelby's approach, the modified Cole-Cole model, and the Bruggeman formulation [2, 3]. Henceforth, this work provides a cost-effective, facile, and scalable approach to construct smart multifunctional composites for soft matter engineering.

TOC Graphic

- [1] P.S. Banerjee, D.K. Rana, S.S. Banerjee, *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* **308** (2022), 102752.
 [2] P.S. Banerjee, S.S. Banerjee, *J. Mater. Sci.* **58** (2023), 14009-14028.
 [3] P.S. Banerjee, D. Mukherjee, D. Mallick, S.S. Banerjee, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **10** (2025), e00262.

New Methods to Characterize the Deformation and Damage Behavior of Tough Double-Network

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Soft polymers, such as hydrogels, exhibit complex mechanical behavior depending not only on the material structure and properties but also on the external loading, e.g. monotonic or cyclic tension. To better understand structure-property relationships, systematic investigations using advanced experimental techniques are required and key challenge is the precise estimation of deformation fields [1]. In this contribution, new methods for strain field analysis specifically designed to address the following challenges will be presented: (i) easily applicable micro-particles for speckle patterns to analyze strain fields at high and in particular inhomogeneous deformation; (ii) sophisticated evaluation software for data analysis of optical images; (iii) (semi)-transparent materials of specimens; (iv) *in situ* measurements for comprehensive investigations on deformation and damage. The results provide deeper insights into the underlying microstructural mechanisms characterizing the deformation behavior of tough double-network hydrogels [2]. Additionally, the use specific spores for speckle pattern generation on hydrogels proves effective not only in air but also in aqueous environments, e.g. to identify inhomogeneous swelling due to structural heterogeneities indicating deformation-induced damage. These data help to improve constitutive modeling significantly and pave the way to more accurate predictions of numerical simulations including local damage parameters [3].

- [1] T. Nakajima, T. Kurokawa, S. Ahmed, W. Wu, and J.P. Gong, [Soft Matter 9 \(2013\) 1955-1966](#).
- [2] S. Wang, E. Euchler, and S. Wiessner, [Polymer 340 \(2025\) 129190](#).
- [3] V. Khiem, T. Xuefeng, S. Wang, E. Euchler, A. Verda, and R. Göstl (manuscript in preparation).

Tough, dual networks with epoxy and metal coordination bonds

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Material stiffness and maximum elongation are usually at odds, with stiffer materials exhibiting a shorter elongation to fracture. Dry polymer networks with dual bonding, here epoxy covalent and metal coordination iron-catecholate bonds, have been shown [1] to create much stiffer and tougher networks from their non-metal coordination precursors, while mitigating the issue of decreased extensibility. In recent work, we attempt to quantify the extent of elasticity increase accounted by the re-arranged spatial topology, combining experiments and atomistic simulations of these complex architectures.

The reversible temperature-dependent elasticity of such networks studied by conventional and piezo rheology points to the metal-coordination bond thermal activation. MD simulations building upon previous ones on non-dual epoxy networks [2] allow us to probe the role of hydrogen bonding and access topology. Finally, network variations using bio-sourced polymers are aimed towards building sustainable tough materials.

[1] Filippidi, Cristiani, *et. al.*, [*Science* **358** \(2017\) 502-505.](#)

[2] Delasoudas, Kallivokas, Filippidi, [*ACS Macro Lett.*, **14** \(2025\) 1783-1788.](#)

Watching Bond Break during Tire Wear by Friction

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Tire wear results from the sliding contact between the rubbery tire tread and the asperities of the road surface. This process leads to material abrasion, altering tire performance and generating wear particles. While the macroscopic characterization of tire wear is well-documented, its microscopic understanding is far from complete^[1]. Here, we build upon a state-of-the-art mechanochemical strategy^{[2][3]} allowing for the direct and quantitative spatial mapping of chain damage in industrially relevant material following frictional wear. This approach relies on the incorporation of a mechanophore molecule as additional crosslinker in a filled rubber, which becomes fluorescent upon scission, acting as a reporter for bond breakage^[4]. Our measurements reveal a complex scenario for the departure of material from the surface. Repeated, fatigue-like solicitations by the sliding contacting asperities first induce diffuse damage in the subsurface. Particles nucleate as rolls of micrometric size from this damaged subsurface, before coalescing into wear particles of several 10-100 μm sizes. Revealing previously invisible processes, our approach provides key mechanistic insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying tire wear.

[1] B. N. J. Persson et al., *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **163** (2025) 14.

[2] J. Sloopman, et al., *Physical Review X* **10** (2020) 041045.

[3] O. Taisne, et al., *arXiv* (2025) [arXiv:2506.17860](https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.17860).

[4] A. Cartier, et al, *Macromolecules* **57** (2024) 8712-8721

Analysis of the force applied on the regular polymer network using FLAP mechanophore

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Understanding the mechanical properties of gels requires the clarification of the forces applied to their network strands. However, methods to experimentally measure these forces are limited. In this study, we conducted a quantitative analysis by correlating the changes in the fluorescence spectrum of the mechanophore, which is a force-responsive chemical moiety, with the mechanical model-estimated forces applied on the polymer chains in the gels. For our experiments, we introduced a mechanophore called FLAP^[1,2] into the tetra-PEG gels. FLAP is a molecule that undergoes structural deformation when mechanical force is applied, resulting in a change in its fluorescence spectrum. A tetra-PEG gel has a highly homogeneous, well-regulated network structure. The structural characteristics of the tetra-PEG gels are known to be in good agreement with the rubber elasticity models.

Tensile and compression tests were performed on these gels. The Arruda-Boyce model was adopted to estimate the forces on the network strands based on the stress-strain relationships.^[3] At the same time, we measured intensity ratio of blue to green fluorescence emitted by FLAP in each conformations. We found a strong correlation between the fluorescence ratio and the estimated force.

Through these experiments, we confirmed that introducing a FLAP mechanophore into a tetra-PEG gel enables the estimation of the average force generated in network strands during its bulk deformation based on changes in the fluorescence spectrum.

[1] R. Kotani *et al.*, *Nat Commun.*, **2022**, 13, 303

[2] T. Yamakado *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **2022**, 144, 2804–2811

[3] M. Arruda *et al.*, *J. Mesh. Phys. Solids.*, **1993**, 41, 2, 389–412

Hydrogel Nanocomposite-Based Ink Materials for 3D Printing

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Nature-inspired hydrogels incorporated with nanomaterials have emerged as potential inks for 3D bioprinting applications. Over the past decade, researchers have shown considerable interest in developing new ink materials at the interface of synthetic polymers, biomaterials, and inorganic nanoparticles, to achieve printability with unique features such as tunable mechanics and desired physico-chemical properties for enabling customized 3D constructs with high shape-fidelity and biological performances.[1,2] Here, I will present our recent research development on new hydrogel nanocomposites, incorporated with photoluminescent nanomaterials,[3] and RAFT-made well-defined polymers. Such hydrogels were formed via supramolecular interactions and exhibited unique mechanical and rheological properties to afford extrusion-based 3D printing with retained photoluminescence. Various microscopic analyses were undertaken to investigate their extruded filament's diameter, surface roughness, and self-sustainability. Further, the cellular compatibility of the hydrogels and their printed scaffolds was examined via in vitro studies, which suggested their potential applications for bioimaging and therapeutic applications.

[1] S. Kumar, *Mater. Adv.* **2** (2021), 6928-6941.

[2] S. Kumar, A. Tharayil, S. Thomas, *ACS Applied Polym. Mater.* **3** (2021), 3685-3701.

[3] S. Dasari, T. Kasilingam, P. Bhatt, M. S. Singh, and S. Kumar, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **46** (2025), e00427.

Reversible Ionic Network Formation in Epoxidized Natural Rubber Yields Biobased Elastomers with High Mechanical Performance & Durability

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Conventional sulfur-cured epoxidized natural rubber exhibits poor long-term stability as oxirane ring opening reactions promote ether bond formation, resulting in an increase in network rigidity, and leading to rapid hardening of the material and loss of elastomer-like properties. As a result, the practical use of sulfur-vulcanized ENR remains challenging. In this study, we demonstrate the formation of a stable and reversibly crosslinked network in ENR using dicarboxylic acids in combination with suitable aromatic heterocyclic amines. The influence of various aliphatic and aromatic heterocyclic amines on the crosslinking behavior was systematically investigated, with the objective of stabilizing ionic intermediates to promote reversible ionic network rather than permanent covalent crosslinks. Rheo-optical FTIR analysis of the orientation function of carboxylate ion during cyclic uniaxial deformation demonstrates its reversible orientation behavior confirming the grafting of carboxylate groups onto the ENR backbone. Compared to sulfur vulcanized ENR, the system based on dodecanedioic acid and 4-dimethylaminopyridine exhibits comparable mechanical strength along with significantly enhanced aging resistance attributed to its iminium-carboxylate-based network structure. This robust and stable ionic network enables self-healing with high tensile strength (~11 MPa) after healing.

[1] Kundu et al. *Chemistry of Materials* **2026** (submitted)

[2] Mandal et al. *Sustainable Materials and Technologies* **2025**, 43, e01243.

[3] Mandal et al. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2023**, 474, 145838.

On the symmetry breaking between gelation and network degradation

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Recent experiments indicate [1] a possible symmetry breaking between gelation and network degradation processes in contrast to the predictions of percolation models and classical mean field models. This problem is analyzed by large scale computer simulations with a focus on reaction kinetics and loop formation, since these factors contribute to a non-ideal position of the gelation threshold and these may indeed cause a symmetry breaking [2]. In contrast to these, corrections known from “percolation with a range” models (describing the transition between the classical nearest neighbor percolation problem and the mean field solution [2]) cannot break the symmetry.

Simulation data and numerical modeling [3] show that loop formation is asymmetric as a function of conversion leading to a slightly lower gelation threshold (in terms of conversion) when breaking the network. This is in qualitative agreement with the experimental data. Moreover, reaction kinetics couples to the contact statistics between objects of different architecture, which leads to significant deviations from a random distribution of reactions at the cross-links. Since this distribution narrows with decreasing concentration, it provides a second correction to the gel point that increases in amplitude with decreasing concentration. Predictions for this effect can be derived by considering model predictions for the contact statistics.

Close to the overlap concentration or below, the approximation for the contact statistics starts to break down. In this concentration regime, the reaction partners have to diffuse and to rearrange conformations upon reactions. These effects lead to further deviations from symmetry as diffusion or a change in conformations are not necessary to break a bond.

Altogether, these results imply that the degree of symmetry breaking is triggered by the molecular architecture implying a significant asymmetry for end-linked model networks at low concentrations, whereas this effect is nearly not detectable for networks made of star polymers, if pending loops are suppressed. In any of these cases, the asymmetry increases with decreasing concentrations.

[1] H. K. Beech, T.-S. Lin, D. Sen, D. Rota, and B. D. Olsen, *Macromolecules* 56 (2023) 9255–9263.

[2] M. Lang, T. Müller, *Macromolecules* 53 (2020) 498-512.

[3] M. Lang, R. Scholz, T. Müller, *Polymer* 330 (2025) 128454.

Adhesive Intelligence Enabled by Polymer Network Topology at Bulk and Interfaces

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Polymer networks have been engineered with a primary focus on bulk properties such as elasticity and dissipation. In biomedical adhesives, this bulk-centric perspective has enabled the development of tough adhesives whose adhesion performance can be rationally tuned through bulk dissipation [1]. Our recent work established quantitative scaling relationships linking fracture energy to bulk polymer network parameters, revealing how swelling mediates elasticity, fracture, and adhesion properties [2]. These insights provide a foundational framework connecting polymer network physics to adhesive performance.

However, many biomedical challenges—such as adhering to soft, hydrated, or brittle tissues—cannot be resolved by bulk network design alone. We envision that adhesive intelligence emerges when polymer networks are deliberately engineered at the interface, forming a distinct yet coupled interfacial polymer network that governs crack initiation and propagation. Building on this concept, we introduced a strategy to program hydrogel adhesion through engineered interfacial network topology [3]. By enabling slip-like interfacial entanglement between polymer networks, we achieved dynamic, rate-dependent, and controllable adhesion without relying on permanent covalent bonding. In subsequent work, we further demonstrate that coupling interfacial entanglement with viscous liquids enables anomalous tough adhesion on brittle and delicate tissues, a regime previously inaccessible to existing adhesive technologies. By fine-tuning the interfacial polymer network and its viscoelastic response, crack propagation can be confined to the interface and prevented from kinking into fragile substrates, thereby protecting substrate integrity while maintaining high adhesion energy.

Together, my talk highlights hierarchical network engineering across bulk and interfaces. This perspective opens new opportunities for next-generation biomedical adhesives that adapt, dissipate energy, and protect living tissues through programmable polymer network topology.

[1] Jianyu Li, et al., *Science*, 357, 6349, 378-381 (2017)

[2] Xiang Ni, Zhen Yang, Jianyu Li, *ACS Macro Letters*, 10, 2, 180-185 (2021)

[3] Zhen Yang, et al., Jianyu Li, *PNAS*, 120, 39 (2023)

Effect of microstructural evolution on macro-mechanical properties of double-network hydrogels

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The double-network polyacrylamide-alginate hydrogel with the additional alginate network cross-linked by Fe^{3+} ions (PAAm-Alg- Fe^{3+}) exhibits excellent mechanical properties due to its special two-scale network microstructure [1]. Systematic investigations on the microstructural evolution of the PAAm-Alg- Fe^{3+} hydrogel under uniaxial tension using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) are conducted. It is found that the whole microstructural evolution process can be divided into four stages with distinct macro-mechanical properties: (I) “Elastic” stage (small strains): few network rupture leading to negligible energy dissipation and almost fully recoverable deformation; (II) “Pre-yielding” stage (moderate strains): small dissipation arising solely from the rupture of small amount of the Alg network; the PAAm network remains almost intact with only slight pore enlargement leading to small residual strain; (III) “Yielding” -stress-plateau- stage (large strains): extensive rupture of Alg network resulting in significant energy dissipation; concurrently, partial PAAm network rupture leading to a noticeable residual strain; (IV) Hardening stage (very large strains): widespread failure of the Alg network and significant rupture of PAAm network producing large residual strain and extremely high energy dissipation. These four stages are consistent with the microstructural features observed in SEM images.

[1] J. Liu, et al., *Journal of Polymer Science* 63 (2025) 3214-3228.

Network mechanics with mechanofluorescent DNA hydrogels.

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How does macroscale stress translate into molecular forces in soft hydrogels? This question is of prime interest for the design of advanced water-based materials with tunable elasticity, stress at break, toughness, and dynamics. It is also key to improving the design of mechanosensitive materials for early damage detection or for cell–matrix force measurements.

We address this question using mechanofluorescent DNA hydrogels that convert mechanical stimuli into fluorescence signals (see figure). In our previous work, we only demonstrated a strain-controlled fluorescence response [1]. We have recently developed a transparent shear cell coupled with a fluorescence imager for stress-controlled mechano-fluorescence measurements. With this new setup, we can rationalize the link between fluorescence response, macroscale behavior, and molecular mechanics. In particular, we show how the increase in fluorescence is linked to the flexibility of the network and to its stress-stiffening properties. Using a new design that reports the forces applied to specific strands within the network, we further show how to tune the sensitivity of the fluorescence response independently of the gel elasticity.

[1] R. Merindol, G. Delechiave, L. Heinen, L. H. Catalani and A. Walther, *Nat. Commun.*, 2019, **10**, 528.

Recyclable Disulfide-Based Vitrimers with Adhesive Properties

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A family of disulfide (S–S) containing [1] thiol–vinyl–epoxy dynamic networks are presented. The networks are obtained through a dual-curing mechanism, wherein a photoinduced thiol–ene reaction at room temperature is followed by a thermally activated, tertiary amine–catalyzed thiol–epoxy curing stage, as shown in **Figure 1**, enabling controlled network development. Cured materials show reprocessability thanks to heat-triggered disulfide bond exchange. The influence of catalyst structure on curing behavior, thermomechanical properties, stress relaxation, and this reprocessability was systematically investigated. These solvent-free materials with a unique ternary composition exhibit efficient network rearrangement and successful thermal reprocessing, demonstrating their potential as sustainable materials.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the dual-curing process involving UV-induced thiol–ene photopolymerization followed by a thermally activated thiol–epoxy reaction.

Lap shear tests were performed on DBA formulations to evaluate their adhesive performance. The force–displacement curves obtained at room temperature and at 80 °C are shown in **Figure 2**. At room temperature, the joint exhibits a significantly higher maximum stress ($\tau_{\text{max}} = 1.89 \pm 0.11$ MPa) and a gradual increase in force up to failure, indicating strong adhesion between the aluminum substrates.

Figure 2. Force–displacement curves from lap shear tests of the DBA adhesive joints at room temperature (RT) and 80 °C.

[1] O. Konuray, S. Moradi, A. Roig, X. Fernández-Francos, X. Ramis, ACS Appl. Polym. Mater. 5 (2023) 1651–1656. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsapm.2c02136>.

Multiscale structure and mechanics of collagen filaments

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Synthetic hydrogels are widely studied as model systems in soft matter and biomaterials because of their high water content, potential biocompatibility and tunable mechanical properties. In vivo, type I collagen constitutes the main component of the extracellular matrix (ECM), where it fulfills structural and biochemical functions. [1] Collagen's ability to self-assemble into a complex network of fibrils and to respond to mechanical signals makes it a relevant model to study the interplay between structure and mechanical behavior. [2]

This study focuses on developing collagen hydrogels produced by in vitro extrusion as simplified biological matrices. This method allows control over fibrillation and induces fibril alignment during filament formation. [3] The aim is to create well-defined filaments that mimic key ECM features and to investigate how their microstructure and physico-chemical environment affect their mechanical responses.

Despite being mostly composed of water, without chemical crosslinking, these collagen filaments exhibit remarkable mechanical performance. Their behavior combines poroelastic and viscoelastic characteristics, reflecting the coupling between fluid transport and collagen network dynamics. [4] Supramolecular interactions between collagen fibrils enable stress-induced structural rearrangements, allowing the network to remodel under mechanical loading. Taking advantage of this intrinsic adaptability, the hydrogel filaments were mechanically conditioned to tune and enhance their mechanical properties. This work highlights how processing-induced architecture and supramolecular interactions govern the mechanical behavior of collagen-based networks.

Figure 1: Tensile behavior of 5 wt% collagen filaments. (a) Water efflux during loading. (b) Tensile response before and after mechanical conditioning. Mechanical conditioning induces an increase in collagen concentration (from 5 to 10 wt%) and in linear modulus (from 0.3 to 2.3 MPa).

[1] P. Fratzl, „Collagen: Structure and mechanics“, New York: Springer (2008).

[2] J. Brun *et al.*, [Polymer 338 \(2025\)](#).

[3] A. Dewle *et al.*, [ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng. 6 \(2020\)](#).

[4] A. Ehret *et al.*, [Nat. Commun. 8 \(2017\)](#).

Unique mechanical properties of model network elastomers driven by supercoiling and strain-induced crystallization

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Conventional elastomers are prepared by random cross-linking of flexible polymer chains. This process leads to various types of defect in the network structure such as nonuniform network chain length. The defects can be reduced by forming a network via end-linking of monodisperse precursor polymer. Such a network is referred to as model network. Despite its significance as a model system, the potential of model network elastomers as a high-performance material has been rarely explored. In this presentation, I introduce our recent studies on the unique and excellent mechanical properties of model network elastomers.

We synthesized a model network elastomer consisting of amorphous aliphatic polyester. Monodisperse star-shaped polyester prepolymers were synthesized by ring-opening polymerization followed by end-group modification. The prepolymer in solution was end-linked to form a gel, which was subsequently dried to obtain a solvent-free model network elastomer. The elastomer showed not only excellent stretchability (stretch ratio at break ~19) and strength (stress at break ~26 MPa) but also extraordinary strain stiffening capability. That is, the initially low stress increased abruptly when the material was stretched beyond a certain strain. The apparent stiffness showed more than 2,000-fold increase. This level of strain stiffening has never been observed in any known soft materials.

Detailed analyses revealed two key factors for the unique mechanical response of the model network elastomer. The low stress and high stretchability before the strain stiffening was due to supercoiling. Supercoiling is a phenomenon in which network chains adopt a highly collapsed conformation upon removal of solvent from a network. On the other hand, the large strain stiffening was caused by strain-induced crystallization (SIC) of the network chains, as revealed by an in situ X-ray scattering analysis. The amorphous network chains partially crystallized under large strains, inducing a significant stress upturn. Although both supercoiling and SIC have already been known for a long time, the combination of the two phenomena resulted in the unique, unprecedented mechanical properties of our model network elastomer.

[1] S. Nakagawa *Polym. J.* (2026) in print. DOI: 10.1038/s41428-026-01158-5

[2] S. Nakagawa and N. Yoshie *Polym. Chem.* **13** (2022) 2074-2107.

[3] S. Nakagawa et al. *Adv. Mater.* **35** (2023) 2301124.

Theory of Gel Dynamics with General Linear Viscoelasticity

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Polymer-gel dynamics are commonly described by phenomenological continuum theories such as the Tanaka–Hocker–Benedek (THB) theory [1] and the Doi–Onuki theory [2]. However, it remains unclear under what conditions these theories are valid and how they should be extended to more general viscoelastic response.

We propose a Lagrangian formulation for polymer-gel dynamics with general linear viscoelasticity based on an energy-conserving minimal model of the polymer network, the solvent, and the saturation constraint. By decomposing the fields into slow and fast components and eliminating the fast modes, we derive effective equations of motion with dissipation, in which the polymer network obeys a generalized Langevin equation with a memory kernel:

$$\rho_p \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_p(\mathbf{r}, t) = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{r}, t) - \int_0^t dt' \gamma(\mathbf{r}, t - t') [\dot{\mathbf{u}}_p(\mathbf{r}, t') - \mathbf{v}_s(\mathbf{r}, t')] + \boldsymbol{\xi}(\mathbf{r}, t)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_p(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the network displacement, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the elastic stress tensor of the polymer, and $\mathbf{v}_s(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the local velocity of the solvent. $\gamma(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is a memory kernel determined by the interaction with the eliminated fast modes: in thermal equilibrium it is related to the autocorrelation of the random force $\boldsymbol{\xi}(\mathbf{r}, t)$. Thus, the friction is governed by the relative motion between network and solvent and becomes temporally nonlocal in general. In the memoryless limit, $\gamma(\mathbf{r}, t) \propto \delta(t)$, the theory reduces to THB- and Doi–Onuki-type equations. It thus provides a common basis for discussing both conventional gel dynamics and memory effects within the same formalism.

As applications, we derive the complex modulus beyond the memoryless limit and study gel swelling within the same limit. In particular, for swelling with a power-law memory kernel $\gamma(\mathbf{r}, t) \propto t^{-s}$, corresponding to fractional derivative, we derive the equation of motion, the collective diffusion coefficient, the characteristic swelling time, and an analytical solution, and show that the relaxation is described by the Mittag–Leffler function.

[1] T. Tanaka, L. O. Hocker, and G. B. Benedek, [*J. Chem. Phys.* **59**, 5151 \(1973\)](#).

[2] M. Doi and A. Onuki, [*J. Phys. II France* **2**, 1631 \(1992\)](#).

Mechanical elasticity of 2-dimensional self-assembled semi-flexible polymer networks

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Synthetic polymer networks and biopolymer assemblies derive their mechanical properties from a combination of molecular architectures, connectivity, and topology. Although factors such as crosslinker density and polymer concentration have been extensively studied, the role of film thickness, particularly in systems with reversible non-covalent crosslinks, remains unexplored.

In this coarse-grained molecular dynamics study, we investigate the molecular mechanisms that can influence the mechanical response of self-assembled transient polymer networks composed of end-linked linear strands under uniaxial deformation. Each strand is modeled as a semi-flexible chain with attractive end monomers that form reversible non-covalent crosslinks.

We determine how the mechano-elastic response of such networks differs from the bulk system by varying (i) network thickness, (ii) strength of attraction between end monomers, and (iii) the concentration of detached-chain defects. To do so, the tensile strength, toughness, Poisson ratio, nematic ordering of polymer chains, and deformation-induced topological changes in these quasi-2D networks are quantified. Our simulations reveal that increasing the thickness of the network shifts the Poisson ratio to bulk-like behavior. Meanwhile, stronger end-end attractions enhance strain stiffening, which increases tensile strength and toughness. Finally, introducing detached-chain defects triggers a transition in the nematic order between the low and high strain regimes. These findings might offer insights into new design principles for polymer films and underlying principles in various biological systems, such as defects in the nuclear lamina.

Programmable shape-memory enabled by polymer-dispersed liquid crystal elastomer composites

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In addition to reversible thermomechanical actuation driven by the order-disorder transition, liquid crystal elastomers (LCEs) can exhibit thermally driven one-way shape relaxation after mechanical deformation via soft-elastic ordering of the liquid crystal polydomain structure. Although such strains are relatively short-lived due to network elasticity, they can be preserved by increasing the glassiness of the LC system at lower temperatures, resulting in unique shape-memory behaviour [1].

This mechanism enables the preparation of reversibly shape-programmed LCE microparticles by thermal cycling under shear flow, leading to temperature- and shear-programmable viscosity of the LCE dispersion [2]. By incorporating LCE microparticles into conventional PDMS to form polymer-dispersed LCE composites, the PDMS becomes thermomechanically functionalised, resulting in a cost-effective material that can be readily moulded into complex geometries while exhibiting programmable shape and reversible morphing.

[1] M. Bobnar, N. Derets, S. Umerova, V. Domenici, N. Novak, M. Lavrič, G. Cordoyiannis, B. Zalar and A. Rešetič, [Nature Communications](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-30000-0) **14** (2023) 764

[2] S. Umerova, D. Kuscer, M. Bobnar, N. Derets, B. Zalar and A. Rešetič, [Materials & Design](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2021.109836) **207** (2021) 109836

Analytical expression for fracture profile in viscoelastic crack propagation: Foundation for de Gennes' viscoelastic trumpet

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We derive an analytical expression for the strain field, including the fracture profile, during steady-state crack propagation in viscoelastic solids [1]. This expression is obtained by exactly solving a fracture model that incorporates the standard linear solid (i.e., three-element Zener) model, one of the most fundamental constitutive models in linear viscoelasticity.

The analytical solution reveals three distinct regions in the fracture profile and in the strain field ahead of the crack tip: glassy, viscous, and rubbery regions. Each region is characterized by a power-law exponent that evolves with distance from the crack tip. As the crack-propagation velocity increases, the viscous region expands, causing the crack tip to sharpen progressively. This result provides a clear explanation for the experimentally observed crack-tip sharpening in rubbers and gels at high propagation velocities, a phenomenon often associated with catastrophic failure triggered by a velocity jump. Notably, this sharpening arises purely from linear viscoelasticity, without invoking nonlinear material effects.

Furthermore, we establish de Gennes' viscoelastic trumpet [2], which predicts that the crack opening profile takes the shape of a trumpet, on a rigorous continuum-mechanical foundation. While de Gennes originally derived the trumpet shape through a scaling argument, our analysis shows that the same result emerges exactly from the governing equations of fracture mechanics. In addition, our solution reveals a strain plateau ahead of the crack tip, consistent with recent experimental observations [3], which was not captured by de Gennes' original theory.

These results provide a unified analytical framework for understanding crack propagation in polymer networks and should contribute to the fracture control and durability improvement of gels, elastomers, and their composites.

[1] H. Nagatakiya, N. Sakumichi, *et al.*, [Phys. Rev. Res. **7**, L042001 \(2025\)](#).

[2] P. G. de Gennes, Soft adhesives, [Langmuir **12**, 4497 \(1996\)](#); "Soft Interfaces: The 1994 Dirac Memorial Lecture", Cambridge Univ. Press (1997).

[3] T.-T. Mai *et al.*, [ACS Macro Lett. **9**, 762 \(2020\)](#).

Crystallization in Polymer Networks under Deformation: A Simulation Study

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We have investigated the crystallization of crosslinked and non-crosslinked polymers under external deformation using the coarse-grained polyvinyl alcohol model (CG-PVA) [1] via molecular dynamics simulations. Following uniaxial deformation, the systems with various crosslink densities are cooled at a constant rate to form semi-crystalline states and subsequently heated at a constant rate to induce melting. For unstretched systems, network junctions do not significantly affect the nucleation temperature but increase the amorphous fraction and reduce the melting temperature. Under constant stress, crystallization induces additional elongation beyond the initial pre-stretch and leads to pronounced mechanical hysteresis upon heating, a behavior characteristic of reversible shape-memory materials, see figure [2]. Our simulations show that during crystallization in the uniaxially deformed state, the formation of crystalline stems compresses the amorphous sequences, increasing their entropy and thereby causing the elastomer to extend further beyond the preparation state.

Uniaxial deformation vs. temperature during cooling/heating cycles for three values of the pre-stretch and various crosslink densities.

[1] C.-F. Luo and J.-U. Sommer, *Computer Phys. Comm.* 180, 1382 (2009)

[2] A. Bhardwaj, H. Shabbir, J.-U. Sommer, and M. Werner, *arXiv:2601.11192* (2026)

Extracting Hard-to-Measure Hydrogel Properties Using Freezing Experiments

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The movement of liquid within hydrogels is crucial for various applications, from swelling-induced actuation in plants and soft robotics to drug delivery, filtration, and catalysis. Key properties governing this behavior include permeability, osmotic behavior, and the elasticity of the polymer network. However, measuring these properties remains extremely challenging.

In this talk, I will introduce a novel approach using freezing experiments to quantify these properties. This method, adapted from freezing-point osmometry [1], involves equilibrating small hydrogel samples with ice. Ice essentially sucks water from the hydrogel, causing shrinkage that depends on temperature. By analyzing shrinkage versus temperature, we determine osmotic properties. Additionally, embedding hydrogels in ice in a temperature gradient induces motion due to differential suction, allowing us to measure permeability. Our results show that widely-used classical theories predicting transport properties in hydrogels can be wrong by orders of magnitude.

Beyond the direct measurement of hydrogel transport properties, I will explain how our experiments offer a useful technique for probing the microstructure of hydrogels.

[1] Feng, Y.; Gerber, D.; Heyden, S.; Kröger, M.; Dufresne, E. R.; Isa, L.; Style, R. W. J. *Mech. Phys. Solids*. 2025, 201, 106166.

Partitioning Law of Polymer Chains into Homogeneous Polymer Networks

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The equilibrium partitioning of linear polymer chains into polymer networks is governed by entropic constraints arising from configurational degrees of freedom, yet quantitative understanding has remained elusive. Partitioning ratios are commonly interpreted using the Ogston model [1] or thermodynamic approaches [2], but these frameworks neglect network topology and thus cannot quantitatively predict partitioning into different gel networks.

Using model hydrogels with precisely controlled network structures formed from star-shaped poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG), we experimentally demonstrate a universal law governing polymer chain partitioning into flexible networks. By employing PEG for both the network and the solute chains, we isolated purely topological constraints. We established a novel label-free method to determine partition ratios from swelling measurements, based on the semidilute scaling law [3]. Our results reveal that the Nernst distribution law holds in the dilute regime, yielding a constant partition ratio $K_0 = \exp[-4(R_g/l_{\text{cycle}})^2]$, where R_g is the gyration radius of the linear polymer and $l_{\text{cycle}} \equiv \xi^{-1/3}$ is the network mesh size defined by the cycle rank ξ . These findings establish l_{cycle} as the fundamental length scale governing partitioning, unifying network topology with mechanical and partitioning properties.

- [1] A. G. Ogston, *Trans. Faraday Soc.* **54** (1958) 1754-1757.
 [2] F. Horkay and M. Zrinyi, *J. Macromol. Sci., Phys.* **25** (1986) 307-334.
 [3] T. Yasuda *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **125** (2020) 267801; N. Sakumichi, T. Yasuda, and T. Sakai, arXiv:2210.15275 (2022).
 [4] H. Takarai *et al.*, [arXiv:2505.05254](https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.05254) (2025).

Transformation of vegetable oils into advanced materials via 3D printing processes

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Additive manufacturing, commonly known as 3D printing, is a rapidly growing industry for producing functional materials for real-world applications from polymers. However, as production worldwide doubled from 234 to 400 million tons over the last 20 years, so did the environmental concerns due to the heavy reliance on petroleum-based polymers and the low recycling rates: only 9% of these non-biodegradable plastics are recycled as 79% end up in landfills.¹ As such, this research focuses on exploring sustainable alternatives for starting materials in photopolymerization-based 3D printing by studying the relationships between structure, processing and material properties. Out of the interesting substitutes available, vegetable oils emerged as a promising alternative for their abundance, their biodegradability and their structural properties. Transforming oils into advanced materials, particularly in developing coatings and printable resins, requires functionalization with acrylate groups to photopolymerize and 3D print functional forms as seen in the figure below.³

Figure 1. Overview of the vat photopolymerization processes and functionalization of vegetable oil.

However, oil-based polymers are on the frailer side, so work to fine-tune their mechanical properties must be done, notably by incorporating other bio sourced monomers to the vegetable oil-based resins. These modifications influence the crosslinking properties and affect the polymer's stiffness, elasticity and thermal properties. The resulting changes are evaluated through different methods such as photo-rheology for the monitoring of viscoelastic properties, dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) for the mechanical behaviour, and complementary thermal techniques. This work aims to establish rational design guidelines for biobased photopolymerizable resins.

[1] OECD, Global Plastics, OECD Publishing, 2022.

[2] Jehanno, C., *et al.* Nature Reviews Materials.,2025, 10, 715-716

[3] Jolly, A., Tanase, A., Durand-Laberge, E., Laventure, A., RCS Applied Polymers Journal, 2026, under revision

Observing thermal history in furan-maleimide Diels-Alder networks through fluorescence

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Dissociative networks comprising reversible Diels-Alder bonds have received increasing attention due to their inherent design for end-of-life recycling [1]. To follow the curing stage of Diels-Alder networks after a given thermal history, we propose the use of a tetraphenylethylene-based luminogen functionalized with two maleimide groups (TPE-M2) and include this in a small amount (< 0.8 wt%) to a network built from an aliphatic bismaleimide and multifunctional furans. The results show that TPE luminogen functionalized with bismaleimide (TPE-M2) leads to clear light-blue fluorescence within Diels-Alder networks as the Diels-Alder conversion progresses, with excellent reversibility. This work provides a first successful concept for the development of reaction conversion tracking within sustainable Diels-Alder networks, which will be valuable in self-healing applications (often requiring local heating) and process development for covalent adaptable networks.

[1] van den Tempel, P.; Picchioni, F.; Bose, R. K. *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* (2022), 2200023.

Network stresses and intracrystalline chain diffusion in semicrystalline polymers

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The mechanical properties of semicrystalline polymers have been extensively studied, showing generally that at larger deformation plastic flow is combined with restructuring of the semicrystalline morphology and strain hardening caused by network forces. However, the influence of the intracrystalline chain diffusion (ICD), which allows chains to move within the crystals, on non-linear mechanics is not well-understood. We studied the non-linear mechanical properties of two model polymers, namely PEO with fast ICD, and PCL without ICD by mechanical testing in plane strain compression in dependence of strain rates and temperature. For both polymers the stress can be decomposed in an elastoplastic contribution and a network contribution. Strong differences in the true stress-true strain curves became evident by comparing the rate dependence at larger deformation, where network stresses dominate. The stress in PEO depends strongly on rate and temperature, indicating network relaxation, while the stress in PCL is rate independent. Experiments for PEO with different molecular weights indicate that the relaxation affects entire chains as expected for ICD.

Green-Deal Graphene Based Flexible Sensor

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The integration of carbon nanomaterials with flexible polymers has received intensive attention as a promising research direction in developing materials with novel properties for advanced applications. Moreover, the progress of flexible materials processing technologies has been remarkable, driven by the growing demand for flexible, ultra-sensitive wearable sensors in applications such as myoelectric prosthetics, soft robotics, and personalized health tracking. We have developed flexible material to be designed for sensing applications by means of thermal and electrical flexible properties. Herein, we report on the fabrication and characterization of flexible porous polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) coated with graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs), explore the mechanisms affecting its various properties under deformation, and propose new applications for it. The results showed lightweight and excellent flexibility characteristics for the obtained GNP-PDMS composite. Measurements of its electrical resistance revealed a change in the electrical resistivity from $2.35 \times 10^6 \Omega/m$ to $194 \Omega/m$ under strain change from 10 to 80% illustrating its ability to shift behavior from an electrical insulator to a relatively low resistivity material and demonstrating the considerable potential for use as a flexible electrical switch.

Figure 1. a) Upward and downward bending movement b) elbow bending test.

- 1) S. Çaylak, O. Demirel, M. Javadzadehkalkhoran, A. Navidfar, M. Yaşacan, and L. Trabzon, "Preparation and characterization of high-performance water-based graphene dispersions for conductive coating on textiles," The Journal of The Textile Institute, pp. 1-9, 2024.

Elucidating the role of solvent viscosity in the dynamics and fracture of soft polymer networks

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The use of conventional gels is limited by their low fracture resistance and their short-term environmental stability. Current strategies to reinforce the fracture resistance of gels often involve laborious synthetic steps to provide the polymer network with energy dissipation mechanisms, for instance, via the inclusion of sacrificial networks or dynamic bonds [1,2]. The solvent has received little attention in this context. Deep Eutectic Solvents (DES) are an emerging class of solvents formed due to an abnormal melting point depression at specific compositions of certain hydrogen bond donors and acceptors. These typically viscous liquids are interesting due to their widely tunable physico-chemical properties, extensive network of hydrogen bonding, and low volatility [3].

Our research has shown that model polymer gels swollen in a DES, called eutectogels, have significantly different linear and nonlinear mechanical properties compared to their hydrogel counterparts. In particular, the fracture energy of the single-network eutectogels is one to two orders of magnitude larger than that of their hydrogel analogs, with the fracture energy of the toughest single-network eutectogels coming close to double-network hydrogels. A novel superposition principle and fracture experiments revealed that the network dynamics and fracture behavior have a strong correlation with the solvent viscosity and the occurrence of specific polymer-solvent interactions. These results are further supported by our molecular dynamics simulations of single polymer chains in DES. This work highlights the role of solvent in tuning the mechanical behavior of soft polymer networks and opens new avenues for designing soft, but dynamic and tough single-network gels.

[1] C. Creton, *Macromolecules* **50** (2017) 8297-8316.

[2] X. Li, J. Ping Gong, *Nature Review Materials*, 9 (2024) 380-398.

[3] B. Hansen, et. al, *Chemical Reviews*, 121 (2021) 1232-1285.

Time-Domain NMR in Rubber Science and Technology

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Proton time-domain NMR experiments performed on low-field spectrometers are feasible and versatile experimental approaches to obtain molecular-level information from the dynamics and structure of rubber compounds with the aim of obtaining a better and more complete understanding of structure-property relationships. This versatile experimental methodology has been applied to provide novel insights in different fundamental fields of rubber science and technology, e.g., rubber dynamics, vulcanization, rubber reinforcement, ageing and recycling.

In this contribution, some fundamental aspects on the relationship of the NMR observable (i.e., dipolar couplings), with the molecular order parameter of macromolecules and its link with polymer dynamics and the structure of polymer networks will be revised. Combination of different time-domain NMR experiments provide the opportunity to obtain a quantitative and complete characterization of the most important factors that determine polymer network structures: dangling chain ends, number of cross-links and their spatial distribution and their effect on the polymer dynamics, observing the suppression of entanglement effects on the segmental dynamics when the molecular weight between cross-links is much shorter than the molecular weight between entanglements [1]. Finally, some new insights in the field of rubber reinforcement will be presented. Two complementary experimental approaches based on tensile test and MQ-NMR experiments were applied for the first time under a unified analysis process [2] to quantify the effect of fillers on the rubber network structure and the molecular parameters that define the reinforcement of filled rubber compounds, including filler-rubber interactions and the stress and strain amplification factors [3].

[1] M. Becher, F. M. Salamanca, J. L. Valentin, K. Saalwächter and E.A. Rössler, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **129** (2025) 1082-1094.

[2] F.M. Salamanca, „ Extending the non-affine tube-model for rubber elasticity: towards a unified physical framework for characterizing rubber compounds “, Ph.D. thesis, Universidad Internacional Menéndez Pelayo (2024).

[3] B. Basterra, „ Correlation of elastomer structures and stress strain amplification mechanisms in reinforced rubber nanocomposites “, Ph.D. thesis, Technische Universität Dresden (2018).

Data-Driven Recognition of Crystalline Order using Machine Learning

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Crystallization in polymer-based materials is a long-standing challenge due to the high dimensionality of molecular conformation spaces. We develop machine learning (ML) methods to study this non-equilibrium thermodynamic process based on molecular dynamics simulation data. Even at the monomer level, the boundary between crystalline and amorphous phases depends strongly on the chosen order parameters. We therefore discuss a purely data-driven approach for distinguishing between ordered and disordered states. In particular, we combine an autoencoder neural network, which compresses local conformation fingerprints, with a Gaussian mixture model for clustering.

The method does not require explicit information on the expected phases or their decision boundaries, yet shows good agreement with human-intuitive order parameters such as average orientation (AO) and stem length (SL). As an example, we use the method to analyze detailed temporal patterns of crystalline order before an apparent signature of the transition is visible in thermodynamic observables.

[1] A. Bhardwaj, J.-U. Sommer, and M. Werner, "Nucleation Patterns of Polymer Crystals Analyzed by Machine Learning Models", *ACS Macromolecules* 57 (2024), 9711-9724.

Impacts of network architecture and composition on liquid crystal elastomer phase transitions

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Liquid crystal elastomers (LCEs) are crosslinked polymer networks that undergo phase transitions between liquid crystalline and isotropic states through incorporation of liquid crystalline mesogens into a flexible polymer backbone. Due to the coupling between nematic order and mechanical strain, LCEs exhibit reversible macroscopic shape change with temperature-induced thermotropic transitions, and can release/absorb heat during strain-induced mechanotropic phase transitions. However, LCEs typically suffer from significant 'smearing' of phase transitions, arising from a combination of stress and network heterogeneities. End-linked crosslinking with a multifunctional crosslinker species results in sharper nematic-to-isotropic (*N-I*) transitions compared to conventional acrylate crosslinking methods. The crosslinker molecules also dilute the mesogen content, leading to a coupling of compositional and topological effects that determine LCE phase behavior. To articulate this interplay, we systematically vary the concentration of the crosslinker molecule in polydomain LCEs and quantify the resulting thermal and rheological properties. We find that the *N-I* transition temperature (T_{NI}) is determined by a competition between mesogenic dilution and the degree of crosslinking. Separately, to further reduce network heterogeneities, we synthesize LCEs from fractionated precursor oligomers with reduced dispersities ($M_w/M_n < 1.4$). The fractionated LCEs exhibit sharper *N-I* transitions compared to unfractionated LCEs ($M_w/M_n \sim 2.1$), especially for short-to-intermediate chain lengths.

Deformation behavior of gel particle in a microgel-reinforced hydrogel

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Microgel-reinforced (MR) hydrogels are tough gels composed of hard/brittle gel particles and a soft/extensible matrix network.[1] The mechanical properties of MR gels are significantly influenced by the deformation and fracture of the gel particles because the hard/brittle gel particles act as a sacrificial network, which fracture preferentially and absorb large mechanical energy. Although the gel particle content is a major factor in controlling the mechanical properties[2], effect of gel particle content on the deformation behavior of the particles remains unclear.

In this study, we clarify the effect of gel particle content on its deformation and fracture behavior. We prepared MR gels with a wide range of gel particle content and evaluated their mechanical properties and gel particle deformation behavior by direct observation using an optical microscope. We demonstrate that increasing the gel particle content enhanced the deformation and fracture efficiency of the gel particles, drastically increasing the mechanical strength.

- [1] J. Hu, K. Hiwatashi, T. Kurokawa, S. M. Liang, Z. L. Wu, and J. P. Gong *Macromolecules* **44**(19) (2011) 7775–7781.
- [2] J. Hu, T. Kurokawa, K. Hiwatashi, T. Nakajima, Z. L. Wu, S. M. Liang, and J. P. Gong, *Macromolecules* **45**(12) (2011) 5218–5228.

Molecular simulations of phase separation in elastic polymer networks

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Phase separation within polymer networks plays a central role in shaping the structure and mechanics of both synthetic materials and living cells. Previous experiments[1] and theoretical studies[2,3] indicate that network elasticity can regulate demixing and stabilize finite-sized domains, yet the microscopic origin of this size selection remains elusive. Here, we use coarse-grained molecular dynamics simulations with an implicit solvent to investigate how network architecture controls phase separation and limits domain growth. By systematically varying the network topology as well as the contour length and bending stiffness of its constituent strands, we uncover that finite domains emerge when intrinsic strand- or network-level length scales, such as persistence length or entanglement length, impose local constraints on coarsening[4]. Further, the size of these finite domains is highly correlated with these microscopic network properties, but depends surprisingly little on the network's bulk elasticity. Taken together, our findings establish a molecular basis for understanding droplet formation in polymer networks, and provide guiding principles for engineering materials and interpreting condensate behavior in cells.

Fig.1 Representative snapshots of phase separation behaviors for (a) unentangled networks with (a) flexible chains, and (b) semi-flexible chains, and (c) entangled networks with flexible chains.

[1] C. Fernández-Rico *et al.*, *Nat. Mater.* 2024, **23**, 124-130.

[2] Y. Qiang *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. X* 2024, **14**, 021009.

[3] O. Paulin *et al.*, *Soft Matter* 2026, **22**, 1098-1108.

[4] T. Yokoyama *et al.*, *arXiv preprint* 2025, arxiv:2511.22300.

In situ study of cavitation and mechanical response in confined soft layers

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Silicone elastomers are widely used in soft robotics, electronics, and microfluidics, where confined geometries can generate large hydrostatic stresses and render the material highly prone to cavitation [1]. However, in conventional poker-chip [2] geometries, cavitation onset is essentially randomly distributed and thus difficult to track experimentally. To overcome these limitations, we have developed a hydrostatic traction platform that confines the elastomeric material between a glass hemisphere and a flat substrate, enabling simultaneous mechanical characterization and in situ optical imaging, allowing for a direct correlation between mechanical response and cavitation dynamics.

With this platform, we systematically investigate cavitation across poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) formulations with Young's modulus ranging from 0.05 to 2.45 MPa and identify a robust thickness-dependent transition in cavitation behavior. As the thickness of the confined PDMS layer increases, cavitation evolves from distributed cavity populations (<200 μm), to multiple discrete cavities (200–500 μm), and finally to a localized single-cavity mode (>500 μm). Numerical simulations of stiffness and energy release rate agree with experiment. Our findings establish a mechanistic framework for cavitation-mediated failure in confined elastomers.

[1] E. Euchler, „Fatigue Crack Growth in Rubber Materials: Experiments and Modelling”, Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020.

[2] A. Kumar, and O. Lopez-Pamies, J. Mech. Phys. Solids, vol. 150, p. 104359, 2021.

3.6 Hydrogels and Ionogels

Ruggedized Colorimetric Hydrogel Platforms for High Temperature-High Pressure Environments

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Monitoring pH in high-temperature, high-pressure (HTHP) condition with high salinity has been a challenging task because conventional glass or metallic electrodes cannot withstand the highly caustic environment, whereas pH influences fluid-rock interactions and corrosion. Here, we report a multifunctional nanocomposite colorimetric pH-sensitive hydrogel that can withstand HTHP environments. By integrating a functionalized pH indicator into the acrylamide-based network, the dye is covalently immobilized to preserve long-term optical performance without being bleached. To mitigate the hydrothermal degradation of polyacrylamide-based hydrogels in HTHP conditions (150°C and 20 kpsi), N-vinyl-pyrrolidone (NVP) and polyethyleneimine (PEI) were employed in copolymerization steps. Variable-time rheology measurement after HTHP treatment indicated that PEI played a role as secondary crosslinker; while 24 h HTHP exposure causes a 7-fold reduction in stiffness $G' \approx 2.9 \text{ kPa}$, the network strengthens overtime (G' recovers to 10 kPa after 72 h at the room temperature). Importantly, the hydrogel was confirmed to retain colorimetric pH response capability after the HTHP treatment. Our multifunctional nanocomposite colorimetric pH-sensitive hydrogel demonstrated its efficacy as a chemical sensor platform technology in extreme HTHP environments. Envisioned application includes environmental monitoring near underwater volcanoes or deep subsurface groundwater adjacent to magma.

Developing effective solar evaporator designs remains a key challenge in achieving high-performance water steam production

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Seawater purification through solar-driven evaporation has gained attention as a sustainable and high-efficiency technique for clean water production. The main challenge is designing an evaporator that simultaneously provides high evaporation efficiency and long-term structural stability [1,2]. This work presents the development of a superabsorbent and thermoresponsive hydrogel composed of N-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAAm) and acrylamide (AAM), modified with poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS) as a photothermal absorber. The material was designed to enhance solar-driven interfacial evaporation for seawater desalination. The synthesized hydrogel exhibited remarkable water uptake and excellent structural stability, enabling continuous water transport to the evaporation interface. Despite the low photothermal loading (1 wt%), high light absorption and thermal conversion efficiency were achieved. By optimizing both the molar composition of

the hydrogel and the solar vapor generator (SVG), a high evaporation rate of 6.23 kg/m²·h was achieved. ICP-MS analysis shows that the hydrogel demonstrated high removal efficiency for both salt ions and heavy metals, around 99% removal [3].

References:

[1] Mingot, J *et al.* The “Pudding Effect” to Promote Solar-Driven Water Purification. **Adv. Funct. Mater.** **2024**, **34** (13), 2311523.

[2] Naranjo, A *et al.* Thermosensitive Hydrogel PNIPAAm–Alg–PEDOT for Sustainable and Efficient Water Purification Powered by Solar Energy. **Adv. Sustain. Syst.** **2024**, **8** (11), 2400234.

[3] Amir, U *et al.* Unveiling the Challenge of Evaporator Design in Clean Water Production Promoted by Superabsorbent Hydrogels and Sunlight. **ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces** **2026**, **18**, 3204–3218.

Acknowledgements: This work has received funding from the Grant PID2024-157005OB-I00 and CEX2023-001300-M by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF “A way of making Europe”, by the European Union. U. A. acknowledges the support of the Joan Oró FI AGAUR fellowship (Grant n° 2024 FI-1 00253) and E. A. the support given by ICREA Acadèmia 2024 award (grant n° 00125) for excellence in Research, funded by the Generalitat de Catalunya.

Recent Advances in Twin-Chain Cryogels for Cultural Heritage Preservation

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Twin-Chain (TC) poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) cryogels are versatile materials that have attracted considerable interest across a wide range of research and technological fields, including biomedicine and cultural heritage conservation. Their sponge-like, interconnected porous structure can be finely tuned by controlling parameters such as the number of freeze–thaw cycles, the freezing temperature, and the incorporation of selected additives.

Thanks to their adjustable micro- and nanoporosity combined with mechanical compliance, TC-PVA cryogels are particularly suitable for applications in cultural heritage preservation, where cleaning treatments must be effective yet sufficiently gentle to avoid surface alteration.[1]

In this contribution, a new library of TC-PVA cryogels functionalized with di- and tri-carboxylic acids is developed and systematically compared with established reference materials.[2,3] Micro- and nanostructural features were investigated by confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) and small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS). In parallel, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) techniques were employed to elucidate diffusion behavior and proton relaxation times, highlighting their key role in the characterization of gelled systems.

The newly developed TC-PVA cryogels were subsequently tested on both model surfaces and original substrates from the Peggy Guggenheim Collection (Venice, Italy) to assess their performance in conservation-oriented cleaning procedures. The results reveal a complex interplay between mechanical properties, structural features at different length scales, and transport phenomena within the gels. Decoupling these parameters proved essential to achieve optimal cleaning efficiency while ensuring surface safety.

Overall, this study provides valuable design guidelines for advanced gel-based materials with enhanced surface performance, with implications extending beyond cultural heritage conservation.

[1] R. Mastrangelo *et al.*, [*Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **117** \(2020\) 7011-7020.](#)

[2] D. Bandelli *et al.*, [*J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **657** \(2024\) 178-192.](#)

[3] R. Mastrangelo *et al.*, [*Adv. Funct. Mat.* **34** \(2024\) 2404287.](#)

Engineering Tough, Injectable, and Self-Healing

Hydrogels Reinforced with Silk Fibroin

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Hydrogels are three-dimensional hydrophilic polymer networks widely explored in biomedical applications due to their high water content, porous structure, and tunable physicochemical properties. Among them, injectable hydrogels have gained significant attention as minimally invasive platforms capable of in situ gelation at target sites. However, conventional injectable hydrogels often suffer from slow gelation kinetics, limited mechanical strength, and potential cytotoxicity associated with reactive precursor components. Injectable self-healing hydrogels have emerged as a promising alternative, as dynamic reversible interactions within their networks enable structural recovery after mechanical damage. Nevertheless, achieving an optimal balance between injectability, self-healing ability, biocompatibility, and mechanical robustness remains a major challenge, particularly for hydrogels based on natural polymers.

In this work, a rational design strategy was employed to develop multifunctional injectable hydrogels based exclusively on biocompatible natural polymers. Dual-crosslinked hydrogel networks were constructed using oxidized sodium alginate (OSA), gelatin, sodium tetraborate (borax), and silk fibroin (SF). The hydrogel structure integrates multiple dynamic interactions, including reversible imine and borate ester bonds together with electrostatic interactions and hydrogen bonding, enabling efficient energy dissipation and enhanced mechanical performance. Silk fibroin was incorporated as a reinforcing component to improve structural stability while maintaining biocompatibility and low immunogenicity [1].

The resulting hydrogels exhibit rapid in situ gelation, injectability, self-healing capability, mechanical toughness, and pH responsiveness. Furthermore, the influence of silk fibroin on the physicochemical and biological properties of the system was systematically investigated. This multifunctional hydrogel platform demonstrates strong potential for minimally invasive biomedical applications, particularly in sustained drug delivery and stimuli-responsive therapeutic systems, offering a versatile approach toward next-generation injectable biomaterials [1].

Probing molecular interactions between polymer and surface through hydrogel friction measurements

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Polymer dynamics near solid surfaces is of great importance for mechanics, adhesion, friction, and interfacial flows, as it sets the boundary conditions and the macroscopic response of polymer systems. However, directly obtaining the physical characteristics of polymer/substrate interaction from macroscopic experiments can be challenging. Indeed, the macroscopic response of interfaces may strongly couple molecular contributions from the interfaces with mechanical response from the bulk.

To isolate polymer/substrate interactions in gels, we develop specific friction experiments in which a spherical silica probe rotates and slides over swollen polymer networks often referred to as gels [1].

In these systems, we demonstrated that measuring the velocity dependence of the friction force enables the determination of both the polymer/substrate interaction energy and the surface density of adsorption sites. The experimental results are analyzed using a theoretical model where energy dissipation at the sliding interface arises from sequences of polymer chain pinning, stretching, and desorption from the gel onto silica [1]. This dissipative mechanism is further explored by tuning the interface's physico-chemistry—modifying silica lenses with various molecules through silanization. We aimed at modulating the grafting density of silanes in order to tune the number of sites for potential hydrogen bonding between polymer and surface.

Additionally, mixtures of silanes are grafted to investigate intermediate frictional regimes.

[1] Ciapa, L. et al., Friction through molecular adsorption at the sliding interface of hydrogels: theory and experiments, *Soft Matter*, 2024, **20**, 5933-5943.

Selective Recovery of Heavy Rare Earth Elements

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This study investigates a simple and environmentally friendly method for separating and recovering heavy rare earth elements using polymer gels containing anions. Heavy rare earths are crucial for manufacturing high performance magnets used in electric vehicles and mobile devices, and the development of sustainable recovery technologies, particularly from waste magnets, has growing importance.

The hydrogels used in this research were synthesized via radical polymerization of a quaternary ammonium-containing monomer. These hydrogels were then immersed in oxalate or carbonate ion solutions, enabling these anions to be loaded onto protonated amino groups within the gel network. For separation, small amounts of the anion-loaded gels were added to mixed $\text{Dy}^{3+}/\text{Tb}^{3+}$ aqueous solutions. The formation of rare-earth salts inside the gels was evaluated by monitoring changes in ion concentration in the surrounding solution.

When initial Dy^{3+} and Tb^{3+} concentrations were equal (0.1 mM each), both ions formed salts inside the gels at similar rates. This indicates that equal concentrations do not yield effective selective separation. To enhance selectivity, experiments varied the initial $\text{Dy}^{3+}/\text{Tb}^{3+}$ ratios (0.3:0.03 mM and vice versa). The results showed that when one ion was initially more concentrated, its salt precipitated more rapidly in the gel, producing a measurable difference in separation coefficients over time. Further experiments using phosphate loaded gels demonstrated even faster separation performance, reaching maximum separation within 20 minutes. This finding suggests that selective Dy/Tb separation is feasible by timing the removal of the gel when the separation coefficients reach their maximum.

Tough ion gel-based CO₂ separation membranes

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Gels containing ionic liquids (ion gels) have great potential as high-performance CO₂ separation membranes. To realize their practical use, it is preferable to form them into thin-film composite (TFC) membranes consisting of a thin ion gel selective layer on a porous support. In this study, we developed an ion gel TFC membrane with high CO₂ separation performance, comprising a thin gel layer containing a highly CO₂-soluble ionic liquid and a porous support membrane. The CO₂ separation layer was composed of an ion gel containing 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tricyanomethanide ([Emim][C(CN)₃]), which exhibits excellent CO₂ solubility and relatively low viscosity. Tetra-PEG was employed to form the gel network.

First, a sacrificial polystyrene layer was coated on a glass plate, followed by the preparation of a thin ion gel layer. A precursor solution composed of tetra-PEGs with thiol and maleimide terminal groups, 2-methylimidazole, and ethanol was spin-coated onto the polystyrene-coated glass plate, where a click reaction between the thiol and maleimide ends was performed at 25 °C for 24 h. After detaching the thin ion gel layer from the glass plate by dissolving the polystyrene layer in toluene, the ion gel layer was transferred to a porous PTFE support membrane. The thickness of the ion gel layer was controlled by adjusting the dilution ratio of the precursor solution. Gas permeation tests revealed that the tetra-PEG ion gel TFC membranes achieved high CO₂ permeance (ca. 1500 GPU) and CO₂/N₂ permselectivity (ca. 35), meeting the performance requirements for CO₂ capture from coal-fired power plant flue gas. It was confirmed that the ion gels containing CO₂-philic ionic liquids are promising materials for high-performance CO₂ separation membranes.

The pH-dependent swelling of ampholyte hydrogels

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Ampholyte hydrogels contain both acidic (negatively charged) and basic (positively charged) groups. The ionization states of both these types of groups are determined by their respective pKa values and can be varied by changing the pH of the solution. The ionization determines the net charge of the gels, which in turn determines their swelling properties.

Our coarse-grained simulations show that the simultaneous presence of acidic and basic groups causes reentrant swelling/de-swelling, as the solution pH is increased. The net charge, given by the difference between the number of ionized acidic and basic groups. It is the primary factor that determines the swelling. However, the spatial distribution of these groups affects not only the swelling response but also the microstructure of partly swollen gels. If the acidic and basic groups are distributed in a block-like fashion, then they form nanodomains, akin to polyelectrolyte complex coacervates, separated by open domains with very low polymer volume fraction. In contrast, if the acidic and basic groups are distributed in an alternating fashion, then the network swells and de-swells homogeneously without any domain formation. These differences in microstructure are not captured by mean-field theories. Yet, they can be the key determinants of the ability of these gels to uptake various low-molecular solutes.

Effect of post-curing and solvent type on swelling and residual dipolar couplings in star-based model homo- and conetworks

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Solution-synthesized amphiphilic polymer co-networks (APCNs) are known to undergo post-crosslinking when dried. This decreases macroscopic swelling degree [1] and the SAXS-detected correlation length [2]. Using disulfide-crosslinked tetra PEG as model end-linked network, proton multiple-quantum (MQ) NMR is used to probe the residual dipolar couplings (D_{res}) of chain segments in networks swollen to $Q = V/V_0 = 5$ in water, toluene, THF, acetonitrile and DMSO, after being subjected to different post-curing conditions and de/re-swelling histories [3].

Post-curing, i.e., the reaction of about 5% previously unreacted ends increases the D_{res} more than twofold. Such effects can be minimized with precursor stoichiometry control and passivation of unreacted arms. Despite different post-curing conditions, PEG chains are found to show a consistent relationship between the solvent-dependent equilibrium degree of swelling and D_{res} , proving the latter to reliably reflect chain conformational statistics and thus the thermodynamic state. Microstructural variation during swelling in different solvents hamper the detailed study of additional influencing factors such as solvent effects on sub-segmental conformational averaging. A possible mechanism of the increase of D_{res} and the decrease of the equilibrium swelling degree due to trapped entanglements formed by post-crosslinked strands is discussed.

[1] C. Bunk et al, *Macromolecules* **55** (2022) 6573-6589.

[2] L. Löser et al, *Macromolecules* **57** (2024) 940-954.

[3] B. Lamsal, L. Löser and K. Saalwächter, *Macromolecular Chemistry and Physics* (2026), accepted.

Stiff and self-healing hydrogels by polymer entanglements in co-planar nanoconfinement

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Biological tissues often exhibit a unique combination of mechanically strong and stiff and self-healing capability, such as human skins with a tensile modulus in the range of tens of MPa, which remains difficult to replicate in synthetic hydrogels. Existing strategies to enhance stiffness typically restrict chain/bond dynamics and thus hinder self-healing.

Here, we report a hydrogel system that achieves both high stiffness and efficient self-healing via polymer entanglements under co-planar nanoconfinement. A highly concentrated monomer solution is polymerized within a scaffold formed by fully exfoliated synthetic hectorite nanosheets, where shear-induced orientation leads to the formation of a macroscopic monodomain.

The resulting hydrogels exhibit a modulus above 50 MPa and tensile strength reaching 4.2 MPa, while maintaining self-healing efficiencies approaching 100%. Furthermore, strong adhesion across various substrates is observed.

This approach provides a general strategy for designing multifunctional hydrogels, enabling their application in additive manufacturing, soft robotics and biomedical systems.^[1]

[1] Liang, C.; Dudko, V.; Khoruzhenko, O.; Hong, X.; Lv, Z.-P.; Tunn, I.; Umer, M.; Timonen, J. V. I.; Linder, M. B.; Breu, J.; Ikkala, O.; Zhang, H. *Nat. Mater.* **24** (2025), 599–606.

Fundamental study on relationship between energy elasticity and internal interactions of ion gels

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The elasticity of gels has long been considered to be dominated by entropy elasticity, with negligible energy elasticity, however, recently it was found that Tetra-PEG hydrogels exhibit negative energy elasticity, which is believed to arise from solvent/network interactions [1]. To clarify the meaning of the energy elasticity experimentally, we prepared Tetra-PEG ion gels containing various ionic liquids (ILs) and determined their energy elasticity. By comparing χ parameters, excess activation enthalpy, and second virial coefficients of PEG/IL systems, we experimentally revealed the relationship between the energy elasticity and solvent/network and network/network interactions.

All ion gels exhibited negative energy elasticity, and its magnitude varied significantly depending on the IL species; the ion gels with hydrophobic ILs showed weak negative energy elasticity, whereas those with hydrophilic ILs showed strong negative values. The relationship between the energy contribution to gel elasticity (G_E/G) and both excess activation enthalpy and the χ parameter revealed that ILs in ion gels with large negative energy contributions interact more strongly with PEG, demonstrating that the energy contribution reflects IL/network interactions. Furthermore, the energy contribution decreased with increasing second virial coefficient, indicating stronger network/network interaction. On the other hand, uniaxial tensile stress-strain curves indicated that ion gels with smaller negative energy contributions exhibited higher fracture energy. These results suggest that the energy contribution to gel elasticity is related to solvent/network and network/network interactions, as well as the mechanical strength of the gels.

[1] Yoshikawa, Y. *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. X.*, **11**, 011045, (2021).

Targeted Mechanical Training of Hydrogels via Sonoprinting-Induced In Situ IPN Formation

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Recently, mechanical training systems for self-growing and self-strengthening have been established by utilizing mechanoradicals generated by mechanophore cleavage.[1–3] These studies demonstrate the exceptional utility of mechanochemistry in material science, revealing that existing materials can dynamically strengthen and exceed their initial limits of mechanical properties. However, conventional systems require large external deformation to generate a sufficient concentration of radicals. Furthermore, it remains challenging to selectively reinforce a specific, targeted region within the material.

To address these limitations, we propose "sonoprinting" as a novel method that enables on-demand strengthening of targeted regions without requiring large deformation of the bulk material. By applying ultrasound to a single network gel with monomer and crosslinker, we successfully achieved rapid formation of a sequential interpenetrating polymer network (IPN) by sono-induced radicals. This method enables "targeted mechanical training" at the meso-scale by changing the ultrasonic probe size and irradiation path. In this presentation, we will report on the formed IPN structure and the effect of ultrasonic irradiation conditions on the mechanical properties of the hydrogels.

[1] T. Matsuda *et al. Science*, **363**, 504–508 (2019).

[2] Z. J. Wang *et al. Nature Materials*, **24**, 607–614 (2025).

[3] J. Jiang *et al. Chemical Science*, **16**, 14278–14285 (2025).

Dynamic Porosity Tuning in Multilayered Polymer-Grafted Silica Networks for Adaptive Filtration

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Precise, reversible control over fluid transport and selectivity in porous media remains a key challenge for energy-efficient water purification and contaminant removal. We present a novel, unanchored colloidal gel composed of multilayered poly(acrylic acid)-grafted silica microparticles that functions as a reversible, non-invasive "colloidal gate" [1]. Iterative carbodiimide-mediated grafting yields up to five stratified PAA layers on micron-scale silica cores, enhancing polymer density and interfacial interactions. Under basic conditions, PAA-driven swelling expands the interconnected particulate network, increasing permeability and enabling tunable flow rates at high pH. At low pH, the polymer network collapses, forming a nearly non-porous barrier with complete occlusion [2].

In situ, noninvasive measurements under realistic flow conditions, combined with quantitative analysis using Darcy's law and the Kozeny-Carman equation, reveal that permeability scales directly with porosity and surface chemistry. This dynamic behavior arises from reversible PAA self-assembly and conformational changes, offering structural control without permanent substrate modification or invasive grafting. The system demonstrates excellent responsiveness and has the potential to filter suspended particles, short-chain PFAS, and nanoplastics. We discuss implications for low-energy adaptive water treatment and future extensions to stimuli-responsive polymer networks.

[1] M. Khaskia, D. Shpasser, R. Cohen, O. Yehezkeli, O. Manor, O. M. Gazit, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 14 (28) (2022) 32657–32664.

[2] G. Onuh, R. Bitton, O. M. Gazit, O. Manor, *Langmuir* 41 (38) (2025) 26202–26212.

Tannic Acid based Adhesive Hydrogel Electrolyte for Flexible Supercapacitor Applications

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Adhesion is an important parameter considering the integrity of flexible electronic devices. For layer-by-layer designed approaches, interfacial adhesion determines the overall performance of the device under complex deformations (compression, bending) which is common in case of wearable applications. Achieving simultaneous adhesion and cohesion (gelation) for catechol-based hydrogel is quite difficult. The conditions required for strong adhesion and sufficient cohesion conflict with each other. For cohesive force to initiate gelation, weak basic atmosphere is desired whereas for adhesion, acidic environment is primary. Here we try to demonstrate that by using an anionic copolymer matrix along with polyphenol supramolecular chemistry, coexistence of strong cohesion and adhesion is attainable utilizing one pot synthesis method. A tannic acid (TA) incorporated system was studied using different concentration of metal-organic framework (MOF) dispersion. MOF enhances proton conduction by providing imidazolate-based proton hopping sites, nano-confined H-bond networks, and polymer-MOF interfacial conductive pathways, collectively lowering the activation energy for proton transport. TA brings high concentration of pyrogallol functionality in the close vicinity of the polymer chains via noncovalent pathway as well as increase the acidity of the matrix significantly. High acidic environment prevents the pyrogallol units from oxidation, showcasing strong adhesion on diverse substrates, including skin, metal (shear stress~ 160 kPa), wood, rubber and plastics. The adhesion property and mechanical strength are tuned balancing the TA content and MOF ratio. In addition, the hydrogel exhibited rapid self-healing ability (> 80 % compressive stress recovery) and high ionic conductivity (43 mS cm⁻¹). This study describes utilization of catechol chemistry and MOF nano filler in construction of adhesive, self-healable hydrogel electrolytes for 60% compression stable (up to 1000 charging-discharging cycles) supercapacitor applications.

From Molecular Interactions to Nanocarrier Transport: Controlling Small Molecule Release from Glycosaminoglycan (GAG) - Based Hydrogels

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Sustained small molecule delivery from hydrogels remains challenging, as traditional matrices often trigger immune responses and act as passive sieves causing rapid burst release [1]. While ECM mimicking hydrogels ensure excellent tissue integration, controlling solute transport requires precise physicochemical tuning. This work systematically explores release strategies in ECM mimicking GAG-based hydrogels through matrix functionalization, incorporating heparin or synthetic GAGs as affinity anchors for direct molecule retention, and tuning network properties to sterically govern nanoparticle mediated transport, with functional validation in inflammatory cell models.

Methylene blue or nanoparticle embedded PEG-PEG, PEG-Heparin, and PEG-synthetic GAG hydrogels were prepared by Michael-type addition [2]. Functional activity of methotrexate-loaded phytoglycogen released from hydrogels was evaluated in macrophages and activated T cells.

In pure PEG gels, methylene blue exhibited rapid, stiffness independent burst release. Incorporating heparin attenuated this initial burst via electrostatic interactions, enabling short-term sustained delivery over 24 hours. A synthetic GAG with hydrophobic domains prolonged release to a week through combined electrostatic and π - π interactions. In PEG-Heparin gels, nanoparticle incorporation decoupled release from molecular interactions, revealing carrier-specific transport mechanisms. Hydrophilic phytoglycogen release was governed by network mesh size, extending delivery to approximately one week and tunable via gel stiffness and the presence of matrix-degrading enzymes. Released methotrexate-loaded phytoglycogen reduced IL-6 release from macrophages and suppressed activated T-cell proliferation, confirming retained therapeutic functionality. In contrast, hydrophobic disc-shaped solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) achieved concentration-independent, near zero-order release over two weeks, and the release was effectively restricted by increasing gel stiffness. Overall, this work demonstrates that GAG-based hydrogels can be engineered for sustained and zero order small molecule delivery through matrix functionalization and carrier choice.

[1] N.A. Peppas, P. Bures, W. Leobandung, and H. Ichikawa, *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 50 (2000) 27–46.

[2] M.V. Tsurkan, M. Chwalek, M. Prokoph, M. Zieris, K.R. Levental, A.R. Freudenberg, and C. Werner, *Adv. Mater.* 25 (2013) 2606–2610.

Photo-triggered but radical-free gelation for multi-scale anisotropy bioprinting

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Anisogels [1] are microgel-in-hydrogel composite materials where the microgels serve as anisotropic guides for the alignment of encapsulated cells [2] to later replicate the anisotropy of tissues. Stiff and magneto-responsive rod-shaped microgels can be aligned in the surrounding polymer solution before gelation. Here, our aim was to reproduce the multi-scale anisotropy of native cartilage for improved regeneration as cartilage defects are one of the leading causes of disability worldwide [3]. We bio-printed constructs with successive orientations of the anisogels, respectively vertical, random and horizontal (Figure 1). To limit potential toxicity of the ink, we developed a straightforward strategy for a light-triggered but radical-free gelation. Avoiding free-radical polymerization gives a high degree of control over the hydrogel properties, and in our case allows to start and stop the gelation at will, without affecting the final hydrogel. We prevented cell-sedimentation in the syringe, which is usually an important bottleneck for the 3D-printing of hydrogels, simply by pre-irradiating the ink. This allows to partially react the polymers increasing the apparent viscosity, and further limiting the light-exposure on the cells. It also enhanced the interlayer chemical adhesion. This novel gelation chemistry is highly biocompatible such that mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) were printed and after a few days of culture they stretched along each microgel orientation, replicating the organization of cells in native cartilage.

[1] D.L. Braunmiller, ..., J.J. Crassous, [Adv. Funct. Mater. **32** \(2022\) 2202430.](#)

[2] J. Kamp, ..., L. De Laporte, [Adv. Healthcare Mater. \(2026\) accepted.](#)

[3] World Health Organization, Fact Sheets on Musculoskeletal Conditions

Beyond Shear: Disentangling Shear and Elongational Stress Effects on Cell Viability in Extrusion-Based Bioprinting

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Extrusion-based bioprinting exposes encapsulated cells to complex mechanical loading that extends well beyond simple shear. While shear stress during nozzle flow has been extensively studied, the contribution of elongational stress, arising from the converging flow at the nozzle entrance and outlet, remains largely overlooked. In this work, we systematically decouple shear and elongational contributions by independently varying five process and material parameters in a full 2^5 factorial design: xanthan hydrogel concentration (3 and 5 % (w/v)), nozzle inner diameter (0.15 and 0.20 mm), nozzle length (0.5 and 1.5 inch), feed rate (0.5 and 1.0 mm/min), and recovery time post-printing (d0 to d4).

Fibroblast viability was quantified using a PrestoBlue metabolic activity assay. A stepwise multilinear regression model incorporating linear, quadratic, and pairwise interaction terms was fitted to the experimental data, yielding an adjusted R^2 of 0.87 with 16 statistically significant terms ($p < 0.05$). The analysis reveals that recovery time is the single strongest predictor of cell viability, followed by nozzle geometry parameters that govern the balance between shear and elongational deformation. Notably, conditions associated with elevated elongational stress consistently reduce viability, whereas moderate shear stress appears to stimulate metabolic activity. This finding challenges the prevailing assumption that all process-induced mechanical stress is harmful.

Based on the fitted model, we compute the gradient vector in the five-dimensional parameter space, indicating the direction of steepest increase in cell viability. Following this gradient provides a rational, data-driven strategy for stepwise evolutionary optimization of bioprinting parameters without exhaustive experimental screening, enabling targeted next experiments from a minimal initial dataset of 32 parameter combinations.

Novel opportunities to control bio-printing

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Novel set-ups will be presented to control and investigate effects occurring in bio-printing. Therefore, the RevoBITs Byte1 bioprinter (available soon) is equipped with various optical systems.

With the innovative ASTRID (**A**dvanced **S**trut **I**nvestigation **D**evice) [1] system the lateral spreading of bio inks can be studied revealing valuable information on viscosity and surface tension. Utilizing additional ELSA (**E**asy **L**inear **S**trut **A**nalysis) [2] a throughput control becomes possible just by analysing how a transparent strut changes the optical image of a pattern, where the strut acts as a cylindrical lens. BERIT (**B**est **E**longation **R**heology **I**nvestigative **T**esting) [3] provides data on elongation viscosity, relevant for cell survival. Examples and fundamental physics [4] behind will be shown.

RevoBITs Byte 1

Scheme ASTRID and ELSA

BERIT scheme

References:

[1] D. W. Schubert, Z. Lamberger, G. Lang, S. Schrüfer, J. Groll, Patent DE102023206928.8

[2] D. W. Schubert, Patent DE 20 2024 101 539

[3] D. W. Schubert, P. Dalton, S. Schrüfer, Patent DE 10 2020 216 545.9

[4] D. W. Schubert, Simple Model for the Spreading of Inks in Bioprinting-Revealing Relevant Scaling Laws-Part I Theory, *Macromolecular Theory and Simulations*, **2022**, 31(1).

Acyl Substituents Control Hierarchical Assembly and Mechanics in Gellan Gum Hydrogels

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Gellan gum is a linear anionic polysaccharide widely employed as a model hydrogel-forming polymer and as a functional biomaterial. Depending on the acylation degree, it exists in two main forms: high-acyl (HA-Gg) and low-acyl (LA-Gg), which produce networks with different mechanical properties. Despite extensive macroscopic characterization, the molecular mechanisms by which acyl substituents regulate gelation remain poorly understood. Here we combine experiments and molecular dynamics simulations (MD) to elucidate how acyl substituents control the hierarchical assembly of gellan gum. This work builds upon previous studies that identified the two-step aggregation mechanism of LA-Gg helices and the rheological signatures of gellan-based networks, which revealed the central role of calcium-mediated inter-helix association in determining gel rigidity.^{1,2} Circular dichroism measurements show that, in dilute aqueous solution, HA-Gg exhibits a pronounced tendency to form stable double helices even below the gelation threshold, whereas LA-Gg remains predominantly in a coil conformation. The addition of Ca²⁺ ions has only a minor influence on this behavior at low concentrations, indicating that acyl substituents intrinsically stabilize the helical state. In the gel phase, the two systems display markedly different network mechanics. LA-Gg forms rigid ionically crosslinked hydrogels characterized by a distinctive two-step yielding process, associated with sequential rupture of Ca²⁺ mediated inter-helix crosslinks followed by disruption of the double-helical domains.^{1,2} In contrast, HA-Gg forms softer and more elastic networks with a wide linear viscoelastic regime and without cooperative yielding. All-atom MD provide a microscopic interpretation of these observations. Glyceryl substituents reinforce intra-helix hydrogen bonding, stabilizing the double-helix structure, whereas acetyl and glyceryl groups introduce steric hindrance that limits calcium coordination and suppresses inter-helix ionic bridging. Consequently, acylation strengthens the individual structural units while weakening supramolecular connectivity within the network. Overall, these results demonstrate that acyl substituents exert a dual hierarchical control over gellan gelation, balancing intra-helix stabilization and inter-helix crosslinking. This multiscale understanding provides a framework for rationally tuning the architecture and mechanics of polysaccharide-based networks for advanced hydrogel applications.

[1] S. Franco et al., Carbohydr. Polym. 354 (2025) 123329.

[2] L. Tavagnacco et al., Sci. Adv. 9, eadg4392 (2023).

Multiscale structure and dynamics in electro- and magnetoactive polymer / ionic liquid ionogels

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Stimuli-responsive “smart” polymeric materials are often engineered through the incorporation of nanoparticle fillers; however, ionic liquids (ILs) offer a promising nanoparticle-free alternative. Electroactive composites based on ILs and piezoelectric poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-trifluoroethylene) (PVDF-TrFE) polymer show strong potential for sensors and actuators. However, the structural organization and dynamics of ILs under confinement in polymer matrices remain poorly understood. We conduct a comprehensive investigation of the structure and dynamics of PVDF-TrFE/IL electroactive composites. By combining small-angle neutron scattering (SANS) with advanced cryogenic electron microscopy and tomography, we resolve IL organization across nano- and microscales. The IL is primarily confined to amorphous regions of the polymer matrix, forming ~10 nm nanostructures, as revealed by SANS and visualized by cryo-HAADF-STEM/EDX. The IL does not penetrate the crystalline lamellae, preserving polymer crystallinity and the electroactive β -phase. Enhanced ionic conductivity is governed by saturation of the amorphous phase. Beyond this limit, excess IL undergoes microphase separation into micron-sized pores, as confirmed by cryo-SEM/FIB/tomography. The dynamics of ILs in the composites are slowed relative to the bulk. This is evidenced by quasielastic neutron scattering (picosecond range), neutron spin echo (nanosecond range), and broadband dielectric spectroscopy (micro- to millisecond range). This effect arises from confinement effects and IL-polymer interactions. These findings establish direct correlations between nano-/microstructure and macroscopic properties, providing clear design principles for high-performance polymer/IL composites in sensors, actuators, and energy applications.

[1] A.V. Shibaev, et al. Resolving complex multiscale structure of magneto- and electroactive polymer composites with an ionic liquid, *Advanced Materials* (2026), accepted, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202516835>

Thermally driven non-equilibrium fates in hydrogels

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Phase separation in soft materials is typically driven by thermodynamic instability. In elastic polymer networks, however, this process can be significantly altered by elastic energy, leading to a competition between thermodynamic driving forces and elastic resistance. We study the thermal response of crowded poly(acrylic acid)-Ca²⁺ hydrogels, where heating strengthens entropy-driven ionic associations and induces dehydration. Rapid heating generates a transient supersaturated state in which trapped water produces internal osmotic pressure that drives phase separation against network elasticity. The unusually high instability threshold compared with predictions from the classical cavitation model suggests that highly stretched polymer strands in polymer-poor domains provide additional elastic resistance.

As the water content changes, polymer-chain vitrification can intervene and arrest the evolution of the system. Consequently, different heating pathways lead to distinct fates. Under slow quasi-isobaric heating, the gel contracts homogeneously until vitrification arrests the structure. In contrast, rapid quasi-isochoric heating produces a phase-separated morphology that is subsequently frozen by vitrification. This mechanism suggests new strategies for programming responsive soft materials by tuning thermal pathways and elastic constraints.

STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CATECHOL-MODIFIED HYDROGELS

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Hyaluronic acid (HA) hydrogels were examined by regulating the gelation kinetics of Fe^{3+} and a catechol cross-linker, including Fe^{3+} -induced covalent bonding and coordination bonds. Dual roles of Fe^{3+} in catechol-modified HA (HA-CA), Fe^{3+} -catechol coordination, and catechol oxidation followed by a coupling reaction, were selectively applied for different gelations. Tetra-poly(ethylene glycol) with catechol end groups (t-PEG-CA) was also crosslinked through coordination bonds between catechol moieties and Fe(III) ions, which produce bis-complex and tris-complex depending on pH levels. This study investigated the property-structure relationship of crystalline polymer gels formed by coordination bonds, focusing on Fe(III)-catechol crosslinked tetra-arm polyethylene glycol (4-PCA) hydrogels. Thermo-rheological properties of gels were examined within the crystallization temperature range by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and rheometer. As the hydrogel was formed by bis coordination bonds at pH 8, the crystallization temperature was significantly lowered, which aligns with our hypothesis. At temperatures below 20°C and lower frequencies, the loss modulus (G'') of 4-PCA gels crossovers with the storage modulus (G'), indicating the gel point, but not above 30°C. The study demonstrates that at low temperatures, gels are formed through coordination bonds, resulting in a highly organized lamellar structure with relatively large periodic spacing between the layers. It indicates that the gel's unique structural properties are temperature-dependent and closely linked to the specific interactions occurring during gelation.

Acknowledgements: *Natioanal Research Foundation of Korea (NRF 2022R1A2C1010580 and 2020R1A6A1A06046728, 2022R1A6C101A779)*

1. Ryu J., Sokjlova A.V., Kang M. *et al.*, Polymer 348(19):129700, 2026.
2. Ryu J., Kim S., Oh I. *et al.*, Macromolecules 52:6502-6513, 2019.

Thermoresponsive double network hydrogels based on poly(2-ethyl-2-oxazoline) and poly(*N*-isopropylacrylamide)

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Soft actuators have gained significant attention in recent years, as they enable the development of flexible and adaptive systems essential for fields such as manufacturing, surgery, and human-machine interaction. Thermoresponsive hydrogels, based on single polymer networks, have been explored for actuation. Current approaches frequently exhibit low stiffness limiting their application capabilities. Double network hydrogels (DNH) are one of the examples of hydrogels with superior stiffness. Most of the thermoresponsive DNHs studied in the literature consist of two acrylates. In this study we present the DNH composed of poly(2-ethyl-2-oxazoline) (PEtOx) and poly(*N*-isopropylacrylamide) (PNiPAAm).

Despite a high water content of 80 wt% in the DNH and a PNiPAAm fraction of 79% relative to the dry weight, the swollen DNHs exhibit excellent mechanical properties, characterized by Young's moduli of 0.90 ± 0.01 MPa at a strain of 71.0 ± 10.3 %. Investigations into the thermoresponsivity of the DNHs reveal that hydrogen bonding between PEtOx and PNiPAAm exerts a significant influence on the mechanical properties.

[1] P. A. Benitez-Duif, M. Breisch, D. Kurka, K. Edel, S. Gökçay, D. Stangier, W. Tillmann, M. Hijazi, and J. C. Tiller, [*Advanced Functional Materials* 32 \(2022\) 2204837](#).

[2] P. A. Benitez-Duif, S. Weckes, Ricardo M. Pinto Ferreira, Daniel Kurka and J. C. Tiller, [*Polymer* 319 \(2025\) 128014](#).

Green hydrogels as bioelectronic interfaces

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The rapid advancement of wearable sensors has transformed real-time health monitoring. Green bioelectronic interface designs as epidermal electronics using natural materials have become attractive due to their superior advantages over conventional ones. In this study, naturally occurring mucilage-based hydrogels were developed. Quince seed mucilage (QSM) and linseed mucilage (LSM) hydrogels were mechanically reinforced by adding agar, a marine-derived gelling agent, through natural crosslinking. PEDOT:PSS, a conductive and biocompatible polymer, was incorporated to enhance electrical conductivity. QSM1A2 hydrogel films immersed in PBS solution showed swelling of $141.71 \pm 5.58\%$ and 168.76 ± 17.44 g/m²/day WVTR. After 5 minutes of placing the hydrogel patch on the skin, a ~ 6 °C lower temperature was captured. These mucilage-based green, biodegradable films can mimic skin successfully.

Figure 1. QSM-based natural hydrogel patches.

[1] M. Eyvazi Hesar, D. Khan, N.S. Seyedsadrkhani, S. Ingebrandt, Contactless, Battery-free, and Stretchable Wearable for Continuous Recording of Seismocardiograms, ACS Appl Electron Mater 3 (2021) 11–20. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaelm.0c00768>.

[2] S. Li, Y. Duan, W. Zhu, S. Cheng, W. Hu, Sensing Interfaces Engineering for Organic Thin Film Transistors-Based Biosensors: Opportunities and Challenges, Advanced Materials 36 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202412379>.

Multiscale Modeling of Functional Polymer Networks for Solar-Driven Interfacial Evaporation

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Recent advances in polymer network modeling and functional hydrogel design provide powerful tools for engineering next-generation materials for solar-driven desalination (SDD) [1]. This presentation integrates insights from recent computational developments in cross-linked polymer architectures [2], experimental studies on conductive and thermoresponsive hydrogel systems [3], and emerging perspectives on structure–property relationships in advanced polymer materials [4]. Together, these works highlight how network topology, cross-link density, and functional inclusions govern mechanical stability, thermal transport, and responsiveness under external stimuli. Building on these foundations, we propose a multiscale modeling perspective for hydrogel-based solar-driven interfacial evaporation, emphasizing the coupling between polymer architecture and photothermal energy conversion. In particular, hybrid agarose-carbon quantum dot (Aga-CQD) hydrogels are discussed as a promising platform that leverages biopolymer network tunability with efficient light-to-heat conversion. This integrated modeling approach aims to bridge molecular-scale network descriptors with macroscopic evaporation performance, offering a rational pathway for the development of sustainable and scalable SDD materials.

References: [1] Naranjo et al. *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **2025**, 316, 109767; [2] Naranjo et al. *Chem. Mater.* **2024**, 36, 9, 4688-4702; [3] Naranjo et al. *Mat. Today Phys.* **2026**, 60, 101998; [4] Naranjo et al. *Adv. Sustainable Syst.* **2024**, 8(11) 2400234

Acknowledgements: This work has received funding from the Grant PID2024-157005OB-I00 and María de Maeztu Excellence Centre (CEX2023-001300-M) by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF "A way of making Europe", by the European Union.

PHOTOPOLYMERIZED GEL POLYMER ELECTROLYTES WITH INTEGRATED FLAME RETARDANCY FOR SAFER LITHIUM-ION BATTERIES

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The global energy transition has intensified the demand for safe energy storage systems. Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are widely used in electronic, medical, industrial, and electric vehicle applications [1] due to their high energy density, long cycle life, and low self-discharge rates [2]. However, the use of liquid electrolytes (LEs) in conventional LIBs raises safety concerns, including fire, explosion, and dendrite formation, while also complicating recycling processes. Solid-state batteries have therefore emerged as a viable alternative to address these challenges [3]. Among solid electrolytes, polymer electrolytes offer advantages such as enhanced safety, low weight, and good mechanical properties.

In this work, gel polymer electrolytes (GPEs) based on poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate (PEGDA) were developed to improve the safety and recyclability of LIBs. These GPEs incorporate 0–60 wt% of a commercial LE (1 M LiPF₆ in a 50/50 v/v mixture of ethylene carbonate (EC) and diethyl carbonate (DEC)) and were synthesized via a one-step photopolymerization process under UV irradiation at room temperature. Successful immobilization of the LE within the polymer matrix was confirmed by FTIR and EDS analyses. Thermal analysis (TGA and DSC) revealed that the GPEs exhibit good thermal stability across a wide temperature range from –40 °C to 90 °C. Dielectric measurements as a function of temperature (20–100 °C, 0.1 Hz to 10⁶ Hz) demonstrated that ionic conductivity increases with LE content. Notably, the formulation with 60 wt% LE achieved an ionic conductivity of approximately $2.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ at 30 °C, consistent with literature values [3].

In parallel, the incorporation of flame retardants (FRs) into the GPEs was investigated to further enhance battery safety. Results showed that FRs were successfully integrated without inducing phase separation or adversely affecting the mechanical, thermal, or electrochemical properties of the samples. Combustion tests demonstrated improved fire behavior, including reduced dripping, suppression of secondary ignition, and the formation of protective char residues.

Overall, this work provides valuable insights into the design of GPEs that combine good ionic conductivity, mechanical integrity, and enhanced fire safety, positioning them as promising candidates for the development of safer and more reliable LIBs.

[1] F. Arshad, L. Li, K. Amin, E. Fan, N. Manurkar, A. Ahmad, J. Yang, F. Wu and R. Chen, *ACS Sustain Chem Eng.* **8** (2020) 13527–13554.

[2] M. S. Grewal, K. Kisu, S. ichi Orimo and H. Yabu, *iScience* **25** (2022) 104910.

[3] B.A. Maia, N. Magalhães, E. Cunha, M.H. Braga, R.M. Santos, N. Correia, *Polymers* **14** (2022) 403.

Ionic Hydrogel and Ionogel Networks as Transparent Electrodes for Soft Electroluminescent Devices

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Ionically conductive soft networks offer a compelling alternative to metallic transparent electrodes, where conductivity, optical transmittance, and mechanical deformability can be independently tuned through network architecture. A double-network polymer framework swollen with an imidazolium-based ionic liquid yields ionogels combining mechanical toughness with high ionic conductivity and solvent-free stability [1]. Replacing the ionic liquid with an aqueous LiTFSI solution within an analogous poly(acrylamide)-based double-network hydrogel shifts the property space toward extreme stretchability beyond 1400% and optical transmittance exceeding 98%, while electroluminescent output is maintained under large deformation [2]. The transparency of these hydrogel electrodes has been further exploited in bifacial electroluminescent devices with quantum-dot color conversion [3]. Direct-ink-writing of photocurable ionic inks translates these network designs into 3D-printed devices with spatially defined multicolor emission patterns, where rheological optimization of the ink precursor allows co-printing of emissive and ionic electrode layers without lithographic patterning [4].

- [1] H. D. Xuan et al., *Adv. Mater.* **33** (2021) 2008849.
 [2] Y. Go et al., *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **33** (2023) 2215193.
 [3] Y. Zhu et al., *Small* **20** (2024) 2400704.
 [4] J. Park et al., *Small* **21** (2025) 2502435.

3.7 Microgels & Soft Colloids

Understanding microgel deswelling kinetics using mesoscale modeling

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We employ mesoscale computational modeling based on dissipative particle dynamics (DPD) to investigate the deswelling kinetics of spherical microgels in a poor solvent. The microgels are represented using a bead-spring model of randomly connected, fully flexible polymer chains. Initially, the microgel is placed in a good solvent, where it swells and reaches equilibrium. The solvent is then replaced with a poor solvent, triggering collapse of the polymer network.

Microgel in swollen and collapsed states.

Using our computational framework, we examine the kinetics of microgel deswelling and the associated evolution of microgel pore structure. Our results reveal that microgel collapse proceeds through three distinct stages. In the first stage, polymer chains bundle locally, leading to a transient increase in the mean network pore size. This is followed by a gradual decrease in pore size accompanied by overall microgel contraction. In the final stage, a dense, solid-like shell forms at the outer microgel surface, arresting transport and dramatically slowing further microgel contraction. We further demonstrate how these processes and their characteristic time scales depend on microgel porosity.

Our results provide mechanistic insights into microgel collapse dynamics and reveal how network porosity governs deswelling kinetics. The results are useful for characterizing transient microgel behavior and informs design of stimuli-responsive materials for applications in drug delivery, sensing, and actuation.

Support from the US Department of Energy (DE-SC0024149) is gratefully acknowledged.

Chitosan-based hydrogels and microgels with controlled microstructure

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Over the last two decades, bio-based soft colloids have received a lot of attention, especially polysaccharide-based microgels [1]. However, controlling their microstructure at different scales to evaluate systematically their rheological properties remains virtually unexplored. challenging. Nevertheless, their different architectures offer many bio-based alternatives to tailor the flow properties of the complex fluid [2]. In case of microgel, a free-defect structure, so-called “model”, means a homogenous crosslink density, without “loop” and free dangling chains, and a narrow distribution in size.

In this work, we aim to synthesize controlled chitosan-based soft colloids to investigate extensively their structure and their rheological properties in aqueous suspension. To do so, chitosan was chosen due to its versatility for chemical modification and as a semi-rigid biopolymer (persistence length from 8 nm [3]) which may provide a unique semi-rigid microgel. Firstly, a strategy based on thiol-ene crosslinking chemistry [4] was optimized at macroscale to evaluate rheological properties of chitosan-based hydrogels prepared at different concentration. Then, the optimal synthesis conditions have been transferred at microscale in a water-in-oil emulsion, to produce chitosan-based microgels. Finally, their physical-chemical properties will be studied in water using rheology, scattering techniques and microscopy.

[1] D. J. McClements, *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* (2017) vol. 240, pp. 31–59, DOI: 10.1016/j.cis.2016.12.005.

[2] D. Vlassopoulos and M. Cloitre, *Current Opinion in Colloid and Interface Science* (2014) vol. 19, pp. 561–574, DOI: 10.1016/j.cocis.2014.09.007.

[3] Y. Kang et al., *Carbohydrate Polymers* (2021) vol. 271, pp. 118402, DOI: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2021.118402.

[4] N. Roas-Escalona, F. Becquart, T. Delair, and F. Dutertre, *Carbohydrate Polymers* (2024) vol. 341, pp. 122329, DOI: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2024.122329.

The structure of core-shell microgels: A light, X-ray and neutron scattering study

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Hybrid colloids that combine polymers and plasmonic nanoparticles, e.g. gold or silver, gained increasing interest over the last years.[1] Gold-poly-*N*-isopropylacrylamide (Au-PNIPAM) core-shell microgels were used for periodic coatings due to the localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) of the cores leading to surface lattice resonance, which position strongly depends on the core size (SLR).[2] Compared to other core-shell microgels, Au cores can be precisely overgrown in the shell *in situ*. [2] Although cores grow in size, the overall hydrodynamic diameter of the microgels does not change. It is not known how the structure of the shell changes during the overgrowth.

Here, we are analyzing Au-PNIPAM microgels with two crosslinker densities (8 mol% and 16.5 mol%). The cores are overgrown from 14 nm in diameter to nearly 100 nm. We perform different scattering methods, namely dynamic light scattering (DLS) and small-angle X-ray and neutron scattering (SAXS/SANS) to study the respective form factors. SAXS provides information about the gold cores, LS about the shell and the cores in dependence of core size and SANS about the shell. We also investigate the changes in the microgel at different temperatures, below, at and above the volume phase transition temperature (VPTT) of the PNIPAM shell. Thus, we can compare swollen and collapsed state of each microgel batch. We also perform reverse Monte Carlo and coarse-grained molecular dynamics simulations of the different microgels. The simulations provide insights into the internal structure of the shell and the polymer distribution before and after the overgrowth of the core.

[1] M. Karg, T. Hellweg, *J. Mater. Chem.* **19** (2009) 8714-8727

[2] E. Ponomareva, K. Volk, P. Mulvaney, M. Karg, *Langmuir* **36** **45** (2020) 13601-13612

Electroactive microgels anchored on a gold electrode surface for electrochemically controlled release

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Microgels are three-dimensional spherical structures with sizes comparable to colloidal particles, composed of crosslinked polymer networks with absorbed solvent. Some microgels are classified as “smart” materials due to their ability to undergo significant changes in volume in response to external stimuli. Among the most extensively studied are those responsive to temperature and pH. However, in recent years, increasing attention has been devoted to electroactive and electroresponsive hydrogels [1,2].

In this study, a poly(acrylic acid)-based microgel was synthesized. The obtained material contains sulfur bridges within the crosslinker structure, which enabled its application for modifying a gold electrode surface via chemisorption. The presence of ionized carboxyl groups was utilized to incorporate a positively charged active substance into the polymer network through electrostatic interactions. Tetrathiafulvalene is incorporated as well into the polymer network - upon application of an appropriate potential, oxidation of the tetrathiafulvalene resulted in the generation of positive charge within the polymer matrix. The appearance of competitive electrostatic interactions subsequently triggered the release of the model molecules into the surrounding environment. The developed system demonstrates potential for application in electrochemically controlled drug release, particularly in drug-eluting implant technologies.

[1] Y. Okuno, and Y. Iwasaki, [Langmuir 41 \(2025\) 7946–7964](#).

[2] P.Gwardys, K. Marcisz, D. Jaglenc, J. Romanski, and M. Karbarz, [ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces 17 \(2025\) 36469–36477](#).

Electrochemically Controlled Microgel Assemblies and Redox-Triggered Release via Host–Guest Interactions

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Incorporating ferrocene units and β -cyclodextrins into a gel matrix endows the material with multifunctional, tunable properties arising from reversible inclusion complexes between Fc and the macrocyclic hosts and from the ability to control those complexes chemically or electrochemically. Such redox-driven control enables switching of hydrophobicity/hydrophilicity, sol–gel transitions, self-healing and shape-memory behaviors, actuated swelling/shrinking, redox-triggered cargo release, and modulation of electrochemical, optical, and mechanical properties [1,2,3].

Electrochemically controlled hydrogel systems exploiting reversible host–guest interactions between ferrocene and β -cyclodextrin will be presented. The spontaneous self-assembly of a microgel double layer on electrode surfaces and the electrochemical control of desorption/adsorption of the upper microgel, with mechanistic interpretation and quantitative characterization (CV, QCM-D, AFM), will be described. Additionally, a thermoresponsive thin hydrogel film synthesized by electrochemically induced polymerization on QCM electrodes that accumulates a ferrocene-tagged model drug via inclusion complexation and enables potential-triggered release at near-body temperature (monitored by QCM-D and fluorescence) will be presented and discussed.

[1] X. Liu, L. Zhao, F. Liu, D. Astruc, and H. Gu, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 419 (2020) 231406.

[2] P. Gwardys, K. Marcisz, D. Jaglenieć, J. Romanski, and M. Karbarz, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 15 (2023) 49865-49873.

[3] K. Marcisz, M. Gharakhloo, D. Jaglenieć, J. Pawlowski, J. Romanski, and M. Karbarz, *ACS Mater. Au* 5 (2025) 191–199.

Interaction of Microgels with Associative Ions and Reactants

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We highlight different microgel systems, where small organic and inorganic entities interact with the colloidal networks[1]. In two cases, electrostatic and secondary hydrophobic/supramolecular interactions lead to a collapse of the oppositely charged microgel because of complex formation between ions and network. In presence of excess of complexant, reentrant swelling was detected. In more detail, we investigated polycationic microgels in presence of hexacyanoferrate [2], or oppositely charged surfactant.

We gained a detailed view on the interactions by a multiscale approach from molecular to macromolecular level (with e.g. NMR and scattering techniques), providing insight into the structural rearrangements in presence of the complexants.

Beside the mere physical interactions mentioned above, we will introduce also a chemically reactive microgel, where redox reactions can be induced in presence of oxidant. Then, the ferrocen groups of the microgel are turned into cationic ferrocenium units. We gained insight into the reaction by calorimetry, including isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) at different temperatures and differential scanning calorimetry. The ITC data shows a rather drastic influence of the network rearrangements upon oxidation with signatures of the local solvation.

[1] F. A. Plamper, and W. Richtering, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **50** (2017), 131–140.

[2] R. Neubert, E. Schumann, V. Schildknecht, A. Lehmann, S. Rosenfeldt, C. Hübler, and F. A. Plamper, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **227** (2026), e00493.

Contact Forces in Microgel Suspensions

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Within a model where micrometer-size soft colloidal particles are viewed as liquid drops, we theoretically study the contact interaction between them. We compute the exact deformation energy across a broad range of indentations and for various model parameters, and we show that it can be reproduced using truncated superball and spheropolyhedral variational shapes in the attractive and the repulsive regime, respectively. At large surface tensions representative of microgels, this energy is pairwise additive well beyond small indentations and can be approximated by a power-law dependence on indentation with an exponent around 2.

[1] L. Athanasopoulou and P. Zihlerl, *Soft Matter* 13, 1463 (2017).

[2] J. Riest, L. Athanasopoulou, S. A. Egorov, C. N. Likos, and P. Zihlerl, *Sci. Rep.* 5, 15854 (2015).

[3] A.-K. Doukas, C. N. Likos, and P. Zihlerl, *Soft Matter* 14, 3063 (2018).

Investigating the network structure of microgels with super-resolution fluorescence microscopy

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Microgels are crosslinked polymer particles that can absorb significant amounts of solvent. Functional microgels have powerful applications for their specific structure and adaptiveness especially when they include polymers that can react to external stimuli such as temperature, pH, ionic strength, solvent composition or light.

One key parameter governing the internal structure, function and application of microgels is their crosslinking density [1-4]. Various techniques have been developed to determine crosslinking density in bulk hydrogels. However, these methods cannot determine the nanoscale crosslinking density.

In our contribution, we present how super-resolution fluorescence microscopy can be used to gain knowledge on diffusion and accessibility of molecules into the central parts of microgels and how this information can help in the design of,

for example, drug delivery systems of molecules and bio-macromolecules [5].

[1] T. Kyrey, J. Witte, V. Pipich, A. Feoktystov, A. Koutsioubas, E. Vezhlev, H. Frielinghaus, R. von Klitzing, S. Wellert, O. Holderer, *Polymer* **169** (2019) 29.

[2] M. Dirksen, P. Fandrich, L. Goett-Zink, J. Cremer, D. Anselmetti, T. Hellweg, *Langmuir* **38** (2022) 638.

[3] N. Hazra, A. Ninarello, A. Scotti, J. E. Houston, P. Mota-Santiago, E. Zaccarelli, J. J. Crassous, *Macromolecules* **57** (2023) 339.

[4] K. Yamanaka, Y. Nishizawa, K. Iwase, D. Kawane, H. Atarashi, T. Uchihashi, D. Suzuki, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **17** (2025) 70793.

[5] P. Lenßen, R. Hengsbach, A. Frommelius, S. Cammeraat, K. Linsen, U. Simon, D. Wöll, *Nanoscale* **17** (2025) 4570.

3.8 Network Defects & Defect Engineering

The Role of Connectivity Defects in Governing the Rheology and Microstructure of tPEG Networks

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We employed coarse-grained molecular simulations to investigate how connectivity defects affect tetra-PEG (tPEG) polymer networks. Both homoleptic and heteroleptic [1] systems were considered, with noncovalent end-group bonds modeled using an inverted Gaussian potential to control valency. Defects were introduced either by deactivating functional end groups or by deviating from ideal stoichiometry in heteroleptic mixtures. Network dynamics and molecular mobility were quantified using the mean-square displacement of individual tPEG molecules and bond lifetime analysis.

Figure 1: (a) Project protocol of adding defects into the system. (b) The long-time diffusion coefficient increases with increasing connectivity defects in the system.

Our results show that connectivity defects promote loop formation and significantly enhance star-polymer mobility. As a result, networks with higher defect concentrations exhibit lower viscosity and faster stress relaxation. By coupling the network to a mesoscale solvent with hydrodynamic interactions, we also probe how solvent-mediated shear influences defect rearrangement kinetics and the competition between loop formation and stress-bearing connectivity. Overall, our findings offer a molecular-level understanding of how defects govern the structure [2], dynamics, and mechanical properties of tPEG networks.

[1] M. Ahmadi and S. Seiffert, *Macromolecules* 2021 54 (15), 7113-7124.

[2] S. Bandyopadhyay, S. Seiffert, and A. Nikoubashman, *Macromolecules* 2026 59 (3), 1191-1200.

Molecular Descriptors of Primary Loop Cyclization in Highly Crosslinked Network Materials

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All cross-linked polymer network materials have multicyclic topologies which are dependent on the network formation conditions [1]. Primary loops, the smallest possible cyclic defects, play a critical role in network structure and macroscopic properties. Advanced characterization techniques such as network disassembly spectrometry (NDS) and computational simulations have established how chain-length and concentration influence primary loop formation in long flexible polymer chains [1-3]. However, the role of molecular features in small-molecule-derived networks remains poorly understood and is key for understanding the structure of thermoset resins and dilute multicyclic polymers. In this work, we apply NDS to a library of A_2 linkers to study how molecular features such as monomer length and rigidity influence primary loop formation in highly crosslinked $A_2 + B_f$ materials. We find that the conformation of the loop-forming $A-B_{f-1}$ intermediate dictates cyclization propensity. By coupling NDS results with molecular dynamics simulations of these intermediates, we identify molecular descriptors that govern loop formation across these materials. These findings establish molecular-level design principles for predicting and controlling the cyclic topology of thermosets and multicyclic polymers.

[1] D. Sen, B.D. Olsen, *Phys. Rev. Materials*. **9** (2025) 015602.

[2] H. Zhou, E.M. Schön, M. Wang, M.J. Glassman, J. Liu, . Zhong, D. Díaz-Díaz, B.D. Olsen, J.A. Johnson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **26** (2014) 9464-9470.

[3] R. Wang, A. Alexander-Katz, B.D. Olsen, J.A. Johnson, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **116** (2016) 188302.

Predicting polymer network elasticity from defect densities via network topology

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Linear elasticity is a cornerstone property of polymeric materials and characterizes the response of the material to small strains. In addition, linear elasticity has been linked to nonlinear mechanics, or the fracture and flow behavior. While linear elasticity is well understood in the case of ideal polymer networks, real networks include deviations from an ideal structure, referred to as network defects. Several models have been proposed to understand and predict the elasticity of polymer networks incorporating various types of defects, but no unified picture has emerged yet to link the microscopic structure of polymer networks to their macroscopic elasticity. We propose here a framework to predict the shear modulus of polymer networks based on a probabilistic description of their topology. We propose that two key parameters, the distribution of the functionality of the cross-links and the distribution of the length of the strands between the cross-links, govern the macroscopic elasticity. Unlike previous approaches, which directly model the elastic behavior of individual defects, our framework involves two steps. First, we show how to calculate the distributions of cross-link functionality and strand length based on the proportions of individual defects; then, we show how the macroscopic elasticity can be calculated based on these distributions. We validate our approach by successfully predicting the shear modulus of systems published in the literature and custom-built networks that were not accurately described by previous models (panels A-C). Our results shed light on the importance of the distribution of strand length and highlight the relevance of a higher-level description of the topology of polymer networks. This suggests that similar principles could be adapted to describe other mechanical properties.

[1] Zhong, Mingjiang, et al. *Science* 353.6305 (2016): 1264-1268.

[2] Nishi, Kengo, et al. *Physical Review Letters* 119.26 (2017): 267801.

[3] Lin, Tzyy-Shyang, et al. *Macromolecules* 51.3 (2018): 1224-1231.

Defect-mediated melting of star polymers in varying solvent quality

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Melting in two dimensions proceeds via the unbinding of topological defects, leading to a two-step transition with an intermediate hexatic phase. While this scenario is well established, its realization in systems with realistic, soft interactions remains poorly explored. Star polymers provide an ideal model system, combining ultrasoft, entropic repulsion with solvent-controlled effective attraction.

In this talk, we investigate how solvent-induced attraction modifies the melting behavior of slit-confined two-dimensional star polymers [1]. Using large-scale Monte Carlo simulations, we systematically vary star functionality, particle density, and solvent quality.

We find that melting remains defect-mediated and consistent with the KTHNY scenario across a wide range of interaction parameters. In contrast to previous studies suggesting that attraction can drive a transition toward first-order melting [2], we observe that solvent-induced attraction instead stabilizes the hexatic phase and modifies the pathway to melting without suppressing the underlying two-step mechanism.

Furthermore, we identify signatures of alternative phase behavior near the triple-point regime, including gas-hexatic coexistence and the emergence of multiple triple points.

[1] A. Farimani, R., Likos, C.N.: Coarse-graining of slit-confined star polymers in solvents of varying quality. *Macromolecules* (2025).

[2] Li, Yan-Wei, and Massimo Pica Ciamarra. "Attraction tames two-dimensional melting: From continuous to discontinuous transitions." *Physical Review Letters* 124.21 (2020): 218002.

[3] Mendoza-Coto, Alejandro, et al. "Melting of the two-dimensional solid phase in the Gaussian core model." *Physical Review B* (2024).

Trapping entanglements in hydrogels by controlled polymerisation

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Highly entangled hydrogels are a new class of tough and elastic polymer networks in which physical chain entanglements outnumber chemical crosslinks. [1] I will present our recent work on the synthesis of ultra-high molecular weight (UHMW) poly(N,N-dimethylacrylamide) (PDMAm) hydrogels with very low crosslinking densities by photoiniferter-mediated controlled radical polymerisation. [2] Fixing the trithiocarbonate photoiniferter to crosslinker ratio and gradually increasing the monomer/photoiniferter ratio (i.e. the targeted degree of polymerization, DP_{target}) allowed for simultaneous control over the crosslinking density and the average molecular weight (M_n) of the primary chains, both below and above the critical molecular weight of entanglement (M_c). These hydrogels exhibit improved toughness, and resistance to swelling and degradation (when prepared with cleavable crosslinkers) due to the presence dense entanglements. Furthermore, mixing or replacing the trithiocarbonate with a xanthate-based photoiniferter, enables oxygen-tolerant preparation of highly entangled hydrogels.

[1] J. Kim, G. Zhang, M. Shi, Z. Suo, *Science* **2021**, 374, 212.

[2] G. Irvine, K. Myronidis, F. Pinto, M. Kopeć, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2025**, 64, e202421970.

Defect-Driven Design of Degradable Gels via Radical Ring-Opening Polymerization

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Radical ring-opening polymerization (RROP) of cyclic ketene acetals (CKAs) represents a potent strategy for synthesizing (bio-)degradable polyesters with distinctive properties. While such materials are predominantly reported as linear polymers,¹ polymer networks derived from the RROP of CKAs remain scarcely explored. By the synthesis and a detailed characterization of polymer networks obtained via only CKA-based RROP this gap is addressed, elucidating the mechanisms of network formation and associated structure-property relationships. In particular, 2-methylene-1,3,6-trioxocane (MTC),

as a typical representative of the CKA family, served as main building block, combined with both a CKA-derived and a vinyl ether-derived cross-linker.² Depending on the choice and type of cross-linker the gel structure, including defects, is changed on multiple length scales which then causes a change in mechanical properties such as material stiffness as well as on the swelling behavior of the gels. By understanding the way these structural defects are formed one can adjust the right structures for desired properties e.g. for the use of drug-releasing scaffolds or barrier materials. Furthermore, CKA-only networks open another class of fully degradable materials making them a promising alternative for ecological challenges.

[1] 1.Folini, J.; Murad, W.; Mehner, F.; Meier, W.; Gaitzsch, J. *European Polymer Journal* **2020**, 134, 109851.

[2] Meissner, T.; Schäfer, S.; Barner-Kowollik, C.; Seiffert, S.; Gaitzsch, J. *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.* **2025**, 7, 20, 13936–13949

Connectivity Defects in Metallo-Supramolecular Polymer Gels

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Supramolecular polymer networks combine the adaptability of reversible interactions with the structural integrity of conventional elastomers, resulting in polymer gels that are promising soft, stimulus-responsive materials. Their macroscopic mechanical properties are determined by transient molecular bonds and the topology of the polymer network over larger length scales, reflecting the contributions of nanoscale structure and dynamics. In metallo-supramolecular polymer networks, reversible metal-ligand coordination enables precise tuning of crosslinking strength and lifetime, while allowing controlled introduction of connectivity defects. Such defects can be implemented by tracers, stoichiometric imbalances in heteroleptic arrangements, and monovalent dopants that create free ends.

Connectivity defects manifest as primary loops and free ends, which reduce the proportion of elastically active strands and alter the homogeneity of the network. In coordination-driven systems, strong association potentially promotes crosslink clustering and static density fluctuations. These microscopic variations directly influence macroscopic behaviour. Increasing defect density usually decreases the elastic modulus and viscosity but increases chain mobility and stress relaxation due to reduced topological constraints.

Defect engineering in metallo-supramolecular polymer networks enables the systematic manipulation of transient connectivity. This provides a framework to directly relate molecular architecture, dynamic bond exchange, and mechanical performance. It also opens pathways toward programmable, adaptive soft materials.

References

1. S. Bandyopadhyay, S. Seiffert, A. Nikoubashman, *Macromolecules* **59** (2026) 1191–1200.
2. M. Ahmadi, L. Löser, K. Fischer, K. Saalwächter K, S. Seiffert, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **221** (2020) 1900400.

3.9 Sensors, Actuators & Responsive Materials

Thermosensitive hydrogel applications and sustainable end-of-life approaches

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Materials are essential to reach the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) encouraged by the United Nations (UN) and the European Union (EU) Green Deal missions.¹⁾ In our Group we have explored the application of **thermosensitive hydrogels (TSH)** in biomedical implants (e.g. sensors with body temperature response, with movement response,²⁾ with theranostic properties to promote detection and killing of bacteria biofilm;³⁾ in solar-driven desalination (SDD);⁴⁾ and in energy generation with SDD processes.⁵⁾ These TSHs can be combined with biopolymers, solar absorbers, and/or polyelectrolytes, to potentiate the materials performance. Their syntheses are affordable (3-4 steps in aqueous solution), require mild reaction conditions (~30-36 °C, 4-5 h), and the gels are free of **critical raw materials (CRMs)** and do not contain any per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (**PFAS-free** material). Thus, the adoption of green chemical processes and **safe** and **sustainable by design (SSbD)** methodologies aligns very well with some of the SDGs traced by the UN and EU.

What should be the next step? The entry of the materials into the circular economy, including hydrogels reuse or recycling **end-of-life** considerations. In this work, some approaches will be discussed.

Advantages:

- ✓ 100 % organic material
- ✓ Highly porous structure
- ✓ Superabsorbent capacity
- ✓ Potential emerging applications in: solar-driven desalination (SDD), capacitive desalination (CDI), ion-exchange membranes for biobatteries, wastewater recovery.

References: ¹⁾ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>; ²⁾ Lanzalaco *et al.* *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2020**, *30*, 2004145; Lanzalaco *et al.* *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **2022**, *8*, 3329; ³⁾ Mingot *et al.* *Chem. Eng. J.* **2024**, *497*, 154617; ⁴⁾ Mingot *et al.* *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2023**, 2311523; Naranjo *et al.* *Adv. Sustainable Syst.* **2024**, 2400234; Naranjo *et al.* *Chem. Mater.* **2024**, *36*, 4688; Mingot *et al.* *Chem. Eng. J.* **2025**, *526*, 171408 ⁵⁾ Borràs *et al.* *Solar RRL* **2024**, 2400661.

Acknowledgements: This work has received funding from the Grant PID2024-157005OB-I00 and María de Maeztu Excellence Centre (CEX2023-001300-M) by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF "A way of making Europe", by the European Union. E. Armelin acknowledges the support given by ICREA Acadèmia 2024 award (grant n^o 00125) for excellence in Research, funded by the Generalitat de Catalunya.

Interconnected Star-Shaped OEGMA Polymers: From Antifouling to Organic Electronics

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Polymer architecture plays a key role in the design of advanced functional materials, particularly in the systems where control over interfacial and electronic properties is required. In this context, star-shaped polymers have attracted increasing attention due to their compact structure, high density of functional groups, and potential to form interconnected or network-like architectures.

In this work, we first explored star-shaped oligo(ethylene glycol) methacrylate (OEGMA) polymers for antifouling surface applications. Their hydrophilicity and dense functional architecture enabled the formation of highly protein-resistant layers of interconnected stars, with antifouling efficacy dependent on the number and length of the arms used to construct these materials.

Building on these results, OEGMA-based star polymers were further extended toward organic electronic systems by incorporating conjugated poly(3-hexylthiophene) segments, providing a platform that combines interfacial functionality with semiconducting properties. In these systems, the star architecture facilitated controlled organization and promoted enhanced interchain interactions, supporting the formation of interconnected morphologies relevant for charge transport.

The resulting materials were investigated using complementary techniques to evaluate their structural, surface, and electronic properties. The multifunctional nature of the star polymers, combined with their architectural design, enables the formation of highly organized and potentially network-like structures bridging surface-functional and electronic materials.

This study demonstrates that star-shaped polymers based on OEGMA provide versatile platforms for the design of functional materials, ranging from antifouling coatings to organic electronic devices, and highlights their potential as building blocks for advanced polymer networks.

Reinforced organogel as a novel system for wax-resin and emulsion removal from oil paintings

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Gel seems to be perfect materials for art conservation due to porous structure, adjustable solvent content-ability to absorb solvent in polymeric network, sorption properties, transparency, and flexibility. In such materials, the polymer network ensures mechanical stability and shape retention, while the solvent phase enables diffusional processes to occur, much like those in liquids. Additionally, polymer network can be modified to achieve specific properties. These features make gels particularly interesting materials for art conservation applications requiring controlled solvent delivery.

In this work we present nanocomposite organogel containing mixture of organic solvent selected from Teas's plots and suitable for removing wax-based lining adhesive. The wax-based adhesives were employed to reinforced oil paints - this lining method is called Dutch method. In conservation work, before a new lining technique can be applied, the old impregnation and lining adhesives typically must be reduced or removed. This stage presents significant technical challenges. Our study demonstrates that the pNIPA-LAP nanocomposite organogel can be effectively applied not only for wax-resin masses but also for complex emulsion systems containing wax, resin, and animal glue. Compared to conventional solvent-based methods, the organogel allows improved control over the area and duration of application, reduces reliance on highly toxic solvents, and limits the need for aggressive mechanical treatment. The examples of application of organogel on real objects - paintings from 18th, 19th and 20th century - will be present.

Dually Cross-linked Stimuli-sensitive Gels

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Cross-linked hydrogels with incorporated supra-molecular host/guest structures are interesting materials for preparation of biosensors due to their ability to swell in a certain medium. Biomolecules of interest are e.g. biomarkers, which are substances as indicators for a possible dysfunction of the system.

In hydrogels the whole volume phase (3D range) of the layer can be used for the detection of special biomarker to multiply the sensor signal. In the present study, the whole research chain of the development of a new biosensor was covered. First molecular compounds able to form sufficient stable supramolecular bonds were designed and synthesized. Such compounds were incorporated into photo cross-linkable polymers, which were processed by spin coating. After photo cross-linking, the obtained networks are the central detection part converting chemical information (molecular recognition) into a detectable signal (swelling of the network due to change in secondary polymer structure). Reversible supramolecular bonds within the bare network will be broken in the presence of a particular analyte resulting in different polar gels showing a swelling change. To prove this principle and to obtain information about the process, supramolecular interactions were analyzed by a variety of methods. Finally, the polymers were incorporated into newly designed sensor set-ups based on piezoresistive sensors. These transducer elements were designed and studied with respect to high sensitivity, fast response and long-term stability. The prototypes for biomedical sensing of e.g. α -lipoic acid and spermine were developed. Such sensors are of great interest for applications, e.g. in medicine, non-invasive medical diagnostics and care, pharmacy, and environmental protection.

Electroactive Microgels for Advanced Controlled Release Systems

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The incorporation of electroactive moieties such as ferrocene or conductive polymers into environmentally sensitive microgel networks introduces reversible redox activity, enabling electrochemical control over their physicochemical properties. In this work, temperature- and pH-sensitive microgels were synthesized and functionalized with ferrocene or poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT). Cystine- or cystamine-based crosslinkers were applied both to stabilize the polymer network and to enable covalent immobilization of microgels onto gold electrode surfaces via disulfide-mediated chemisorption, resulting in densely packed and uniform microgel monolayers. Microgel-coated electrodes were investigated as platforms for electrochemically triggered release of model drug compounds. The positively charged dye (crystal violet, CV) was incorporated into the microgel network through electrostatic interactions with carboxyl groups. Upon application of an appropriate oxidation potential, redox transformation of electroactive groups altered the charge distribution within the polymer network, leading to controlled dye release. The amount of released substance could be precisely tuned by adjusting the applied electrochemical signal [1,2]. These results demonstrate that electroactive microgel monolayers are promising platforms for electrochemically controlled release systems with potential applications in transdermal and implantable drug delivery devices.

Multistimuli-responsive polydopamine nanobowl- armored emulsions for imaging and theranostics

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Polydopamine nanobowls (PDA NBs), formed via oxidative polymerization of dopamine into crosslinked catecholamine networks, are bioinspired polymer nanostructures with strong optical absorption and photothermal activity [1]. We report a novel class of multistimuli-responsive PDA NB-armored emulsions engineered as soft polymeric interfaces for biomedical imaging and therapeutic activation. These nanobowl structures stabilise perfluorocarbon droplets containing perfluorohexane (NB-H) or perfluoropentane (NB-P), enabling controlled droplet-to-microbubble phase transitions. Thermal and near-infrared (NIR) stimulation produced distinct responses governed by core volatility and polymer shell structure. Contrast-matched SANS/USANS resolved droplet architecture and tracked *in situ* phase transition dynamics. NB-H droplets resisted heating, whereas NB-P droplets readily vaporized. Short NIR irradiation induced more efficient transitions than bulk heating, demonstrating the advantage of photothermally active polymer interfaces for spatiotemporal control. Moreover, both emulsions generated strong ultrasound contrast with good cytocompatibility. PDA NBs also provided robust photoacoustic contrast [2] with distinct behavior compared to thin-shelled droplet systems [3]. This work illustrates potential of PDA NB-armored emulsions as multifunctional platforms for ultrasound imaging, photoacoustic imaging, and photothermal theranostics.

[1] M. L. P. Vidallon, *et al.* [Small](#) **21** (2025) 2406019.

[2] Z. Lu, *et al.* [Journal of Materials Chemistry B](#) **10** (2022) 9662-9670.

[3] M. L. P. Vidallon, *et al.* [Ultrasonics Sonochemistry](#) **86** (2022) 106041.

Stimuli-responsive hydrogels as smart materials in microfluidic application

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Responsive polymeric materials are becoming a highly studied field especially with regard to their use in technical applications, e.g. as sensors and actuators in microsystems and microfluidic applications, since they are able as volume gels to carry out mechanical work reacting on an e.g. chemical stimulus. In addition, compartmentalization becomes an issue for being able to localize specific actions and reactions e.g. by patterning specific hydrogel compartments. We will report on the preparation and integration of responsive hydrogel dot arrays of high flow and shear stability in microfluidic channel and chamber reactors. Further optimization has been achieved by combining in double-crosslinked systems permanent and dynamic and reversible crosslinking points introducing redox functions and host-guest interactions.[1,2] The dynamic responsive behavior could be translated into micrometer hydrogel dots in microsystems combining actuator function with specific bioresponse. First results are presented to use reversible redox bonding in hydrogels for triggered peptides capturing and release, and to adapt hydrogel dots as enzyme carriers in multi-chamber microreactors for complex cascade enzymatic reactions including enzymatic polymerization. [3,4,5]

[1] Y. Che, S. Zschoche, F. Obst, D. Appelhans and B. Voit, *Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry*, 2019, **57**, 2590-2601.

[2] Y. Che, J. Gaitzsch, N. Liubimtsev, S. Zschoche, T. Bauer, D. Appelhans and B. Voit, *Soft Matter*, 2020, **16**, 6733-6742.

[3] C. Jiao, F. Obst, M. Geisler, Y. Che, A. Richter, D. Appelhans, J. Gaitzsch, B. Voit, *Polymers* **2022**, *14*, 267.

[4] C. Jiao, D. Appelhans, B. Voit, N. Bruns, J. Gaitzsch, *Polym. Chem.*, 2025, *16*, 742–750

[5] C. Jiao, N. Liubimtsev, Z. Zagradka-P., D. Appelhans, J. Gaitzsch, B. Voit, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* 2023, 2200869

Uncovering Aggregation-Induced Emission in Carbon Dots for Color-Changing Hydrogels and Information Encryption

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Smart fluorescent hydrogels with dynamic, color-switching capabilities are highly desirable for advanced information security and visual sensing. However, constructing such platforms using simple, stable, and highly reversible fluorophores remains a challenge. Herein, we present a novel solvent-responsive, color-changing smart hydrogel fabricated by incorporating red-emissive carbon dots (R-CDs)—derived from the classic citric acid–urea system—into a poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) matrix. Distinct from conventional CDs that suffer from aggregation-caused quenching (ACQ), the embedded R-CDs exhibit unique aggregation-induced emission (AIE) characteristics. The color-changing behavior of the hydrogel is fundamentally governed by the solvent-triggered microscopic distance between different R-CDs. The resulting R-CDs/PVA hydrogel demonstrates rapid, highly reversible, and high-contrast dual-color fluorescence switching. Leveraging this dynamic spatial and temporal optical response, we successfully demonstrate the hydrogel's utility as a versatile and robust platform for advanced information encryption, erasable coding, and anti-counterfeiting. This work not only provides fresh insights into the AIE mechanisms within classic carbon dot systems but also offers a scalable strategy for designing next-generation smart photofunctional hydrogels for high-level security applications.

Optically Programmable 3D Movement of Dandelion-Inspired Ultra-light Microfliers

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Manoeuvring untethered, milligram-scale airborne structures remains a central challenge in micro-robotics. Active flapping systems require high power density and onboard electronics ^[1], limiting miniaturization and endurance, whereas passive wind-dispersed structures lack controllable steering ^[2]. Here we present a dandelion-inspired ultra-light microflier capable of programmable three-dimensional (3D) motion through light-induced aerodynamic asymmetry.

The platform combines a porous hexaradial architecture with photomechanically responsive liquid crystal elastomer (LCE) actuators that dynamically reconfigure filament geometry during passive wind-assisted descent. With a mass on the milligram scale and terminal velocities comparable to natural dandelion diaspores, the artificial flyer exhibits enhanced positional and rotational stability. Flow visualization reveals that shape morphing induces asymmetric separated vortex rings ^[3], generating lateral forces while preserving drag-based vertical support.

Under low-turbulence airflow, the system demonstrates altitude regulation, reversible body flipping, orbital motion, and steerable 3D trajectories. Control is achieved without onboard power or rigid transmission components; instead, spatially patterned illumination modulates aerodynamic symmetry in real time.

By integrating passive vortex stabilization with optically programmable morphology, this work establishes a materials–aerodynamics co-design framework for controlled passive flight, offering a lightweight and energy-efficient pathway toward distributed microfliers for environmental sensing and atmospheric monitoring.

[1] Y. Chen, H. Zhao, J. Mao, et al., [*Nature* 575 \(2019\) 324–329](#).

[2] J. Yang, H. Zhang, A. Berdin, et al., [*Adv. Sci.* 10 \(2023\) 2206752](#)

[3] C. Cummins, M. Seale, A. Macente, et al. [*Nature* 562, \(2018\) 414–418](#)

Thermoresponsive Polymer-Grafted Egyptian Blue Nanosheets for NIR Photothermal Drug Release

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Photothermal active nanomaterials functionalized with thermoresponsive polymers offer an attractive strategy for remotely triggered drug release.[1] However, their development requires the combination of scalable synthesis, biocompatibility, and efficient photothermal conversion within the near-infrared (NIR) biological window.

Egyptian blue nanosheets (EBNS, $\text{CaCuSi}_4\text{O}_{10}$), a cost-effective, scalable, nontoxic, NIR-active material,[2] were functionalized with thermoresponsive *N*-isopropylacrylamide/acrylic acid copolymers in this work. The hybrid nanoparticles exhibited tunable temperature-dependent size changes in water and reversible aggregation in a simulated blood fluid containing bovine serum albumin. Furthermore, the intrinsic photothermal activity of EBNS enabled localized heating of the dispersions during NIR laser irradiation. As a proof-of-concept application, doxorubicin-loaded hybrid EBNS displayed temperature-triggered drug release. These results demonstrate that thermoresponsive polymer grafting provides an effect platform as drug carrier with tunable colloidal behavior, while the EBNS core enables remote activation through photothermal heating.[3]

[1] D. S. Chauhan, *et al.*, *Sig Transduct Target Ther* **11**, 95 (2026).

[2] Y. Cai, *et al.*, *ACS Appl. Opt. Mater.* **1** (2023) 465–472.

[3] Y. Zhang, Y. Cai, P. Vana, [Manuscript in preparation]

3.10 Vitrimers, Sustainable Materials & Recycling

D-Isosorbide and Furfural-Derived Monomers for Glassy Bio-Based Vinylogous Urethane Vitrimers

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Bio-based covalent adaptable networks (CANs) or vitrimers, that simultaneously offer high glass transition temperatures, strong mechanical performance, and reprocessability are still relatively rare, especially within vinylogous urethane vitrimer systems. In this work, we present the synthesis of rigid vinylogous urethane CANs based on bio-derived D-isosorbide bis-acetoacetate and the furfural-based diamine, propane-2,2-di(2-furylmethylamine) (PDFA). These materials were produced via a solvent-free bulk curing approach, employing combinations of di- and trifunctional amines to directly generate crosslinked networks without the need for additional solvents. Incorporation of PDFA enhanced the renewable carbon content while preserving the structural rigidity necessary for high-performance glassy materials. The resulting polymer networks showed adjustable thermomechanical behavior depending on the amine composition, achieving glass transition temperatures up to 125 °C and thermal stability up to 290 °C. Stress relaxation studies revealed rapid, catalyst-free bond exchange in the rubbery state, with relaxation times ranging from tens to hundreds of seconds and activation energies influenced by the diamine structure. Moreover, selected samples demonstrated good reprocessability through compression molding, largely retaining their thermal and mechanical properties after reprocessing. Overall, this study highlights that combining D-isosorbide with a rigid, furfural-derived diamine is a promising route to bio-based, glassy vinylogous urethane vitrimers that integrate high renewable content, elevated service temperatures, and recyclability.

Acknowledgements: This research was financially supported by the BioCAN project, selected in the Joint Transnational Call 2024 of M-ERA.NET 3, which is an EU-funded network of 49 funding organisations (Horizon 2020 grant agreement No. 958174). The project with ID No.TQ17000002 is also co-financed from the state budget by the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic under the SIGMA Programme within the M-ERA.NET 3 Call 2024 ERA-NET Cofund Call/European Partnerships.

Repairable Latent-Reactive Adhesive via Nucleophile Mediated Ring-Opening Copolymerization of Benzoxazine and Elemental Sulfur

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The growing demand for sustainable advanced materials motivates the development of reprocessable crosslinked polymers via accommodating polysulfide chains into the crosslinked network thereby, combining high performance with repairability. In this work, we present a synthesis of latent reactive adhesive based on nucleophile mediated, thermal assisted ring opening copolymerization of cardanol based benzoxazine (CAR-apd) and elemental sulfur thereby yielding poly(benzoxazine-co-sulfur) crosslinked network. Unlike conventional polybenzoxazines which contain only permanently cross links, copolymerization with sulfur incorporates reversible sulfur-sulfur linkages that endow the material with vitrimer like behavior. The copolymerization was conducted at 135 °C, a temperature markedly lower than the ceiling temperature for polymerization of sulfur (159°C). These copolymers were further analyzed using structural, thermal and mechanical characterizations. Furthermore, through this work, the impact of sulfur content on the crosslinking density, relaxation behavior and adhesion strength of copolymers has been studied through comparative analysis of surface energy measurements, swelling experiments, dynamic mechanical analysis, and lap shear test. Surface energy measurements confirm good wettability on stainless steel substrates, supporting strong interfacial adhesion. Among all, poly(CAR-apd-S1) was further studied for rheological analysis exhibiting relaxation time of 27 s at 90 °C with activation energy for sulfur-sulfur exchange of 66.2 kJ/mol. Based on known sulfur chemistry, a plausible mechanism for the synthesis of copolymers is proposed, resulting into adhesive which combines the intrinsic mechanical and thermal stability of polybenzoxazines with the dynamic covalent chemistry of polysulfides, offering a high performance, latent reactive adhesive that utilizes industrial sulfur waste.

[1] Rafiq Mohammad, Nilanjan Mukherjee, **Priyanshi Goel**, Mahipal Meena, Prasun Roy, Leena Nebhani, "Applied Polymer Materials" (2026).

[2] Pratibha Sharma, Pramit Dutta, Leena Nebhani, "Polymer", **184** (2019), 121905.

[3] Acerina Trejo-Machin, Laura Puchot, Pierre Verge, "Polymer Chemistry", **11** (2020), 7026-7034.

Furanic Cyclobutanes as Renewable Building Blocks for Diels–Alder-Based Circular Polymers

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The circular economy marks a crucial shift from the linear "take-make-use-dispose" model to a more sustainable approach. In polymer science, this transition involves prioritizing renewable raw materials, developing low-waste synthetic processes that incorporate most starting materials into the final product, and designing materials that are easily repaired, reprocessed, or recycled. Consequently, dynamic network polymers have gained relevance as sustainable alternatives to conventional materials like thermosets. In this context, the present study explored *cis*-3,4-di(furan-2-yl)cyclobutane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid (CBDA) as a renewable platform for synthesizing thermoreversible crosslinked polymers via the Diels–Alder reaction. CBDA was synthesized through UV-promoted dimerization of *trans*-3-(2-furyl)acrylic acid using commercial UV LEDs, achieving over 90% conversion in 12 hours. Its Diels–Alder reactivity with mono-, bi-, and trifunctional maleimides was monitored by ¹H NMR, showing slow adduct formation at 65 °C and rapid retro-Diels–Alder dissociation at 110 °C. Network polymers in gel form were produced from CBDA and trifunctional maleimide (TMI), though thermoreversibility was not observed in the bulk material. A sustainability assessment highlighted CBDA's green credentials: an E factor of 1.6, 100% atom economy (AE), and 87% reaction mass efficiency (RME). In contrast, TMI synthesis posed a major sustainability bottleneck, with a high E factor of 270 and low RME of 26%. The final Diels–Alder polymerization step, however, showed excellent theoretical efficiency—100% AE and an estimated RME of about 72%. Thus, this work is the first to link the green, accessible CBDA molecule with Diels–Alder chemistry, establishing its potential as a building block for biobased, dynamic polymer networks.

Sugar based resin for sustainable thermoset

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Methacrylate resins incorporating bio-based building blocks were synthesized from commercially available galactarate (GalX) and xylofuranose (IPrXF).

Thermal analysis showed high thermostability, with decomposition above 230 °C exceeding UMA 121 thermosets. Mechanical testing by AFM revealed elastic moduli of 2.9–3.8 GPa, comparable to UMA 121 (4.7 GPa). The materials also showed strong resistance to enzymatic and chemical degradation. The sugar-based thermosets contain up to 70 wt % bio-based content and form transparent, colorless coatings with excellent film-forming properties, making them promising sustainable alternatives for durable coatings.

[1] Kiriy, N.; Gausmann, P.; Shamraienko, P.; Chekhovskiy, S.; Frank, R.; Kiriy, A.; Voit, B. Sugar-based methacrylate resins for use in high performance, transparent, and sustainable thermoset coatings. *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.* 2025, 7, 5, 3233–3244. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsapm.4c03924>.

Polybenzoxazine vitrimers for unconventional electronics applications

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Among thermosets, polybenzoxazines (PBz) are gaining attention for use in printed circuit boards, encapsulation and potting compounds. Benzoxazines offer the advantage of self-crosslinking under thermal stimuli, and the resulting polymers exhibit excellent thermomechanical, electrical properties and moisture resistance. However, like other thermosets, their permanently crosslinked network hinders recycling, raising environmental concerns regarding the generation of electronic waste. As an alternative, a new generation of recyclable thermosets, called vitrimers, has been developed. By introducing dynamic covalent bonds within the network, vitrimers retain the performances of thermosets while enabling recyclability approaching that of thermoplastics. This work consists of two applied studies. In the first, dual-dynamic (ester-disulfide) and flexible single-dynamic (ester) PBz vitrimers were developed. Here, the possibility of combining dissimilar vitrimers by welding, while enabling selective chemical disassembly by targeting a single type of dynamic bond, is demonstrated. These substrates were used for the encapsulation of functional resistance temperature detectors (RTDs). In the second study, a bio-based PBz vitrimer, exhibiting strong thermomechanical properties ($T_g=140$ °C, $E=3.5$ GPa) and dielectric performance (dielectric constant ϵ' of 6.2 at 1 kHz and 5.4 at 1 MHz, both at 20 °C) comparable to conventional substrates, was developed for transistor applications. This bio-based vitrimer demonstrates both chemical and mechanical recyclability, with transparent films of the recycled vitrimer used for RTD fabrication. These two studies represent an initial step toward more sustainable electronic device design, addressing the growing challenge of electronic waste.

Multifunctional and Sustainable Vitrimer Coatings

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Bio-based covalent adaptable networks are emerging as a promising platform for the development of sustainable protective systems combining durability, self-healing capability, and recyclability. In this work, we report the design of a solvent-free, photocurable vitrimeric system based on dynamic imine chemistry, specifically tailored for protective coating applications.

The resin was synthesized from bio-derived building blocks, namely methacrylated vanillin reacted with a flexible diamine through Schiff-base chemistry, and formulated with methacrylated eugenol as a reactive diluent. This formulation enables efficient UV-curing while maintaining a fully solventless process. To enhance the functional performance, silica nanoparticles were surface-functionalized, promoting both homogeneous dispersion and covalent integration into the network. Three formulations were developed: a pristine vitrimer and nanocomposites containing 2 wt% and 5 wt% functionalized silica nanoparticles. Structural and morphological analyses confirmed successful nanoparticle functionalization and uniform dispersion. The resulting coatings exhibit intrinsic self-healing behavior driven by thermally activated imine exchange reactions. Notably, the incorporation of 2 wt% nanoparticles significantly accelerates healing kinetics, enabling complete scratch closure within minutes even at relatively low temperatures (80 °C) and without external pressure. Mechanical characterization revealed a marked improvement in scratch resistance upon nanoparticle incorporation, while maintaining high adhesion strength to steel substrates, as confirmed by pull-off tests showing no coating-substrate interfacial failure. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy demonstrated excellent corrosion protection for pristine coatings, maintaining impedance moduli above $10^7 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ during prolonged exposure to saline environments. Importantly, the vitrimeric coatings can be fully removed from substrates via transimination reactions in the presence of diamine solutions, enabling complete delamination and recovery of oligomeric fragments while restoring a clean substrate surface. This feature highlights the potential of these systems for circular material design and sustainable coating technologies.

Upcycling Innovations: Transforming Waste into High-Performance Bio-Based Monomers for a Sustainable Future

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In the quest for sustainability, upcycling waste materials into high-performance bio-based monomers has emerged as a game-changing strategy. This talk unveils exciting advancements in utilizing commercially available agricultural byproducts and industrial waste to create innovative materials that reduce environmental impact.

I will begin by demonstrating that a material derived as a byproduct of soda pulping of non-woody biomass and soybean oil can be used to create UV-curable anticorrosion coatings that not only provide superior protection against corrosion and bacteria but also contribute to a more sustainable materials landscape [1]. Next, I will present the development of high-performance covalent adaptable network polymers derived from the bioconversion of rice bran ferulic acid. These polymers exemplify how upcycling can yield materials with good reprocessability and impressive thermomechanical properties, enhancing both functionality and sustainability while utilizing resources that would otherwise be discarded.

Finally, I will present a method to transform fish-waste-derived collagen into a stable photocurable hydrogel for wound dressings.

In conclusion, this talk illustrates how leveraging the potential of industrial byproducts not only fosters innovation in material science but also paves the way for a more sustainable and circular economy.

[1] S. Moradi Boldaji, L. Iannucci, S. Grassini, L. C. Pariani, L. Anna Maria Rossato, P. D'Arrigo, C. Noè, M. Messori, [Progress in Organic Coatings \(2026\) 214, 110024](#)

One-Pot Synthesis and Reactive Extrusion of Vitrimers

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Vitrimers are an innovative class of polymers characterized by a unique combination of mechanical and chemical stability, along with dynamic covalent bonds. They undergo thermally activated associative exchange reactions that modify the network structure without decreasing their cross-link density. Their permanently cross-linked yet reprocessable networks enable features such as shape memory, self-healing, and recycling, which extend their lifespan and improve end-of-life options.

In this study, we present a rapid and versatile one-pot synthesis approach for vitrimers. The one-pot method is ideal for reactive extrusion. By reacting the monomers in an extruder, a vitrimer can be produced in under 10 minutes, a process that is actually faster than bulk synthesis in a flask. We investigated and compared the thermomechanical and chemical properties of vitrimers produced using both methods. By combining monomers of different chain lengths, we also successfully tailored the thermomechanical properties of the final material. Finally, we demonstrated that these materials can be reprocessed and recycled through mechanical and chemical processes, as well as through extrusion. This highlights their potential for sustainable applications.

From Lignocellulosic Biomass to Vitrimers: Turning Waste-Wood Lignin into Smart Materials

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Lignin is amongst the most abundant biopolymers on earth and is rising as one of the most promising raw materials for substituting the high demand of fossil-based educts with bio-based ones. The unique aromatic structure leads to properties such as thermal stability, mechanical strength, chemical resistance, hydrophobicity, as well as antimicrobial and antioxidant activities, and make lignin itself an interesting chemical starting material.^[1]

WASTE WOOD LIGNIN-BASED VINYLOGOUS URETHANE VITRIMERS

Herein, we present catalyst-free vinylogous urethane vitrimers based on lignosulfonate and enzymatic lignin, using a commercial bio-based diamine and a bio-based diol linker. Materials are synthesized following green chemistry principles using a direct acetoacetylation process of lignin in non-toxic solvents, which can subsequently be used to produce homogeneous materials. The thermomechanical properties and recyclability over five cycles demonstrate that the materials represent a promising class of tough, green, and sustainable vitrimers. Additionally, processing through injection molding was demonstrated, producing homogeneous samples for tensile testing which enhances recycling and industrial applicability.^[2]

[1] R. Shorey, A. Salaghi, T. H. Mekonnen, *RSC Sustain.* **2** (2024) 804.

[2] F. C. Klein, N. Sobania, V. Abetz, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **13** (2025) 29120.

Improving interfacial properties of immiscible polymer with vitrimers

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A significant portion of polymeric materials consists of polymer blends, multilayer polymers, and adhesive joints. Nevertheless, most polymer pairs exhibit unfavourable thermodynamics for blending, leading to macroscopic phase separation and poor interfacial adhesion, reducing final material performances [1]. Therefore, improving the mechanical strength of the polymer-polymer interface has always been a focus of interest. Vitrimer networks are studied as an alternative to address this issue, since they are polymers with dynamic cross-links that can rearrange their network topology through bond-exchange reactions [2].

In this work, adhesion properties of a dioxaborolane-based vitrimer [3] embedded into two immiscible polymers, polystyrene and polymethyl methacrylate, have been assessed. The dioxaborolane bond exchanges can be easily thermally activated at high temperatures, enabling dynamic bond breaking and reformation at the interface between the two polymers, thereby increasing the adhesion. An asymmetric double cantilever beam test was performed to quantify changes in adhesion properties [1,4] as a function of adhesion temperature, dwell time, and vitrimer content, by measuring the critical energy release rate (G_c). Layered samples were employed, with adhesion assessed on spin coated vitrimers films on polymer substrates, with low usage of vitrimer. Subsequently, the disassembly of the adhered polymers will also be explored by using the dynamic nature of vitrimer bonds, which strengthen the interface at low temperatures but weaken it as the bonds become dynamic.

[1] C. Creton, E.J. Kramer, H.R. Brown, C.-Y. Hui, *Molecular Simulation Fracture Gel Theory* (2002) 53–136.

[2] D. Montarnal, M. Capelot, F. Tournilhac, L. Leibler, *Science* **334** (2011) 965–968.

[3] M. Röttger, T. Domenech, R. van der Weegen, A. Breuillac, R. Nicolaÿ, L. Leibler, *Science* **356** (2017) 62–65.

[4] C. Creton, E.J. Kramer, C.-Y. Hui, H.R. Brown, *Macromolecules* **25** (1992) 3075–3088.

Rheological and Electrical Properties of Poly(ionic liquid)-based Vitrimers

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To simultaneously achieve high ionic conductivity and recyclability, we developed ion-conductive vitrimer-like main-chain poly(ionic liquid) (TPIL) elastomers that integrate ionic transport with dynamic network rearrangement. The TPILs were prepared via thermal click polymerization of clickable imidazolium-based ionic liquid monomers [1], followed by crosslinking through trans-*N*-alkylation using dihalogenated crosslinkers. The effects of monomer structure and anion species on the glass transition temperature, ionic conductivity, stress relaxation behavior, and reprocessability were systematically investigated. We found that vitrimers with lower glass transition temperatures exhibited higher ionic conductivity. Furthermore, mixed-anion systems (e.g., iodide (I⁻) and bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (TFSI⁻)) enhanced ionic conductivity while maintaining vitrimeric properties [2]. These results suggest that a design strategy combining flexible polymer backbones with mixed-anion engineering can yield recyclable, highly conductive polymer electrolyte networks.

Figure 1. Schematic image of ion conductive vitrimers with mixed anion systems.

[1] R. Hirai, T. Hibino, T. Watanabe, T. Teranishi and T. Ono, *RSC Adv.*, **10** (2020) 37743.

[2] H. Tsunekawa, A. Matsumoto, Y. Iida, T. Ono and T. Watanabe, [ChemRxiv \(2026\)](https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2026-12345).

4 Poster

4.1 Poster Session 1

pH-Responsive Hydrogels for the Delivery of Trehalose–Gold Nanoparticles as Inhibitors of Protein Amyloid Fibrillation

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Trehalose is a non-reducing disaccharide that, in addition to its stability and cryoprotective properties, has recently gained prominence as an inhibitor of protein aggregation. This sugar can be chemically functionalized with various groups, and both its analogues and their combinations with gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) have been investigated in neurodegenerative disease research for their potential protective effects, including lifespan extension [1]. We have already synthesized a trehalose- and lipoic acid-functionalized gold nanoparticles (Au@Lip-Tre) with a 10–20 nm gold core to investigate their inhibitory efficiency on protein amyloid fibrillation. The aim of this study was to evaluate the ability of pH-responsive hydrogels to release these particles in gut-like environments, motivated by their potential relevance to gut–brain signaling. Hydrogels were selected as the delivery matrix due to their suitability for controlled drug release and their responsiveness to environmental stimuli such as pH [2].

In this study, a series of pH-responsive hydrogels were synthesized using sodium alginate (Alg), acrylic acid (AAc) as monomers, and derivatives of ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (EGDMA) as cross-linkers. These gels were characterized to assess their pH-responsive swelling behavior and their ability to release Au@Lip-Tre nanoparticles under different pH conditions simulating physiological environments. Formulation-dependent variations indicated that both cross-linker type and alginate incorporation significantly influenced the mechanical properties and swelling behavior. The gold nanoparticles exhibited approximately 50% release from the hydrogel system. Both hydrogel and nanoparticle samples were also examined for cytotoxicity. Overall, the results demonstrate that polymer composition and crosslinking density can be strategically tuned to modulate nanoparticle release profiles, highlighting the potential of these hydrogels for gut-targeted delivery of trehalose-functionalized AuNPs.

[1] Mandal, S., et al., *Langmuir*, 2017. 33(49): p. 13996-14003.

[2] Khalid, I., et al., *Advances in Polymer Technology*, 2018. 37(4): p. 985-995.

Designing Degradable Conjugated Networks: DPP–Thiophene Polymers with Dynamic Imine Backbones

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Conjugated polymer networks that combine electronic functionality, processability, and controllable degradability are emerging as key enabling components for sustainable printed electronics and soft sensing materials or technologies^{1,2}.

In this context, we propose the design and synthesis of a new family of DPP–thiophene polymers incorporating dynamic imine linkages within the backbone and functionalized side chains, intended for future digital light processing (DLP) 3D printing applications.

The molecular architecture based on a DPP core with tuneable alkyl spacers enables balancing solubility, optical absorption, and chain mobility, while aldehyde/amine functionalities facilitate main chain formation through imine bonds and provide a chemical handle to modulate polymer degradability post-application³.

Overall, this work introduces an advanced chemical framework for conjugated networks that integrates organic semiconductors with potential principles of photopolymerizable network engineering, offering a modular platform for future next-generation functional, 3D-printable inks targeting soft sensors, disposable electronics, and transient devices.

References: 1. Ding, Z., Qiao, J., Gao, W., Wang, C. & Guan, Y. *Adv. Mater. Technol.* (2025). 2. Zarei, M., Lee, G., Lee, S. G. & Cho, K.. *Adv. Mater.* 35, (2023). 3. Chakraborty, D. & Plajer, A. J.. *J. Polym. Sci.* 63, 4383–4393 (2025).

Acknowledgements: This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101151987 (BioCP-3DInk). It is also supported by the María de Maeztu Excellence Centre programme (CEX2023-001300-M), funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the ERDF, “A Way of Making Europe”.

Combining Mechanical Experiments and Modeling to quantify the behavior of Collagen Filaments

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Collagen hydrogels are an innovative material formed by integrating collagen, a natural protein, into a hydrogel structure. In vitro collagen molecules can be self-assembled into fibrils by pH and ionic force control. This process is used to form hydrogels with 95% water and 5% collagen, stabilized only by supramolecular interactions. These hydrogels mimic some of the properties of natural tissues, consequently it can have several interesting applications, mainly in the biomedical sector. When developing new materials, understanding the coupling between mechanical properties and their architecture is essential. Modeling provides an analytical description of non-linear mechanical properties.

Figure 1: Coupling microstructure and mechanical properties. (a) Macroscopic image of the hydrogel. (b) Fibrillar microstructure of dried hydrogel. (c) Tensile response under a cyclic uniaxial loading. Test conducted while immersed in PBS1X and at a elongation speed of 0.06 s^{-1} .

The macroscopic scale is advantageous because it is easily observable and testable. This approach provides an overall understanding but doesn't provide the complex details of microscopic mechanisms. Incorporating multi-scale details into a model enhances its reliability and provides a clearer explanation for the overall material behavior observed at larger scales [1]. As a result, this work attempts to build a simple model [2] that considers all the complex phenomena that have been observed experimentally: collagen structural effects, mechano-chemical coupling, inverse poro-elasticity [3], visco-elasticity and viscoplasticity.

[1] J. Brun *et al.*, „Multiscale analysis of biomimetic type I collagen gels under stretch: from molecular collagen to fibrillar network“, *Polymer* **338** (2025).

[2] Kenji Urayama and Toshikazu Takigawa, „Volume of polymer gels coupled to deformation“, *Soft Matter*, **8**, 8017 (2012)

[3] A. Ehret *et al.*, „Inverse poroelasticity as a fundamental mechanism in biomechanics and mechanobiology“, *Nat. Commun.* **8** (2017).

Bio-Based Thiol-Acrylate Vitrimers for Light-Based 3D Printing of Soft Active Materials

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Dynamic covalent networks in 3D printing have emerged as a powerful platform for creating adaptive, reprocessible, and self-healing materials, particularly when combined with sustainable, bio-based precursors [1]. Here, we report the development of bio-based thiol-acrylate vitrimer systems tailored for light-based 3D printing of soft, functional structures [2,3]. The photopolymerizable resin formulations are based on acrylated epoxidized soybean oil (AESBO), a glycerol-derived reactive diluent, and thiol crosslinkers with varying functionalities, enabling precise control over network architecture and viscoelastic behaviour. The thiol-acrylate networks contain dynamic hydroxyl and ester functionalities that facilitate vitrimer behaviour through thermally activated transesterification reactions catalyzed by a tin-based catalyst ($\text{Sn}(\text{Oct})_2$). Notably, $\text{Sn}(\text{Oct})_2$ plays a dual role by promoting efficient bond exchange at elevated temperatures while also improving resin shelf stability by suppressing premature gelation. Digital Light Processing 3D printing was used to fabricate soft structures with high resolution and shape fidelity. Dynamic mechanical analysis revealed that both AESBO content and thiol crosslinker functionality significantly influence the glass transition temperature, mechanical properties, and dynamic adaptability of the networks. Stress relaxation experiments demonstrated rapid network rearrangement, with up to 63% stress dissipation achieved within 2.6-3.6 minutes at temperatures between 180 and 200 °C, while substantially slower relaxation was observed at lower temperatures. The printed vitrimers exhibit efficient self-healing, reprocessability, chemical recyclability, degradability, and advanced shape-memory behaviour, making them ideal for soft active devices and soft robotics applications.

[1] Bijalwan, V., Rana, S., Yun, G.J., Singh, K.P., Jamil, M. and Schlögl, S. *Polymer Reviews*, 64(1), (2024) pp.36-79.

[2] Bijalwan, V., Schlögl, S. and Rana, S. *RSC advances*, 15(58), (2025) pp.49714-49727. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D5RA07879B>

[3] Bijalwan, V. and Rana, S. *Monatshefte für Chemie-Chemical Monthly*, (2025) pp.1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00706-025-03381-x>

Investigating the mechanical properties of amyloid gels through their mesoscopic structure

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Amyloid fibers gels are used as adhesive throughout the marine animal kingdom [1]. These materials have shown a wide range of interesting properties as bio-based underwater adhesives. Upon heating, some proteins are able to refold, then assemble into fibers, forming highly inter-connected networks. We aim to better understand these gel networks across multiple scales to create a bio-inspired underwater adhesive.

We've been able to create hydrogel from Hen Egg-White Lysozyme (HEWL) and Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) within a rheometer. Beyond the analysis of their mechanical and adhesives properties, these gels were characterized through atomic force microscopy, light and X-rays scattering, and scanning electron microscopy to probe their mesoscopic structure. We investigated how key physicochemical parameters, such as pH, ionic strength, protein concentration and behavior in aqueous environments affect network formation and established correlations with resulting mechanical properties.

A deeper understanding of these parameters is the key to formulate and tune these materials for an actual usage.

[1] D. E. Barlow, G.H. Dickinson, and B. Orihuela, [Langmuir 2010, 26 \(9\)](#).

Rheological and thermal evaluation of green nanocomposites based on starch-containing biodegradable polymer

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Reducing environmental impacts significantly requires the substitution of conventional polymers, which originate from non-renewable resources, with bio-based alternatives that are ideally also biodegradable. Mater-Bi® (MB) represents a range of commercially available biopolymers derived from starch, which have been successfully employed in various applications due to their favorable mechanical characteristics, good processability, sufficient thermal stability, and their ability to biodegrade or compost, as well as their compatibility with natural-organic fillers for reinforcement. Zeolite is known for its exceptional properties such as ion-exchange, adsorption, and molecular sieving, enabling its use in water treatment, agricultural practices, and as chemical catalysts. In this study, innovative green composites were developed by combining a starch-based biodegradable polymer (Mater-Bi®, MB) with microporous, crystalline aluminosilicate mineral (zeolite) and/or Sea buckthorns. The optimum processing parameters and various filler concentrations were investigated, and the resulting samples underwent structural, rheological and thermal characterization. The selected filler concentrations demonstrated good processability and adequate dispersion within the polymer matrix.

Acknowledgements:

The grant of the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization, CNCS-UEFISCDI, project number PN-IV-P1-PCE-2023-1968, within PNCDI IV is gratefully acknowledged.

Bio-based Itaconic Acid Hydrogels: Network Formation in Deep Eutectic Solvents

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Hydrogels are three-dimensional polymer networks capable of absorbing large amounts of water while maintaining their structural integrity. Depending on the nature of the crosslinking, they can be classified as chemical, physical, and hybrid. Owing to their high hydrophilicity and tunable network architecture, hydrogels are widely used in agriculture, biomedicine, hygiene, and cosmetics. However, most conventional hydrogels, particularly those based on poly(acrylic acid), are petroleum-derived and non-biodegradable, raising critical environmental concerns.

In this context, this work aims to develop bio-based hydrogels derived from itaconic acid, a monomer obtained from biomass fermentation. Owing to the presence of both a polymerizable vinyl group and hydrophilic carboxylic acid groups, itaconic acid is a promising building block for the design of hybrid hydrogel networks combining covalent bonds and physical interactions such as hydrogen bonding.

Free-radical polymerization of itaconic acid is studied in aqueous medium and in deep eutectic solvents (DES). The DES-based approach is explored as a potentially more sustainable and efficient alternative, allowing the use of high monomer concentrations and accelerating the polymerization kinetics.

A key objective of this study is the synthesis and incorporation of biosourced crosslinkers to tailor crosslinking density and network architecture while increasing bio-based content. Current work focuses on optimizing polymerization conditions and controlling network formation through tailored crosslinking strategies. Structure–property relationships will then be investigated through rheological characterization, swelling behavior analysis, and biodegradation studies under controlled composting conditions.

[1] B. Szczepan, M. Fluder, and I. Maciejaszek, [*Journal of Applied Polymer Science* **131** \(2014\) 40608](#).

[2] J. Mota-Morales, R. Sanchez-Leija, and G. Luna-Barcenas, [*Progress in Polymer Science* **78** \(2018\) 139-153](#).

Thermally induced formation of hydrogels from thermoresponsive POEGMA

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Polymer gels are versatile soft materials widely used in biomedical technologies and soft matter engineering. Among them, thermogels based on synthetic polymers have recently attracted attention for injectable applications and 3D-printable biomaterials. Unlike natural polymer systems, synthetic thermogels offer precise control over molecular architecture and physicochemical properties, resulting in improved mechanical performance [1]. Functionalized thermogels further expand their potential, enabling chemical crosslinking or conjugation with biologically active molecules, which is highly valuable for drug delivery and regenerative medicine.

In this work, thermogels based on functional derivatives of poly(oligo(ethylene glycol) methacrylates) (POEGMA) were designed and studied. Using RAFT polymerization [2], non-toxic, well-defined high-molar mass BAB copolymers ($M_n \approx 120\,000$ g/mol) were synthesized, with a hydrophilic PEG as an A-block and thermoresponsive POEGMA as a B-blocks. The incorporation of hydroxyl-terminated oligo(ethylene glycol) methacrylate units introduced reactive sites for further modification.

Copolymer composition and concentration control phase separation, gelation and physically crosslinked networks formation in water and PBS. Upon heating, POEGMA segments aggregated forming nanoparticles that assembled into a thermogels between 25-55 °C. Rheological tests confirmed mechanically stable networks with storage moduli (G') of 40-3000 Pa. The presence of hydroxyl groups in the polymer structure enabled acrylate functionalization and N,N'-bis(acryloyl)cystamine-mediated dual-crosslinking, combining thermogelation with additional chemical crosslinking.

This study aimed to explore how POEGMA copolymer composition influences thermogelling, dual-crosslinking and gel properties. The materials show potential for injectable hydrogels and 3D-printable soft biomaterials.

- [1] S. Chatterjee, P.C.L. Hui, and C. wai Kan, *Polymers (Basel)*, 10 (2018).
- [2] Y. Yuan, K. Raheja, N.B. Milbrandt, S. Beilharz, S. Tene, S. Oshabaheebwa, U.A. Gurkan, A.C.S. Samia, and M. Karayilan, *RSC Appl. Polym.* 1 (2023) 158–189.

Network Topology and Phase Behavior in Polyisoprene Vitrimers: A Solid-State NMR Study

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Polyisoprene (PI) vitrimers based on telechelic precursors and dynamic imine bonds represent covalent adaptable networks that combine permanent connectivity with thermally activated associative bond exchange. For this system, indications of phase separation (SEM, SAXS) and thermally activated equilibration at ≈ 80 °C have been reported². In this study, time-domain solid-state NMR is employed to probe network structure and phase behavior in detail under different preparation and thermal treatment conditions.

The bulk network structure was analyzed by ¹H double-quantum (DQ) NMR at 80 °C, where segmental mobility allows probing of the equilibrium network structure. The residual dipolar coupling, D_{res} , as a measure of network chain constraints, decreases with increasing molecular weight, consistent with the expected reduction in crosslink density. At the same time, the width of the coupling constant distribution, σ , reflecting network heterogeneity decreases, indicating reduced spatial heterogeneity of network constraints. The elastically inactive (isotropic fraction) increases with molecular weight, consistent with an increasing contribution of dangling chains, loops, and entanglements. In systems exhibiting phase separation, these observables are additionally influenced by contributions from aggregated domains.

To disentangle chemical and topological contributions, swelling experiments were performed. Consistent with the concept of desinterspersion, solvent uptake separates interpenetrated strands, releases packing and entanglement constraints, and dissolves aggregated domains. The resulting phantom reference values reveal that bulk constraints are significantly overestimated due to topological contributions, particularly at low molecular weight. Also, comparison of different preparation routes reveals non-equilibrium structure.

Overall, the results reveal that network constraints in PI vitrimers are strongly influenced by aggregation and topological effects, and that swelling-induced structural changes are not fully reversible within the experimental time scale despite dynamic bond exchange.

[2] [S.Bhaumik, D.Vlassopoulos, *Macromolecules* 2024, 57, 1751-1760](#)

Thermoset meets Thermoplastic: Upcycling PLA in Digital Light Processing 3D Printing of Dynamic Thiol-Ene Composites

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This work explores a covalent adaptable network approach based on dynamic functional groups capable of transesterification.¹ We introduce polylactic acid (PLA) as a functional filler to enhance circularity and reduce material costs. The ester-rich structure of PLA enables dynamic bond exchange at the matrix-filler interface, facilitating interfacial compatibility and stress transfer. At room temperature, PLA acts as a reinforcing phase, enhancing stiffness and creep resistance.² Above the melting point of PLA, the system retains fast stress relaxation behaviour comparable to the pristine vitrimer. This interface-driven dynamic exchange offers a new strategy for designing vitrimer composites and may lower technological barriers for industrial implementation.

[1] D. Reisinger, M. U. Kriehuber, M. Bender, D. Bautista-Anguís, B. Rieger and S. Schlögl, *Advanced Materials* 35, (2023) 2300830.

[2] L. M. A. Joosten, P. Cassagnau, E. Drockenmuller and D. Montarnal, *Adv Funct Materials* 34 (2024) 2306882.

Dynamic Bispiperidone Derivative-Jeffamine-based Poly(imine) Networks

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With regard of their limitation, handling resources in a responsible and sustainable manner is indisputable. To address this, dynamic polymer networks have gained much interest within the last years. While offering the mechanical stability of classical thermosets those materials introduce new pathways to reprocessing, self-healing and recycling triggered by specific stimuli.^[1,2]

Herein, we focus on a bis(piperidin-4-one) and Jeffamine-based poly(imine) network, respective its synthesis, properties, the dynamic features it offers and examine its usability as electrolyte in solid state batteries. Structural characterization of the raw material in comparison to the re-processed material was done *via* ATIR and NMR spectroscopy. Furthermore, thermal and mechanical properties wave been examined in regard to the network density *via* DSC and tensile testing. By adding bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI) as a lithium source, the useability as solid polymer electrolyte was investigated using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy.

[1] S. Maes, N. Badi, J. M. Winne, F. E. Du Prez, *Nat Rev Chem* **2025**, 9, 144–158.

[2] P. Godermajer, A. J. Achazi, D. Mollenhauer, A. Seifert, M. Sommer, *Polym. Chem.* **2024**, 15, 1427–1436.

Linking Soft Gripper Performance to Standardized Material Behavior in SLA-Assisted Hybrid TPU Manufacturing

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This work investigates a hybrid manufacturing route of flexible components from thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) that combines extruder-driven injection with molds printed via Stereolithography (SLA), enabling rapid and low-cost material analysis and prototype production [1].

Two experimental studies were conducted to link processing parameters to material performance. The influence of the manufacturing parameter on crack initiation and growth under DeMattia flex cracking was investigated. Additionally, these parameters were linked to the tensile strength of produced samples. The results show that the hybrid process can achieve strengths comparable to or exceeding conventional injection molding.

To evaluate how material behavior translates to functional soft robotic systems, TPU samples and pneumatic soft gripper were fabricated using the optimized settings. Uniaxial hysteresis measurements were investigated as predictors of long-term gripper fatigue. Additional tests on two silicone rubbers, combined with millions of pneumatic cycling experiments, revealed correlations between material hysteresis and soft gripper angle drift across materials and processing routes.

Overall, the study demonstrates that extrusion-injection into SLA-printed molds is a viable method for producing customized components and that simple material tests can support early prediction of long-term performance in soft robotics.

[1] G. Pelin, M. Sonmez, and C.-E. Pelin, *Polymers* 16 (2024) 1055.

Relationship between Elongation Behavior and Silica Particle Mobility in Composite Elastomers

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Introduction and Aim of this work

Materials combining flexibility and toughness are in high demand for applications in medical devices and soft robotics. We achieved such properties by compositing silica particles with poly(2-methoxyethyl acrylate) (PMEA); however, this behavior has not been reproduced in other polymer systems^[1]. One possible reason for this limitation is the difference in polymer adsorption behavior onto filler particles. In conventional composites, polymers strongly adsorb onto inorganic particles, whereas PMEA shows little affinity for silica surfaces. In this study, aiming to extend this concept to other polymer systems, we sought to establish a method for controlling elongation behavior by regulating polymer-particle adsorption through silica surface modification. We report an approach to transform a composite elastomer based on poly(diethylene glycol) methyl ether methacrylate (PMEO₂MA), which strongly adsorbs onto silica, into a flexible and tough material by reducing the adsorption strength.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1 shows the results of uniaxial tensile tests. The composite containing unmodified silica particles exhibited stiff mechanical behavior, whereas the surface-modified system showed low stress at small strains followed by a pronounced stress increase at higher strains, resulting in flexible and tough elongation behavior. Heat generation during deformation and hysteresis measurements revealed reduced energy dissipation in the modified system, indicating suppressed PMEO₂MA adsorption and reduced interfacial rupture during deformation. Hansen solubility parameter analysis showed decreased hydrogen-bonding interactions between the polymer and modified silica particles. At the presentation, these results will be further discussed to demonstrate the general applicability of this approach to flexible and tough polymer systems.

Fig.1. Stress-strain curves for PMEO₂MA-silica composites elastomers (a) Untreated (b) Treated

[1] F. Asai et al., ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces, 2020, 12, 46621.

Amphiphilic polymer co-networks synthesized via hetero-complementary amide forming reaction of PEG and PCL 4-arm stars

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Amphiphilic co-networks (ACNs) synthesized by hetero-complementary coupling reactions represent a fascinating field of research with regard to their hydrophilic and hydrophobic character. Based on their network structure ACNs are the perfect material for the transport of small molecules. Consequently, ACNs are the most prominent and successful examples as a material for soft contact lenses with extended wear. [1]

To provide such properties, it is essential to control the structural composition during the network synthesis. A successful control of the structure-properties includes a defined length and number of monodisperse polymer strands. Studies by Sakai *et al.* [2] in 2008, based on the end-linking of two 4-armed polyethylene glycol (tetra-PEG), set a milestone to establish model networks.

Our focus lies on the synthesis and characterization of end-functionalized hydrophobic ϵ -polycaprolactone (tetra-PCL) and hydrophilic polyethylene glycol (tetra-PEG) 4-arm stars. In order to achieve ACNs via amide-forming cross-linking strategies, two different systems concerning the oxazinone-amine reaction and the carboxy-amine reaction activated by carbonyldiimidazole (CDI) are pursued. [3] Comparisons of temperature, concentration and solvent were carried out by NMR-spectroscopy as well as the equilibrium volume swelling degrees (Q_v). Information about the degree of cross-linking is obtained from proton low-resolution multiple-quantum NMR investigations. Although the coupling methods differ distinctly, ACNs with similar properties are obtained.

[1] G. Erdodi and J.P. Kennedy, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **2006**, *31*, 1-18.

[2] T. Sakai *et al.*, *Macromolecules* **2008**, *41* (14), 5379-5384.

[3] S. Ihmann *et al.*, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **2026**, submitted.

Development of microgel composite double network gel with low modulus and high mechanical strength

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Double network (DN) gels are synthesized by combining a hard and brittle 1st network with a soft and highly stretchable 2nd network, exhibiting high mechanical toughness [1]. Because of this excellent mechanical toughness, DN gels are expected to be applied as biomaterials such as artificial skin. However, since the rigid 1st network is developed throughout the entire structure, DN gels exhibit a high Young's modulus and show an S-shaped stress–strain curve. In contrast, animal skin exhibits a low Young's modulus and a J-shaped stress–strain curve, allowing it to respond quickly to large deformations [2]. Therefore, it has been difficult for DN gels to exhibit skin-like mechanical properties.

In this study, we developed a microgel composite DN (MCDN) gel composed of microgels formed via radical polymerization of N,N-dimethylacrylamide (DMAAm) and a polyethylene glycol (PEG) matrix formed via end-coupling reactions. The MCDN structure was formed by simultaneously reacting these two components independently. In contrast to conventional DN gels, the MCDN gel exhibited a low Young's modulus and a J-shaped stress–strain curve. It also showed higher mechanical toughness than the PEG single network (SN) gel. Transmission electron microscopy confirmed that PDMAAm microgels on the nanometer scale were formed inside the MCDN gel. In addition, the MCDN gel exhibited hysteresis in stepwise cyclic tensile tests, indicating that its high mechanical toughness was attributed to energy dissipation.

References

- [1] J. P. Gong, Y. Katsuyama, T. Kurokawa, Y. Osada, *Adv. Mater.*, **2003**, 15, 1155-1158.
 [2] F. H. Silver, J. W. Freeman, D. DeVore, *Skin Research and Technology*, **2006**, 7, 18-23

A hierarchical scheme for network homogeneity analysis of polymer gels: A guide to structure control

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Polymer gels inherently include the inhomogeneous network structure, such as spatially inhomogeneous polymer density, dangling chains and loop structure [1]. As these non-ideal structure would lead to deterioration of physical properties, a quantitative framework for evaluating and controlling the network homogeneity has been needed. Recently, evaluation of tetra-PEG gels with controlled network structure revealed that osmotic pressure (Π_{gel}) of polymer gels in a good solvent follows the scaling relationships [2]:

$$\Pi_{\text{gel}} = Ac^n \quad 1$$

where, c is polymer concentration, A is coefficient, and $n = 3\nu/(3\nu - 1) \approx 2.31$ with the excluded volume exponent $\nu \approx 0.588$ in a good solvent. Based on this scaling of osmotic pressure, we established quantification methods to evaluating the structure homogeneity of polymer gels by correlating density homogeneity with the polymer fraction effective for osmotic pressure [3]. Based on this analysis, we herein establish a quantitative framework to evaluate network homogeneity in polymer gels by integrating optical, osmotic, and elastic criteria. The polymer gels synthesized not only by a conventional free radical polymerization (FRP) but also by reversible addition fragmentation chain-transfer (RAFT) polymerization. Adding RAFT agent increase in monomer concentration achieved optical transparency and osmotic homogeneity, respectively. From the perspective of elastic efficiency, the homogeneity of the network topology in osmotically homogeneous gels was further evaluated. As a result, networks prepared by RAFT polymerization exhibit elasticity closer to the ideal proportionality between elastic modulus and cycle rank than those prepared by FRP. These results establish a hierarchical relationship among optical transparency, osmotic homogeneity, and elastic effectiveness in polymer gels, and a guideline to achieve homogeneous networks.

[1] M. Shibayama, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.* **79** (2006) 1799-1819.

[2] T. Yasuda et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **125** (2020) 267801; N. Sakumichi et al., arXiv:2210.15275

[3] R. Ito et al., *Macromolecules*, **58** (2025) 5487-5493.

[4] Y. Yoshikawa et al., *Phys. Rev. X*, **11** (2021) 011045.

Cross-Linked Shape Memory Polymer Blends with Tunable Heating Rate Sensitivity

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Shape Memory Polymers (SMPs) are known to respond to multitude of external triggers, such as heat, light, solvents, and others. Powerful SMPs can be created by crosslinking a polymer to a degree of crosslinking right at the borderline between thermoplastics and elastomers. If done properly this creates an SMP with the properties of the original polymer. Dependent on the amount of phase changes, multiple temporary or intermediate shapes can be observed. The next generation of SMPs will not only be able to respond to a stimulus, such as exceeding a temperature threshold, but also to the rate of change of that stimulus. The few known examples of heating rate sensitive SMPs are homopolymer systems, such as syndiotactic polypropylene [1] and poly(ethylene terephthalate) [2] that cannot be tuned in the heating rate sensitivity, which limits their applicability.

In this work we follow a novel approach to SMPs by co-crosslinking two polymers. This strategy enables precise tailoring of the resulting co-network properties. Using a semi-crystalline polymer, poly(vinylidene fluoride), as the basis while adding a partially miscible amorphous polymer, in this case Poly(2-ethyl-2-oxazilone) enables control over the co-network characteristics. By adjusting the composition and/or the degree of crosslinking, the crystallization kinetics within the co-network can be systematically controlled, thereby allowing the sensor properties to be tailored to specific applications.[3]

[1] R. Hoehner, T. Raidt, F. Katzenberg, J.C. Tiller, [*ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 2016 **8** \(22\), 13684-13687](#)

[2] R. D. L. Jerusalem, M. Maricanov, T. Raidt, F. Katzenberg, J. C. Tiller, [*Macromol. Rapid Commun.* 2024, **45**, 2400346](#)

[3] R. D. L. Jerusalem, M. Maricanov, F. Katzenberg, J. C. Tiller, [*ACS Applied Polymer Materials* 2025 **7** \(2\), 932-937](#)

Construction of Acrylic-Based Homo-IPN and Manifestation of J-shaped Elongation Characteristics

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Biological soft tissues exhibit nonlinear elongation characteristics (J-shaped elongation characteristics), being flexible during initial stretching yet rapidly hardening against excessive deformation. However, reports of polymeric materials exhibiting J-shaped elongation characteristics remain scarce.

We have previously developed materials exhibiting J-shaped elongation characteristics by introducing a crosslinking agent and silica particles into the polymer Poly(2-methoxyethyl acrylate) (PMEA) (Fig. 1). However, considering biological applications, the risk of silica particle migration remains, necessitating material design that reproduces this characteristic using polymers alone.

Using acrylic monomers, we fabricated a homo-interpenetrating polymer network (homo-IPN) structure composed of two distinct networks with different crosslinking densities from the same monomer. We evaluated the elongation characteristics through uniaxial tensile testing (Fig. 2). We then systematically evaluated the effects of parameters such as crosslink density on the J-shaped elongation characteristics. As a result, we report on the guidelines we investigated for achieving nonlinear elongation response solely through polymer network design.

Fig 1. Stress-Strain curves for PMEA-Silica composited elastomers

Fig 2. Stress-Strain curves of IPN, and 1st & 2nd networks

[1] F. Asai et al., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **12** (2020) 46621-46628

Estimation of Shear Modulus during Network Formation Process via Dynamic Light Scattering

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During the gelation process, polymer solutions lose fluidity and the shear modulus increases upon the network formation. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) is a contactless and widely used method for evaluating the gelation process of transparent samples [1]. DLS measures the collective diffusion coefficient D , which describes polymer concentration fluctuations caused by thermal fluctuations of the polymer network. According to the Tanaka-Hocker-Benedek (THB) theory [2], D exhibits a linear relationship with the shear modulus G . While this relationship has been demonstrated for samples after the completion of gelation [3, 4], its validity during the gelation process has not been verified.

In this study, we investigated the relationship between the collective diffusion coefficient D and the equilibrium shear modulus G during the network formation process. We used a tetra-PEG gel system, which allows precise control of the reaction rate of network formation. We measured the time course of D by DLS and that of G by rheometry. Throughout the network formation process for all samples, D increased linearly with G . Analyzing the results with THB theory, we revealed that the $D - G$ relationship depends only on polymer concentration and is independent of molar mass between branching points and the reaction rate.

- [1] M. Shibayama and T. Norisuye, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.* **75** (2002) 641.
 [2] T. Tanaka, L. O. Hocker, and G. B. Benedek, *J Chem. Phys.* **59** (1973) 5151.
 [3] T. Fujiyabu, N. Sakumichi, T. Sakai, *et al.*, *Macromolecules* **52** (2019) 9613.
 [4] T. Fujiyabu, T. Sakai, *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **127** (2021) 237801.

Evaluation of J-shaped elongation characteristics of interpenetrating polymer network gel

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Hydrogels possess flexibility and biocompatibility, but their low mechanical strength has been a challenge for practical applications. To overcome this, introducing an interpenetrating polymer network (IPN) structure into the gel, where two independent polymer networks are physically intertwined, has gained attention. Typical IPN gels combine two types of networks formed from different polymer chains. In uniaxial tensile tests, this IPN gels show a higher initial elastic modulus and high elongation after yielding, resulting in exceptional toughness (Fig.1). Meanwhile, our laboratory discovered that homo-IPN elastomers using poly(2-methoxyethyl acrylate) (PMEA) exhibited J-shaped elongation characteristics: flexible in the initial elongation phase and a significant increase in stress during the later elongation phase. This strain-hardening behavior is also observed in biological soft tissues, enabling them to retain flexibility and toughness while containing large amounts of water.

In this study, we combined polymer networks composed of poly(*N*-isopropylacrylamide) (PNIPA) to prepare a homo-IPN gel. Combining a “hard and brittle” 1st network with high crosslink density and a “flexible and highly extensible” 2nd network with low crosslink density resulted in material properties similar to biological soft tissues. We also investigated changes in mechanical properties by varying the crosslink density of each network. The results revealed that the first network governs the properties up to strain hardening, while the second network influences elongation after stress onset.

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Fig.1 Stress-Strain curves for several typical hydrogels and tissues.

Fig.2 Stress-Strain curves of IPN gels composed of 1st networks with different crosslink densities

Decoupling Crosslink Stability and Network Connectivity in Coiled Coil Crosslinked Hydrogels

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Biomimetic hydrogels serve as a powerful platform for investigating how cells sense and respond to the mechanical cues in their environment. Despite significant progress, the precise mechanisms how cells evaluate the elastic and viscoelastic properties of their surroundings remain incompletely understood. While hydrogels are typically characterized based on their bulk material properties, cells probe these materials on the molecular scale through receptor-ligand interactions. Bridging the gap between molecular-scale interactions and macroscopic material behavior is thus essential for advancing our understanding of cell-material interactions. Inspired by proteins found in the extracellular matrix, we are investigating biomimetic hydrogels crosslinked with coiled coil forming peptides. These modular building blocks enable precise control over their molecular characteristics, such as thermodynamic, kinetic and mechanical stability as well as oligomerization state. Our findings show that the bulk material properties are governed more strongly by network connectivity than crosslink stability. These insights deepen our understanding of how molecular design impacts the macroscopic behavior of hydrogels, opening new avenues for tailoring materials for specific biological applications.

The α -Relaxation as a Novel Shape Memory Switch

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Thermally triggerable shape memory polymers (SMPs) typically exploit the glass transition temperature (T_g) or melting temperature (T_m) as switching mechanisms to transition from one shape to another. However, recent studies on cross-linked polyethylene networks have demonstrated that the α -relaxation temperature (T_α) can also serve as a novel trigger for cross-linkable semi-crystalline thermoplastics. T_α enables the migration of polymer chains through lamellar crystals, allowing for shape switching that is accompanied by a reversible change in morphology.

Initial investigations using cross-linked low-density polyethylene (xLDPE) showed that crystallizing the polymer under strain fixes it in an intermediate shape. Subsequent post-stretching at a temperature between T_α and T_m , followed by cooling, programs a temporary shape. Reheating to this intermediate temperature initiates the retraction back to the intermediate shape. Because the T_α of xLDPE partially overlaps with its broad melting range, the precise contribution of partial crystal melting to this effect could not be fully ruled out. [1]

To isolate the effect of the α -relaxation, cross-linked high-density polyethylene (xHDPE) was investigated. The thermal transitions of xHDPE offer a distinct separation, where T_α is well separated from the onset of melting. The xHDPE networks demonstrated reversible switching between temporary and intermediate shapes exclusively at temperatures above T_α and below T_m . This establishes that the α -relaxation alone drives the shape recovery without any melting, confirming it as a genuine switching mechanism in semi-crystalline SMPs. Furthermore, it enables the complete recovery of plastically deformed morphologies in the solid state, without the need for crystal melting. This concept opens up new possibilities for the design of advanced multi-shape memory materials within a single semi-crystalline network. [2]

[1] M. Maricanov, R. Becker, R. D. L. Jerusalem, J. C. Tiller, and F. Katzenberg, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **141** (2024) e56241

[2] M. Maricanov, R. D. L. Jerusalem, C. Meykranz, L. Schultz, J. C. Tiller, and F. Katzenberg, *Polymer* **341** (2025) 129287

Creation of Nano-Phase Separation Double Network (DN) Hydrogels Using Hydrophobic Monomers

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Double-network (DN) gels are synthesized by combining a brittle 1st network with a flexible 2nd network, which results in materials exhibiting flexibility, high strength and high toughness [1]. The two networks in the DN gels are miscible due to the presence of solvent. DN elastomers are obtained by drying certain types of DN gels. It has been reported that nano-phase-separated structure is generated in the DN elastomers due to the evaporation of solvents that make the two network immiscible [2]. The phase separation unwinds the first network and separates into nano-aggregates and the stretched chains connecting them. This nano-phase separation improves high mechanical performance of the DN elastomers.

In this study, we introduced the nano-phase-separated structure, observed in the DN elastomer, into the DN hydrogels to improve their mechanical properties. Hydrophobic methyl methacrylate and hydrophilic *N,N*-dimethylacrylamide were used as the main precursors of the first and second networks, respectively. DN organogels were synthesized using *N*-methylformamide as a solvent in which these two networks are miscible. The nano-phase-separated DN hydrogels were then obtained by immersion of the organogels in pure water. The obtained gels exhibited two-step yielding on the stress-strain curve and partial recovery of the damage.

References

[1] T. Nakajima *et al.*, *Koubunshi Ronbunshu*, **2008**, 65, 707.

[2] Y. Zheng *et al.*, *Chem. Mater.*, **2021**, 33, 3321.

Heterocycle-based Dynamic Covalent Chemistry for Dynamic Functional Materials

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Dynamic covalent chemistry (DCC), which renders reusable and degradable thermoset polymers, is a promising tool for solving the global problem of plastic pollution. Although DCC can construct covalent adaptable networks (CANs), it rarely introduces additional functionalities, which limits the development of dynamic functional materials. Herein, we develop heterocycle-based dynamic covalent chemistry (H-DCC), in which functional heterocycles act as reversible linkages while simultaneously conferring inherent properties to the resulting materials.^[1] As a proof-of-concept study, we demonstrate the reversibility of the aza-Michael addition reaction between dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-thione (DHPMT) and electron-deficient olefins (See Scheme). This approach produces a degradable linear polymer as well as recyclable and self-healable crosslinked polymers similar to traditional CANs, but the heterocycles simultaneously provide excellent ultraviolet-blocking, high-energy blue light-attenuation, and tunable fluorescence and phosphorescence. Such properties integration remains challenging with traditional DCC. Therefore, besides providing insights into heterocycle-based dynamic reactions, this study may also prompt the development of new DCC and dynamic functional materials.

a Heterocycle-based dynamic covalent chemistry

b Dynamic functional materials

Adaptable network: • Reusable • Self-healable • Degradable

Other functions: • Light-blocking • Luminescence ...

[1] Z. Ma, S. Pan, Y. Yang et al. *Nature Communications* **16** (2025) 3679.

Wrapping of polymeric particles at bio-membranes

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The wrapping of nano- and microparticles is a fundamentally important pathway for their cellular uptake and depends on the physicochemical properties of both particle and membrane. Polymeric gels are a versatile class of materials whose elastic properties can be tuned in a wide range from ultrasoft to hard by changing the density of cross-linkers. Using spring networks for the microgels and triangulated surfaces for the membranes, we study microgel wrapping with computer simulations [1]. The interplay of microgel and membrane deformation is controlled by the competition between microgel elasticity and membrane bending rigidity. Compared with hard particles, the range of adhesion strengths for which partial-wrapped states are stable is enlarged. Volume and surface area of partial-wrapped microgels can be significantly reduced compared with those of free microgels. Understanding microgel wrapping can help us to design polymeric particles for biomedical applications, e.g., as membrane markers and targeted drug delivery vectors.

[1] T. Debnath, J. Midya, T. Auth, and G. Gompper, *ACS Macro Letters* 14 (2025) 1412-1417.

Creation of a hydrogel enhanced in toughness through increased ionic crosslinking by stretching

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Polymer-crowded hydrogels, unlike conventional high-water-content gels, exhibit excellent mechanical properties and unique functionalities due to the close proximity of polymer strands, which leads to the formation of numerous intermolecular interactions. In particular, their properties will be governed by interplay between the lifetime of noncovalent interactions and the timescale of deformation. In this presentation, we report a stretch-induced toughening hydrogels utilizing polyacrylic acid (PAAc) gel into calcium acetate (CaAc) solution.

Above a critical concentration of calcium acetate, the gels exhibit pronounced whitening at a certain strain rate, accompanied by a substantial enhancement in mechanical response. Furthermore, an increase in ionic crosslink density is observed during this process. This phenomenon is expected to function as a self-toughening mechanism in fracture events such as tearing, where efficient strengthening at the crack tip suppresses crack propagation.

[1] Liu et al., *Science*, **2021**, 372, 1078-1081

[2] Jiayu Wu et al., *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **2023**, 33, 2210395

[3] T. Nonoyama, et al., *Adv. Mater.*, **2020**, 32, 1905878

Coordination-Driven Vitrimers from Functionalized Polyisoprene: Design, Synthesis, and Dynamic Behavior

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Vitrimers are promising recyclable and sustainable polymer materials, and their properties depend strongly on the chemistry that governs network rearrangement. In this work, we investigate polyisoprene and polyisoprene-polystyrene block copolymers that were modified through several functionalization pathways, such as the formation of Schiff bases, vinylogous urethane linkages, or other synthetic routes, to introduce coordinating functionalities.

These groups can undergo the typical reversible exchange reactions responsible for the vitrimer properties. In our work, we also investigate the influence of transition metal cations on the exchange dynamics, as such cations are known to form coordination complexes with these functional groups. Structural, thermal, mechanical, and rheological analyses were used to study how the functionalization method and the amount of coordinating groups influence exchange reactions in the network and the resulting vitrimer-like flow behavior. This study demonstrates how combining tailored polymer functionalization with coordination chemistry enables the development of tunable, reprocessable, and sustainable elastomeric materials.

Renewable urethane vitrimers for sustainable additive manufacturing

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Additive manufacturing methods such as vat photopolymerization (VP) are expected to play a major role in industry in the near future. However, VP is far from sustainable, mostly owing to its fossil-based resins and its non-recyclable products [1]. Vitrimers are stimuli-responsive polymer networks that can undergo bond exchange reactions under specific conditions such as high temperature. This characteristic gives vitrimers the ability to flow on demand, while they behave closely to regular thermosets (permanently crosslinked networks) under standard conditions [2]. Their controlled flow could be key in improving the reprocessability of VP products and introducing circularity. In this work, we focused on improving the sustainability of VP products by developing renewable urethane methacrylate resins that can be used to print recyclable vitrimer materials [3]. The materials can then be recycled using a closed-loop process, where they are printed repeatedly via fused deposition modeling (FDM).

[1] V. S. D. Voet, J. Guit, K. Loos, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* 42(3) (2021) 2000475.

[2] W. Denissen, J. M. Winne, F. E. Du Prez, *Chem. Sci.* 7(1) (2016) 30–38.

[3] K. Janssen, G. H. M. Schnelting, M. Waterink; J. Guit, J. Hul, C. Ye, K. Loos, V. S. D. Voet, *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* 309(6) (2024) 2400036.

Thermoelastic Mayer's Relation: Isobaric-to-Isochoric Transformation in Thermoelasticity

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Thermoelastic experiments provide a standard method for separating the elastic force of polymer networks into entropic and energetic contributions. The intrinsic entropic elasticity is defined under isochoric conditions; however, experiments are almost always performed at constant pressure. Transforming isobaric data to their isochoric equivalents has traditionally relied on microscopic models such as Gaussian chains and affine deformation [1], which break down when solvent-polymer interactions are significant [2], deformations are large [3], or the material exhibits elastic anisotropy [4].

Here we establish a purely macroscopic thermodynamic framework for this transformation. By extending the framework of Mayer's relation transforming heat capacities between isobaric and isochoric conditions [5], we derive thermoelastic transformation functions that quantify the difference between isobaric and isochoric measurements without invoking any microscopic network model. These functions are reformulated in an experimentally accessible form via a modified Elliott-Lippmann anisotropy factor [6]. Explicit formulas are derived for representative experimental geometries and for nonlinear constitutive models, including the neo-Hookean, Mooney-Rivlin, and Yeoh models, enabling accurate correction even under large deformations.

Furthermore, we show that the well-known thermoelastic inversion observed under isobaric conditions arises as an apparent effect of the isobaric-to-isochoric transformation, provided that the thermal expansion coefficient is positive and the material is nearly incompressible in the tensile regime, conditions satisfied by most polymer networks. This framework provides a robust basis for reanalyzing thermoelastic data across diverse polymer networks, such as rubbers and gels.

[1] A. Ciferri *et al.*, J. Am. Chem. Soc. 83, 1015 (1961). [2] Y. Yoshikawa *et al.*, Phys. Rev. X 11, 011045 (2021). [3] R. L. Anthony *et al.*, J. Phys. Chem. 46, 826 (1942). [4] K. Sano *et al.*, Chem., Int. Ed. Engl. 57, 2532 (2018). [5] L. D. Landau and E. M. Lifshitz, *Statistical Physics* (Butterworth-Heinemann, 1984). [6] D. R. Elliott and S. A. Lippmann, Rubber Chem. Technol. 18, 579 (1945).

Surface Engineering of MWCNTs via Gamma Irradiation and Functionalization for Advanced Nanocomposite Materials

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The exceptional mechanical, thermal, and chemical properties of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) make them ideal candidates for advanced materials. However, their potential is limited by strong van der Waals forces, leading to tube bundling and poor interfacial bonding within polymer matrices. This study explores surface engineering strategies to enhance the dispersion and functionality of MWCNTs in nanocomposites.

A key focus of this study is on the use of gamma irradiation as a solvent-free modification method. Structural analysis, including Raman spectroscopy, XRD, and TEM, revealed that exposing MWCNTs to irradiation doses between 100 kGy and 150 kGy in an O₂-rich environment introduces critical surface defects and functional groups, which lead to significant tube disentanglement without compromising the fundamental tubular integrity [1]. These modifications are essential for enhancing the compatibility of MWCNTs with both hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymers.

The modified MWCNTs significantly enhanced the mechanical and thermal properties of polymer systems. In a PMMA/PEG matrix, a nanofiller composed of amino-modified MWCNTs (PDA-CNT) and nanodiamonds (NDs) increased the tensile strength from 21.79 MPa to 29.4 MPa and elastic modulus from 1083.84 MPa to 1419.41 MPa at 5 wt% loading [2]. Thermal stability (T₁₀) also improved from 390°C to 515°C [2]. In addition to structural reinforcement, surface-engineered MWCNTs enable applications such as environmental remediation, pesticide delivery, and swelling kinetics control [1-4]. Overall, the results demonstrate that targeted surface engineering of MWCNTs is an effective route toward high-performance multifunctional nanocomposites.

[1] S. Bibi, M. Nawaz, T. Yasin, and M. Riaz, *J. Polym. Res.* **23** (2016) 154.

[2] S. Jabeen, S. Gul, A. Kausar, B. Muhammad, M. Nawaz, K. M. Saud, and M. Farooq, *Polym.-Plast. Technol. Mater.* **58** (2019) 1810.

[3] S. Bibi, T. Yasin, S. Hassan, M. Riaz, and M. Nawaz, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* **46** (2015) 359.

[3] A. Bibi, S. Rehman, R. Faiz, T. Akhtar, M. Nawaz, and S. Bibi, *Mater. Res. Express* **6** (2019) 085065.

Molecular simulation of electroadhesion

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Electroadhesion, or adhesion induced by an electric field, occurs between otherwise non-adhesive hydrogels; one cationic and the other anionic. After the application of an electric field (10 V) for several seconds, the hydrogels adhere to each other. The adhesion persists until an electric field of opposite polarity is applied. This phenomenon can be used in various biomedical applications; for example, sutureless repairs in tissue engineering and surgery [1]. Despite very promising applications, the molecular mechanism of electroadhesion is not yet understood. This lack of understanding limits the possibilities for a rational choice of suitable hydrogel materials for electroadhesion to various surfaces.

Here, we present preliminary results of a molecular simulation of two surfaces coated with oppositely charged polyelectrolyte brushes that interact with each other. Our model is a simplified representation of two hydrogels in contact during electroadhesion. Using this model, we predict how the local structure of the interface is affected by bringing these surfaces close to each other and how the potential of mean force depends on the separation between these surfaces. Furthermore, we analyze the influence of polymer chain grafting densities, applied electric field intensity, and salt concentration on the system's behavior.

References

- (1) Borden, L. K.; Gargava, A.; Raghavan, S. R. *Nature Communications* **2021**, *12*, 4419.

Effect of electrolyte structure on the Piezoionic Effect in Hydrogel

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The piezoionic effect generates an internal potential difference due to deformation-induced disparities in ion mobility [1]. We considered that this electrical response originates from the internal ionic structure. Therefore, we focused on low-molecular-weight electrolytes and cross-linked polyelectrolytes. We hypothesized that fixed charges within the material accentuate the mobility difference between immobilized ions and counterions, thereby increasing the generated voltage. This study aims to elucidate the influence of the electrolyte structure within hydrogels on the piezoionic effect.

To evaluate electrolyte structural effects, we measured the generated voltage and current in a double-network (DN) gel [2] and polyacrylamide gels containing low-molecular-weight electrolytes (NaCl or NaAMPS). The DN gel exhibited the highest voltage, driven by the substantial mobility disparity between its fixed polyelectrolyte network and counterions. Conversely, the fully mobile state of ions in the NaCl- and NaAMPS-PAAm gels minimized this disparity, yielding lower voltages. Regarding current, the NaCl-PAAm gel peaked, whereas the DN and NaAMPS-PAAm gels showed lower values. Because current generation relies on internal conductivity, the smaller ionic radius of NaCl promotes higher conductivity and lower resistance. We attribute the lower currents in the DN and NaAMPS-PAAm gels primarily to their larger ion sizes, which diminish ionic conductivity.

[1] Y. Dobashi, *et al.*, *Science* **376**, (2022) 502–507.

[2] J. P. Gong, *et al.*, *Adv. Mater.* **15**, (2003) 1155–1158.

From Clusters to Networks: Grafting-Density-Controlled Assembly of Polymer-Grafted Nanoparticles

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Polymer-grafted nanoparticles (PGNPs) combine the optical, magnetic or electronic functionality of inorganic cores with the elasticity and responsiveness of polymers. This hybrid character provides multiple, orthogonal design parameters for controlling the structure and properties of PGNP-based materials [1-4]. In this work, we study spherical nanoparticles grafted with amphiphilic diblock copolymers composed of two blocks with opposing solvent affinities, enabling reversible transitions between assembly and disassembly states [5].

In the assembly state, the inner polymer blocks are solvophilic, while the outer are solvophobic and collapse into attractive patches; in the disassembly state, the inner blocks form a dense polymer shell surrounded by a stabilizing hydrophilic corona. To access device-relevant time and length scales, we develop a bottom-up coarse-grained (CG) model, in which PGNPs in the assembly state are represented as particles with flexible, spring-tethered attractive patches. By varying the grafting density, we control the number of effective patches per particle, which strongly influences the assembly pathway and resulting structures. At low volume fractions, systems with fewer patches predominantly form finite clusters, whereas higher patch numbers promote the formation of percolated, gel-like networks.

[1] C. Bilchak et al., ACS Nano (2020).

[2] M. Moinuddin et al., Macromolecules (2022).

[3] J. Midya et al., ACS Nano (2020).

[4] C. Rossner, Macromolecular Rapid Communications (2025).

[5] M. Sebastian et al., ChemPhysChem (2024).

Structural design of organic/inorganic nanohybrids based on sustainable polysaccharides and inorganic nanoparticles

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Organic/inorganic nanohybrid materials are a combination of inorganic nanoparticles and organic polymers, representing improved performance compared to conventional polymeric materials [1]. This study focuses on the design and synthesis of multicomponent hybrid gels and organic/inorganic nanohybrid materials, with a particular emphasis on polysaccharide-based nanocomposites. Combination of nanohybrid structures with hybrid gels brings the extraordinary properties of both types of materials together, offering significant opportunities to enhance their physical and mechanical characteristics [2].

The study is based on the design of bionanocomposites using sodium alginate (NaAlg) as host biopolymer and *N,N*-dimethylacrylamide (DMAAm) and sodium acrylate (NaA) as functional monomers, *N,N'*-methylenebisacrylamide as crosslinking monomer and bentonite as filler molecule. In this context, anionic hybrid gels designed based on the hypothesis that bentonite, which consists of montmorillonite as an inorganic component and has a layered silica structure, can be mixed or interlayered with polymer systems to form good matrices for the preparation of hybrid structures. Furthermore, this study investigates the effect of crosslinking polymerization temperature on the mechanical properties and swelling behavior of hybrid P(DMAAm/NaA)-NaAlg/Bentonite gels. Five different polymerization temperatures, that is, -18, 1, 5, 24 and 60 °C chosen for the preparation of cryogels and hydrogels. Moreover, freeze-thawing technique utilized to study the effects of the incorporation of freeze-thaw cycles on the measurable differences in network structure and functional properties with gels prepared without freeze-thaw treatment which serves as controls. For this purpose, freeze-thaw cycles carried out at identical freezing temperature of -18 °C and thawing temperatures are selected as 1, 5, 24 and 60 °C in order for gels prepared without freeze-thaw treatment to serve as controls. The prepared hybrid hydrogels were systematically investigated in terms of swelling behavior, mechanical strength, and chemical characterization, including FTIR, XRD, and TGA analyses.

The combination of renewable polysaccharides, synthetic monomers, and inorganic nanofillers demonstrates an effective strategy for designing alkylacrylamide-based bionanocomposites with potential applications in biomedical, environmental engineering.

[1] Kalia, S., Haldorai, Y. (ed.). *Organic-Inorganic Hybrid Nanomaterials*. New York, NY, USA, Springer (2015).

[2] Ikake, H., Hara, S., & Shimizu, S. [Polymers 14 \(2022\) 3247](#).

Optimized Additive manufacturing of styrene-ethylene-propylene-styrene block copolymer via Direct Ink Writing

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Direct ink writing, as an additive manufacturing technique for thermoplastic elastomers (TPEs) has garnered significance via overcoming the challenge of filament buckling owing to their soft and flexible structure. This work is primarily focused on the DIW of styrene-ethylene-propylene-styrene (SEPS) triblock copolymer, a promising TPE known for its superior elasticity, thermoplastic processability. Despite its several advantages, SEPS remains underexplored in DIW-based fabrication. This is the first work focusing on the development of a print-ready SEPS ink by selecting toluene as a suitable solvent based on Hansen Solubility Parameter analysis, as a crucial step in DIW. Rheological investigations were also performed to study the ink behaviour with varying solvent concentration. Viscosity, thixotropic recovery, and extrudate shape stability revealed that the inks containing 35–40 wt% SEPS were suitable for additive manufacturing, exhibiting anisotropic shrinkage in different directions upon solvent evaporation. The DIW-printed parts exhibited high elongation at break $\sim 1000\%$ and a mean tensile strength ~ 6.8 MPa with a Shore A hardness of ~ 62 . This work highlights the potential of DIW-based additive manufacturing of SEPS-TPE parts with excellent physical and mechanical properties.

- [1] C. M. Hansen, Hansen solubility parameters: a user's handbook, 2nd ed. CRC press Taylor and Francis group, 2007.
 [2] S. S. Banerjee, S. Burbine, N. K. Shivaprakash, and J. Mead, *Polymers*, **11(2)** 2019. doi: 10.3390/polym11020347.
 [3] A. Kumar, D. K. Rana, P. M. Pandey, C. Sasmal, and S. S. Banerjee, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.*, **2400409** (2025), 1–11. doi: 10.1002/macp.202400409.

Ultrasonication-Controlled Self-Assembly of Polymer-Capped Gold Nanorods and Nanoparticles

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Polymer-capped metal nanoparticles can self-assemble into well-defined architectures exhibiting tunable plasmonic coupling and collective optical responses^[1,2]. However, achieving controlled structural transformations of nanoparticles through self-assembly at the nanoscale remains a challenge. In this work, we present a hydrogen bond (H-bond) driven controllable self-assembly system composed of polymer-functionalized gold nanorods (AuNRs) and gold nanoparticles (AuNPs). H-bonds form between PEG and P(St_{0.7}-r-HSt_{0.3})_m grafted on the surfaces of AuNPs and AuNRs, which promote the attachment of multiple AuNPs around individual AuNRs. Importantly, the self-assembly process can be regulated by ultrasonication. Ultrasonication strengthens the H-bond interactions within the clusters and decreases the interparticle distance, thereby tuning the spectral position. This work provides a controllable strategy for constructing AuNR–AuNP self-assemblies and highlights their potential in mode-selective plasmonic coupling and nanoscale sensing.

- [1] Y. Cai, P. Vana *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* **62**(47) (2023): e202309798
[2] Y. Cai, S. Sarkar, Y. Peng, TAF König, P. Vana, *ACS nano* **18**(45) (2024): 31360-31371.

Mechanical Studies of Amphiphilic tPEG-tPCL Metallo-Supramolecular Polymer Networks

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Metallo-Supramolecular Polymer Networks (MSPNs) have emerged as a versatile platform for the design and construction of tailor-made functional and responsive materials, due to their dynamic structures and tunable properties. While the design of soft matter remains a key challenge, such networks offer great adaptability and show promising behavior for use in drug delivery, sensors, catalysis and imaging. [1] Based on pioneering studies concerning tetra-arm polyethylene glycol (tPEG) MSPNs [2], in our work we focus on mixed networks formed with half of the network polymer being tetra-arm poly- ϵ -caprolactone (tPCL). Gels are formed from end-capped star polymers with literature known “slim” ligands 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen) and 2,2':6',2"-terpyridine (Tpy), sterically demanding “bulky” ligands 2,9-dimesityl-1,10-phenanthroline (DMPHEN) and 6,6"-di(anthracen-9-yl)-4'-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-2,2':6',2"-terpyridine (DATpy) and various metal ions (Pd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+}).

Using small angle oscillatory rheology, the resulting gels are analyzed and compared to literature known tPEG-tPEG analogues considering their overall network percolation, macroscopic network mobility, and network stability. First insights reveal overall comparability for slim-slim type tPEG-tPCL gels while metal ion selective loss of network percolation, due to selective complexation motifs, is noted for self-sorting complexation approaches (bulky-slim). The herein reported gels pave the way for tailor-made amphiphilic dynamic soft materials with great potential for external stimuli responsiveness and highly modular material design. [3]

[1] D. Hassanian-Moghaddam, M. A. Aboudzadeh, M. Ahmadi *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **540** (2025) 216796.

[2] M. Ahmadi, A. Poater and S. Seiffert, *Macromolecules* **56** (2023) 1390–1401.

[3] R. D. Mukhopadhyay and A. Ajayaghosh, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **52** (2023) 8635-8650.

Phase-Separation and Mechanical Properties of High Molecular Weight Acrylate Block Copolymers with High Polydispersity

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High molecular weight acrylic block copolymers with broad polydispersity have been synthesized by RAFT polymerization in solution. These block copolymers consist of a series of copolymers with varying numbers of blocks. In theory, such block copolymers with high molecular weight and broad polydispersity face challenges in achieving homogeneous phase separation.[1] For this reason, scientific research has mostly focused on monodisperse block copolymers. However, block copolymers with broad polydispersity can exhibit special properties that are of great importance for some applications.[2]

A series of different block copolymers with variations in the A-block were analyzed by SEC for molecular weight distribution (MWD) and by SAXS and AFM for phase morphology in bulk and on the surface. Preliminary results indicate that, despite the broad polydispersity, these block copolymers exhibit distinct phase separation and diverse morphologies. SAXS data reveal well-defined microphase separation, while AFM images show varied surface structures, suggesting successful phase separation. In addition to the phase morphology, the viscoelastic properties were also investigated.

[1] Au Kim, I.; Li, S. Recent progress on polydispersity effects on block copolymer phase behavior. *Polymer Reviews* 2019, 59 (3), 561-587. DOI: 10.1080/15583724.2019.1579227.

[2] Hillmyer, M. A. Polydisperse block copolymers: Don't throw them away. *Journal of Polymer Science Part B: Polymer Physics* 2007, 45 (24), 3249-3251. DOI: 10.1002/polb.21323.

From Bathroom Sealants to 3D-Printable Double Network Granular Elastomers

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Elastomers can be formulated as double-network granular elastomers (DNGEs), enabling 3D printing via direct ink writing (DIW). DNGEs are prepared by swelling elastomer microparticles in a precursor solution for a secondary elastomer network, which is crosslinked after 3D printing [1]. This crosslinking step is typically achieved through UV or thermal initiation. Unfortunately, UV initiation is ineffective for opaque materials, while thermal initiation leads to collapse of the printed structures. Here, moisture from ambient air is used to crosslink DNGEs, enabling room-temperature curing even in the presence of fillers. These materials are envisaged for future applications in soft robotics.

[1] E. Baur, B. Tiberghien, and E. Amstad, [Advanced Materials](#) **36** (2024) [2313189](#).

Segregation Kinetics of Biphasic Polymer Brushes Grafted from Spherical Substrates: Insights from Simulation

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Polymer brushes grafted onto curved substrates represent a minimal model system for understanding how confinement and geometry regulate phase separation. While equilibrium morphologies of such systems have been widely explored, their nonequilibrium coarsening dynamics remain largely unresolved. Here, we study the phase-separation kinetics of symmetric, chemically incompatible A- and B-type homopolymer brushes randomly grafted onto spherical substrates using coarse-grained dissipative particle dynamics simulations. We quantify the morphological evolution by the time-dependent growth of a characteristic domain length. We show that spherical confinement strongly influences domain coarsening, slowing the power-law growth at early times. At later times, a gradual crossover to a pronounced reduction in growth rate is demonstrated. By systematically varying chain length, grafting density, and solvent quality across solvophilic to solvophobic conditions, we demonstrate controlled tuning of cluster connectivity, interfacial sharpness, and surface microsegregation patterns. Our results identify solvent selectivity and grafting density as decisive parameters governing kinetic arrest and domain stabilization in binary polymer brushes. The results provide mechanistic insight into microphase separation on modified surfaces and offer design principles for patchy colloids, biointerfacial architectures, and stimuli-responsive polymer coatings.

[1] J. A. Johnson, M. G. Finn, J. T. Koberstein, and N. J. Turro, *Macromolecules* 40 (2007) 3589–3598.

[2] X. Yong, O. Kuksenok, and A. C. Balazs, *Polymer* 72 (2015) 217–225.

[3] R. D. Groot and P. B. Warren, *J. Chem. Phys.* 107 (1997) 4423–4435.

Thermo-Oxidative Aging and Reprocessability in Epoxy-Based Vitrimers Cured with Disulfide Hardeners

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Epoxy-based vitrimers cured with disulfide hardeners are attractive model systems for studying the interplay between dynamic covalent network rearrangement and irreversible chemical aging. While disulfide exchange facilitates network rearrangement at comparatively moderate temperatures, thereby enabling stress relaxation, repair, and reprocessing, the sulfur-containing network structure may also be particularly susceptible to thermo-oxidative exposure. For engineering applications, this creates a fundamental challenge: the material response is governed not only by reversible bond exchange but also by irreversible aging processes that may progressively alter the network architecture and thereby affect subsequent reprocessability.

The contribution focuses on the lifecycle-dependent material behavior of epoxy-based disulfide vitrimers under thermal and thermo-oxidative conditions. Particular attention is given to how aging influences thermo-mechanical properties and long-term deformation behavior, and to how these changes evolve after mechanical recycling and reprocessing by hot pressing. In this context, the key question is whether vitrimer-specific network adaptivity remains sufficiently effective once the material has undergone prior service-related aging, or whether irreversible degradation increasingly dominates the response.

By linking aging state, thermo-mechanical performance, creep-related behavior, and reprocessed material properties, the study aims to contribute to a more differentiated understanding of reversibility in disulfide-based vitrimer networks. This perspective is particularly relevant for assessing the potential and limitations of such materials in engineering applications where both long-term stability and post-use reprocessability are required.

Photocrosslinked Water-in-Water Emulsion Hydrogels: A Novel Bio-ink for 3D Bioprinting

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Regenerative medicine aims to develop functional systems by integrating cells, scaffolds, and signaling factors. Although 3D in vitro models, particularly cellular spheroids, provide a superior biomimetic bridge over traditional 2D cultures, their high-throughput production and structural preservation during bioprinting remain significant technical challenges. To overcome these limitations, we developed a high-performance water-in-water (w/w) emulsion bio-ink.

Introducing a "spheroid formation within w/w emulsions" strategy—a first in the literature—this platform offers a scalable, robust solution for personalized drug screening and functional tissue engineering. The methodology utilizes a biphasic system with a continuous gelatin methacrylate (GelMA) outer phase and an aqueous polyethylene glycol (PEG) inner phase containing the cellular cargo [1]. While the outer phase undergoes photo-polymerization to form a protective, ECM-mimetic network, the inner phase provides a localized microenvironment that facilitates spontaneous spheroid organization within the aqueous droplets. This emulsion bio-ink, integrated with extrusion-based bioprinting, enables the high-fidelity fabrication of personalized tissue scaffolds.

1. Yue, K., et al., *Synthesis, properties, and biomedical applications of gelatin methacryloyl (GelMA) hydrogels*. *Biomaterials*, 2015. **73**: p. 254-271.

Self-growing of DN gels with glucose oxidase in the presence of oxygen

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The self-growing capabilities of double-network hydrogels (DN gels) under mechanical stimuli rely on mechanoradicals generated by homolytic bond cleavage in the brittle first network, which lead synthesis of an additional polymer network when monomers are present in the gel ^[1]. However, realizing this growth in open air remains challenging due to radical deactivation by oxygen through peroxidation. Herein, we developed a glucose oxidase incorporating double-network hydrogel (GOx-DN gel) to address this limitation.

Glucose oxidase was effectively trapped by the polymerization of the second network with smaller mesh size than diameter of glucose oxidase. When the GOx-DN gel is immersed in a glucose-containing monomer solution, the dissolved oxygen is depleted through glucose oxidation, effectively preserving mechanoradicals activity. Such enzyme introducing DN gels with pre-fed glucose deplete dissolved oxygen fast by glucose oxidation, effectively preserving mechanoradicals activity. Moreover, glucose oxidization persists until all the glucose is consumed, allowing polymerization to tolerate continuously dissolving oxygen for longer periods. Concurrent introduction of sodium pyruvate enables the removal of hydrogen peroxide byproduct via its conversion into inert carbon dioxide.

GOx-DN gel demonstrates effective mechanical strengthening after cyclic loading in open air for the first time. This oxygen-manipulation strategy enables air-compatible mechanoresponsive growth of DN gels, paving the way for developing bio-inspired self-adaptive materials through structural reorganization.

[1] Matsuda, T. et al., Science, 2019, 363, 6426.

Processing-Dependent Morphology and Rheology of Polystyrene-Based Dynamic Network/Thermoplastic Blends

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Blending thermosets with thermoplastic matrices offers a promising approach to obtain materials that combine the advantageous properties of both classes. However, retaining processability and achieving high compatibility between the blend components remain challenging due to the permanent network structure of thermosets and their chemical disparity with thermoplastics. These limitations can be addressed by using a dynamic covalent network (DCN), as the thermoset component, as its reconfigurable topology can promote flow and entanglements with the thermoplastic phase.^[1]

Herein, a polystyrene-based DCN is used as a blend partner for a polystyrene matrix. Notably, despite the chemical similarity between the two components, phase separation occurs from the micro- to nanometer scale. Variation of preparation and processing methods resulted in distinct blend morphologies. Microscopic analyses revealed a direct correlation between the degree of dispersion of the minor phase creep resistance at higher temperature.

These findings demonstrate that the degree of phase separation critically governs the rheological and mechanical properties and should be carefully considered when incorporating dynamic networks into a thermoplastic matrix for reinforcement or compatibilization.^[2]

References

- [1] Joosten, L. M. A.; Cassagnau, P.; Drockenmuller, E.; Montarnal, D. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 2024, 34 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202306882>
- [2] Formon, G. J. M.; Storch, S.; Delplanque, A. Y. G.; Bresson, B.; Van Zee, N. J.; Nicolaÿ, R. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 2023, 33 (52). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202306065>

SI-ATRP from Hydrophilic Fe₃O₄ Nanoparticles: Linking Surface Initiator Density to Grafting Density, Polymer Brush Conformation, and Responsiveness

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Controlling polymer brush growth on nanoparticle (NP) surfaces and understanding how surface initiator density influences grafting density and chain conformation remain key challenges, particularly for hydrophilic systems compared to widely studied hydrophobic substrates [1]. Here, hydrophilic tetraethylene glycol (TREG)-stabilized Fe₃O₄ NPs (IO NPs) were employed as a model to study how interfacial initiator loading governs polymer brush growth under confinement.

A pre-synthesized ATRP initiator was immobilized on IO NPs of size ~ 8nm, followed by SI-ARGET ATRP. Initiator loading was systematically varied to tune the polymer grafting density while maintaining identical polymerization conditions. Using poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) as a non-pH responsive model [2], this enabled isolation of interfacial effects and direct evaluation of how initiator density influences chain propagation from curved surfaces. Initial studies yielded grafting densities of approximately 0.02–0.07 chains/nm². These were quantified using TGA, MP-AES, and STEM-derived particle size, GPC molecular weight data, enabling comparison across different initiator loading ranges.

The platform was extended to pH-responsive poly(2-(diethylamino)ethyl methacrylate) (PDEAEMA) brushes, where grafting density strongly influenced chain conformation and responsiveness. DLS revealed density-dependent swelling, with enhanced chain extension at lower pH due to protonation of tertiary amine groups; higher grafting densities led to significantly amplified size changes. These results demonstrate that grafting density, tuned via initiator loading, governs the structural evolution and functional response of polymer brushes on hydrophilic IO NPs surfaces.

[1] W.L.Chen, R. Cordero, H. Tran, and C. K. Ober, *Macromolecules* 50 (2017) 4089-4113.

[2] S. K. Jewrajka, U. Chatterjee, and BM Mandal, *Macromolecules* 37 (2004) 4325-4328.

Design strategy of creating nanosilica-integrated poly(acrylic acid sodium salt)/polyacrylamide hybrid gels

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Bionanocomposite materials are hybrid systems that incorporate an organic or inorganic filler with a biopolymer matrix containing at least one nanoscale component [1]. Based on recent developments in nanotechnology, the production of hydrogel bionanocomposites by incorporating inorganic nanofillers into gel systems has recently attracted great interest in innovative material design. Hydrogel bionanocomposites provide various unique features over traditional hydrogels, including high mechanical and thermal strength and toughness [2].

This study hypothesizes that the unique properties of anionic comonomers can be combined with the extraordinary properties of nanoparticles to create hybrid bionanocomposite gels. In materials research, the focus is particularly on the production of anionic engineered systems, with a particular emphasis on the design of advanced biomaterials possessing controlled physical, elastic, and structural properties. In this context, nanosilica-integrated poly(acrylic acid sodium salt)/polyacrylamide, SiO₂-PSA/PAAm, hybrid gels were prepared at two different polymerization temperatures by free radical crosslinking polymerization of AAm with anionic linear PSA chains. The chemical structures of the hybrid gels were characterized by FTIR, XRD, and TGA analyses. To adjust the compressive elasticity and swelling properties, the nanosilica concentration in the gelation feed was varied between 0% and 10% (volume/volume). Depending on the nanosilica concentration, the swelling behavior of hybrid gels was carried out in water, at pH, and in aqueous salt solutions. The increase in the silica concentration decreased the swelling ratio in water due to the increased network density. The presence of carboxylate groups in the PSA structure resulted in the hybrid bionanocomposite gels exhibiting pH-sensitive behavior, with maximum swelling observed at a pH of 11.2.

This study promotes tuning the compressive elasticity and swelling of nanoparticle-integrated hybrid bionanocomposite gels with customized functionality and the synergistic effects of components, making them suitable for a wide range of applications.

- [1] Shimpi, N. G. (Ed.). *Biodegradable and Biocompatible Polymer Composites: Processing, Properties and Applications*. Woodhead Publishing. (2017).
- [2] Boonmahitthisud, A., Nakajima, L., Nguyen, K. D., & Kobayashi, T. [*Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 134 \(2017\)](#).

Decoupling initial and large-strain mechanical responses through nano-gel interlocking

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The "non-linear stress-strain response" of biological soft tissues exhibits a highly rational nature: they are compliant during the initial stages of deformation but undergo a rapid increase in stress under large deformations. This property allows for unrestricted natural movement while protecting tissues from damage under excessive loads [1]. When we tune and mimic the mechanical properties using polymer gels, initial and large-strain response are not controlled independently but are usually coupled. To address this, the introduction of submicron-size particle gels interpenetratingly in global gel network has been proposed [2]. We fabricated an interlocked "nanoparticle-composite network" gel comprising a rigid nanoparticle gel as the first network and a flexible polymer network as the second network. By varying the parameters of the particles and the gel, we investigated the resulting changes in their mechanical properties, aiming to decouple fracture strength from the initial flexibility. In this presentation, we will discuss the effects of particle loading and particle stiffness on the macroscopic mechanical properties of the gel.

Figure. Schematic illustration of the research strategy and changes in mechanical properties of the gel with varying particle loading

[1] Mengyao Zhou, et al., *Biomech Model Mechanobiol*, **23**(2024), 911-925.

[2] Jian Hu, et al., *Macromolecules*, **47**(2014), 3578-3594.

Rapid Test for Water Contamination Using Snail Mucus-Based Microfluidics

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High water quality is essential for both human health and the environment, with contamination of water bodies representing a key challenge. In this project, a sustainable rapid test for determining contamination will be developed based on snail slime (mucus). As an alternative raw material, snail mucus offers a multifunctional basis for producing hydrogels due to its broad spectrum of constituents, including the characteristic structural proteins known as mucins. In the form of micrometre-sized dots, hydrogels provide a large reactive surface area and are therefore ideal for use in microfluidic rapid tests.

In this project, the snail mucus serves simultaneously as a reactive substance for the synthesis of gold nanoparticles, as a stabiliser for the nanoparticles produced, and as a carrier material for these nanoparticles in the final hydrogel chip. As a result, the antimicrobial and catalytic effect of both snail mucus and gold nanoparticles is exploited in the rapid test. A simple readout is enabled by a straightforward competition reaction between a red dye and the potentially contaminated sample. If the water is contaminated, dye remains after passing through the chip, which is clearly indicated by the red signal colour.

In line with the principles of the bioeconomy, petroleum-based building blocks for hydrogel synthesis are replaced by renewable raw materials, while environmentally friendly methods for the formation and coupling of nanoparticles are established.

Figure 1: Development of snail slime-based hydrogels containing gold nanoparticles and integration into a microfluidic flow chip. Indication by degradation of Rhodamin-6G and inhibition of degradation by competing contaminants in water sample.

1. Koball, A.; Gaitzsch, J. *Bio-based microfluidics with snail slime: A by-product of agriculture plays an exciting role in the chemistry of microfluidic reaction chambers. Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2025**, *46*, e00578.

Applying dissociative chemistry to obtain gradient hydrogels

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Gradients in the extracellular matrix (ECM) play an important role in tissue development and disease progression. In Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC), the ECM's mechanical properties correlate with the staging of the disease. Studying PDAC *in vitro* requires models that mimic its ECM's mechanical anisotropy. We present an innovative approach to create hydrogels with tunable stiffness gradients using dissociative bioorthogonal chemistry.

Our method uses cross-linkers that can be selectively cleaved by a diffusing chemical agent as the external trigger. Controlling the spatial distribution of this cleavage agent allows the formation of continuous stiffness gradients in hydrogels. PEG-based hydrogels were selected as versatile, biocompatible model systems. In-depth characterization relates the hydrogels' mechanical properties (obtained via compression testing) to their molecular structure (studied via NMR spectroscopy or derived from gel characteristics) and the reaction kinetics of the studied dissociative chemistry.

This contribution showcases a novel application of dissociative bioorthogonal chemistry. The resulting materials are expected to better emulate the complex tumor microenvironment and may provide a powerful platform for fundamental cancer research by enabling precise studies of how mechanical cues influence tumor development, cellular behavior, and disease progression.

Complex coacervate double network hydrogel

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Complex coacervation is the phase separation of oppositely charged polyelectrolytes due to their electrostatic interaction, resulting in a polymer-dense coacervate phase and a polymer-depleted supernatant phase. Recently, we demonstrated that kinetically arrested complex coacervates can function as the sacrificial network in double network hydrogels¹.

These hydrogels exhibit the characteristic mechanical performance of double network systems while also serving as a proof of concept for leveraging the rich phenomenology of complex coacervation for advanced material design.

In this talk, I will examine how the electrostatically crosslinked sacrificial network influences the mechanical properties of the hydrogel. Additionally, I will discuss how embedding the coacervate within a polymer matrix modifies the coacervation process itself, highlighting the coupling between phase behavior and network mechanics².

[1] Es Sayed, Julien, et al. "Structure–property relationships of granular hybrid hydrogels formed through polyelectrolyte complexation." *Macromolecules* 57.7 (2024): 3190-3201.

[2] Vengallur, Nayan, and Andrea Giuntoli. "Complex coacervation in a polymer network", *in preparation*.

Quantifying Elastomer Damage via Physical Mechanophore Doping

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Most currently developed mechanophores require covalent incorporation into polymer backbones, which inevitably alters the host material's intrinsic mechanical properties. To address this, we introduce DAAN,[2] a high-yield, easily synthesizable mechanophore that functions via simple physical doping. This non-covalent approach is expected to preserve the matrix's inherent mechanics while offering broader applicability across diverse polymer systems. Accordingly, we propose a fluorescence-based strategy to quantify covalent bond scission in an EA-based triple-network (TN) elastomer physically doped with DAAN.[1]

By establishing a calibration curve between fluorescence intensity and DAAN-derived free radical concentration, we aim to translate these dynamic optical signals into the exact number of cleaved covalent bonds. This versatile methodology provides deep insights into the microscopic damage evolution and toughening mechanisms of soft materials.

[1] Etienne Ducrot, Y. C., Markus Bulters, Rint P. Sijbesma, Costantino Creton*. Science 2014.

[2] Yamamoto, T.; Takahashi, A.; Otsuka, H. RSC Mechanochemistry 2024.

Tuning Network Topology for Ultrastrong Poly(2-ethyl-2-oxazoline) Double Network Hydrogels

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Double network hydrogels (DNHs) enhance the mechanical performance of conventional hydrogels by combining a rigid primary with a ductile secondary network. Poly(2-oxazoline)s (POx) are promising precursors due to their hydrophilicity and versatile chemistry[1]. Here, we investigate how cross-linking strategy and polymerization method influence the mechanical properties of poly(2-ethyl-2-oxazoline)/poly(acrylic) DNHs.

A highly entangled primary network was formed via thermal backbone cross-linking of PETox and compared to an end-group cross-linked reference systems. Secondary networks based on different poly(acrylic)s were introduced via radical polymerization.

Backbone cross-linked PETox networks exhibited superior mechanical properties across all investigated systems due to trapped chain entanglements, resulting in up to a 17-fold increase in fracture energy and an increase in compressive strength from 15 to 48 MPa. These findings emphasise the important role that network topology plays in controlling energy dissipation in PETox-based DNHs, highlighting their potential for use in demanding mechanical applications.[2]

[1] P. A. Benitez-Duif, M. Breisch, D. Kurka, K. Edel, S. Gökçay, D. Stangier, W. Tillmann, M. Hijazi, J. C. Tiller, *Advanced Functional Materials* 2022, **32**, 2204837.

[2] S. Weckes, C. Rawert, J. C. Tiller, *European Polymer Journal* 2025, **237**, 114194.

Structural Control of POx Networks: A Click Chemistry Approach

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Poly(2-Oxazoline)-based networks have great potential in various applications due to the versatile functionalization possibilities of their chain ends. An efficient and highly controlled synthetic strategy for the synthesis of defined polymer network is presented through a selective Copper(I)-catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition (CuAAC) of bifunctional poly(2-ethyloxazolines) with a 4-arm pentaerythritol ethoxylate (4-arm PEG) as a cross-linker, which ensures highly selective reaction that prevents side reactions. The gel point is significantly reduced to only 33 % of conversion by using a 4-arm PEG crosslinker. This enables the formation of polymer-network at relatively low conversion and allows variable adjustment of degrees of cross-linking with precision.

This synthetic approach allows precise control over the topology of polymer-network including cross-linking density, the length of the spanning chains, and the quantity of functional dangling groups.

[1] von der Ehe, C., Kempe, K., Bauer, M., Baumgaertel, A., Hager, M.D., Fischer, D. and Schubert, Macromol. Chem. Phys. (2012), 213: 2146-2156

[2] Wawro, A., Muraoka, T., Kato, M. Kinbara K., Org. Chem. Front., (2016) 3, 1524

Probing the toughening mechanisms in silica elastomer nanocomposites by fluorescence imaging

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Nanoparticles such as carbon black and silica are widely used to reinforce elastomers in industrial applications, including tires and damping systems[1]. While these fillers significantly enhance stiffness and toughness, the underlying reinforcement mechanisms remain poorly understood[2,3]. In this work, silica nanoparticle reinforced poly(ethyl acrylate) elastomers are synthesized via UV-initiated radical polymerization. The role of silica nanoparticles in governing mechanical behavior is investigated by combining tensile testing with microscopic characterization using fluorescence labeling and mechanophores. Increasing the silica content from 0 to 30 wt% results in a substantial increase in toughness and leads to a tenfold increase in fracture energy up to $13,576.9 \pm 2,517.8 \text{ J/m}^2$, exceeding that of natural rubber. Step-strain cyclic tests reveal a pronounced increase in hysteresis across all strain levels, with a 40-fold enhancement already at 10% strain, indicating substantial energy dissipation even at small deformations. To probe the morphology near the crack tip, notched samples were stained with fluorescein. Fluorescence imaging reveals the formation of a damage zone characterized by cavities devoid of fluorescence signal in stretched, silica-reinforced elastomers. This observation suggests that energy dissipation arises from cavity nucleation and polymer chain scission within these cavitated regions. Complementary mechanophore analysis further reveals a more delocalized distribution of bond scission compared to unfilled elastomers. These results provide direct evidence that nanoparticle-induced stress redistribution promotes enhanced energy dissipation and toughness in elastomer nanocomposites. Notably, this work presents the first direct observation of delocalized chain scission and quantification of molecular damage in elastomer nanocomposites using mechanophores.

[1] S. Sarikaya, T. C. Henry, M. Naraghi, *Exp Mech* 2020, 60, 753.

[2] J. Steck, J. Kim, Y. Kutsovsky, Z. Suo, *Nature* 2023, 624, 303.

[3] Y. Chen, A. Kovalenko, A. Brûlet, B. Bresson, A. Lantheaume, L. Olanier, C. Creton, *Macromolecules* 2023, 56, 5336.

4.2 Poster Session 2

From bottlebrush melts to polymer networks: Architectural heterogeneity as a design variable

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Bottlebrush polymers offer a powerful route to soft yet mechanically robust networks, but the role of architectural heterogeneity remains insufficiently understood because average molecular parameters often conceal the distributional features that govern local packing, connectivity, and stress transmission. Here we establish a multiscale structure-property framework for bottlebrush polymer networks in which the mean backbone length, mean side-chain length, and grafting density are held constant while the breadth and shape of the architectural distributions are varied. By connecting precursor-melt analysis with post-crosslinking network characterization and mechanical testing, we show that dispersity is not merely a synthetic byproduct, but a governing design variable in bottlebrush network formation and response. Variations in backbone and sidechain distributions reorganize brush dimensions, interpenetration, and conformational heterogeneity in the melt, and these precursor-level fluctuations are subsequently encoded into the network as differences in connectivity heterogeneity, defect population, and load-bearing uniformity. Broad side-chain distributions primarily broaden local relaxation pathways and increase stress sharing heterogeneity, whereas backbone dispersity additionally amplifies topological heterogeneity by biasing crosslink allocation and increasing the population of weakly connected network elements. These differences manifest in stress relaxation and nonlinear tensile response, demonstrating that bottlebrush-network mechanics are governed not only by mean strand dimensions, but by the full statistical character of precursor architecture. Together, these results identify distribution shape and dispersity as practical molecular design parameters for tuning softness, extensibility, and viscoelastic response in bottlebrush polymer networks.

Design of modular ecological Poly(trimethyleneCarbonate) based coating

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There is growing interest in aliphatic polycarbonates, due to their biocompatibility, and biodegradable properties. Moreover, the monomers used to produce aliphatic polycarbonates can be biobased, and various functional groups can be incorporated to control the properties of the resulting polymers. For example, they can be incorporated to control the polymer structure or to regulate biodegradation. Currently, aliphatic polycarbonates are primarily being studied for biomedical applications¹.

The aim of this study is to develop poly(trimethylene carbonate) (PTMC) coatings and investigate their properties. PTMC exhibits limited mechanical properties and therefore requires a cross-linking step to form coatings. To achieve this, we propose the development of copolymers with trimethylene carbonate (TMC) and 5-methyl-5-allyloxycarbonyl-1,3-dioxan-2-one (MAC), using ring-opening polymerization (ROP)². MAC contains an allyl functional group that enables cross-linking of the copolymer chains via a thiol-ene reaction. However, to obtain a homogeneous coating, it is essential that the allyl group is randomly incorporated into the copolymer chain. The randomness of the copolymer was evaluated by analyzing dyad distributions using ¹³C NMR. The synthesized copolymers enable the formation of networks with tunable crosslinking densities by varying molecular weight, monomer ratio, and the nature of the crosslinking agents. Preliminary results reveal significant differences in thermal and mechanical properties, with glass transition temperatures (T_g) ranging from -17 °C to 16 °C and elastic moduli between 2 and 13 MPa. Further investigations are required to fully assess the network properties, including swelling measurements by ellipsometry and solid-state ¹H NMR spectroscopy. Interestingly, these networks seem to unlock promising new possibilities, in particular through a wider modulation of the crosslinking density.

1. K. Fukushima, *Biomater. Sci.* **4** (2016) 9–24.
2. F. Azemar, O. Gimello, J. Pinaud, J.-J. Robin, and S. Monge, *Polymers* **13** (2021) 1589.

Functionalized polyampholyte hydrogels for water purification

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The contamination of drinking water by polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and heavy metal ions represents a growing environmental and health risk. PFAS are excessively used in textiles, coatings and packaging. They remain persistent in the environment due to their strong C-F bonds leading to bioaccumulation and toxicity, which is directly linked to cancer as well as liver and kidney damage [1]. Similarly, heavy metal ions such as Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Ni^{2+} that stem from industrial sources are highly toxic even at minimum level [2]. Conventional removal methods include ion exchange, precipitation and membrane filtration often suffer from low selectivity, high cost and non-efficient regeneration [2].

Polymer-based hydrogels represent a promising and sustainable alternative due to their porous and functional networks, allowing effective adsorption and straightforward modification. If polyampholytes are used for hydrogel formation, the resulting materials contain both positive and negatively charged functional units, leading to response to changes in pH value and ionic strength and allowing the adsorption different metal ions, depending on surrounding conditions. Additionally, functional groups such as $-\text{COOH}$ and $-\text{NH}_2$ further enhance the binding capacity and reusability of the functionalized hydrogel systems [3].

This project develops poly(dehydroalanine) (PDha)-based polyampholyte hydrogels as multifunctional sorbents for water purification. PDha combines carboxylic and amine functionalities. This offers high charge density, tunable pH behavior and reversible adsorption. The aim is to design and synthesize PDha-based hydrogels for selective PFAS and heavy metal removal and ensure efficient regeneration and reuse.

References

- [1] K. K. Donovan, et al., *Front. Chem. Eng.* 7 (2025) 1565754.
- [2] Z. Darban, S. Shahabuddin, R. Gaur, I. Ahmad, and N. Sridewi, *Gels* 8 (2022) 263.
- [3] T. Çeper, S. W. Mohotti, L. X. Lange, and F. H. Schacher, *Org. Mater.* 06 (2023) 1-11.

Versatile biocomposites fabricated by harmonizing metal nanoparticle and mace extract with anionic polyacrylamide / itaconic acid matrix doped with polysaccharides

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Based on the multiple functions of the network and its dynamic interactions with the surrounding matrices, biocomposites are innovative materials with a biopolymeric structure reinforced with natural fibers [1]. As the most abundant biopolymers, polysaccharides offer a green alternative to synthetic polymers in the preparation of soft nanomaterials [2]. The significance of the application potential of biocomposites is based on the unique properties of polysaccharides, such as biocompatibility, abundance, and low cost. The need to control the structural-physical and functional property relationships of these polysaccharide-based structures has gained importance.

Within the scope of the proposed study, the starting monomer acrylamide was modified with the anionic comonomer itaconic acid, and bio-based hybrid materials were designed through polymerization in the presence of natural polymers with different chemical characteristics (anionic, cationic, and neutral). The design of hybrid networks containing acrylamide and itaconic acid in a one-pot synthesis is based on investigating the effect of various polysaccharides on the network structure. The copolymeric gels were synthesized by free radical polymerization at two different temperatures to obtain both hydrogel and cryogel formations, while a series of syntheses were carried out by adding carboxymethyl cellulose, sodium alginate, hyaluronic acid, and carrageenan. The aim was to understand the effect of polysaccharide addition on the swelling and mechanical properties of the designed materials. The mechanical data showed that polysaccharide addition to the network caused a decrease in the strength of the materials, while cryogelation also altered the mechanical strength of synthesized gels. Hybrid gels were characterized using XRD, FTIR, and TGA analyses. This study demonstrates that the addition of polysaccharides significantly alters the structural and mechanical behavior of acrylamide-itaconic acid hybrid gels. The results revealed that tunable swelling properties and different network architectures were achieved, particularly under cryogelation conditions. These findings highlight the potential of bio-based hybrid gels as customizable functional materials.

- [1] Harries, K., & Sharma, B. *Nonconventional and Vernacular Construction Materials: Characterisation, Properties and Applications*, 2nd ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, Netherlands (2020).
- [2] Fekete, T., & Borsa, J. *Polymer gels: Science and Fundamentals*. Springer Singapore, Singapore (2018).

Swelling Dynamics of Polymer Gel in Explicit Solvent: A Theoretical and Computer Simulation Study

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The swelling of polymeric hydrogels is governed by the coupled dynamics of solvent transport and polymer network elasticity. Here, we use molecular dynamics simulations of model polymer networks with varying strand lengths in explicit solvents to investigate swelling dynamics from the dry state to the equilibrated swollen state. The temporal evolution of solvent and polymer density profiles, as well as the swelling ratio, is systematically analysed. To interpret the simulation results, we develop a nonlinear diffusion model formulated as a moving boundary problem, in which polymer mass conservation is coupled with a nonlinear Darcy-type flux, leading naturally to a density-dependent effective diffusion coefficient. The nonlinear swelling behaviour arises from the combined entropic and elastic contributions to the osmotic pressure, described respectively by Flory-Huggins theory and polymer network elasticity. Theoretical predictions for gel front propagation show semiquantitative agreement with simulation results, providing clear physical insight into the driving forces underlying hydrogel swelling.

Comparative Study of Binary and Ternary DEAEAM-Based Crosslinked Hydrogels for Controlled Drug Delivery

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Abstract

Stimuli-responsive hydrogels are emerging platforms in biomedical engineering due to their ability to undergo reversible phase transitions. Among functional monomers, *N*-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]acrylamide (DEAEAM) has recently been highlighted in literature for its unique multi-responsive properties. [1,2] However, its integration into various crosslinked architectures has not been studied so far in literature. To the best of our knowledge, this study represents the first synthesis and comparative characterization of binary (DEAEAM–NIPAAm, DEAEAM–AAc) and ternary (DEAEAM–NIPAAm–AAc) crosslinked hydrogels for targeted therapeutic applications.

In this work, a series of hydrogels were synthesized via free radical polymerization using *N,N'*-methylenebisacrylamide (MBAAm) as the crosslinking agent. Comprehensive structural, morphological, and thermal characterizations confirmed the successful incorporation of the monomers into the crosslinked networks. Mechanical properties were investigated through compression tests, revealing that comonomer composition significantly affects the elastic modulus and structural integrity of the networks.

Swelling kinetics and equilibrium swelling ratios were examined across various pH levels. The results demonstrated that the swelling behavior could be precisely tuned by varying the binary and ternary compositions, which conforms the synergistic effects of DEAEAM's tertiary amine groups, AAc's carboxylic acid groups, and NIPAAm's isopropyl moieties. The potential of these novel hydrogels as smart carriers was evaluated using Ethidium Bromide (EtBr) as a model molecule and Tetracycline as a therapeutic drug. In vitro release studies indicated that the release profiles were highly dependent on the hydrogel composition and environmental pH, suggesting that DEAEAM-based crosslinked systems are promising candidates for advanced controlled drug delivery.

Keywords: Diethylaminoethylacrylamide (DEAEAM), NIPAAm, Acrylic acid, Binary and Ternary Hydrogels, Compression tests, Ethidium Bromide, Tetracycline delivery.

[1] Z. Song, K. Wang, G. Gao, S. Wang, and W. Zhang, *Macromolecules*, **49** (2016) 162-171

[2] F. Yin, B. Lonetti, J. D. Marty, N. L. de Viguerie, *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* **674** (2023) 131930

This work was supported by the Scientific Research Projects Coordination Unit of Gebze Technical University under the ADEP project (Grant No. 2024-A-113-01).

Influence of precursor molecular weight on swelling and elastic modulus of cross-linked PDMS films

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Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) is a chemically inert, highly flexible elastomer widely used in soft-matter applications ranging from microfluidics to bionterfaces and stretchable electronics. This mobility results in a low T_g (-145 °C) for the polymer. To obtain a solid and infusible material, a crosslinking reaction is required. Depending on the PDMS end-group, two addition reactions can be used. The condensation addition occurs on alkoxy silane groups to obtain the polymer network. The mechanical and transport properties of PDMS networks are governed by their internal architecture. In particular, the average molecular weight between cross-links (M_c) determines the density of elastic strands and the mesh size of the polymer network.

In this study, we investigate the effect of precursor molecular weight on the swelling behavior and mechanical properties of PDMS films prepared at a constant cross-linker ratio. Increasing the chain length is expected to reduce the effective cross-link density, thereby enhancing solvent uptake and decreasing the elastic modulus of the resulting networks. This working hypothesis is examined by combining swelling experiments with network analysis based on the Flory–Rehner framework and independent measurements of Young's modulus by nanoindentation¹ (Figure). This combined approach clarifies the role of precursor chain length in shaping the internal network structure.

[1] J.D. Kouakou, M.A. Bangoura, R. Mérindol, K. Réhel, I. Linossier, G. Vignaud and F. Azemar, *Soft Matter* 22 (2026) 508-517.

Dynamic Fracture Resistance of Elastomers through

Synergistic Antioxidant Systems

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This study looks at how synergistic antioxidant systems affect the dynamic fracture resistance of natural rubber elastomers designed for pneumatically actuated "Soft Grippers." It is important to extend service life under dynamic-mechanical stress. Therefore, the fatigue behavior were systematically evaluated using the De Mattia test (DIN ISO 132). The reference compound (NR1), which did not include protective additives, degraded quickly. Adding a synergistic mix of primary antioxidants and antiozonants (77PD and TMQ) leads to up to a sevenfold increase in service life. In exploratory trials, 1 to 3 phr of waxes or TNPP were added. [1], [2].

Fig. 1 - De Mattia test results of rubber compounds with various antioxidants compared to compound NR1 (without antioxidants).

Fig. 2 - Cracks after the De Mattia test. Left: sample NR1 (no antioxidants) after 20,000 cycles; center: sample AO (77PD, TMQ) after 140,000 cycles; and right: sample 2*AO after 200,000 cycles.

The De Mattia test results (Fig. 1) clearly show the delayed crack propagation. Visual inspection of the post-test samples (Fig. 2) shows the improvements in form. NR1 sample failed after 20,000 cycles. In contrast, the formulation containing 4 phr of 77PD and 2 phr of TMQ (2*AO) lasted 200,000 cycles. Even under ten times the mechanical stress, this improved sample had much smaller and less deep cracks. These improvements mainly result from the additives reacting preferentially with ozone, which helps preserve the polymer's main chain [3].

- [1] A. Kraibut, et.al, "Suppressed degradation by stabilizers during mixing of silica/silane-filled natural rubber," *Polym. Degrad. Stab.*, 2025.
- [2] N. Roche and L. Perier, "Influence of elastomers formulation on fatigue crack growth properties," *Procedia Eng.*, 2013.
- [3] E. Rossomme, et.al, "Computational studies of rubber ozonation explain the effectiveness of 6PPD as an antidegradant and the mechanism of its quinone formation," *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2023.

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Pioneering a Circular Economy: Sustainable Co-Upcycling of Polyethylene and Polypropylene Waste via Dynamic Vitriemer Networks

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Abstract: We introduce a pioneering method for the sustainable upcycling of polyethylene (PE) plastic waste, a widely used material that has contributed significantly to environmental issues. Although vitriemer technology offers a promising solution for creating recyclable and mechanically resilient materials. Our novel approach overcomes this obstacle by blending post-consumer recycled (PCR) PE from sources like milk pouches with a preformed vitriemer network made from PCR polypropylene (PP) crosslinked with an aromatic disulfide (1,4'-diaminodiphenyl disulfide, AFD). This strategy uniquely incorporates styrene as a comonomer, along with glycidyl methacrylate (GMA), to enhance grafting efficiency and mitigate harmful chain scission, representing a significant advancement in vitriemer chemistry. This innovative upcycling process results in a material with greatly improved mechanical performance, as the yield strength, Young's modulus, and elongation at yield of PCR-PE increased by 108%, 70%, and 21%, respectively, while also showing full recovery after three recycling cycles when blended with 70% PCR-PP vitriemer. By pioneering the co-upcycling of two major thermoplastic waste streams, this work creates a powerful pathway to transform plastic waste into high-performance, reusable materials through advanced manufacturing techniques, thereby speeding up the global shift toward a circular economy.

Keywords: Sustainable Upcycling, Post-consumer Recycled Polyolefins, Vitrimers, Circular Economy

A Switchable-Transparency Eutectogel Enabled by Multiple Dynamic Interactions for Smart Display Applications

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Eutectogels represent an emerging class of soft materials that combine the advantages of traditional hydrogels with the unique properties of deep eutectic solvents. In this study, a smart thermo-responsive eutectogel (STE) was synthesized using an N-isopropylacrylamide/metal salt-based deep eutectic solvent. By leveraging synergistic hydrogen-bonding and coordination interactions, the STE exhibits robust mechanical performance with a tensile strength of 2.7 MPa. Notably, the STE displays Upper Critical Solution Temperature (UCST) behavior, enabling a reversible transition between opaque and transparent states. Beyond its inherent self-adhesiveness and water-detachable capability, the STE features thermally enhanced adhesion, demonstrating tunable adhesive behavior. Furthermore, the STE functions as a reliable strain sensor for human motion detection across a broad temperature range, complemented by excellent self-healing and antibacterial properties. This work provides a versatile platform for designing multifunctional eutectogels tailored for next-generation smart optical switches and wearable electronics.

Smart Polyampholyte Gels to Enhance EEG Headset Wearability in Brain-Computer Interfaces

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Current electroencephalogram (EEG) headsets used in brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) face significant barriers to daily use. Conventional conductive hydrogels are used to bridge the electrical signals between the scalp and the EEG electrodes; however, due to their toothpaste-like consistency, these hydrogels are prone to motion artifacts leading to unstable EEG signal transmission. Often, a chin strap is required to ensure high signal quality; however, this causes discomfort, especially for hypersensitive patients. Here, we propose a conductive and adhesive smart polyampholyte (PA) hydrogel synthesized via the copolymerization of sodium 4-vinylbenzenesulfonate and [3-(methacryloylamino)propyl]trimethylammonium chloride. By adjusting the overall charge of the PA gel, we observed various degrees of adhesion on different substrate surfaces. Rheology and adhesion test results revealed a more charge-imbalanced PA gel can increase the interfacial adhesion due to their changes in both the bulk gel structure as well as the gel surface charges. The abundance of ionic interactions within the gel provides a high toughness. Along with the adhesion property, the gel can maintain the EEG electrode-scalp connections without the help of chin straps, even under conditions with head movements. In addition, an on-demand transition from a solid-like gel state to a water-like fluid state in the presence of salt enables easy removal after use. This conductive, tough, adhesive hydrogel has shown improved signal acquisition in a preliminary EEG headset testing.

Curcumin-Derived Prodrug Soft Segments for the Design of Degradable Polyurethane Hydrogels

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Hydrogels integrated with therapeutic molecules exhibit intrinsic bioactivity, making them promising candidates for tissue repair. However, achieving uniform incorporation and controlled release of hydrophobic therapeutic molecules from hydrogel networks remains a significant challenge. In this study, curcumin, a hydrophobic bioactive molecule, was utilized as an initiator for ϵ -caprolactone polymerization to synthesize curcumin-initiated poly(ϵ -caprolactone) diols (Cur-PCL), which served as a prodrug soft segment (SS). Then, Cur-PCL was integrated into polyurethane (PU) networks to construct degradable PU hydrogels. The prodrug SS strategy covalently integrated curcumin into PU chains, achieving uniform distribution and network stability within the PU hydrogel. Cleavage of covalent bonds during PU hydrogel degradation triggered the curcumin release, resulting in a degradation-coupled and sustained release behavior. Meanwhile, modulation of the hard segment (HS) content further endowed the PU hydrogel with tunable network density, mechanical properties, and degradation behavior. With increasing HS content from 15% to 40%, the swelling ratio of the PU hydrogel decreased from 281.2% to 142.4%, whereas its tensile strength increased significantly from 0.1 MPa to 1.1 MPa. In addition, the PU hydrogels exhibited good biocompatibility (cell viability >70%), indicating their promising potential for tissue engineering applications.

Molecular-level insights into ion-induced structural changes in SIPN gels: Swelling, mechanics, and FTIR analysis

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Semi-interpenetrating polymer networks (SIPNs) offer advanced structural design capabilities due to their chemical structure, which consists of two or more interpenetrating networks, one component of which is a cross-linked network structure and the other component is a linear, high-weight polymer without cross-links [1]. In this study, SIPN strategy was used to design hybrid gels with improved mechanical and physical properties to utilize the synergistic effect between biopolymer Xanthan Gum (XG) and chemically crosslinked network based on biocompatible 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA), functionalizable glycidyl methacrylate (GMA) and di(ethylene glycol) dimethacrylate. The study focuses on the effect of the synergistic phenomenon on material properties such as composition-dependent swelling and elastic modulus by synthesizing polymer gels at constant XG w/v% concentration while varying the GMA mol% amount in the gelation feed.

Focusing on the effect of salts, the swelling characteristics of Poly(HEMA-co-GMA)/XG-based SIPN gels were systematically investigated as a function of GMA mol% in three different Hoffmeister salt solutions, namely, K₂CO₃, KCl, and KNO₃, over a wide range of concentration gradients between 10⁻⁵ mol/L to 3.0 mol/L and compared with their swelling behavior in deionized water. Following salt-responsive equilibrium swelling of SIPN gels in CO₃²⁻, Cl⁻, and NO₃⁻ solutions, selected gel samples that swelled in anion concentrations of 10⁻⁵, 1, and 3 mol/L, were subjected to compressive testing to evaluate their mechanical performance. The results indicated that not only swelling but also the mechanical properties of SIPN gels are affected by the presence of kosmotrope and chaotrope anions. To further investigate the structural changes in Poly(HEMA-co-GMA)/XG-based SIPN network induced by ionic swelling, FTIR analysis was performed on gels after swelling in each salt solution. Significant shifts in the characteristic absorption peaks were observed compared to water-swollen samples. The observed spectral changes indicate that the nature of the surrounding ionic medium directly affects polymer chain organization and network composition.

The combined swelling, mechanical, and spectroscopic investigations carried in this study demonstrate a strong correlation between ionic environment and gel structure–property relationships. These findings provide valuable insight for the design of ion-responsive hydrogel systems in biomedical, environmental, and advanced material applications.

[1] Zhao, X., Chen, X., Yuk, H., Lin, S., Liu, X., & Parada, G. [Chemical Reviews 121 \(2021\) 4309-4372.](#)

Liquid Drops Meet Star Polymers

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Soft colloidal and nanocolloidal particles are typically modeled using either discrete bead-and-spring-type numerical models or continuum free-energy approaches. The discrete models capture the monomer-level details and architecture of the particles, whereas continuum models describe them without an immediate microscopic foundation. Here we demonstrate how these views can be combined. That aggregate geometry serves as a unifying framework between these complementary descriptions. Using monomer-resolved simulations, we study the morphology of clusters of quasi-two-dimensional star polymers in varying solvent quality, and we map their shapes onto those predicted by the liquid drop model. These findings show that the two approaches are complementary and can address each other's limitations. We find a linear relation between solvent quality and the effective tension ratio as the key parameters controlling adhesion in both models, and we uncover a crossover in the reduced Egelstaff-Widom length. Moreover, the coarse-grained description reveals a solvent-driven morphological transition within individual stars that is not directly apparent at the monomer level, showing how these complementary approaches may be fruitfully used in conjunction.

[1] Riest, J., Athanasopoulou, L., Egorov, S.A., Likos, C.N., Ziherl, P.: Elasticity of polymeric nanocolloidal particles. *Scientific reports* 5(1), 15854 (2015).

[2] Vrban, F.I., Šiber, A., Ziherl, P.: Contact forces in microgel suspensions. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2509.25583* (2025).

[3] A. Farimani, R., Likos, C.N.: Coarse-graining of slit-confined star polymers in solvents of varying quality. *Macromolecules* (2025).

Renewable and Repairable Coating Design with Debonding on Demand

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The global inks and coatings market was valued at ~\$195 billion in 2024 and is projected to continuedly grow in the near future.¹ However almost none of the products are recycled, because traditional coatings are not designed for substrate removal. Separating coatings from its substrates requires a significant amount of energy and cost, which makes the recycling of both coating and substrate inefficient and economically unattractive.^{2,3}

Vitrimers are a novel class of promising polymeric materials with a network of covalent adaptable bonds. These undergo constant bond exchange reactions at every temperature. However, their lifetime is dependent on stimuli such as temperature or pressure, allowing vitrimers to transition from a viscoelastic solid to a viscoelastic liquid without a decrease in connectivity. This makes it possible to reprocess vitrimers, unlike materials conventionally used in coatings.⁴

The goal of this project is to establish a polymer system for sustainable and renewable coatings that can be triggered to allow effective removal from a substrate. Our approach involves the design of different vitrimer systems based on dynamic transesterification and transcarbamylation exchange reactions. To minimize the environmental impact, this strategy utilizes renewable carbon from biomass and photopolymerization directly onto substrates.

Literature

- [1] Paints and Coatings Market - Size, Share, Industry Trends, and Forecasts (2024 - 2031); *Consegic Business Intelligence*, **2024**
- [2] Vogt, B. D., Stokes, K. K. & Kumar, S. K., *ACS Applied Polymer Materials*, **2021**, vol. 3 4325–4346
- [3] H. Jung, G. Shin, H. Kwak, L.T. Hao, J. Jegal, H. J. Kim, H. Jeon, J. Park, D. X. Oh, *Chemosphere*, **2023**, vol. 320, 138089
- [4] Denissen, W., Winne, J. M. & Du Prez, F. E., *Chemical Science*, 2016, vol. 7, 30-38

Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of Jammed Dispersion of Nanogels

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This study employs dissipative particle dynamics simulations to investigate the equilibrium microstructure and mechanical properties of jammed nanogel dispersions in a good solvent. The nanogels, composed of crosslinked linear polymers, exhibit impenetrability. Significant changes in size (radius of gyration) and shape (asphericity parameter) occur beyond a critical concentration (e.g., 15 wt%), resulting in densely packed configurations. The coordination number increases with rising concentration and stabilizes at a constant (approximately 13) for a jammed structure. For the jammed dispersion (25 wt%), rheological measurements reveal shear-thinning behavior and the presence of a static yield stress. Furthermore, oscillatory tests confirm the dominance of the storage modulus, indicating solid-like behavior. According to the compressive test, the Young's modulus increases with the nanogel concentration due to denser packing. Sudden relaxation tests show an elastic response for small strains but a plastic response for large strains. This comprehensive analysis elucidates the relationship between the microstructure of nanogel dispersions and their solid-like characteristics.

Synthesis of Magnetic Graphene Oxide and Lauryl Acrylate-Based Polymeric Adsorbents for Efficient PAH Removal in Wastewater Treatment

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Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), an important class of environmental pollutants, threaten human health due to their high lipophilicity and mutagenic, teratogenic toxicities, as well as their persistence in marine ecosystems. Therefore, reliable monitoring of PAHs in wastewater and marine environments is essential for environmental sustainability and public health protection. Owing to its low energy requirement, high removal efficiency, large surface area, and tunable structural properties, adsorption has become a preferred method for the removal of PAHs from various aqueous matrices [1]. Graphene oxide (GO)-based adsorbents facilitate the adsorption of PAHs through strong π - π interactions and hydrophobic interactions, enabled by their single-atom-thick carbon structure and functional surface [2]. Recent studies have also demonstrated that lauryl acrylate (LA), with its long alkyl chain, is an effective adsorbent for hydrophobic PAHs via π - π stacking and van der Waals interactions [3]

In this study, the strong π - π and hydrophobic interaction capacity of GO was combined with in situ synthesized magnetic Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles to enhance adsorption efficiency toward PAHs and enable facile magnetic separation. Adsorbent magnetic hydrophobic beads with high surface area and porosity were successfully obtained using alginate and MGO/ LA were combined to form a composite via a green synthesis approach. Key parameters (GO concentration and LA/SA content) were optimized, and the effects of pH, adsorbent dosage, and contact time on removal efficiency were evaluated. The structural and physicochemical properties of the composites were characterized by FTIR, SEM, and TGA analyses. The amount of adsorbed PAHs was determined using UV-Vis spectrophotometry, and adsorption capacities were calculated accordingly. Under optimized conditions, removal efficiencies of 96% for methylene green as a model compound and 89% for anthracene as a PAH analyte sample were achieved, and additional PAH analytes will be evaluated.

[1] Brião, G. V., Jahn, S. L., Foletto, E. L., (2018). Highly efficient and reusable mesoporous zeolite synthesized from a biopolymer for cationic dyes adsorption. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering*, 556, 43–50

[2] Zhou Y, He J, Chen R, Li X (2022). Recent advances in biomass-derived graphene and carbon nanotubes. *Mater Today Sustain* 18:100138

[3] Gupta, J., Keddie, D. J., Wan, C., Haddleton, D. M., & McNally, T. (2016). Functionalization of MWCNTs with poly(lauryl acrylate) polymerized by Cu(0)-mediated and RAFT methods. *Polymer Chemistry*, 7(22), 3884-3896.

Multi-responsive and conductive hydrogels as biochemical sensors

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Hydrogels are a promising class of soft materials. Stimuli-responsive hydrogels can respond to environmental changes by changing their volume, thereby broadening the range of potential applications. A dual-responsive hydrogel system was developed. On the one hand, it is thermo-responsive, based on the LCST of poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (PNiPAAm), and on the other hand, it is redox-responsive, due to the disulphide groups of the cross-linker N,N'-bis(acryloyl)cystamine (BAC). The permanent cross-linker N,N'-methylenebis(acrylamide) (BIS) stabilised the network. The swelling behaviour was investigated on various scales, considering the influence of structural defects.¹⁻⁴ The integration of electrical functions into the hydrogel – e.g. by adding a (semi-)conductive polymer like poly-3,4-ethylenedioxythiophen (PEDOT) – would make it more attractive, especially for bioelectronics. This combines responsiveness with electrical properties and offers great potential as integrated sensors with electrical readout. The PNiPAAm hydrogel is transformed into a PEDOT-based interpenetrating polymer network (IPN). A microfluidic device incorporating this hydrogel is designed. Under microfluidic conditions, the influence of reactive swelling behaviour on electrical properties is investigated. This enables the electrical detection of environmental changes, allowing the system to function as a sensitive sensor.⁵

[1] D. Hofmann, D. Sychev, Z. Zagradka-Paromova, E. Bittrich, G.K. Auernhammer, and J. Gaitzsch, [Macromolecular Rapid Communications](#) **45** (2024) 2400049.

[2] D. Hofmann, E. Bittrich, D. Appelhans, and J. Gaitzsch, [Journal of Polymer Science](#) **18** (2025) 3631–3639.

[3] C. Jiao, F. Obst, M. Geisler, Y. Che, A. Richter, D. Appelhans, J. Gaitzsch, and B. Voit, [Polymers](#) **14** (2022) 267.

[4] Y. Che, S. Zschoche, F. Obst, D. Appelhans, and B. Voit, [Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry](#) **57** (2019) 2590-2601.

[5] D. Hofmann, T. F. Akbar, O. Patel, I. R. Minev, and J. Gaitzsch, manuscript in preparation.

Reconfigurable Microenvironments Uncover Mechano-Sensing Timescales and Direct Cell Polarity

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In vitro tissue and disease models require hydrogel matrices with precisely tunable mechanical properties. However, existing systems lack independent control over viscoelasticity or rely on chemical modifications that alter composition. Here, we introduce DyNAtrix [1, 2], a fully synthetic DNA-crosslinked hydrogel with programmable mechanical behavior [3]. By leveraging combinatorial DNA crosslinker libraries, DyNAtrix enables independent tuning of stiffness and stress-relaxation over physiologically relevant ranges. The platform supports the culture of diverse cell types, including human mesenchymal stromal cells, induced pluripotent stem cells, and epithelial organoids. Systematic variation of mechanical parameters reveals that MDCK cyst polarity is governed by matrix viscoelasticity, and two distinct timescales of mechano-sensitive processes controlling polarity are uncovered. Furthermore, a switchable DNA crosslinker enables reversible, in situ modulation of stress relaxation via external signaling strands, inducing dynamic and reversible polarity transitions. DyNAtrix establishes a versatile platform for engineering cell-instructive microenvironments and advancing studies in mechanobiology and tissue engineering.

- [1] Hsiao, S.-K., Mukenhirn, M., Werner, C., Honigmann, A. & Krieg, E., *Adv. [Funct. Mater.](#)* **35**, no. 49 (2025): [e13028](#).
- [2] Peng, Y.-H., Hsiao, S. K., Gupta, K., Ruland, A., Auernhammer, G. K., Maitz, M. F., Boye, S., Lattner, J., Gerri, C., Honigmann, A., Werner, C. & Krieg, E., *[Nat. Nanotechnol.](#)* **18**, [1463–1473](#) (2023).
- [3] Speed, S. K., Gupta, K., Peng, Y.-H., Hsiao, S. K. & Krieg, E., *[J. Polym. Sci.](#)* **61**, [1713–1729](#) (2023).

Highly Stretchable PDMS Ring Networks

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Silicone elastomers have been widely investigated for applications in soft robotics, actuators, and wearable devices, due to their exceptional elasticity and mechanical resilience [1][2]. Silicone elastomers comprising concatenated ring structures represent a notable class of highly elastic materials, capable of achieving ultimate strains above 1000% in the absence of conventional covalent crosslinking [3].

In this study, ring-based networks were synthesized via condensation curing of silanol-terminated poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS). A low molecular HO-PDMS-OH precursor ($\sim 1400 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$), was selected in combination with a tin-based catalyst, resulting in the formation of an elastomeric material. There is no universally accepted method for determining whether an elastomer has a cyclic structure and is part of a ring network. Network architecture was evaluated using $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and $^{29}\text{Si-NMR}$ to determine the presence or absence of terminal functional groups and distinguish concatenated rings from conventional PDMS networks. Additionally, the hydrodynamic volumes of the sol fractions were analyzed by size exclusion chromatography (SEC). The combined results of these methods indicate the presence of concatenated ring networks.

To maximize the material's stretchability, key synthesis parameters were systematically varied including the catalyst concentration, temperature, and the addition of trace amounts of water. The preliminary results of condensation-cured silicone elastomers with concatenated ring networks show exceptional stretchability. The mechanical performance of the synthesized elastomers revealed an elongation at break of 1000% with a Young's modulus of 0.05 MPa. The pursuit of highly stretchable silicone elastomers is motivated by their potential applications in rubber band batteries. These batteries use elastic deformation to store energy, releasing it during relaxation. Preliminary tensile testing on a dog-bone specimen of the synthesized elastomer indicated an energy absorption of approximately 100 mJ/g. The viability of this system depends critically on the material's ability to combine high elasticity, resilience, and energy density, properties inherent to silicone elastomers.

REFERENCES:

- [1] K. Mondal, G. Kaur, R. Advincula, [RSC Applied Polymers 4 \(2026\)](#)
- [2] P. Mazurek, S. Vudayagiri, A. L. Skov, [SPIE – International society or Optical Engineering \(2019\)](#)
- [3] P. Hu, J. Madsen, Q. Huang, A. L Skov, [ACS Macro Letters \(2020\)](#)

Industrial Hydrogel Research at P&G

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Superabsorbent polymers (SAPs), typically crosslinked polyacrylates, are key functional materials enabling the performance of modern absorbent hygiene products. Since their introduction into Pampers® in 1986, SAP requirements have evolved with the Pampers® structural design from maximizing liquid uptake toward a balanced performance profile that combines high retention, fast swelling kinetics, sufficient gel-bed permeability, and mechanical robustness under load.

Surface-crosslinked SAP (AI).

This poster highlights how P&G academically collaborates to investigate molecular network architecture and surface crosslinking. **Network-level understanding is enabled by ¹H double-quantum NMR^[1,2]**, providing insights into crosslink-density heterogeneity, network defects such as loops and dangling chains, as well as mobile sol fractions.

Surface-crosslinked SAP particles are discussed as engineered inhomogeneous hydrogels, where a higher crosslink-density at the particle surface improves swollen particle stability and supports gel bed permeability.

In addition, **idealized SAP particles were generated via microfluidics^[3]** providing nearly monodisperse, spherical SAP particles, e.g. with controlled coatings. This enabled **kinetic studies^[4]** in which particle size and morphology effects can be separated from intrinsic material properties.

[1] X. Guo, S. Theissen, J. Claussen, V. Hildebrand, J. Kamphus, M. Wilhelm, B. Luy, G. Guthausen, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **2018**, *219*, 1800100.

[2] Prof. K. Saalwächter kindly provided the low-field DQ pulse sequence.

[3] A. Simonyan, J. Kamphus, S. Seiffert, T. Habicht, P&G patent WO2018/194779.

[4] T. G. Linder, A. Heinzelmann, J. Kamphus, S. Seiffert, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **2024**, *225*, 2400138.

The pAAm-sIPN-HA/AuNPs hybrid gel - synthesis, characterization and application as an anti-freezing, sensitive pressure sensor

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With their advantageous properties, hydrogel materials have attracted a lot of interest in the context of their applications in soft electronics, e.g. wearable sensors, electronic skin, soft robotics. While gels resemble human tissue, with their high water content and softness, native polymer matrices often lack the specific properties required for the application, for example: electrical conductivity, mechanical durability or long-term stability. To address these limitations, different fillers can be introduced into the matrix.

In this work, sodium hyaluronate (HA) was used as a multifunctional filler to construct a semi-interpenetrating network (sIPN) gel with a poly(acrylamide)-based network. Its function isn't limited to enhancing mechanical properties, but also it functions as a platform for AuNPs synthesis – acting as both a reducing agent and a stabilizer, yielding a hybrid nanocomposite gel containing a covalently crosslinked polymer, linear HA chains and AuNPs. Due to the presence of HA, ionic conductivity is introduced and interfacial adhesion is improved, while AuNPs provide electronic conductivity. Additionally, water inside the gel was exchanged for a binary mixture of water and glycerol, improving long term stability by limiting evaporation and lowering the freezing point of the gel. Obtained material exhibits resistance dependent on compression, and the electromechanical signal is independent of rate of the movement. This sensor possesses exceptional sensitivity (90 Pa^{-1}) for small pressure range and fast response and recovery time of 200 ms. A practical use case of this gel is presented as the ability to sense touch, both light taps and heavier presses, and to detect Morse code signals. Overall, good mechanical properties, high sensitivity and fast response times make the material suitable for use in the creation of smart interfaces and robotic limbs.

Covalently Crosslinked Alginate-Poly(ethylene glycol) Hydrogels for Wastewater Treatment

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Despite clean water being an important resource, many industrial processes decrease the availability of water by contaminating it with harmful compounds such as organic dyes and metal ions.^[1] To gain further insight into sustainable wastewater treatment, we present a novel alginate-based hydrogel with favorable adsorption characteristics in regard to organic and inorganic model contaminants.

Many alginate gels are formed by the introduction of multivalent cations or the use of the carboxylic group for chemical crosslinking, thereby using this negatively charged group also needed for the adsorption of positively charged contaminants.^{[2], [3]} To retain the carboxylic groups located along the alginate backbone, a two-step synthesis consisting of glycol cleavage and reductive amination is used. Alginate is covalently crosslinked by linear poly(ethylene glycol) bis(amine) with different molecular weights via a hydrolysis-insensitive secondary amine group to ensure swelling in aqueous media. Oscillatory shear rheology and swelling experiments in aqueous media were conducted to characterize the resulting hydrogels, showing that their properties are dependent on the crosslinker molecular weight and amount used. Adsorption experiments reveal comparable adsorption of the organic dye methylene blue and vastly increased adsorption of calcium cations compared to ionically crosslinked alginate hydrogels. The results of this work position the novel alginate hydrogels as versatile materials in regard to wastewater purification with high potential for further modification.

[1] T. Shindhal, P. Rakholiya, S. Varjani, A. Pandey, H. H. Ngo, W. Guo, H. Y. Ng, M. J. Taherzadeh, *Bioengineered* 12(1) (2021) 70-87.

[2] J. Berg, S. Seiffert, *Journal of Polymer Science* 61(18) (2023) 2203-2222.

[3] P. Eiselt, K. Yong Lee, D. J. Mooney, *Macromolecules* 32, 17 (1999) 5561-5566.

Inhomogeneous Shape Distributions and Size Effects in Jammed Deformable Microgel Dispersions under Microchannel Flow

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The flow behavior of jammed monodisperse microgel dispersions in a narrow microchannel is examined using Dissipative Particle Dynamics, with emphasis on the roles of microgel size and deformation. Larger microgels produce a higher maximum velocity in the velocity profile and reach lower values of the local apparent viscosity at the same shear rate. Relating to the Herschel–Bulkley model, this size effect appears mainly as a decrease in the material constant k , whereas the flow index and yield stress remain nearly insensitive to size. Despite differences in absolute velocity, all normalized velocity profiles from both simulations and experiments collapse onto a single universal master curve, showing flow universality across different microgels. This universality is associated with shear-rate-dependent and strongly inhomogeneous deformation across the channel, where particles in high-shear regions experience pronounced stretching. Larger microgels, being more compressible and deformable, display more pronounced stretching and thus experience lower flow resistance, while variations in deformation are reflected mainly in the material constant k .

Multiscale design of transient plasticisation in high-Tg waterborne latex coatings

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Coalescing agents are widely used to enable film formation in high-Tg waterborne latex coatings, but their use creates a persistent trade-off between coating performance and VOC content [1]. Their effectiveness depends not only on polymer chemistry, but also on additive retention and film-formation history, making coalescent selection largely empirical [2]. Here, we present a multiscale, data-driven framework for analysing formulation-dependent glass-transition depression in latex coatings. Using experimentally measured Tg values obtained under controlled conditioning protocols, we quantify how latex composition, coalescent identity, and processing history govern effective Tg depression and the resulting film behaviour. Rather than treating Tg depression as a fixed intrinsic quantity, the framework defines it relative to a specified conditioning endpoint, capturing the transient nature of plasticisation in practical coating systems. This provides a route to predictive screening of coalescents for lower-VOC film formation and establishes a general framework linking latex chemistry, transient softening, and final coating performance.

[1] K. Pieters and T. H. Mekonnen, RSC Sustainability 2 (2024) 3704-3729.

[2] W. Tangsongcharoen and M. Paulis, Prog. Org. Coat. 196 (2024).

Thermally Activated Stress Relaxation and Creep in Ideal Hydrogel

Elastomers: Rupture of Tensile Strands

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The microscopic origins of time-dependent mechanical responses, including stress relaxation and creep, in a hydrogel film composed of a chemically crosslinked network are investigated using dissipative particle dynamics. After free relaxation following uniaxial stretching, the model hydrogel exhibits full recovery at moderate strains but develops a small residual strain at larger deformations, indicating elastomeric behavior accompanied by irreversible plasticity. Microscopic analyses reveal the evolution of bond length, strand length, internal energy, strand stretch ratio, and bond rupture during deformation and relaxation. Stress relaxation and creep are essentially absent at moderate strains, consistent with negligible frictional dissipation, but become pronounced at larger strains due to the occurrence of rare bond-rupture events. During stress relaxation, the decay of stress closely correlates with reductions in bond length and internal energy, with the response dominated by bond-length relaxation associated with network reorganization. During creep, the mean bond length remains nearly constant, whereas the mean strand length evolves through primary/secondary regimes and accelerates into tertiary creep-to-failure. Both time-dependent behaviors arise from structural reorganization induced by rare, thermally activated bond-rupture events localized within highly stretched tensile strands.

[1] Lin, C. J., Tsao, H. K., and Sheng, Y. J., *Extreme Mechanics Letters* (2026) 102443.

High-resolution swelling data using a simple method

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In this work, we present a simple method in which solvent induced swelling of crosslinked polymers is monitored continuously (Figure 1). We demonstrate how analysis of the high-resolution data enables insights into the different stages of swelling, network properties, and network-solvent interactions. The method can identify transient swelling behavior as highlighted by the discovery of a swelling overshoot in silicone elastomers, which, to our knowledge, has not previously been observed.

Figure 1. Schematic of the method for measuring and analyzing the relative area increase over time of silicone elastomers immersed in heptane (dark red) and ethyl acetate (pink).

The method uses a portable microscope (Dino-Lite AM4115ZT-EDGE, NL) to capture images of elastomer discs during solvent immersion. A purposely written script in Fiji (ImageJ, US) semi-automatically analyzes the images and returns swelling data, from which the different swelling phases, swelling rate, and swelling degree can be extracted.

Using the method, we studied the swelling of hydrosilylation-cured silicone elastomers with controlled network properties (crosslinking densities and filler loadings) in various solvents. The study enabled conclusions on complex solvent-polymer-filler interactions and gave insights into how swelling dynamics are influenced by network parameters and solvent quality.

Equilibrium structure and mechanical properties of bidisperse concentrated emulsions

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Concentrated emulsions possessing a jammed structure exhibit distinct solid-like behaviors, with their properties significantly influenced by droplet size and polydispersity. As a first exploration of polydispersity, bidisperse concentrated emulsions with precisely controlled droplet sizes are studied using dissipative particle dynamics simulations. The effects of varying droplet size ratios and large droplet fractions (ϕ_L) on the microstructure, thermodynamic properties, and mechanical properties are examined. From the radial distribution functions, the spatial arrangement of droplets is similar to that in monodisperse emulsions, with small droplets distributed among large ones. Considering the mean droplet radius (\bar{R}) as the reciprocal mean, both interfacial internal energy and osmotic pressure are proportional to $1/\bar{R}$, while the self-diffusion coefficient of the continuous phase increases as \bar{R} increases. Each elastic modulus (bulk, shear, and Young's) rises linearly with either decreasing ϕ_L or increasing $1/\bar{R}$, indicating that smaller characteristic droplet sizes and higher effective Laplace pressure lead to greater resistance to deformation. In addition, the linear mixing model and the modulus-size relation for determining the moduli are presented. The Poisson's ratio remains close to 0.5, confirming the incompressibility of the material.

Shear-thickening behaviour in aqueous solutions of hydroxypropylcellulose crosslinked by superchaotropic Keggin polyoxometalate $H_4[SiW_{12}O_{40}]$

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Cellulose ethers (CEs) such as hydroxypropylcellulose (HPC) are low-cost, widely available, water-soluble, biocompatible, semiflexible polymer known to either show Newtonian or shear-thinning behavior. Recently, nanometer-sized ions such as Keggin-type polyoxometalates (POMs) have recently emerged as powerful gelating agents for non-ionic cellulose ethers (CEs), including HPC [1]. Due to their low charge density and weak hydration, these POMs interact with CE through a water-mediated “superchaotropic” effect, releasing their hydration water and leading to bulk water structure recovery [2].

Here, we show that addition of superchaotropic POM $H_4[SiW_{12}O_{40}]$ in millimolar concentrations to HPC solutions induces shear thickening behavior. To demonstrate this, we investigated HPC polymer of different molecular weights using rotational and oscillatory rheology. For HPC with low molecular weights, steady shear experiments reveal Newtonian fluid behavior. Addition of $H_4[SiW_{12}O_{40}]$ leads to an increase in the zero-shear viscosity of HPC and appearance of shear thinning at high shear rates. However, for HPC with $M_w > 700$ kDa, we observed Newtonian plateau at low shear rates followed by shear thickening *i.e.*, an increase in viscosity at higher shear rates. We studied in detail the effect of HPC and $H_4[SiW_{12}O_{40}]$ concentration on the appearance of Newtonian/shear-thinning/thickening behavior. Additionally, we also determined the effect of salt and temperature on the extent of shear thickening. The shear behavior of HPC/ $H_4[SiW_{12}O_{40}]$ solutions is related to shear induced structural changes, where the formation of new interchain crosslinking on shearing contributes to shear thickening.

[1] M. Hohenschutz, P. Bauduin, C. Lopez, B. Foerster and W. Richtering, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 62 (2023), e202210208.

[2] K. Assaf and W. Nau, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 57 (2018), 13968.

Negative energetic elasticity in a hydrogel synthesized by free radical polymerization

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Polymer gels have attracted great attention owing to their potential applications including soft robotics and biomaterials. It is imperative to optimize the elasticity to cater to the specific requirements of each application. Elasticity of materials can be divided into the following two components: energetic elasticity and entropic elasticity. Conventionally, entropic elasticity has been considered the dominant factor in the elasticity of polymer gels, similar to natural rubber. Recently, our studies on tetra-branched poly(ethylene glycol) (tetra-PEG) hydrogels with highly homogeneous network structures have revealed the existence of significant negative energetic elasticity, challenging the conventional understanding of polymer gel elasticity.[1] The existence of negative energetic elasticity has been also experimentally and theoretically suggested in various polymer gels.[2] However, it remains unclear whether negative energetic elasticity exists in conventional polymer gels with inhomogeneous network structures. Investigating the existence of negative energetic elasticity in inhomogeneous polymer gels is crucial for developing accurate models to predict and control their mechanical properties. In this study, we investigate the elasticity of poly(*N,N*-dimethylacrylamide) (PDMAAm) hydrogels with inherently inhomogeneous network structures prepared by free radical polymerization, focusing on the existence of negative energetic elasticity. By measuring the temperature dependence of the shear modulus, we found that significant negative energetic elasticity exists in PDMAAm hydrogels, which was tunable by the network structure parameters (Figure).

[1] Y. Yoshikawa, N. Sakumichi, U. Chung, and T. Sakai, *Phys. Rev. X* **11** (2021) 011045.

[2] N. C. Shirai, N. Sakumichi, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **130** (2023) 148101.

PDMAAm gel

Rheological Study on Gentamicin-loaded PVA/Chitosan Hydrogels

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Poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) and chitosan (CHI) are complementary polymers that can be combined to obtain hybrid hydrogels aimed for wound dressing in medical treatment. *In situ* application of gentamicin (Gent) is more convenient in respect to systemic antibiotic administration because it allows faster delivery of the drug to the site of infection, with the use of lower doses to achieve the same or stronger effect. The PVA, PVA/CHI and PVA/CHI/Gent hydrogels were prepared by physical cross linking using freezing-thawing method in five cycles (freezing for 16 h at -18 °C, thawing for 8 h at 4 °C) [1]. FE-SEM revealed hydrogels porosity as a desirable property of biomaterials that allows better incorporation of antimicrobial agents. FTIR showed characteristics bands between 4000 cm⁻¹ and 400 cm⁻¹, indicating established bonds between PVA, CHI and Gent. MTT cytotoxicity test and antibacterial test in suspension proved that PVA/CHI/Gent hydrogel is nontoxic towards MRC-5 and L929 cell lines and exhibits strong antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Rheological measurements similar as in [2] showed that in all hydrogels (with and without Gent) the storage modules dominate over the loss modulus in the entire frequency range. The highest values of both G' and G'' modules as well as complex viscosity were obtained for the PVA/CHI hydrogel, while the lowest values were shown by the PVA/CHI/Gent hydrogel. Also, the results revealed that all investigated hydrogels regenerate almost completely, immediately after the exposure to the high force ended.

We also formulated a mathematical model that describes the rheological experimental results. The proposed model is General fractional derivative (GFD) of the Standard linear visco-elastic body described by the constitutive equation. We used the procedure proposed in [3] to determine the values of the parameters in the model. The prediction of the model are in good agreement with the experimental results.

[1] V. Miskovic-Stankovic, M. Janev, and T.M. Atanackovic, *J. Pharmacokinet. Pharmacodyn.* **50** (2023) 79-87. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10928-022-09834-8>

[2] K. Enoch, C.S. Rakavi, and A.A. Somasundaram, *Surf. Interfaces* **41** (2023) 103178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfin.2023.103178>

[3] V. Mišković-Stanković, and T. Atanacković, „Novel Antibacterial Biomaterials for Medical Applications and Modeling of Drug Release Process“, Taylor & Francis/CRC Press, Boca Raton (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781032668895>.

Designing Vanillin-Based Dynamic Networks for the Development of Sustainable Thermosets

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In the field of polymer science, thermosets have been employed in a wide range of applications, from aerospace and automotive sectors to coatings, 3D printing and composite materials industries. [1] Their excellent performance is linked to the chemically cross-linked networks which translate into high mechanical and thermal properties. Despite these qualities, the intrinsic persistence of thermosets is also contributing to the growing awareness regarding plastic pollution and its environmental impact. This work addresses the sustainability of thermosetting systems through a dual-strategy approach. First, the incorporation of Dynamic Covalent Bonds (DCBs) into the polymer structure was crucial. DCBs can undergo reversible exchange reactions under external stimuli enabling the material to flow and be reshaped without losing its cross-linked integrity.[2] Second, vanillin was added as a building block to develop biobased Covalent Adaptable Networks (CANs) with imine bonds as dynamic crosslinks.

Two distinct formulations were prepared and fully characterized, and results demonstrate the versatility of this type of systems: it was possible to achieve both a high-performance material, exhibiting no chemical degradation and better flame resistance when compared to fossil-based alternatives, and a lower T_g material with shape-memory behavior. The aim of the project was then to ensure the dynamic properties of the networks, performing stress relaxation tests followed by a recycling procedure. Briefly, cross-linked samples are subjected to mechanical failure via tensile testing, and the resulting fragments are reprocessed in a hot press to restore the original form.

In conclusion, vanillin is a promising candidate to replace petroleum derivatives, representing a new frontier that aligns with the principles of circular economy and offers a path worth exploring. The development of this research study has been made possible thanks to the collaboration and financial support of the Italian government body Agenzia Spaziale Italiana (ASI).

[1] M.A. Rashid, M.N. Hasan, M.A.R. Dayan, M.S. Ibna Jamal, M.K. Patoary, [*Reactions* **4** \(2023\) 66–91](#).

[2] H. Zhang, J. Cui, G. Hu, B. Zhang, [*International Journal of Smart and Nano Materials* **13**\(3\) \(2022\) 367–390](#).

Hydrogel-based biosensors for long-term and mobile EEG measurements

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Electroencephalography (EEG) is a well-established and widely used technique for clinical diagnostic (e.g. seizures) and a wide variety of research areas (e.g. brain computer interfaces). There are currently a plethora of medical and consumer systems and devices for EEG acquisition, but its implementation is dominated by paste-based sensors requiring laborious and time-consuming preparation. Dry and semi-dry electrode systems address this limitation and have been commercialized, leading the way in the growing interest on mobile and outside-the-lab systems. However, concerns about higher electrode-skin impedance (ESI), increased motion artifact susceptibility, and reduced wearing comfort have limited a wider implementation. Hydrogels-based electrodes, belonging to the semi-dry category, have recently attracted attention due to their lower long-term ESI, improved comfort, and desirable scalp conformability while retaining facile application, making them attractive candidates for mobile and long-term applications.

We developed a biosensor composed of an Ag/AgCl coated polyurethane and a polyacrylamide/alginate/gelatine/AMPS hydrogel – the first serving as mechanical fixing point (polyurethane) and electrochemically stable electrode (Ag/AgCl coating), and the second as electrolyte carrier and skin conformal interface. Different hydrogel formulations were mechanically (compression and adhesion), morphologically (SEM) and electrochemically (intrinsic impedance for 24 h) characterized to assess individual components' effect and fabricate three lead hydrogels. Lead hydrogels were then used to perform 2-pole ESI measurements, placed 8 cm apart on the forehead of three healthy volunteers for 8 h to investigate transferability of our observations on intrinsic impedance results to biosignal acquisition. ESI measurements with paste-based electrodes were carried out in the same conditions for comparison. The best performing hydrogel (lowest ESI) was finally used to assemble biosensors for a low-density EEG system and perform proof of concept measurements.

Increased polymer content showed the strongest effect on mechanical strength (2-fold increase in compression modulus – 8.8 kPa), while increased glycerol content and reduced crosslinking of the polymer network improved long-term impedance stability. ESI (at 10 Hz) of hydrogel-based biosensor at 0 h was 31 k Ω , a comparable result to paste-based electrodes in the same conditions – 36 k Ω . Preliminary results provide evidence for the hydrogel's capability to maintain low intrinsic impedance over 24h (1394 Ω at 10 Hz) and thus proves its potential for long-term and mobile EEG systems. Future studies will aim to investigate the role of hydrogels' mechanical properties in application-focused properties, such as conformability to the scalp, user's comfort, motion artifacts susceptibility.

Chemically Crosslinked Agarose–CQD Hydrogels for Solar Desalination

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Solar-driven interfacial evaporation is a promising approach for sustainable desalination, yet the development of efficient and environmentally friendly photothermal materials remains challenging [1,2]. Here, we present a novel hydrogel platform based on agarose, a renewable biopolymer, chemically crosslinked using divinyl sulfone (DVS), providing enhanced control over network architecture and significantly improved mechanical and operational stability under repeated evaporation cycles. Amine-functionalized carbon quantum dots (CQDs-NH₂) are incorporated within the hydrogel, acting both as crosslinking elements and efficient solar absorbers, leading to improved photothermal conversion and water transport. In addition, to gain molecular-level insight, coarse-grained molecular dynamics simulations using the Martini force field [3] were performed, revealing how network structure and CQD incorporation influence water interactions and transport pathways. The resulting system combines sustainability, robustness, and functionality, offering a promising route toward durable and scalable solar evaporators for water purification.

References:

[1] Naranjo et al. *Adv. Sustainable Syst.* **8**(11) (2024), 2400234.

[2] Mingot et al. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **34**(13) (2024), 2311523.

[3] Souza et al. *Nature Methods* **18**(4) (2021), 382-388.

Acknowledgements: This work has received funding from the Grant PID2024-157005OB-I00 and María de Maeztu Excellence Centre (CEX2023-001300-M) by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF “A way of making Europe”, by the European Union. D.N. acknowledges AGAUR for his PhD fellowship funding (2023 FISDUR 00296).

Polyphosphoesters, a new family of degradable elastomers

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The polyphosphoesters (PPEs) are an emerging family of degradable polymers. Its easy copolymerization into several architectures, like amphiphilic block copolymers, has been already widely reported for drug-delivery applications where it can be tracked by ³¹P MRI [1]. The main advantage of this polymer family is that the degradation kinetics can be tuned from minutes to years [2] simply via the nature and ratio of monomers, with a library of such monomers in constant expansion. Nevertheless, rare examples of PPE networks [3] were already published and important fragilities (soft and ultimate strain of 15%) prevented further development of PPE-based materials. Here, we present the first elastomers of PPE sustaining more than 250% of elongation. The unique control over the XYZ tri-block copolymerization enables to fine-tune the length of a long central block (Y) acting as a spacer and two short lateral blocks (X and Z) acting as crosslinking nodes. The nature of the central block governs the overall hydrophilicity of the elastomers while not participating in the crosslinking nodes thus not affecting the mechanical behavior in the dry state. This passive block can be synthesized with any ratio of co-monomers and hydrophobic or hydrophilic elastomers were obtained. The precise ratio of monomers governs the exact swelling degree, then the ultimate deformability in wet conditions (80% for the fully hydrophilic) and finally the kinetics of degradation. Lastly, these elastomers were 3D-printed and foamed as first proof of concepts for PPE materials, opening the door to porous and highly deformable personalized scaffolds for cell culture.

[1] T. Rheinberger, ..., F.R. Wurm, *Communications Chemistry* **6** (2023) 182.

[2] T. Rheinberger, ..., F.R. Wurm, *Eur. Polym. J.* **190** (2023) 111999.

[3] R. Riva, ..., C. Jérôme, *Biomacromolecules* **21** (2020) 349-355.

Multifunctional biomaterials for intelligent freshness sensing

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Biodegradable materials based on naturally derived polymers are being intensively investigated as substitutes for conventional synthetic indicators [1]. When integrated with bio-based functional additives, these materials can simultaneously exhibit sensing functionality alongside antimicrobial and antioxidant activities, enabling multifunctional packaging platforms within a single, environmentally compatible system [2]. Polysaccharides have demonstrated particular efficacy as carriers for anthocyanins due to their ability to establish electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions, and hydrogen bonding with the functional groups of these pigments. The aim of this study was to fabricate ultra-light, physically and double cross-linked xanthan gum (Xn)-based cryogels incorporating anthocyanin-rich bilberry (BLB) extract by cryogelation to act as multifunctional materials for real-time monitoring of Prussian carp spoilage [3]. The cryogels were stabilized through both physical and chemical cross-linking, resulting in a synergistically reinforced porous network with improved physicochemical performance. Incorporation of the bioactive extract and chemical cross-linking led to increased structural density, with encapsulation efficiencies reaching 39.27% and antioxidant activity exceeding 90% as determined by DPPH radical scavenging assays. BLB-loaded Xn cryogels exhibited strong antimicrobial performance, achieving up to complete growth inhibition against *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Listeria monocytogenes*. The cryogels displayed rapid, reversible, and reproducible pH-dependent color responses during repeated exposure to volatile acidic and basic environments. A clear visual color transition from purple to blue was observed during *Carassius gibelio* spoilage, correlating with pH evolution. These findings confirm the potential of anthocyanin-loaded xanthan cryogels as eco-friendly, multifunctional biomaterials for intelligent food packaging applications.

Acknowledgement: Project PN-IV-P1-PCE-2023-1968 is acknowledged.

[1] S. Mohammadlinejad, M. Kurek, I.-J. Jensen, and L. Jørgen, Current Research in Food Science 7 (2023) 100560.

[2] Y. Yun, X. Cheng, J. Xu, Y. Wang, H. Jin, and J. Li, Food Hydrocolloids 163 (2025) 111077.

[3] I. E. Răschip, I.-V. Platon, N. Fifere, R.-N. Darie-Niță, A. C. Aprotosoiaie, and M. V. Dinu, Food Hydrocolloids 168 (2025) 111566.

One-pot upcycling of waste acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene using a commercial ionic crosslinker.

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Owing to their ease of availability and versatility, plastics production has exploded in the recent decade. With an increase in plastics production, there also arises the all-important question of plastics waste management, specifically how will this produced plastic be dealt with at end-of-life. Mechanical recycling is a viable option for thermoplastics and is widely adopted, however the issue lies in reduced mechanical integrity of the recycled plastics compared to the commercially available virgin plastic. In this study, we explored the ionic crosslinking of post-consumer recycled acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene (PCR ABS) which is one of the most important engineering thermoplastics used in a wide variety of applications. A commercially available zinc salt known as zinc dimethacrylate (ZDMA) was used to ionically crosslink the PCR ABS via reactive extrusion, which is a solvent-free, industrially scalable and economically viable method which can be executed in one step. These ionically crosslinked samples showed 12% higher tensile strength and good elongation at break. The samples also showed good thermal stability and could be recycled for three cycles without any loss in their tensile strength.

Innovative on-demand debonding strategies for disassembly of adhesion joints

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In response to the increasing global demand for sustainable materials and circular economy design strategies, this work introduces the concept of chemical amplification mechanisms and latent catalysts in a covalent adaptable network (CANs) for reversible adhesive system.¹ Chemical amplification refers to a process in which a single external trigger induces a cascade of subsequent reactions, for instance catalyst activation and transesterification.² CANs are capable of undergoing chain rearrangement in response to external stimuli, thereby offering on-demand adaptability. In the absence of a stimulus, bonds exchange is slow, and network remains fixed into rigid structures with strong adhesive interaction and high mechanical strength. Upon application of an external stimulus, heat in this work, a rapid covalent bond exchange occurs, leading to a decreasing in modulus and viscosity. This behaviour enables the adhesive de-bonding and material reprocessing. To achieve spatiotemporal control over this process, the integration of latent catalyst can regulate the exchange reaction.³ The inactivated catalyst maintains a low exchange rate for vitrimer network at lower temperatures, thereby guaranteeing structural integrity and preventing irreversible creep deformation. Once activated at high temperature, it efficiently promotes bond exchange reactions, as evidenced by a rapid decrease in stress relaxation, enabling on-demand debonding.

Fig. 1: General scheme of de-bondable on-demand mechanism.

References:

1. J. M. Winne, L. Leibler, and F. E. Du Prez, *Polymer Chemistry* **10** (2019) 6091-6108.
2. W. J. Blaedel, and R. C. Boguslaski, *Analytical Chemistry* **50** (1978) 1026-1032.
3. Nikita, A. Kumar, and L. A. Connal, *Polymer Chemistry* **15** (2024) 1932-1936.

Depolymerized Lignin as a Versatile Platform for Sustainable Bioaromatic Polymer Design

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The transition toward a circular polymer economy requires sustainable alternatives to fossil-based building blocks. Renewable bio-based feedstocks offer a promising route for material development, with lignin emerging as an attractive candidate due to its abundance and aromatic-rich structure, which imparts rigidity. However, its complex and heterogeneous nature limits its direct utilization in advanced applications. To address these challenges, we have previously demonstrated that depolymerized lignin (DL), obtained through controlled depolymerization, provides a more accessible platform with lower molecular weight, reduced polydispersity, improved solubility, and enhanced reactivity, making it better suited for polymer design.

Herein, DL is explored as a versatile feedstock for functional bioaromatic materials. Through targeted functionalization, it enables the synthesis of a broad range of polymer systems, including epoxy and acrylate resins with tunable properties. In addition, covalent adaptable networks based on Diels–Alder adducts derived from Lignin have been developed, enabling improved recyclability, self-healing behavior, and overall material circularity. These examples demonstrate that DL serves as a flexible and tunable platform for next-generation polymers, bridging biomass valorization with advanced polymer chemistry to achieve high-performance and circular material solutions. In parallel, the development of a pilot-scale lignin depolymerization platform facilitates the transition from laboratory research to industrial implementation, supporting the establishment of a new value chain for bioaromatic materials.

Microscale modeling of polymer network breakage under mechanical deformation

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Elastomers, as a class of polymer network, exhibit excellent mechanical properties under deformation, providing a wide range of technical applications. The applicability of elastomers (or more generally, polymer networks) is subjected to the predictability of their mechanical failure under high deformation ranges. The failure of polymer networks arises from a subtle interplay between bond rupture, chain interactions and the underlying topology of the network.

Predictability remains a challenge for modeling and computer simulations due to the complexity of those structures in the molecular level [1]. In this work, Monte Carlo simulations are used to explore how bond breakage shape the mechanical response of crosslinked polymers subjected to mechanical stress.

Our main goal is to evaluate, in a controlled manner, the key elements that modify the mechanical response by computer simulations: the criteria for bond rupture, the mathematical modelling of interactions potentials and force fields, the effect of entanglements and excluded volume. Model networks are evaluated with diverse approaches to quantify the effect of each contribution to elastic modulus.

The simulations yield detailed rupture statistics and stress-strain behavior across a broad parameter space, which are compared with predictions from established theoretical descriptions of network elasticity and fracture and mechanical experiments [2]. Overall, this work provides basic information for understanding network failure and for establishing a first-principles based model for real polymer networks.

References

[1] S. Danielsen, et. al. [*Chem. Rev.* **121**, **8** \(2021\) 5042-5092](#)

[2] T. Matsuda, et.al. [*Macromolecules* **58**, **12** \(2025\) 6017-6032](#)

Magnetic Reusable Polycaprolactone Based Sponge: Effective Removal of Oil Pollution

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An oil spill poses a significant hazard to the environment and natural habitats. In 2025, three leaks over 700 tons and three spills ranging from 7 to 700 tons were documented as a result of tanker accidents [1]. Such large-scale oil spills can have permanent consequences for water resources and ecosystems. One innovative solution to this problem is the use of porous polymeric sorbents [2]. These materials are capable of efficiently absorbing petroleum derivatives and BTEX solvents due to their porous nature. Their porous structure enhances their absorption capability by offering extensive porosity [3]. The utilization of 3D templates is a practical and well examined method of generating porosity while imparting a certain shape to structures. This process involves loading a pre-curing sample with a sugar cube scaffold, resulting in the formation of a hardened network structure around the polymeric backbone [4].

The present study assesses this technique utilizing a 3D template of a sugar cube to produce a magnetic hydrophobic sponge. This porous sponge demonstrates significant oil absorption capabilities, with a selectivity for oil and organic contaminants of 35 g/g. The sorbent has a nature-friendly, one-pot fabrication process that does not require an activator, catalyst, or solvent. In kinetic studies, the sponge exhibited a rapid capacity to absorb substantial quantities of pollutants due to its elevated porosity. The WCA results showed that the sponge exhibits hydrophobic property, enabling it to reject water and selectively capture organic contaminants. Furthermore, the sorbent is reusable, providing a cost-effective and environmentally friendly option.

In conclusion, magnetic sponges offer an eco-friendly and efficient way of mitigating oil pollution. This technology can make a significant contribution to preserving ecosystems and providing a pristine environment.

[1] ITOF. 2026. [Oil Tanker Spill Statistics 2025](#)

[2] KOSE. C., & SONMEZ, H. B. [Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering 2025\(13\)118745](#)

[3] Kose, C., & Bulbul Sonmez, H. [Ind. Eng. Chem. Res. \(2025\),64,18427–18439](#)

[4] Syazmin, N. A., Shahadat, M., Razali, M. R., & Adnan, R. [\(2022\) "Green Chemistry for Sustainable Water Purification Ch.9"](#)

Ferrocene-Appended Polycarbazole Based Polymer Network for Electrochemical Urea Sensing

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In this study, a novel enzymatic electrochemical urea biosensor was constructed based on a Nafion/polyaniline (Nf/PANI) composite, integrated with a ferrocene-appended polycarbazole (FAPCz). Notably, the ferrocene-functionalized polycarbazole was synthesized via oxidative polymerization, yielding a highly crosslinked polymeric network that enhances structural stability and electron-transfer efficiency. This crosslinked architecture was subsequently deposited onto a glassy carbon electrode, followed by urease immobilization through glutaraldehyde-mediated crosslinking.

The synergistic combination of Nafion, PANI, and FAPCz significantly improved electron transfer efficiency and electrochemical response. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) confirmed enhanced charge transfer properties, while differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) demonstrated a linear detection range of 0.62–60.6 μM with a low detection limit of 0.55 μM [1].

The biosensor exhibited high selectivity toward urea in the presence of common interfering ions and biomolecules, along with excellent reproducibility (RSD < 2%). The applicability of the sensor was validated in real soil and water samples, showing good agreement with GC–MS results [1].

These findings demonstrate that ferrocene-functionalized polymer networks provide an effective platform for designing high-performance electrochemical biosensors for environmental monitoring.

[1] Sari, E., Şenocak, A., Tümay, S. O., & Demirbas, E. (2025). Development of novel electrochemical urea biosensor with ferrocene appended polycarbazole. *Microchemical Journal*, 116322.

Relationship between Structure and Mechanical Properties of Model Network Elastomers

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Polymer networks constituting elastomers generally contain structural defects, making it difficult to clarify the relationship between network structure and mechanical properties. To reduce such defects, model network elastomers (MNEs) have been developed by coupling the chain ends of monodisperse polymers. We have previously shown that polyester MNE exhibited excellent stretchability and strain stiffening due to supercoiling and strain-induced crystallization (SIC)^[1]. Herein, we investigate the effects of chain lengths, dangling chains, and loops on the mechanical properties of MNEs^[2]. Azide-terminated four-armed prepolymers were synthesized by ring-opening polymerization of 1,5-dioxepan-2-one, followed by end-group modification. Mixing prepolymers with a strained dialkyne linker in solution yielded a gel, which was dried to obtain an MNE. Samples with different network chain lengths (M_x) were prepared using prepolymers with different molecular weights. Dangling chains were introduced by lowering the conversion (p) of azide groups through linker feed adjustment, whereas loops were introduced by end-linking prepolymers at a concentration (ϕ_0) below the overlap concentration (ϕ^*). In tensile tests, the onset of strain stiffening shifted to higher strains with increasing M_x , decreasing p , and increasing ϕ_0/ϕ^* . These trends can be broadly attributed to delayed SIC caused by a looser network. Scaling analysis based on the tension blob^[3] suggested that the defects had minimal effects on the conformation of network chains, whereas M_x affected it.

[1] S. Nakagawa et al., *Advanced Materials* **35** (2023) 2301124.

[2] R. Sasaki et al., *Macromolecules*, **58**, (2025) 13180-13190.

[3] P. Pincus, *Macromolecules* **9**, (1976) 386-388.

A thermosensitive α -amino acid hydrogel layer deposited on an electrode surface: Actuator and sensor performance

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Electrochemical actuators and sensors have attracted significant attention due to their ability to convert electrical stimuli into mechanical responses and to provide sensitive, real-time analytical signals. In particular, stimuli-responsive hydrogel systems offer unique opportunities for integrating actuation and sensing functionalities within a single material platform. The aim of my work was to develop a novel stimuli-responsive hydrogel layer containing an acryloyl derivative of an α -amino acid and to investigate its electroanalytical properties. The electroactive, electrosensitive, and thermosensitive hydrogel was fabricated via a two-step process. Initially, a hydrogel based on N-isopropylacrylamide (NIPA) and an acryloyl derivative of ornithine (ArOr) was synthesized and electrodeposited using electrochemically induced free-radical polymerization. Cyclic voltammetry combined with gravimetric analysis enabled simultaneous formation and real-time monitoring of the gel layer. Subsequently, the material was modified with copper ions, forming stable complexes with α -amino acid groups and increasing the crosslinking density. The resulting p(NIPA-ArOr-Cu²⁺) layer exhibited dual functionality, acting both as an actuator and as an electrochemical sensor for hydrogen peroxide detection. Its thickness could be reversibly modulated by an applied electrical potential, as confirmed by Quartz Crystal Microbalance with Dissipation (QCM-D), with a clear temperature-dependent response. The sensor demonstrated good practical applicability and stability, retaining approximately 91% of its initial response after three weeks. Furthermore, the effect of different supporting electrolytes revealed a significant influence of ion size on the electrochemical behavior.

Overall, the developed system shows strong potential as a stable and versatile platform for integrated sensing and actuation in smart materials applications.

[1] M. Sawicka, K. Marcisz, J. Romański, M. Strawski, O. Smutok, M. Gonchar, E. Katz, K. Kaniewska, M. Karbarz, "A thermosensitive α -amino acid hydrogel layer deposited on an electrode surface: Actuator and sensor performance." *Talanta*, 296, 128454 (2026).

Preparation and characterisation of immobilised hydrogels as sensor materials

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Hydrogels are soft three-dimensional crosslinked networks that can absorb many times their mass in water. Their properties can be tuned by using different monomers, crosslinkers and preparation methods. Owing to this variability, they offer a broad range of applications, including medical uses (tissue engineering, drug delivery, and antimicrobial surfaces) and electronic applications owing to conductivity. Hydrogels composed of stimuli-responsive polymers enable sensor applications because they can react to physical, chemical, and biochemical stimuli. Typical chemical stimuli include pH, concentration, and molecular species. These stimuli influence the refractive index of the hydrogel. Integrated photonic sensors are suitable for sensing changes in the hydrogel refractive index, where light guided by waveguides interacts with an analyte in its vicinity. The output signal differs depending on the refractive index. A representative example is an optical-integrated Mach-Zehnder interferometer (MZI) produced by laser writing. The phase of the guided light changes depending on the refractive index of the sample. Its capability to sense refractive indices over a broad range was demonstrated in a previous study [1]. In this study, stimuli-responsive hydrogels based on the monomer 3-sulfopropyl methacrylate potassium (MAESO) were prepared via photopolymerization and investigated as sensor materials. Their versatile applications have been demonstrated in previous studies [2, 3]. Here, we show the effect of different ions and salt concentrations on the swelling behaviour of MAESO-based hydrogels and characterise it using a laser-written MZI. To enable better handling and testing of a broad range of modified MAESO-based hydrogels, they were covalently immobilised on glass surfaces modified with 3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl methacrylate. Immobilised hydrogels swollen in aqueous solutions of varying salt concentrations show a corresponding relationship between the swelling degree and the MZI phase change. With decreasing swelling, the phase change increases owing to the increasing refractive index.

[1] K. Becker, J. Schnegas, A. Thies, F. Klauck, T. Korn, A. Szameit, T. Wolterink, U. Kragl, M. Heinrich, *Opt. Mater. Express* **2025**, 15, 2437-2446.

[2] J. Claus, A. Brietzke, C. Lehnert, S. Oschatz, N. Grabow, U. Kragl, *PLOS ONE* **2020**, 15(4).

[3] J. Romischke, T. Eickner, N. Grabow, U. Kragl, S. Oschatz, *RSC Adv.* **2024**, 14, 28881-28888.

Porous hydrophobic nanocellulose matrix for simple fabrication of environmental trace gas QCM sensor

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Quartz crystal microbalances (QCMs) are cost-effective and highly sensitive transducers for molecular detection. By integrating adsorbent materials onto the electrode surfaces of QCMs, it is possible to develop highly sensitive and molecularly selective sensing devices. However, a key challenge in sensor fabrication is the stable and firm immobilization of adsorbents on the electrode surface while maintaining a film thickness at least below 1 μm and minimizing fluctuations in the resonant frequency of the QCM.

In this study, a polymer gel matrix that firmly adheres to the QCM electrode surface and remains inert toward the target gas was investigated to establish a simple fabrication method for QCM sensors capable of highly sensitive detection of trace environmental gases while satisfying the above requirements for adsorbent immobilization. Ni-based metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) and mordenite, both synthesized in our laboratory, were employed as N_2O -selective adsorbents.

Various polymer matrix materials were examined to identify a suitable matrix polymer that can stably adhere to the QCM electrode and uniformly immobilize the adsorbents. Among the materials tested, hydrophobic nanocellulose gel [1] was found to be particularly effective. By optimizing the fabrication conditions and procedures for matrix formation on the QCM, a thin and porous hydrophobic nanocellulose matrix incorporating the adsorbents was successfully formed on the QCM surface. The gas-sensing characteristics of the resulting QCM sensors were then evaluated to assess the effectiveness of the proposed matrix.

[1] N. Seida, „Int. Chem. Cong. Pacific Basin Soc. 2025“, Abstract, CLHGP #188 Honolulu (2025).

Universal Equation of State Describing Osmotic Pressure of Polymer Gels

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The swelling behavior of polymer gels is governed by osmotic pressure. The total osmotic pressure is decomposed into mixing and elastic contributions, $\Pi_{\text{tot}} = \Pi_{\text{mix}} + \Pi_{\text{el}}$ [1], and the equilibrium swollen state is given by $\Pi_{\text{tot}} = 0$. Among these contributions, Π_{mix} plays a central role in determining the equilibrium state, as it depends strongly on polymer concentration and solvent quality. Conventionally, Π_{mix} has been described using the Flory–Huggins mean-field theory [2], which becomes inaccurate particularly in the low-concentration regime where concentration fluctuations are significant.

In this study, we investigate Π_{mix} of tetra-PEG hydrogels over a wide range of network parameters, temperatures, and solvent conditions (135 data points). We find that Π_{mix} is independent of network structure and can be described by a universal equation of state. Following the blob picture [3], we define a characteristic length scale ξ as $\Pi_{\text{mix}} \equiv k_B T / \xi^3$. When expressed in terms of this length scale, all data collapse onto universal curves across different conditions, consistent with the scaling behavior of a single polymer chain [4]. This demonstrates that the osmotic thermodynamics of polymer gels is governed solely by intrinsic chain statistics, independent of network structure.

[1] P. J. Flory and J. Rehner, *J. Chem. Phys.* **11**, (1943) 521. [2] P. J. Flory, *J. Chem. Phys.* **10**, (1942) 51. [3] P. G. de Gennes, "Scaling Concepts in Polymer Physics", Cornell University Press, Ithaca (1979). [4] M. Rubinstein, R. H. Colby, "Polymer Physics", Oxford University Press, Oxford (2003).

Kinetic–Statistical Modelling of Gelation and Structure of Polyaspartic-Polyurea Networks

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Understanding and controlling gelation is essential for designing polyaspartic–polyurea (PU–ASPE) materials with tailored properties. We present a modelling approach that combines chemical kinetics with statistical network theory to describe both the formation and structure of these crosslinked systems.

The model integrates experimentally based reaction kinetics with statistical reconstruction of the polymer network [1], enabling prediction of key quantities such as the gel point, gelation time, and network density. Importantly, it captures the influence of competing reactions and realistic features of the crosslinker, which are often neglected in simpler models.

A key advantage of the present approach lies in its ability to distinguish between multiple chemically distinct bond types connecting the same pair of building units. In contrast to standard statistical network models, which characterize links solely by the identities of the connected units, our framework explicitly accounts for bond heterogeneity. This feature is essential for accurately describing PU–ASPE networks, where different reaction pathways can produce structurally distinct connections between identical units, and its neglect may lead to significant inaccuracies in predicted network structure and gelation behavior.

This combined approach provides a practical tool for interpreting experimental data and explaining unexpected behavior observed in PU–ASPE systems. It thus supports the rational design of advanced polymer materials by linking reaction conditions to final network structure and properties.

[1] A. Sharma, Z. Morávková, S. Abbrent, O. Kočková, S. Natourová, Z. Walterová, J. Podešva, J. Šomvářsky, M. Dušková-Smrčková, Experimental and statistical modelling of gelation in aspartate-based polyurea networks, [Polymer 339 \(2025\) 129100](#).

Thermo- and pH- Responsive PNIPAAm-Based Hydrogels for Controlled Drug Delivery Applications

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Abstract

Poly(*N*-isopropylacrylamide) (PNIPAAm) is a widely used smart polymer in drug delivery systems (DDS) due to its lower critical solution temperature (LCST) close to body temperature, reversible swelling–deswelling behavior, and biocompatibility. However, its limitations in controlled release performance and mechanical strength necessitate further improvement. In this context, pH-sensitive comonomers such as *N*-[2-(diethylamino) ethyl] acrylamide (DEAEAM) and acrylic acid (AAc) can be incorporated into PNIPAAm networks to develop dual-responsive (pH/temperature) systems with enhanced mechanical stability. This study aims to synthesize such hydrogels and investigate the effects of crosslinking density and pH on their mechanical and thermo-responsive properties for potential drug delivery applications.

In this study, NIPAAm-based copolymers (NIPAAm-DEAEAM) and terpolymers (NIPAAm-DEAEAM-AAc) with varying crosslinking ratios were synthesized via free-radical polymerization using *N,N'*-methylenebisacrylamide (MBAAm) as a crosslinking agent. The structural and morphological properties of the resulting hydrogels were characterized by FTIR, SEM, and DSC analyses, while their mechanical properties were evaluated through compression testing. In addition, equilibrium swelling ratios, as well as swelling and deswelling kinetics, were systematically investigated under various temperatures and pH conditions. The results demonstrated that the hydrogels exhibited both temperature and pH sensitivity, and that LCST and mechanical behavior were significantly influenced by the crosslinking ratio and pH. Furthermore, compression test results confirmed that both crosslinking density and pH environment had a decisive influence on the maximum compressive strength and elasticity of the hydrogels.

In conclusion, NIPAAm-DEAEAM and NIPAAm-DEAEAM-AAc hydrogels are promising candidates for controlled drug delivery applications due to their tunable thermo- and pH-responsive behavior. Moreover, their mechanical properties can be optimized by adjusting parameters such as crosslinking density and environmental pH, making them suitable for a wide range of biomedical applications.

Keywords: NIPAAm-based hydrogels, DEAEAM, AAc, dual-responsive systems, mechanical test, LCST.

[1] M.K. Yoo, Y.K. Sung, Y.M. Lee, and C.S. Cho, *Polymer* 41 (2000) 5713–5719.

[2] Z. Song, K. Wang, G. Gao, S. Wang, and W. Zhang, *Macromolecules*, 49 (2016) 162-171.

This work was supported by the Scientific Research Projects Coordination Unit of Gebze Technical University under the ADEP project (Grant No. 2024-A-113-01).

Anti-thrombotic hydrogel coatings for endovascular devices

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Deploying foreign materials, like implants or endovascular devices, in blood results in inflammation and thrombus formation. A protease-cleavable hydrogel of the anticoagulant heparin and four-armed poly(ethylene glycol) (starPEG) showed promising anti-coagulant properties *in vitro* [1]. Hydrogel components are covalently crosslinked by a coagulation-responsive cleavable peptide. In a local coagulation event, the activated coagulation factor thrombin (FIIa) selectively cleaves the peptide and releases heparin by degrading the hydrogel network. The hydrogel was coated on coronary and neuroradiological stents, and the anti-thrombogenic property was investigated in flow systems *in vitro* and *in vivo* in a rabbit model [2].

In vitro and *in vivo* analysis showed suppressed activation of coagulation and platelets for coated stents in comparison to bare metal stent (BMS). Although a release of anticoagulant in the responsive system (tcPHG) was verified *in vitro*, no beneficial effect on hemocompatibility compared to non-responsive heparin hydrogel (PHG) was observed *in vivo*. This discrepancy is attributed to additional platelet activation by higher shear stress in the arterial system. Thus, it is aimed to develop a further improved hydrogel system that additionally releases a platelet inhibitor via a coagulation-cleavable peptide linker to address the specific hemostatic conditions of the application site.

[1] M. F. Maitz, U. Freudenberg et al, Nat. Commun. **4** (2013) 2168.

[2] M. F. Maitz, D. P. O. Kaiser, A. Cuberi, [J NeuroIntervent Surg **17** \(2025\) 625-631.](#)

Association behavior of some electrolyte saccharides chain and whey protein

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We can find electrolyte polysaccharide with carboxylate and/or sulfate groups in seaweeds, for example, alginate, carrageenan, fucoidan and so on. They are applied for food additives or supplement. For example, carrageenan is a sulfate polysaccharide extracted from red seaweed. Its aqueous solutions undergo thermoreversible sol-gel transition by formation or deformation of double helix structure. As another example, alginate is extracted from brown seaweed, and has carboxylic acid groups. It takes place gelation by addition of calcium ions by coordinating them with carboxylic acid sites on saccharide chains. The observation of these kinds of structural features is important for comprehension of apparent phenomena and functionalization. Fucoidan has physiological activities as anticoagulant, immunomodulatory, antitumor, etc. The mechanism of these effects is complicated and not clear. One approach to solve it is to study the interaction of electrolyte polysaccharide and key protein as signal molecule.

One powerful method for structural characterization of the polysaccharides and their interaction and complexation with protein is small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS), which is available for analyzing nano-scale structure in solution and/or gel. In this work, the SAXS was performed to analyze the associated structure. The time-resolved SAXS during making low pH by addition of gluconolactone (GDL) was also carried out. The interaction and complex structure of electrolyte polysaccharide and protein were studied as model system. The fucoidan or sulfated cyclodextrin mixed with β -lactoglobulin (β -Lg) were used for samples. The results indicated that the mixture solution becomes turbid at low pH, indicating the aggregation. The variation of SAXS pattern indicated the aggregation process of electrolyte polysaccharide and protein at nano-order level.

Biaxial characterization of natural rubber with a focus on strain-induced crystallization

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Natural rubber (NR) exhibits remarkable mechanical performance, largely due to its ability to develop strain-induced crystallization (SIC) during deformation. While the mechanisms of SIC under uniaxial tension have been investigated in detail, for example by in situ synchrotron X-ray diffraction (Toki et al., 2004), the influence of multiaxial deformation remains less well understood. In particular, biaxial stretching has been shown to frustrate strain-induced crystallization compared with uniaxial loading (Chen et al., 2019). The present contribution therefore focuses on the biaxial characterization of NR under different and freely adjustable biaxiality ratios in order to clarify the influence of the strain state on the mechanical response and on the onset and evolution of SIC.

To this end, biaxial mechanical testing is combined with in-situ synchrotron studies, infrared (IR) measurements, and digital image correlation (DIC). This coupled experimental approach enables the simultaneous observation of temperature evolution, local strain fields, and crystallization phenomena during deformation. In this way, the interplay between arbitrary biaxial loading, strain heterogeneity, self-heating, and microstructural changes can be analyzed in a comprehensive manner. The results contribute to a deeper understanding of SIC in NR under complex loading paths and provide an experimental basis for the development and validation of advanced constitutive models for elastomers.

[1] S. Toki et al., *Macromolecules* **37**(9) (2004) 3294–3299.

[2] X. Chen et al., *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **11** (2019) 47535-47544.